

D.3.2: Focus Groups – *Findings.* *Exploring Institutional Roles in Fostering Public Trust in Science*

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ABSTRACT:	This deliverable describes the main findings of the focus groups in the seven POIESIS partner countries.
Keyword List:	focus groups, institutions, scientific integrity, public integration in science, trust

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Executive Summary

This report presents the main results of the research work carried out by the POIESIS project partners as part of Workpackage 3. POIESIS develops an extensive research programme to systematically examine the interrelatedness of integrity, integration, and trust, exploring also the role of institutions in fostering a research climate that is conducive to societal trust in science. The global aim of WP3 was to define, at the European level, to what extent and how can institutions provide policies and procedures that enable researchers to act in ways that are conducive to public trust in science.

The POIESIS consortium opted for a survey methodology that was both qualitative and participatory: qualitative, with 22 focus groups involving more than 130 participants; participatory, with 24 institutional stakeholders working with us as co-investigators. All partners were able to implement the research protocol (See deliverable 3.1) and, where necessary, adapt it to local realities in order to obtain unprecedented qualitative data on how the various institutional actors involved in scientific integrity and social inclusion perceive both the current state of integrity and inclusion in their respective national contexts. The data also provided an unprecedented perspective on the different institutional priorities that could be undertaken rapidly.

The structure of the report is as follows; The first section presents an introduction about the POIESIS project. It allows us to specify the institutional orientation adopted for this task, but also to provide a general characterisation of the method used to conduct the Focus Group Study. This first part is followed by a second part describing the various elements involved in carrying out the research project: selection of participants, resources provided, organisation of groups, data analysis, etc. Finally, the third part presents an overall cross-country analysis of the results based on six main themes: the relationship between science and society, public trust in science, the culture of scientific integrity, the culture of social inclusion, the actors in the mediation chain, and recommendations and priority actions. The final section highlights several key institutional priorities, including the 15 detailed below:

- o Implement clear guidelines, codes of conduct and promote shared research integrity standards across institutions and countries.
- o Increase administrative support throughout the research process, covering areas such as budget management, external collaboration and relations, and data management.
- o Encourage scientific institutions to address the organizational tensions, conflicting imperatives they contribute to generate.
- o Ensure science independence and develop public conversation about the private funding of universities and research organisations.
- o Continuous, career-long training and education programmes for students, scientists, but also other professionals working in the institution.
- o In-depth revision of the performance evaluation system: Towards more qualitative measures.
- o Ensure a culture of transparency regarding the institutional handling of misconduct.
- o Provide scientists with the necessary knowledge and resources to engage in a sustainable and meaningful process of social integration.
- o Protect own members, and particularly scientists, from external attacks.
- o Promote collaborative spaces and buildings: When citizens are invited for the physical space of institutions, buildings should be designed and built to favour this openness.
- o Develop and consider new ways of consulting citizens at local and regional level. For example, by holding citizens' assemblies or other specific groups.
- o Insofar as the battle for scientific information is being waged at both global and local levels, act at both levels, combining comprehensive participation with mass dissemination.
- o Use institutional communicators to make citizens aware of research in the early stages.
- o Implement the inclusion of scientific knowledge in school curricula - the only moment in life when all societal groups can be reached simultaneously - but also foster life-long learning opportunities in this regard.
- o Avoid assuming a "crisis of trust", it is a strong and problematic term: talk of crisis can be self-fulfilling and is best avoided.

1. Introduction

1.1. About POIESIS

POIESIS is a three-year project funded by Horizon Europe. This project brings together seven partners: Aarhus University (Denmark), London School of Economics and Political Science (United Kingdom), Wissenschaft im Dialog (Germany), National Technical University of Athens (Greece), Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (France), Iscte - Instituto Universitário de Lisboa (Portugal), Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas (Spain).

POIESIS develops an extensive research programme to systematically examine the interrelatedness of integrity, integration, and trust, exploring also the role of institutions in fostering a research climate that is conducive to societal trust in science. POIESIS aims to do this through (i) analysis of existing data streams on citizen trust, responsible and questionable research practices, and institutional policies to enhance responsible research; (ii) implementation of a portfolio of small scale studies, specifically tailored to capture empirically the relatedness of integrity, integration, and trust, with a focus on the chains of mediation that connect research practices with, ultimately, the interpretation and assessment of these by wider, non-academic publics; and (iii) conducting a set of participatory research actions in which stakeholders actively co-create knowledge.

The POIESIS project can be characterised by the importance given to the empirical survey methods, but also by the conceptual model adopted by the members of the consortium, the so-called 3i4t for "Integrity, Integration, and Institutions for trust".

Figure 1 - The 3i4t model

POIESIS considers research integrity and social integration in science as broad concepts facilitated by institutions, which through chains of mediation potentially affect public trust in science. The concept of public trust refers to the confidence individual or social groups may have in the reliability of science and scientists. It is entangled with broader constellations of positive and negative “attitudes” towards science which have been explored in both cross-sectional and longitudinal studies. The concept of integrity is concerned with the extent to which research practices are in accordance with appropriate ethical, legal, and professional frameworks, obligations, and standards¹. The concept of integration relates to the increased inclusion of citizens and societal stakeholders throughout the different phases of research and innovation cycles². The concept of institutions refers to the key

¹ See Horbach, S.P. and W. Halfman, Promoting virtue or punishing fraud: Mapping contrasts in the language of ‘scientific integrity’. *Science and Engineering Ethics*, 2017. 23(6): p. 1461-1485

² See Wilsdon, J. and R. Willis, See-through science: Why public engagement needs to move upstream. 2004: Demos; Stilgoe, J., S.J. Lock, and J. Wilsdon, Why should we promote public engagement with science? *Public understanding of science*, 2014. 23(1): p. 4-15.

actors and core processes involved in the pursuit of delivering robust and relevant research results in the interests of both science and society. Finally, the concept of “chain of mediation” relates to the mechanisms and processes that connect research practices at the work floor with the interpretation and assessment of these by wider publics³.

1.2. The institutional dimension

The POIESIS project is organised into five main workpackages. The research results presented in this global synthesis report were produced as part of workpackage 3 of the POIESIS project, a WP coordinated by the project's CNRS partner in France and leader of the focus group study.

WP3 is primarily designed to address the following research question: To what extent and how can institutions provide policies and procedures that enable researchers to act in ways that are conducive to public trust in science?

POIESIS' research on institutional processes and actors aims to explore how institutions engage, facilitate, or constrain responsible research practices and how public recognition of such practices in turn influences trust in science. This involves detailed analysis of various actors involved including research performing organizations (RPOs) and research funding organizations (RFOs), and mediating actors such as science journalists, open access repositories, technology transfer offices, scientific publishers, actors in technology assessment, and civil society organisations, that are key to disseminating information, promoting new and improved practices, and mobilising citizens to contribute to research and innovation.

In order to provide effective and robust outcomes, WP3 carries out **participatory research activities involving institutional stakeholders to co-construct knowledge and policy recommendations**

³ See Bauer W. M., Schiele B. (eds), Science Communication: Taking a Step Back to Move Forward, CNRS Editions, 2023.

about the ways in which institutions can help create fertile conditions for responsible research practices.

1.3. Focus groups

The survey methodology adopted for this task was the focus group method. Sometimes used in social sciences as a preliminary step before a more quantitative approach, this qualitative methodology is present in numerous studies devoted to the transformations of the scientific community. The influential studies of Martinson et al. on scientists' misconducts were systematically empirically based on qualitative material collected in focus groups⁴. More recently, one can cite the articles produced within the context of the European funded project Standard Operating Procedures for Research Integrity (SOPs4RI, <https://sops4ri.eu/>) that also rely extensively on this method to capture the variety of issues and experiences related to research integrity⁵.

The focus group technique offers several methodological values. Without seeking to be exhaustive, it is useful to stress four distinct points : a) the group discussions can provide a wealth of information that can help researchers formulate hypotheses and refine research questions (exploratory research); b) the group discussions can provide rich and detailed data that can be used to gain a deeper understanding of people's attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors (data collection); c) as focus groups are interactive and dynamic, the group discussion can lead to a more nuanced and complex understanding of the topic being discussed (interaction); d) the group discussion can provide participants with an opportunity to share their thoughts and experiences with others. This can lead to a greater sense of

⁴ See for example Martinson, B., Anderson, M. & de Vries, R. Scientists behaving badly. *Nature*. 2005 (435): 737-738.

⁵ See for example Mejlgaard N, Bouter LM, Gaskell G, Kavouras P, Allum N, Bendtsen AK, Charitidis CA, Claesen N, Dierickx K, Domaradzka A, Reyes Elizondo A, Foeger N, Hiney M, Kaltenbrunner W, Labib K, Marušić A, Sørensen MP, Ravn T, Ščepanović R, Tijdink JK, Veltri GA. Research integrity: nine ways to move from talk to walk. *Nature*. 2020 Oct;586(7829):358-360.

investment in the research process and a more positive attitude towards the research (engagement).

The focus groups aimed to explore institutional stakeholders' perceptions of the links between integrity, integration and trust in science. In order to organise the discussions in the groups, the general WP3 research question has been broken down into several sub-questions: A) How do institutional stakeholders perceive, globally and locally, the level of public trust in science and technology and its implications? B) How do institutional stakeholders perceive the culture of research integrity and social integration in their own institutional and national environment? C) To what extent do institutional stakeholders consider that responsible research practices and social integration could be fostered by conducive institutional governance arrangements and policy environments? D) What kind of institutional governance arrangements and policy environments should be considered as key priorities?

The data collected during the focus groups allow us to investigate:

- perceptions of public trust, research integrity and social integration
- concerns, hopes and expectations towards research integrity and social integration
- procedures and policies translating research integrity and social integration into communicational or organizational processes
- expectations about the impact of these procedures and policies.

2. Methodology: A retrospective on implementing the empirical focus group investigation

The research findings presented in this document are the product of an empirical investigation based on a research protocol proposed by the CNRS coordinator and discussed collectively by all project partners. This protocol corresponds to deliverable 3.1.(D.3-1. Protocol for participatory research actions with institutional stakeholders)

As the Centre national de la recherche scientifique (CNRS) in France do not have a Research ethics committee established, the coordinator submitted an updated version of the protocol for approval by the Sorbonne University Research Ethics Committee (CER). The committee issued a favourable opinion with identifier CER-2023-DUBOIS-POIESIS.

It is important to note that this application took a long time to process because of the committee's limited experience with social science projects. Sorbonne Université's research ethics committee was set up in 2019 and the vast majority of the protocols to be evaluated come from Sorbonne Université's Faculty of Medicine. The coordinator spent a significant amount of time explaining the project's approach and why it was not possible to mechanically apply some of the rules that apply in biomedical research. In particular, the question of the conservation of qualitative data gave rise to a great deal of discussion.

At the same time as this document was being prepared, a Joint Controller Data Agreement (JDA) was developed, transmitted and signed by all the partners.

This section presents a variety of information related to the implementation of the empirical investigation: it describes the recruitment strategies for both the co-investigators and the focus group participants, as well as the various resources sent to the project partners, in particular the interview and coding guides. Readers may wish to consult the national reports in the annex H to this report for more detailed methodological information on each national study.

2.1. Participatory research

One of the methodological objectives of WP3 was to develop a qualitative participatory research design involving institutional stakeholders. The general idea was to involve institutional stakeholders as "co-investigators" in the conduct of the research based on the assumption that this participatory dimension would make it possible to obtain results that are both more accurate and more useful. In the context of participatory research, there are several ways to define the role of a co-investigator and the nature of the

participatory collaboration. The co-investigator may be involved more or less upstream of the actual definition of the research questions. They may also be involved, as in this project, in the collection and analysis of research data and in the publications based on the data collected. The POIESIS partners have already planned the first use of the data in the form of a publication. This will include any co-investigators who wish to participate.

The coordinator drew on his previous positive experience in a project on research ethics and integrity funded by the French national research agency: the CovETHOS project. A project that generated two waves of national empirical studies, one in 2022 at the French national research center (CNRS)⁶ and the other in 2024 at the French biomedical research center (INSERM)⁷.

It should be noted that the elaboration of these participatory design gave rise to lengthy discussions within the research consortium. At first, some partners questioned if this was of the best way of involving institutional players in the research, while others were sceptical about the possibility of identifying these institutional players in their own national institutional landscape given that the profession is not developed or existent in some countries.

The implementation of the research design has shown that some of these initial concerns, while justified, were not insurmountable. For example, while some partners were concerned that they would not be able to find enough co-investigators, the recruitment of a co-investigator has opened up new opportunities. More generally the implementation of a research design centered on research institutions cannot ignore the great diversity of national institutional landscapes. For example, while it was relatively easy to identify research integrity officers in France, it was much more challenging in countries such as Greece or Spain.

⁶ See CovETHOS 2022 report, available online: <https://www.gemass.fr/projet-covethos-le-rapport-de-recherche-est-boucle-lintegrite-scientifique-et-lethique-de-la-recherche-a-lepreuve-de-la-crise-covid-19-une-enquete-par-questionnaire-aupres-du-personnel/>).

⁷ See CovETHOS 2024 report available online, <https://www.gemass.fr/enquete-inserm/>

2.2. Selecting the co-investigators

According to the protocol described in Deliverable 3.1, each POIESIS national partner was responsible for the organization of at least 3 focus groups in close collaboration with at least 3 institutional stakeholders acting as co-investigators. Each partner was asked to select their co-investigators in two broad thematic categories: stakeholders related to scientific integrity and stakeholders related to social integration. The table below shows the nature of the positions potentially held by the participants in each category.

Table 1 - Two categories of co-investigators

Research integrity	Social integration
[1] leaders and managers in research performing organizations	[7] open science policy advisers
[2] leaders and managers in research funding organizations	[8] communication and outreach officers in research performing organizations
[3] editors of peer-reviewed journals	[9] communication and outreach officers in research funding organizations
[4] members of the committee on publication ethics	[10] press officers
[5] research integrity officers	
[6] R&I policy makers	

To ensure the best selection of institutional stakeholders, the partners were asked to take a number of criteria into account: age, gender, type of institutional positions, degree of experience, degree of public exposure, geographical location, etc.

Recruitment strategies have of course been adapted to local constraints. Some partners, unable to rely on the existence of a pre-existing institutional landscape, relied on their own professional network to approach the potential coinvestigators. Others, despite having established institutional resources, faced challenges in identifying individuals with experience in their roles due to rapid turnover in certain positions'. Generally speaking, however, it can be observed that this initial recruitment phase, which was essential for the empirical investigation, proceeded smoothly, overall. The few refusals were linked not so much to a lack of interest but to a

predictable lack of availability or a perceived lack of skills to act as a co-investigator.

The table below shows the distribution of POIESIS co-investigators (n=24). For more details about the POIESIS co-investigators see appendix A.

Table 2 - distribution of co-investigators

Country	Male	Female	RI	SI
Denmark	0	3	2	1
France	2	1	3	0
Germany	3	1	2	2
Greece	3	1	3	1
Portugal	0	3	1	2
Spain	2	1	2	1
United kingdom	1	3	3	1
Total	11	13	16	8

2.3. Training the co-investigators

As with all participatory research, a certain number of conditions had to be met to ensure that participation was genuine. It was essential not only to ensure that the research objectives were clearly understood by the co-investigators, but it was also important to make them feel at ease during the research process. Individuals taking part in participatory research often have doubts about their own ability to carry out the research process successfully. They therefore need to be reassured, in particular by providing them with the information and resources they need.

Two online training sessions were organized by the coordinator on 29 February and 2 March 2024. These online training sessions were conducted in English. The aim was to review the general objectives of the research project, but also to familiarize the co-investigators with the focus group method. These sessions took place in a very pleasant atmosphere, and participants expressed their satisfaction

regarding the usefulness of the information provided. The first training session attracted 10 participants. The second session brought together 6 additional participants. A special session for the 3 French co-investigators was organized in French by the coordinator. When participants were not available, it was up to the national partners to use the training resources available or the recordings of the training sessions to ensure that the research objectives and the research method were properly understood.

2.4. Selecting the participants

Once the co-investigators were selected, the empirical investigation required a new recruitment phase: that of the focus group participants. In conformity with the WP3 protocol, participants were selected from and through the co-investigator's professional networks. These participants had to represent, through their experiences or professional positions, one of the two thematic categories already identified: scientific integrity and social integration.

In most cases, the recruitment strategy was defined and implemented in a collaboratively manner, based on a comparison of the proposals of the co-investigators and those of the partners. In some cases, the co-investigators contacted potential focus group participants themselves, in other cases contact was made by the project's national partners. In either case, it should be emphasized that this recruitment strategy, which explicitly relies on the co-investigator's established professional network, proved to be particularly effective.

Overall, as shown in the table below and with a number of groups slightly higher than the initial target, 22 focus groups were set up - three per country -, with a total of 131 participants, 55 men and 76 women. The general characteristics of the participants are described in Appendix B.

Table 3 - Focus groups and participants

Country	Number of Focus Groups	Number of Participants	Male	Female
Denmark	3	18	5	13
France	3	16	7	9
Germany	3	18	7	11
Greece	3	17	12	5
Portugal	3	20	7	13
Spain	3	16	10	6
United kingdom	4	26	7	19
Total	22	131	55	76

2.5. Materials for running the focus groups

In order to support partners in running the focus groups efficiently and ensure the coherence of the methodology among countries, the CNRS coordinator provided the materials listed below:

- Guidelines for running the focus groups (see Annex C)
- Information booklet for the co-investigators (See Annex D)
- The Participant Information Sheet (See Annex E)
- The Informed Consent form (See Annex F).

In addition to these essential resources sent to all the partners was also the moderator guide for conducting the focus group. The initial version of this guide was proposed by the CNRS coordinator, but was subsequently revised following discussions with all the project partners. It should be noted that this guide was also discussed with the co-investigators and sometimes gave rise to revisions, modifications or adaptations depending on the national context.

For example, the concept of "social integration" used in the POIESIS project was sometimes considered too ambiguous or inappropriate in some of the national contexts. Some partners preferred to use other notions such as "public engagement" (Portugal, United Kingdom), "citizen participation" (France) or "citizen involvement in science and technology" (Denmark).

The general structure of the moderator guide is reproduced below:

Sections	Topics & Questions	Follow-Up / Comments
Introduction	<p>Welcome the participants and introduce the facilitators.</p> <p>Discuss the purpose of the focus group and set some ground rules for the discussion.</p>	<p>Thank you for taking part in this discussion group.</p> <p>You have been contacted to take part in this discussion, because it seems to us that in one way or another this is a subject on which you will have interesting, original things to say...</p> <p>Mode of operation: approx. 2h of discussion The aim is to be as spontaneous as possible. First names may be used... / and formal address may be used.</p> <p>And your participation will enable us to feed our questioning and analysis.</p>
Icebreaker: Institutional Engagement with Science (10 minutes)	Have the participants introduce themselves and their roles within their respective institutions.	
Opening question (10 minutes)	Q_0 _ What words do you spontaneously associate with the relationship between science and society?	<p>If you need to stimulate the collective discussion, suggest the following dimensions:</p> <p>Crisis Education Culture Innovation Dialogue Empowerment Progress Misinformation</p>
<p>Understanding Perceptions: Trust in Science (20 minutes)</p> <p>RQ1. How do institutional stakeholders perceive, globally and locally, the level of public trust in science and technology and its implications?</p>	<p>Q.1 _ We often hear about a crisis of trust in science. How do you feel about this? What are your thoughts or experiences with this?</p> <p>Q.2 _ Advances in science and technology or</p>	<p>If you need to stimulate the collective discussion, suggest the following dimensions:</p> <p>a crisis that affects all countries in the same way, or is more visible in specific countries - and why...</p> <p>a crisis that affects science as a whole or, on the contrary, a crisis that affects only certain sectors of science</p> <p>a deep crisis or, on the contrary, a temporary crisis with no major consequences</p> <p>a crisis that affects all scientists, experts and scientific mediators, or, on the contrary, a crisis that affects a specific group</p> <p>a crisis that affects all scientific organizations, or that primarily concerns certain organizations, such as public research or industrial research</p> <p>If you need to stimulate the collective discussion, suggest the following dimensions:</p>

	<p>certain scientific practices sometimes might provoke enthusiasm but also sometimes hesitation or uncertainty. What do you think about these reactions?</p>	<p>Are these different reactions observed present in society as a whole, or only in certain parts/groups of society?</p> <p>When some members of the general public have doubts about technological advances, are these doubts generally well-founded or based on misinformation? Can opposition or mobilization against a particular innovation be useful, or do they undermine scientific culture in general?</p>
<p>Exploring Scientific Integrity (20 minutes)</p> <p>How do institutional stakeholders perceive the culture of research integrity in their own institutional and national environment?</p>	<p>Q3. _ We often hear about scientific integrity as a more or less shared culture. From your perspective or experience, what are the qualities expected of a scientist with integrity?</p> <p>Q4 _ We sometimes wonder about the extent of scientific misconduct. How common do you think such misconduct is? What can drive a researcher to ignore scientific integrity?</p>	<p>If you need to stimulate the collective discussion, suggest the following dimensions:</p> <p>Values, principles, rules, norms : honesty, transparency, objectivity, impartiality, etc. Who's concerned? Colleagues, Academics, Researchers, Administrative staff, Students, etc. Are you familiar with "good" practices, related to scientific integrity? Are you aware of guidelines, codes or declarations related to scientific integrity?</p> <p>If you need to stimulate the collective discussion, suggest the following dimensions:</p> <p>Do you think misconducts are rare or frequent? What kind of misconduct have you heard about? Do you think misconducts are committed by isolated individuals? ("bad apple") And what about ... scientific competition, lack of training, publication metrics, private interest and funding, etc.</p>
<p>Exploring Social Integration (20 minutes)</p> <p>How do institutional stakeholders perceive the culture of social integration in their own institutional and national environment?</p>	<p>Q5 _ Let's turn now to the question of social integration in science and technology. To your knowledge, what form can the social integration of science and technology take? And what</p>	<p>If you need to stimulate the collective discussion, suggest the following dimensions:</p> <p>The inclusion of non-academics or citizens into the scientific knowledge production process the inclusion of non-academics or citizens in the ethics boards responsible for assessing the consequences of a scientific project the inclusion of non-academics or citizens in the scientific councils responsible for defining research orientations Should all social groups be involved in the research process or its evaluation, and if not, which groups should be involved as a priority?</p>

	<p>forms are the most interesting to you? And in your own institution, what are the most common forms of social integration used?</p> <p>Q6. Do you think that the social integration can be useful for the dissemination of scientific knowledge and innovations to the general public?</p>	<p>If you need to stimulate the collective discussion, suggest the following dimensions:</p> <p>Science communication, science popularization, Participatory Exhibits and Museums citizen science initiatives, citizen committee public forums, citizen conferences Collaborative platforms, collaboration between artists and scientists</p>
<p>Institutional Contributions to Trust in Science (30 minutes)</p> <p>To what extent do institutional stakeholders consider that responsible research practices and social integration could be fostered by institutional governance arrangements and policy environments? What kind of institutional governance arrangements and policy environments should be considered as key priorities?</p>	<p>Q7 _ How can your institution make a positive contribution to promoting scientific integrity?</p> <p>Q8 _ How can your institution make a positive contribution to promoting social integration?</p> <p>Q9 _ Let's now try to think about how we can have a</p>	<p>For Q7 and Q8 If you need to stimulate the collective discussion, suggest the following dimensions:</p> <p>Promoting the transformation of structural factors such as pressure to publish or competition between scientific teams Transforming the metrics of evaluation associated with the recruitment and the promotion of scientists better training for researchers and students (Integrate ethics training into scientific education and research programs, promote accessible online courses). Organize events where scientists can interact with the public in informal settings, discussing their work and answering questions. Provide simplified summaries of research findings or communicate in plain language to help the general public understand the significance of scientific findings Create and promote podcasts or webinars that explore scientific topics in an accessible and entertaining format. Structures and guidelines for scientific integrity</p> <p>If you need to stimulate the collective discussion, suggest the following dimensions:</p>

	<p>positive impact on the public's trust in science. How can we act on the institutional dimensions of integrity and integration to improve this trust?</p>	<p>Create new positions such as referents or correspondents dedicated to these issues Ensure diversity in research teams, leadership, and decision-making bodies. Implement outreach programs that engage with local communities. introduce forms of regulation and moderation around scientific communication and combat misinformation fund research or technological programs on scientific misinformation (science informed policies) Empowering marginalized communities and addressing social inequalities through research or technological programs</p>
Wrap Up and Next Steps (10 minutes)	<p>Summarize key points from the discussion. Invite final thoughts and comments from the participants. Discuss the next steps after the focus group, such as how the data will be used and any follow-up that will be done</p>	

The moderator guide was designed for an approximative duration of 2 hours. This expected duration was met by all partners.

Although the discussions sometimes revealed differences of opinion or opposition between the various participants in the discussion group, in most cases the partners felt that the discussion groups had gone very well. There were no complex situations for the facilitators to manage. There was mutual respect between the participants, resulting in excellent quality discussions. Each participant was able to express his or her opinion freely. The feedback sessions that systematically followed the discussion groups showed also that the co-investigators had found the research situation sometimes difficult but always rewarding and useful. As always with a moderator guide, some facilitators chose to put more emphasis on one or other part of the guide depending on the interest and experience of the participants. Overall, however, all the topics that were supposed to be covered were dealt with in depth.

2.6. Setting up of the focus groups

The focus groups across seven countries were conducted by each consortium partner in their own country, and in their national language. The date and venue were chosen according to local convenience. The table below presents the dates and locations of the 24 focus groups.

The research partners had the option of organizing these focus groups either on site or online. As shown in the table below, all the focus groups were held between February and March 2024. Most of them were conducted online (15) and 7 were conducted on-site, in particular to ensure maximum availability of participants. The viability of these discussion groups depended largely on the availability of institutional stakeholders. While most of the partners conducted 3 focus groups in accordance with the protocol, the UK partner chose to add an additional focus group.

Table 4 - Focus groups: dates and venues

Country	Period	Venues
Denmark	Between 5th and 8th February 2024	2 on-site (IT University of Copenhagen) 1 on-site (University of Southern Denmark in Odense)
France	Between 4th and 14th March 2024	3 online
Germany	Between 6th and 14th of February 2024	3 online
Greece	From 19th to 23th February 2024	1 on-site (Athens) 2 online
Portugal	February 2024	2 on-site (Iscte - Instituto Universitário de Lisboa) 1 online
Spain	Between 5th, and 26th of March 2024	3 online
United kingdom	Between 29th February and 5th March	1 on-site 3 online

The English and Portuguese partners suggested combining the focus groups with a classification exercise to map communication tasks that these practitioners see as related to science communication (See Annex G). This exercise could be carried out on site or online. The results of this classification exercise will be presented in a separate report.

2.7. Data analysis

The qualitative data from the focus groups was collected through audio recordings. When the focus group was held on site, the recording was made using a standard digital recorder. When the focus group was held online, the recording was made using the integrated functions of the digital tool used online (zoom, teams, etc.).

Each partner produced a verbatim transcript of the content of their focus groups. The transcriptions were made in the original national language. Using computer-assisted qualitative data analysis software (CAQDAS/NVivo), the data from the transcripts was coded by each partner using a common coding scheme provided by the coordinator.

The coding approach initially adopted consisted of distinguishing between sociological notions or concepts - perception, attitude, factor, reasons and recommendations - on the one hand, and empirical dimensions or empirical objects associated with the use of sociological notions - science, trust, integrity, integration or institutions - on the other. The result was a theoretical matrix containing 25 possible codes.

Table 5 - Coding matrix

	Science	Trust	Integrity	Integration	institutions
Perception	1	2	3	4	5
Attitude	6	7	8	9	10
Factor	11	12	13	14	15
Rationale	16	17	18	19	20
Recommendations	21	22	23	24	25

This coding approach consists of covering a set of links between sociological concepts and various empirical dimensions, but apart from the fact that not all the codes have the same probability of being used, the qualitative material may go beyond this matrix in one way or another. It was therefore essential not to have too rigid a vision of this matrix and to add specific codes if necessary, depending on the qualitative material obtained. All the partners have been able to preserve a form of flexibility in relation to this code grid. Emerging sub-topics and themes were inductively coded and added

to the codebook. The co-investigators were also asked to comment on and, if necessary, add to the qualitative analysis produced on the basis of this code grid.

A cross-country analysis was then performed by the CNRS coordinator based on the reading and coding of the 7 national reports produced by POIESIS research partners. The latter were asked to make the empirical material visible through extracts and quotes in the original version (national language used during the discussion) but also in a English version. Some translated extracts are included in the section 3 of this general report.

Comparative analysis of the various national reports undoubtedly highlights both convergences and divergences between the different countries represented. However, one need to be relatively cautious when interpreting the results, because the focus groups are neither intended to constitute a representative panel of a population, nor to produce an exhaustive representation of a national reality. Furthermore, it should be remembered that the 22 focus groups brought together institutional stakeholders who developed a "situated" point of view based on their position as well as their professional trajectory. This institutional inscription of the discourse of both participants and co-investigators must be taken into account in any attempt to generalize the results. Nonetheless, the comparative analysis provides food for thought in terms of generalizations that can be tested using other methods, in particular questionnaire-based approaches involving larger populations of respondents.

3. Lessons from the focus groups

The 'HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-44' call for proposals on 'Societal trust in science, research and innovation' stipulated a set of three intuitively appealing assumptions:

- First, that "... trust depends on scientists and engineers' capacity to demonstrate high standards of research integrity" and that breaches to research integrity, i.e. research misconduct or questionable research practices, will lead to mistrust.

- Second, that "... citizen and civil society's involvement in co-creating R&I agendas and contents makes research more relevant and responsive to society and strengthens co-ownership and trust".

- Third, the call assumes that these markers of responsible research practices - integrity and societal integration - are "fostered by conducive institutional governance arrangements and policy environments". The assumption is that institutions matter by enabling and supporting researchers to act responsibly.

As stated during the POIESIS proposal submission process, these three assumptions are all interesting and plausible but deserve to be confronted with empirical findings. Is it possible, for example, that trust in science is only indirectly linked to the behaviour of researchers? Or might extensive inclusion directly, or indirectly, contribute to mistrust, for example through suspicion about the lack of independence of research? While the 22 focus groups conducted may not definitively resolve these questions, they provide rich insights into how a broad spectrum of institutional stakeholders across European countries perceive the connections between the concepts of integrity, integration, institution, and public trust in science.

The structure of this section is partly based on the moderator guide used during the focus groups, with 3.1) a first section devoted to the relationship between science and society, 3.2) a second focusing on trust in science, 3.3.) a third discussing scientific integrity, 3.4.) a fourth dealing with social integration, 3.5) a fifth devoted to the "chains of mediations", and finally 3.6) a sixth detailing the recommendations for institutions willing to take positive action on trust in science. It is not the objective of this section to go into the details of each national situation - readers wishing to delve deeper into the characteristics of a particular country may usefully refer to the national reports in the annex H.

Since we believe that the importance of the work carried out in POIESIS lies in the quality of the empirical material collected through the focus groups, we have chosen to make this qualitative material visible in this report through numerous extracts from the transcripts.

3.1. About science and society

In Europe and around the world, the Covid crisis has given rise to much debate about the nature of the relationship between science and society. Some have emphasized the contribution that science can make to overcoming a pandemic situation. Others, on the contrary, emphasized the challenge to the cultural authority of scientific discourse in the public arena.

To start the collective discussion, participants were all asked to spontaneously describe what they considered to be the main characteristics of the relationship between science and society. Without commenting on the diversity of words used by the participants, most focus groups described this relationship as “complex” and “multidimensional”.

It is made up of “interest” but also of “ignorance”. It is made up of “fascination” but also of “disenchantment”. It is made up of “expectations” but also of “contestation”.

There is a consensus that during the COVID crisis, the public's interest in advancements in science and technology grew significantly. Due to the high stakes and the extensive coverage of scientific discourse in the media, science became a frequent topic of conversation among the general public. As one participant observed, during this period, people were discussing the biology of RNA with the same interest they previously reserved for football competitions. But for a large number of participants, this obvious interest was combined with an “ignorance” of the very nature of the scientific process. The place given to “uncertainty” in science has given rise to a great deal of public misunderstanding. Some participants spoke of a lack of scientific literacy, while others referred to a “disconnection” or “gap” between the way the general public perceives science and the reality of the scientific process itself.

“It's embarrassing (...) since society is ignorant of what science is made of, it takes science as a belief. So what constitutes the differentiating status of science is not perceived” (France_FG2_2)

Other participants described the ambivalence inherent to the relationship between science and society by evoking, on the one hand, a form of public “fascination” for the new knowledge, new technologies and all the innovations, and, on the other hand, a “doubt” or acute “critical sense” about the capacity of these innovations to transform social life in a positive way. This issue of the social impact of science was frequently combined with contrasted views about the balance to be struck between basic and applied research. In Germany, as in Denmark, it was pointed out that funding agencies were sometimes too unilateral in their support to applied science looking short term social impact to the detriment of research being “curiosity driven”.

Finally, and this is not unrelated to what has just been said about the importance given to social impact, many participants contrasted what they perceived to be society's high “expectations” towards the scientific community with what they also perceived to be a growing questioning of the “legitimacy” or “authority” of the scientific institution itself, but more generally of all institutions in society.

“Science itself does not have a crisis, but how we deal with unscientific theses that are dressed up as science, in this regard we have a crisis of communication, a crisis of legitimisation or a crisis of politics” (Germany - FG_University communication)

“(…) and there is this ambivalence, [because on the one hand there is] this loss of authority, i.e. it is science and is not a saviour. It can't provide us with answers. On the other hand, however, there is a total exaltation of science, i.e. the expectation in the corona crisis that scientists should fix it. And I believe that this ambivalence is a crucial point”. (Germany - FG_Good scientific practice)

For many participants in all focus groups, it would be unrealistic to consider the relationship between science and society without acknowledging changes in the public perception of all social and political institutions. Scientific institutions, particularly universities, are nowadays increasingly entangled in political discussions, with expectations for them to take stances in debates such as the Middle East conflict.

3.2. Public trust in science and technology

Is it possible to speak of a general crisis of trust between science and society in our post-COVID context? Although many public debates assume the existence of a growing lack of trust among the general public, our participants offer a much more nuanced view.

In Denmark, Germany, Portugal, Spain, United Kingdom, and to a lesser extent in France and Greece, participants agreed that the scientific community, and science in general in contrast to other institutions, enjoyed globally a high level of trust from society.

"...there is a scientism where people need to trust something, they don't trust institutions anymore. I think they trust quite a lot, quite a lot in scientists and they demand absolute certainties from them". (Spain, FG1_1)

"The data on trust in scientists, it's gone down a little bit in the last few years it seems, but no, no, there's no widespread distrust. Quite the contrary. And in fact in Spain the confidence is quite high, when we also see data regarding other professions". (Spain - FG1_4)

[Crisis of trust]... I think that might be over-egging it [...] there are research areas that do face a lot of public backlash and difficulties for certain researchers [...] I would say they're very minority and it's important not to over-emphasise what a few individuals are doing." - (United Kingdom - P14)

"There is no reason to think that there is mistrust in science. However, there are certain attitudes, increasingly present in contemporary society, that are blatantly anti-science. And I think it's very difficult to fight such attitudes with the weapons of science." (Portugal, FG3_7)

As these excerpts suggest, even if the notion of a general crisis of trust in science is not backed by our participants, nor by empirical evidence, this does not rule out more specific attention given to particular critical areas or critical situations. Some partners mention in their national environment the existence of "pockets of distrust" (UK), "instances of mistrust" (DK). Indeed, it is well

documented that certain fields or certain scientific or technological subjects – stem cells, climate agenda, vaccines, new developments in technology, artificial intelligence, and genetically modified crops – remain controversial in the public sphere.

Participants appear to be generally guided by the idea that even if there is no general crisis of trust yet, various discrete or limited signals point to the possibility of a growing fragilization of the scientific institution in the near future. Hence, there is a need to act on a range of factors considered to be more or less problematic.

Four factors illustrated below were regularly mentioned: scientific literacy, independence from economic or ideological interests, social relevance, and scientific mediation.

- science communication, scientific literacy or general public understanding of the very nature of the scientific research process

"The question of science being something that one day is true, another day is not... (...) And for scientists that's the advancement of science and for other people that might be what leads to greater mistrust." (Portugal, FG3_6)

"(...) global warming and the covid crisis (...) have amplified the problem of the crisis of trust, because people don't usually know how it works. People have always challenged the results of science, because they don't know how it works (...) they have realised that what a scientist says at a given moment can be contradicted ten months later (...)" (France, FG2_1)

- the independence of scientists from political or economic interests

"Independence. So that you can then really say no matter in which direction, funding or doing someone a favour or something, that is a very important component for me." (Germany Focus Group University Communication)

"The fact that I hear a researcher who is independent of politicians means a LOT to me and my impression of research. If I believe that someone is in the pockets of others, then that person

loses their credibility. As long as I can believe that research is independent, then I can actually trust that - it's again a counterbalance against political currents and so on, but this places very large - what's it called - or high demands on research ethics, that it's in order" (Denmark, P2, female, RPO, FG1).

*"With regard to the funding of research to a researcher working in a public institution, in the case of the medical sciences, this question is often raised by conflicts of interest and the suspicions that exist because certain studies are paid for by pharmaceutical companies. This can generate some mistrust."
(Portugal, FG3_2)*

- the relevance of scientific research for people's everyday lives
-

"If people have nothing to do with science, then it's easy to trust. 'I don't care what they do.' Like that, right? But the moment it diffuses into everyday life, I have to take a stand on it somehow. I actually think we're all completely overwhelmed right now, really everyone. And some perceive this as powerlessness, and I can totally understand that." (Germany, Focus Group University Communication)

- the work carried out by the generalist media and the specialised media to inform the general public about science and technology
-

*"[I]t is a matter of media approach, I think in the end that is a sensationalist approach: fear. "What about artificial intelligence?", "Oops, machines are going to dominate us and I don't know what", and "millions of jobs are going to disappear so and so" and that, that's what sells and that's what is being published, especially in the area of artificial intelligence.
(Spain, FG3_2)*

"In general, scientific colleagues who publish take precautions, but the translation in the media takes shortcuts and leads people to take at face value results that have yet to be consolidated... and so this creates mistrust because, in the end, afterwards... The media sometimes relay the results a little too quickly, or take shortcuts. When the public isn't fully aware of how the process works, we may end up taking shortcuts that ultimately create a bit of mistrust in my opinion..." (France, FG1_2)

While reflecting on the various factors that can act positively or negatively on the expression of trust, a number of participants across countries discussed this expectation of trust coming from most institutions. Do scientific institutions necessarily need to cultivate trust, and if so, what kind of trust should be favored? After all, isn't there something contradictory about seeking to cultivate a critical rationality in the general public while at the same time asking for a high level of trust? If critical rationality is to be cultivated, this presupposes that this mindset can be applied to the scientific community itself, by becoming aware of its shortcomings as well as their potential effects on society.

"I think you should have trust in research, but I don't know if you should have blind trust in researchers (...). You should trust what is being presented more than the one presenting it" (Denmark, P3, male, RFO, FG 2).

Some participants observed that these internal dysfunctions were likely to be more apparent to the scientific community itself than to the general public. Hence, the general idea that it might be worth reconsidering the issue of trust from the perspective of the scientific community. Instead of solely focusing on the public's trust in scientists, participants suggested that it would be more valuable to examine the level of confidence that scientists themselves have in the scientific community. How do scientists perceive the behaviour of their colleagues? How do scientists perceive the functioning of recruitment, evaluation and promotion bodies within the scientific community?

"I think there may be some mistrust on the part of the public, but I think there's a lot of mistrust on the part of scientists towards themselves, towards each other." (Portugal, FG1_2)

Shifting the focus on trust from the general public to the scientific community would undoubtedly open up new avenues for the social sciences. In particular, this would help to identify more clearly how scientists perceive the role of scientific institutions in generating scientific misconduct, but also the perceived institutional

dysfunctions associated with the institutional handling of misconduct cases.

3.3. Research integrity

While it has been possible to identify a broad consensus on the topic of public trust in science, the situation appears to be much more mixed when it comes to research integrity.

All the participants were asked to define the general state of the culture of research integrity in their respective countries. In some countries, such as Denmark, Germany and Portugal, the participants agreed that their respective communities were generally highly respectful of the rules and values of research integrity.

"I don't think lack of integrity is that common. I honestly think that most people do research with integrity." (Portugal, FG1_5)

In countries such as Greece, Spain, France and the United Kingdom, the participants found it more difficult to reach a consensus about the current state of research integrity. Scientific misconduct was described as a problematic issue but relatively difficult to measure precisely.

Fraudulent practices of all kinds can be found in all contexts (Spain, FG2_1)

"For a long time I believed that such and such a scientist, by definition, was transparent, honest, upright, etc. The reality, unfortunately, is quite different. (...) We had the intergalactic example of Professor Raoult. (...) He's someone who stops at nothing, who has an incredible ego (...) you can see that he's a thug... and that the people who worked with him are thugs too... (...) they used false certificates, they included patients in unauthorised studies, and so on. But that's what happened on a daily basis at the Marseille IHU, but it shouldn't just happen at the Marseille IHU (...) (France, FG3_2)

The participants were also divided about the state of development of the institutional management of research integrity in their respective countries. The national institutional landscape has been judged to be weak or non-existent in countries such as Spain, Portugal and Greece. In other countries, such as Germany, France and Denmark, although the participants agreed in recognising the institutional efforts made over the last 20 years, they didn't always share the same perception of the consequences of these efforts. In France, for example, those who have been involved in the various reforms carried out considered that the bulk of the reforms have been carried out and that we should now wait for them to bear fruit. Others argued that while these reforms were beneficial, they fell short of addressing the remaining challenges of research integrity. Notably, significant emphasis was placed on the institutional culture surrounding the management of scientific misconduct.

Values and factors of integrity

The participants agreed more on the characterization of the values of research integrity. Generally speaking, a researcher with integrity was described as "reflexive", "honest", "transparent", "competent", "sharing data", "open to counterevidence", "able to communicate about his doubts", "having no vested interest", "avoiding advocacy". These values were described as much as personal and organisational attributes.

"[A scientist with integrity is] someone who is open to scrutiny and, if there are mistakes, is willing to own them." (Portugal, FG3_3)

"A researcher with integrity also has to develop characteristics such as knowing how to work in a team, knowing how to relate to society, having certain communication and relationship skills with society and his environment". (Spain, FG1_2)

In contrast, researchers in situations of potential misconduct were regularly described as "driven by personal ambition", working in "isolation" or in a "problematic professional environment", sometimes "experiencing difficulties in their personal lives", and subject to "high pressure" or a "heavy mental workload".

Following on this general profile, participants agreed on the list of various personal, situational, organizational or institutional factors likely to account for breaches of research integrity. Some of these factors are already well documented in the existing literature on research integrity and scientific misconduct:

- Precarious employment in academia

"But it also becomes existential for people like me who am not tenured and people who live in this limbo between PhD and tenure, we are in a hunt for a security and are forced to play by the rules of productivity (...) You can see the anxiety among younger colleagues to produce a paper in which I will discover. I'm going to put a name on something. Which may not have been named by someone before. Various such things." (Greece, FG2_1)

- Pressure-to-publish mentality

"There's a lot of pressure for researchers to have CVs with lots of papers, lots of papers, the number. It's the number that counts. Quality, at a certain point, was no longer relevant." (Portugal, FG3_1)

- Competition for recognition or reputation

"I think we need to talk about competition when it comes to integrity. We are facing a strong competition, amplified from the outside. Which is not generic. And which naturally drives scientists towards excellence, for example. [...] And the competition relates to everything, including third-party funding, publications, etc. And of course, in this context, there are incentives to violate good scientific practice." (Germany, Focus Group University Communication)

- Lack of integrity training

"Research Centres, both Universities and Centres, I think that we have to train people, not only young people, but also people who have been doing research for a long time and who think that they are doing nothing wrong and probably do many bad things". (Spain, FG1_4)

- Insufficient time to open up and make data available

"Its lack of time and the pressure that everybody's under that gets surfaced time and time again, and I think again that the system is a major problem, and I think that's where academics feel, you know, sort of quite hostile to the topic, not completely [...] well I suppose you know grumpy, not hostile grumpy." (United Kingdom, p20).

- Conflicts of interests

"(...)It's true that there have been abuses, there have been people who have filled their pockets, who haven't revealed their conflicts of interest, that's absolutely true, but it's up to us to counterbalance that, to set up counter-fires, tools, to conduct research that is aware of the impact it has on society, and that provides itself with the means to be more honest, more balanced." (France, FG2_3)

- Peer-review and open access

" (...)there's also a huge peer-review crisis, because so much research is being produced, and then this - excuse me - open access monster has been created. Everyone talked about this 'open access.' 'We just need open access,' and now it's just - if you ask, many researchers think it's a nightmare. Because there are far too many journals and far too lax control over data, with the presentations (...)". Many of them [researchers] share this story. That they often say no to peer review or to reviewing, right? Because they don't get anything out of it. And the same happens when they themselves submit something, so it's extremely difficult for journals to actually find reviewers. And this just means that much, or some, will more likely get through without the proper

quality stamp and without the proper processing before being published. And I just think we've seen the beginning of this. It's going to become a bigger problem moving forward" (Denmark, P1, female, RFO, FG2).

- Predatory journals
-

"(...) scientific integrity is a major issue! it's an absolutely major issue! (...) There's a lot to be said about predatory journals and about the behaviour of researchers themselves (France, FG1_3).

These various factors are well documented in the available scientific literature, and it is interesting to note that most participants agree on their importance. But it seems also interesting to emphasize certain institutional dimensions which are perhaps less often discussed but which help to highlight some of the differences between the different countries represented in this project.

Need for shared codes of integrity.

Across all groups, participants considered that research integrity cannot be taken for granted: all scientists must be trained and regularly updated on the guidelines and codes of good practices produced at national or European level.

While participants in some countries believed that scientists were familiar with these codes, in others, participants suggested that these codes were rarely read, even by leading scientific organizations. It is therefore necessary to ensure not only the quality of these guides, but also their optimal dissemination. Insofar as scientific activity is developing on an international scale, it was considered essential for these codes to be standardized, simplified and shared. The Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) initiative was cited in several groups (Denmark, France, Portugal) as an example of establishing shared rules that can enhance trust and promote research integrity.

"We're in COARA, a European group where research evaluation models are being questioned, particularly to deal with this "publish or

perish" pressure. (...) Today there's also a lot of talk about the impact that research has on society." (Portugal, FG1_1)

Contradictory injunctions.

Several participants, particularly from Germany, France, and the UK, underscored the tensions, the conflicting expectations or injunctions that scientists face through their professional endeavors. Some of these tensions are well established and come from many fronts including the institutions where research takes place. For example, scientists are frequently asked to be ever more specialized in their field of research, but also to be ever more capable of communicating to an ever wider public. Scientists are asked to give up publishing in prestigious journals with a high impact factor, while at the same time asked to submit applications to European funding agencies, which presuppose a highly competitive publication record, and so on. But all the tensions and contradictions are not always so visible, in participants' views. Identifying, analyzing and resolving these organizational contradictions has sometimes been presented as a professional role in its own right:

(...) That's the institution's job, to work in all areas of the institution to limit tensions. Whether it's evaluation processes, recognition processes, human resources support for groups... that's the job I've given myself (...) to work with all the departments in the institution to track down all the places where their processes could come into conflict with scientific integrity, ethics and professional conduct. And that's really the job of the institution. So the outside world is what it is, we don't necessarily have any control over it (...) but what we do have control over, and by that I mean our institutions, is to build an environment within the institution that is as favourable as possible, as conducive as possible, and therefore as free from paradoxical injunctions as far as values are concerned. (France, FG2_2)

Promoting a positive and open culture of research integrity.

While all the participants agree on the objective of establishing research integrity as a "shared culture", they do not all emphasize the same dimensions of this culture. In Denmark, the emphasis has been on the need to move away from a "reactive culture" driven by the

market. In two of the three focus groups (university communication and research funding, current debates about scientific misconduct, were described as “driven from the outside of academia by companies that have specialised in the search for plagiarism. Instead of proactively countering scientific misconduct, research only reacts once there are allegations” (DK report, p.11). In Germany, the emphasis has been on the need to acknowledge the importance of doubt and error in the research culture: “(...) a change of the internal scientific culture towards an actual ‘culture of error’ (“Fehlerkultur”), in which it would not only be accepted but supported and encouraged to make mistakes and learn from them. Currently, the high pressure to publish as much as possible – also because obtaining external funding very much depends on it – hinders scientists from a) going new and unexplored ways in their research because they cannot be sure that the former will work out and b) to openly address mistakes or uncertainties with regard to their research” (GER report, p.11). In France, the emphasis has been on the need to transitioning from an institutional culture of secrecy to wholeheartedly embracing a positive and transparent culture of research integrity. Non-transparent integrity management was described as problematic in terms of fostering the development of a shared culture of integrity:

“I have the impression that (...) we haven't completely taken the step of saying “there comes a time when it's better to reveal and deal with problems head-on, in a transparent way, rather than sweep them under the carpet”. We haven't yet taken that step, at least not everywhere and on all issues... there's still a real temptation to say “let's not talk about it”, like family secrets in the end... let's not talk about it and it will cease to exist”
(France, FG2_3)

It was also stressed that this positive culture of integrity should be shared uniformly and equally by all research organisations, regardless of their specific field of investigation. Differences in misconduct management between organisations can only lead to misunderstandings and the feeling among researchers that nothing is really being done to ensure that the rules and values of integrity are globally respected.

About integrity and trust.

Finally, it is important to consider how participants described the relationship between integrity and public trust in science. In Portugal, “even though the participants believe there is no crisis of trust in science, they identified a few situations and contexts that might lead to distrust. One of these situations refers to cases of lack of integrity” (PT report, p.12). In Denmark, participants acknowledged the possibility that scientific misconduct could have a negative effect on public trust in science, but this effect was generally considered to be fairly limited: “they believed these instances are not capable of overturning the ‘supertanker’ as a whole” (DK report, p.21). In Germany, participants emphasised the role of transparency in increasing trust in science. They argued that scientists should make their doubts and uncertainties more clearly visible to the general public. This would contribute to a better understanding of the scientific process, but would also avoid possible misunderstandings that could undermine trust in science.

"I believe that trust [...] is not strengthened by saying: 'it is like this', but rather 'it is PROBABLY like this', but there is also doubt, and we have to be clear and transparent about this doubt." (Germany, FG Research funding organizations)

In France, participants involved in facilitating public debate on scientific and technological issues pointed out that the term “integrity” itself was very rarely used by the general public. For those who express distrust of science in the public debate, the important issue was not a lack of integrity, but rather a lack of “independence” from political or economic interests. This remark shows that the conceptual distinction between ethics and research integrity should not be just a matter of theoretical debate but also a question of empirical investigation.

3.4. Social integration

The most significant disagreements between participants were undoubtedly related to the topic of “Social Integration”. There are

at least two reasons for this. The first relates to the degree of advancement or familiarity with social integration mechanisms, which varies greatly from one country to another. The second reason has to do with the complexity of the very notion of "social integration". As previously stated, the notion was occasionally replaced by other terms, including "public engagement" (Portugal and the United Kingdom), "citizen participation" (France) and "citizen involvement in science and technology" (Denmark). Some focus groups concentrated on communication and dissemination strategies rather than participatory mechanisms.

In Denmark as in the United Kingdom the prevailing sentiment among the participants was that there was a discernible positive dynamic surrounding citizen participation: "Participants commonly perceived a growing number of initiatives being launched to support the involvement of citizens into scientific knowledge production processes. This trend was observable both in universities, at large, and within individually funded research projects. Beyond traditional science communication formats, several participants referred to the use of participatory formats within their own organisations. These approaches include citizen science apps and initiatives, public consultations, user involvement in technological service innovations, and dialogue formats that emphasized deliberation and co-production of knowledge" (DK report, p.26); "Public engagement varies in magnitude and audiences, is now a pathway to impact, and increasingly features civic engagement. There is also a spectrum of formats (lectures, conferences, consultations) (...) public engagement is now almost an accepted way of working which was not there at the time of debates about genetically modified foods" (UK report, p.15).

In other countries, such as Portugal, Spain or France, participants observed a tendency towards greater societal involvement in scientific and technological decision-making. However, this trend was perceived as still fragile or ineffective : "some types of publics are still not interested or do not participate in science, some regions of the country do not have access science initiatives, and often the most appropriate channels or language are not used to capture the public's attention" (PT report, p.28); "once the idea of public participation accepted, scientists have to be trained, funding agencies have to allow sufficient time to develop original research protocols. However, training courses are not often available and

funding agencies have only very recently become involved in participatory science” (FR report, p.29).

“I think northern Europe is more advanced than France. We're in a programme with some universities in Northern Europe and we can see very clearly that they've been setting up science shops for several decades, where we're able to draw on the needs of society... we're a bit behind, it takes time to acculturate, to make our staff and colleagues understand that we have a real challenge here. The first challenge is to understand what science or participatory research is all about” (France, FG1_2)

A critical perspective on public participation

Beyond these notable discrepancies in terms of the advancement of participatory mechanisms, in Greece, Germany France or Spain, participants frequently exhibited critical opinions regarding the intrinsic value of developing such mechanisms : “The topic of social integration (...) led to controversial debates about whether the ongoing increase of integrating citizens in the scientific process was actually something positive, and also what ‘participation’ actually means and should look like” (GER report, p.8); “most group members recommended that the participation of ‘lay people’ in research should be mainly or exclusively limited to a consulting role if not any. Particularly useful according to them is the participation in such consulting committees in Medicine (patients, doctors, nurses etc.), exceptionally in groups like people with disabilities (...)” (GRE report, p.15).

“I think it's a question like, public jury, yes? or public jury, no? You can't put normal citizens to debate on subjects where there are people who have studied them, who know them. [...] What we must do is to try to get science to arrive in some way, through ethics committees, dissemination by public entities. But not to bring the public to the heart of the matter, because I don't think they will be able to understand it, or disseminate it, or help... No, I don't see it, I don't really see it, as the public jury, I don't see it”. (Spain, FG3_1)

“There's a difference between involving the public, as more active participants in your research, as opposed to things like the priorities of your research. Can you imagine if we asked the

public to scrutinise [...] research programme and give feedback on our programme and we would then take action based on it. I mean I don't think any researcher would be willing to do that, would they?" (United Kingdom, P6)

These extracts focus on the difficulty or supposed inability of the public to understand and engage with scientists. But more fundamentally, it seems that participatory mechanisms were sometimes perceived as undermining the value of scientific autonomy. A core value around which most scientific communities rally.

When the general principle of public participation was accepted, participants emphasised the risk of public participation being used as a superficial device. All too often, citizens were perceived as involved in the downstream phase of research (collecting data) without being involved in the design of the research or having access to the initial discussions that help to shape the participatory research process or the type of questions asked.

It was also stressed that it is important to create real participation from all parts of society and not just rely on social groups that are used to interacting with the scientific community. But this access is not always easy to create. In Portugal, "several participants in the three focus groups mentioned that scientific institutions and scientists keep 'preaching to the converted' and it is difficult to engage the other public, those who do not attend events such as the European Night of Researchers, science fairs, and do not go to museums, etc. (...) The biggest challenge of social integration is, in the view of the participants, to attract new people to science-related events and activities, create networks and establish new partnerships (...) participants suggested that researchers should develop and consider new ways of auscultating the citizens at a local and regional level such as assemblies for citizens or other specific groups (e.g., teachers, parents, people living in specific neighbourhoods). Thus, cooperating with local institutions/municipalities and organised movements (i.e., local associations) is imperative" (PT report, p.27). Moreover, once this diversity is achieved, there is also the crucial question of how citizens should be trained. Hence, as observed by most participants, the importance of having a precise and differentiated vision of the mechanisms of citizen participation.

In the United Kingdom for example, one participant “who works in the health sector, where people who use care services get involved in designing the research, said she often asks researchers if they learnt anything from the participants in the co-produced research and the answer is quite often ‘no, why would we change what our model was, based on feedback from people’.” (UK report, p.15). Other participants questioned the way in which participatory mechanisms could be perceived in one way or another as contributing to weakening the public image of science. Participatory schemes were perceived as complex and potentially counterproductive if misused: “[a participant] noted that public engagement could be damaging if researchers do not have the required skills, or they have not really thought through their engagement methods or who it is that they are engaging with.” (UK report, p.14).

Positive attitude towards social integration

It is noteworthy that participants who expressed the most positive attitude towards citizen participation were those who had the opportunity to develop or support these initiatives, particularly in two key areas: health and environmental issues. In Denmark, “While participants generally agreed on the benefits of citizen involvement in research, it was evident that those directly engaged in citizen science and public engagement generally held a more favourable view of the advantages. For instance, they highlighted the educational potential of sparking an interest in science from a young age, improving data and research outcomes, and enhancing trust in science, at large” (DK report, p.26).

The idea that citizen participation might be an interesting way to increase the scientific literacy of a given population was considered potentially interesting, but not without challenges. “On the one hand, citizen participation in science was considered to be ideally desirable and could be a driver for increasing science literacy. On the other hand, it was argued that without an adequate level of science literacy, participation in science, especially in decision-making, was not desirable” (ES report, p.10).

Participants who had had the opportunity to be part of these participatory actions clearly linked inclusion with the social “relevance” of research:

(...) in biomedical science, there have been some very fine experiments in participatory research, including patient associations in research projects, with of course people who possess the scientific knowledge (...) the robustness was guaranteed by the presence of people who have mastered the scientific approach, but the relevance... the relevance of the results obtained and their transferability, innovativeness, operability, etc, were significantly enriched by the presence of another perspective, of potential users, of people who were really concerned in another way by this. It's not easy, we're taking it slowly, but it's extremely interesting, not least because it's another way of forging the link between science and society.
(France, FG2_2)

"In the case of a research centre that works only with Parkinson's, we could have someone from civil society, someone who represents Parkinson's patients, a patients' association, for example, present on a scientific council, and who actually dictates the institute's research policies and which projects should be submitted for funding." (Portugal, FG2_3)

Some participants who have had the opportunity to develop participatory research projects stressed that involving non-researchers in a research project can be an effective way of becoming aware of one's own biases and thus improving the quality of the research:

(...) citizen involvement is insanely good where it's about uncovering bias, uncovering researchers' biases, bringing some diversity and variety into this, making researchers say 'okay, I have some assumptions and hypotheses, but how do other people actually see this, and people who aren't so steeped in this research world, how do they perceive things and so on and so forth'. So for me, I see citizen involvement very much as something that can improve research. Create more trust." (Denmark, P2, female, RPO, FG1).

What is described here is not so much the positive effect of participation on society through the creation of trust or 'social relevance', but the positive effect of participation on the nature of the research process itself. Ultimately, the trust suggested in

this extract is less the public's trust in research than the scientist's trust in his or her own research.

Social integration and trust

One of the expected benefits of social integration is, of course, public trust in science. But it is striking to notice that the participants were quite divided on this issue.

Several participants described the participatory mechanisms as "selling" a situation of exchange and dialogue that was not always fully realized. But if we create an expectation that is not met, there is an obvious risk of creating frustration and growing mistrust. This is clearly discernible in this exchange between two participants:

"(...) I think it's very important because very often, when we think we're doing participation, we're really doing consultation, that is, we're collecting opinions and different and diverse points of view, but with no real intention of taking them into account, or at least with the firm intention of taking them into account only up to a certain point. So we remain in our position of expert who is in charge, and we only take a little bit of input from outside. And that's really problematic in terms of the trust that people can place in participatory processes. We end up selling them a dream, we sell them a seat at the table that we don't really give them..

...Which can also be a problem in terms of scientific integrity... we come up with a process for getting data and then suddenly we decide to ignore it... so that's a problem... (...)" (France, FG2_3 & FG2_6).

Among the participants, those who were most familiar with these participatory mechanisms were generally those who thought they could have a positive impact on trust in science. The building of trust was described as being dependent on a number of factors: training of researchers in participatory research, institutions able to allow longer timeframes to take account of the complexity of the process, a diverse and educated public and, in most cases, a limited scale of participation:

(...)I was very surprised by the reactions of the citizens... suddenly there was trust... the fact of involving them, listening to them, coming back to them with the results, created trust in the protocol, but also trust in the results. It gave us a different point of view (...) participatory science is an excellent way to connect with science (...) mini-publics, small units that allow dialogue, these are the things we're going to activate regularly to provide citizens with information that is effective and not top-down. We know that the top-down approach has its advantages but also its disadvantages in the context of citizen participation... the ideal format is 6 to 8 people per table to create an exchange of views... (France, FG1_1)

This list of conditions brings us back to a division that emerged regularly in the focus groups between, on the one hand, participatory science, which was described as potentially effective in building trust but on a limited scale, and, on the other hand, more traditional scientific communication, which is likely to have a positive impact on a much larger population. In Denmark, “[a] participant felt that science communication efforts might generate more trust in science than public involvement in science. Echoing this sentiment, another participant working in science communication argued that “while citizen science allows for deeper participation, science communication initiatives have the potential to influence a larger number of citizens” (DK report, p.10).

Public participation at the cost of dissemination

Some participants contrasted “participation” and “dissemination”, pointing out that the issue of scientific information is a “battle” that should be fought on a large scale. Focusing too much on participation rather than dissemination could weaken the scientific community in this battle, and indirectly public trust in science. In Spain for example, “the main battleground regarding distrust in science was believed to be social media forms of communication. A fundamental gap between the younger and older generations, between ‘boomers’ and ‘tiktokers’ was portrayed as shaping both the channels of communication being used, but also a difference in the capacity to really understand the contexts and drivers of the new platforms” (ES report, p.16). In France, this emphasis on the right scale of

intervention in social networks was also discussed with the same confrontational terms:

"(...) Social networks are neither good nor bad, except that at the moment we're losing this war. The average use of Facebook for the 45-60 age group is 2.5 hours a day... and it's an old people's medium... that's where we need to be. There's no point in having a conference for 20 people, there's no point in sending a researcher into a classroom... To rebuild trust between the public and science, you need mass communication campaigns, mass information, more committed scientists taking a stand, and institutions putting a lot of resources into raising awareness. Some of this was done during the COVID period, but for me it's a battlefield and an information war (...)." (France, FG1_5)

Ultimately, what is being discussed here is precisely the strategy of trying to build public trust through participatory mechanisms. This strategy is seen as potentially effective on a very limited scale, but unable to address the problem of public trust in its full scale.

3.5. The chains of mediation

The POIESIS project examines how the notions of integrity, social integration and trust are articulated through a series of mediators. Who are these mediators? How are the various actors of this chain of mediation perceived by our participants? There is a relatively broad consensus that those involved in communicating science, whoever they may be, face a challenging task. Communicating science requires an understanding of how the scientific community operates, the importance of debate and uncertainty, the complexity of knowledge, and so on. It is also essential to know how to talk to the general public, to understand their areas of interest but also their potential unfamiliarity. Science communicators have to strike a fine balance that is not necessarily compatible with the value of the information market.

Traditional media

The traditional media clearly play an important role in the public's perception of science. However, these traditional media are often criticized by the participants for their “sensationalist” or “polarized” approach to scientific information. In Germany, participants argued that there is not so much a crisis of science as a crisis of science communication: “there is a crisis of communication and an important problem in the representation of scientific processes in science communication. This applies especially to the communication of scientific findings in the media, whose role in the linkage between science and society, for example during the pandemic, is seen very critically. In search of the strongest headlines, media is perceived to rather polarise than contextualise, thereby increasing uncertainty and fears or even distrust in science among the public” (GER report, p.12). In the United Kingdom, focus group participants, when discussing the alleged prevalence of scientific misconduct, observed that “scientific misconduct is not a widespread problem, but the media sensationalises some cases, putting careers into jeopardy. Some of these cases result more from incompetence or negligence (ethics failures, biased sampled, etc.) than intent” (UK report, p.12). There is also a perception that the media are too often in the habit of playing on the public's fears in order to attract attention:

“[I]t is a matter of media approach, I think in the end that is a sensationalist approach: fear. “What about artificial intelligence?”, “Oops, machines are going to dominate us and I don't know what”, and “millions of jobs are going to disappear so and so” and that, that's what sells and that's what is being published, especially in the area of artificial intelligence”.
(Spain, FG3_2)

This way of relying on fear rather than reasoned judgement is undoubtedly effective in getting immediate attention, but does not really have a lasting positive effect on building interest and knowledge. Another common criticism of traditional media is that they artificially play with the idea of neutrality by putting opposing views on an equal footing. “[media] need to make sure not to encourage and allow the increase of ‘false balance’, meaning not to give a platform to opinions with weak evidence or pseudo-scientific

discourses in trying to be overly 'transparent' about scientific uncertainties as this further increases insecurity and mistrust in science among the public" (GER report, p.24).

Science journalism

Beyond the expected criticism of the traditional media, it is interesting to observe that some participants may have a more positive view of the work done by a selected population of science journalists. This population is described as being in a relatively small minority. In Portugal, "participants considered that the space for science in the media has decreased in recent years, and that there are few newspapers and journalists specialising in this topic. The newspaper 'Jornal Público' is an exception and its journalists know how to reach people using simple language, such as infographics" (PT report, p.21).

But they see also challenges to science journalism. In the UK, "The participant argued that (...) trustworthy sources, such as the Guardian and the BBC, are also guilty sometimes of reporting things that are based on tiny studies or things where there are flaws" (UK report, p.10). In Greece, "science communication is often conducted by journalists and while some of them are **act** with integrity, some others are mainly interested in publicity, damaging both science communication and Trust In Science as a result" (GRE report, p.17).

In France, participants praised the quality of scientific information in a national newspaper where another participant of the same focus group worked. However, this participant, a science journalist, clearly pointed out that even in a favourable professional environment, certain issues, such as research integrity, remain difficult to deal with:

"You're not going to be very interested in my psychological state, but I can assure you (...) that it's not easy for us to deal with these issues of integrity ... because we could tell a story every week, because there are researchers all over the world who do really bad work, and so we could tell that story every week or every month, but well... And we ask ourselves which cases are going to interest us. And we try to talk about the ones that are going to be of interest to the public, the ones that, for example, highlight a dysfunction in the current regulations or highlight a

sad new trend in research. Because that's something that's very far-reaching, or, of course, if it's a star or a research manager. But because I hear some people say that we're hurting science by exposing its bad sides and its flaws. So I'm not really affected by it.... Because these comments are irrelevant..." (France, FG3_1).

Conscious of the impact of information on breaches of integrity has on the public image of science, this journalist defines the general lines of an information practice that can be qualified as "responsible": avoiding the sensationalist accumulation of cases, defining criteria on the basis of which the most relevant cases can be selected according to their informational value.

Social networks

Of course, as already mentioned, much of the discussion revolved around the role of social networks. Although the various surveys available highlight the fact that scientists frequently see social networks as an opportunity to renew scientific communication, the discussions focused mainly on their ability to accelerate disinformation among the general public. In Spain, "Contemporary media, and particularly social media platforms, was (...) framed as the primary factor undermining trust in science. The lack of authority of the traditional scientific voice, and the prioritization of entertainment over expertise seemed important principles at work. (...) In terms of taking steps to improve the trust relationship, participants recommended the relatively standard approach of joining the battle and some more radical innovations addressed to the 'influencers' who may deliberately or unwittingly promote distrust in science and technology (...) A 'vocal minority' are seen to be particularly important in driving the agenda on social media in such a way that a controversial social issue becomes more directly linked to the credibility of scientific evidence." (ES report, p.12).

"Maybe this more traditional media model has been broken by... by the emergence of social networks, that right now every person can, can be a media, can say something and can influence society ... What we are talking about, that the institutions, let's say, let's join the battle or let's make that speech using those media too, right? being Youtubers or being on Youtube - even if we are not Youtubers with millions of subscribers". (Spain, FG2_1)

[T]he whole issue of COVID vaccines, to give a very clear example, but I think that society as a whole or mostly did not see a problem, they were confident that this vaccine, it was supported by science, but there is a small group of very vocal people who say: "this is not proven, this has these side effects that are not proven, this has these side effects that are not supported by science. (Spain FG1_5)

In addition to this negative role of social networks in terms of disinformation, the participants agreed that social networks contribute to artificially competing voices with radically different values. The voice of the scientist on the networks has no more value than that of a self-proclaimed expert:

"There has always been a competition of knowledge, but in the past it was more between science and religion (...) Now this competition for knowledge is much more diversified, and members of society can have access to alternative knowledge, with a phenomenon of relativisation of knowledge where 'everything is equal'. There are people who claim to be 'expert' on this or that subject, writing a blog or posting things on YouTube, and who mix scientific knowledge with other things... There's a lot of muddle in the public production of science. And that's complicated for scientists to manage, especially as the media aren't always there, and the political relays are lacking." (France, FG2_5)

This participant points to an interesting topic for the social sciences, namely the impact of the social media on the perception of scientificity. Studying the "public production of science" means studying the ways in which traditional boundaries between science and non-science can be temporarily weakened in the public mind through social networks.

Non-institutional science communicators

The population of professional science communicators is very diverse: science educators, broadcasters, filmmakers, bloggers and influencers. As science journalists are still considered a fringe group in the traditional media, professional science communicators outside of institutions may have an important role to play in dealing with the flood of misinformation. Some discussion groups emphasized the need to innovate and renew formats of science communication. In

Portugal, “one participant commented that she was in the presentation of the book 'The End of the World in Underpants' where several experts and science communicators in Portugal describe different apocalyptic scenarios in a scientific but also entertaining way, with illustrations and organisation by one communicator and social media influencer” (PT report, p.21).

In France, the head of a scientific communication association pointed out that this pursuit of innovation means not only taking into account the reputational damage caused to institutions on social networks, but also sometimes even questioning the limits of professional ethics:

*“To illustrate this, at *** we run the *** media, which is a social networking account, and we started from the premise that the battleground was social networks, and we were going to use every possible weapon to get out there and fight. And we thought about it and we took out the word 'science', we took out all the references to institutions... because they're counterproductive in terms of trust capital. That's why it's called *** If we'd 'branded' it as science, the project manager would have told us he wouldn't take the job because he knew it wouldn't work. ... We're working on it, and sometimes we're on the verge of being super, super clean, because it's a struggle, it's a question of audience, of visibility, and a question of collective manipulation”.*
(France, FG1_5).

Need for training scientists and innovation in communication.

Scientists are part of the chain of mediation. They are increasingly being invited to engage with the general public. This public exposure of scientific discourse can be linked to the dissemination of research findings over a short period of time, but it can also be linked to scientific popularisation work over a longer period of time. This raises questions about their training but also their ability to deal with potential negative attitudes. In Germany as in Greece, participants observed that “science communication is (...) a challenge in the sense that many scientists have no training in this regard and do not know how to successfully communicate about their research. Increasing attacks and hate campaigns, on- and offline, increase the hesitancy of scientists to go public with their work” (GER report, p.12); “All educational levels should have lessons about

science communication and this expands also to tertiary education (i.e. Universities). It was implied that formal education has a more important role than targeted seminars, since science communication has to become part of the “consciousness” of citizens, some of which will become researchers. Another recommendation was that faculty members and researchers staff of research performing organisations should be guided on how to use social media” (GRE report, p.18).

“Sometimes I have thought that we should give seminars to researchers and faculty members and those scientists who belong to organizations, how they should use social media, or rather how not to use social media.” (Greece, FG2_6)

Despite strong institutional and sometimes commercial incentives, a critical approach to the popularisation of science was developed by some participants:

“I think popularisation has many dangers. I feel that it can be seen as legitimate etc. to make everybody aware of certain things, but in fact it works negatively, because some things are valid under certain circumstances and only then. And when we popularize, we generalize and it can ultimately lead to the opposite result from what... from the truth and so people will understand something which is fundamentally not true because they don't understand all the logic, what is being described. I personally have a slight dislike for popularization.” (Greece, FG1_2)

In Portugal, participants invited the scientists to renew their way of communicating with the public: “participants suggested video-abstracts and clear abstracts as two interesting tools for dissemination. Video-abstract is an educational tool to create bridges between academia and schools, where video is seen as a new language for communicating science, with a very appealing graphic side. Clear abstracts are summaries of scientific articles in simple, plain language and in Portuguese, which makes it easier for many people to understand the subject” (PT report, p.26).

Participants also emphasized that the visibility of scientific debates and controversies is changing due to the presence of

scientists on social networks: "As disputes between scientists do increasingly happen in public, on social media, and accessible for everyone, the public is much more exposed to scientific uncertainties as it has been before" (GER report, p.17). In other words, the public image of science now also depends on the way in which scientists use social networks on a daily basis to inform themselves or debate with their colleagues. The open debate between researchers becomes an access point for all actors in the mediation chain.

Institutional science communicators : Need to move away from a reactive culture.

Finally another key player in the mediation chain is, of course, the academic institution itself. Research institutions and scientific organisations have their own communication services. Particular emphasis was placed on the way in which institutional communication reflects, by principle, the interests of the institution: "(...) it would also mean to rethink the way university communication currently works. One participant stated that such communication is often led by own interests - at least to some extent - and consciously employs framing that attracts attention, for example with future funding in mind. Instead, it would be important to communicate about research and its findings in a truly transparent and honest way" (GER report, p.23). Participants in the focus group also questioned the institution's ability to move away from a reactive culture of communication. Whether in cases of alleged misconduct or in public debates on policy issues, research and teaching institutions are now expected to speak out: "the group of university communicators discussed the fact that scientific institutions and especially universities are increasingly torn into political debates, and that, for example, it is expected from them to position themselves in debates about the Middle East conflict. In reaction to that, participants once again invoked the image of institutions being driven and just re-acting, often in an uncoordinated and rushed manner. The negative public impression arising from this reaction was perceived as being transferred to the image of the university as a whole with no differentiation between the university as an 'institution', with a board of directors and a communication department etc., and the university as a place of science" (GER report, p.15).

3.6. Recommendations & key priorities

This final section reviews the recommendations developed in the national reports.

Topic	Country	Recommendations
Research integrity	Denmark	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote shared research integrity standards across institutions and countries • Increase administrative support throughout the research process, covering areas such as budget management, external collaboration and relations, and data management
	France	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Change the culture of research organisations when it comes to the handling of scientific misconduct: from a culture of secrecy to a culture of transparency • Change the evaluation culture in science by giving priority to collective success over individual success, to quality over quantity • Ensure training for the entire scientific community in the values of scientific integrity, including senior researchers • Encourage scientific institutions to address the organizational tensions, conflicting imperatives they contribute to generate.
	Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be self-reflexive and coherent in your self-definition process: Institutions should systematically reflect on themselves and their role. • Implement a culture of integrity. To successfully and sustainably deal with topics related to research integrity and Good Scientific Practice at

		<p>institutions, there is a need develop a comprehensive culture of integrity.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure independence and transparency. Independence needs to be maintained, even under pressure Transparency applies to power structures within institutions but also to research processes in general, doubts, errors, and failures • Continuous, career-long training and education programmes for students, scientists, but also other professionals working in the institution • Implement clear guidelines, codes of conduct and structures that allow for these guidelines to be followed: qualified contact persons for counselling, but also clear consequences and sanctions in case of misconduct applied systematically and in a transparent way. • Institutions need to stand and work together closely as a system of science that wants to improve itself. One single actor cannot change a culture.
	Greece	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stiffer penalties to violators in Greece (students and researchers) like the ones that apply on the other side of the Atlantic • creation of role models which are more efficient than punishments most of the times • Introduction of training programs on research integrity • Modernisation of the existing (or non-existing for that matter) Code of Conduct. • Evaluation should be done not according to h-index and citations but to the wider reputation of the candidate

	Portugal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a new role in most institutions - an ethics officer. These officers would be responsible for receiving and handling allegations of unethical behaviour in the institution. • Elaborate ethical guidelines for researchers and create an Ethics Council or Committee • Ensure the training of researchers, about integrity in research • Foster a continued discussion on integrity, creating forums where people can read documents with guidelines from the European Commission or scientific national institutions, debate these and their application. • Discourage publication in predatory journals, identify publishers that are not recommended for publication and provide a list of journals that would not be considered for awards or performance evaluation. • Revision of the performance evaluation system of researchers and professors, which should be less focused on metrics or quantitative indicators and more focused on impact and benefits of research for society. • Rewarding researchers who comply with the ethical principles of research could also be a starting point to promote a culture of integrity
	Spain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop specific training on reliability and integrity of science, through the research career trajectory and make societal aspects such as data privacy more integrated in the formation process • Universities need to display a greater commitment to the importance of research ethics and integrity and

		<p>provide greater levels of infrastructure support;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognise and reward researchers for participating in ethics and integrity work in their organisations • Processes of formation and development of human capital must integrate a culture of research integrity from entry into the university community and continue across the research career • Adopt a 'no-blame' strategy in relation to improving the ethical conduct of research and the advancement of research integrity, by trying to shift institutional culture through training and support over time;
	United kingdom	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mandatory training for postgraduates and all research staff • Ensure a culture of transparency: There is not enough transparency in the UK about misconduct compared with the United States where such cases are centrally recorded. It appears universities in the UK are fostering an environment of cover-up although there is also a culture of whistleblowing. The British culture is not to name and shame, unlike the American model. • Transform the research culture: pressure on researchers to publish, to find funding for research and to advance careers... factors which makes researchers feel they have no choice but to cut corners • Increase administrative support for the development of scientific projects: a financially sound project reduces the chance that shortcuts will be taken.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote a more formal spotting approach in order to prevent breaches: United Kingdom Research and Integrity Office (UKRIO) appears too low key to be effective.
Topic	Country	Recommendations
Social integration	Denmark	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop an app that could provide citizens with an overview of all citizen science projects at Danish universities Increase awareness and diversity of initiatives for public engagement in science, which could positively impact on social integration in science Create organisational infrastructures and incentive structures that enhance public participation in research. The implementation of citizen councils was cited as one example of how to increase citizen engagement.
	France	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implement small-scale events to create and cultivate the links between citizens and scientists Ensure training for the entire scientific community to develop social integration mechanisms
	Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide scientists with the necessary knowledge and resources to engage in a sustainable and meaningful process of social integration. There is no 'one size fits all' approach in social integration. Recognize social integration as part of the scientific work, therefore it should be evened with the scientists' obligations in research and teaching. Protect own members, and particularly scientists, from external attacks - a topic which has become more important than ever in recent years. Being a good employer' is crucial because only with the actual support of the institutions' members, research

		integrity and social integration can become a living reality.
	Greece	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training of researchers in science communication were among the main factors and recommendations of the participants • Inclusion of Committees and Unions of patients in Bioethical Committees if they have received proper training before • Be cautious about participatory research and limit as much possible the social integration to public consultation • Improve the communication skills of scientists
	Portugal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote collaborative spaces and buildings : When citizens are invited for the physical space of institutions, buildings should be designed and built to favour this openness without walls, more collaborative spaces, desacralizing the university or research institute • Ensure the capacity building of science communication offices in institutions, providing more resources to each and creating synergies between them. • Improve the communication skills of scientists through innovation: video-abstracts and clear abstracts as new tools for dissemination. • develop and consider new ways of auscultating the citizens at a local and regional level such as assemblies for citizens or other specific groups (e.g., teachers, parents, people living in specific neighbourhoods). Thus, cooperating with local institutions/municipalities and organised movements (i.e., local associations) is imperative.

	Spain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop professionalized science communication in local media, research groups, and projects • Improve the communication and engagement skills of scientists with of outputs that could be more easily consumed by lay persons • Processes of formation and development of human capital must integrate a culture of societal engagement from entry into the university community and continue across the research career • Promote the involvement of citizens in funding research priority settings • Use institutional communicators to make citizens aware of research in the early stages of its planning and development and to try and invite their participation.
	United kingdom	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • maintain and establish relationships with societal stakeholders • Ensure transparency about the motivation of science : the main issue for the public is motivation if the scientist is being driven by malign or vested intent or the desire to make money for self and employer • Ensure capacity of scientists to deal effectively with public enagement: PE staff are also mostly part-time, with implications for continuity. Silo working is also prevalent. Scientists struggle with public engagement due to capacity constraints.
Topic	Country	Recommendations
Trust in science	Denmark	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourage a greater breadth and diversity among the experts featured in the media • Enhance the support for the 'science of science communication' to encourage cross-cutting research that could yield more empirical knowledge about

		the diversity of research debates and dissemination methods.
	France	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop scientific education in school as early as possible • Develop a massive public communication strategy to promote science and critical thinking on social networks, seeing them as an "informational war zone". • Develop the area of "research on research" and on the various forms of trust in research
	Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transparency should be encouraged. Transparency must be lived in external relations with society and stakeholders as much as to the inside within the institution. • Implement the inclusion of scientific knowledge in school curricula - the only moment in life when all societal groups can be reached simultaneously - but also foster life-long learning opportunities in this regard. • Promote diversity: research funding organisations should be aware of their subjective perspective when making decisions and be self-reflexive on the processes of funding allocations. Their actions and decisions should also be directed towards the reduction of inequalities and an increase of diversity in science
	Greece	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote science literacy: Informing society about the research community's disputes and why they come into being is important for citizens to comprehend the process of scientific progress.
	Portugal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote scientific culture: Laypeople need to have scientific literacy to know how to interpret information, evaluate its quality and avoid manipulation

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foster transparency and open science practices (e.g., sharing data, open access publications) to extend the network of people that can access the information. In this way, funding institutions can contribute to maintain and increase people's trust in science
	Spain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve science literacy of the public, starting at early stages of education • Institutional communicators need to fight a continuing battle on the terrain of social media to support public trust in science - scientists are weak performers in this domain. • The communication and dissemination of scientific results does not need to be ubiquitous in principle, but rather the guiding principle should be their relevance to specific societal audiences
	United kingdom	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoid using the term "crisis of trust", it is a strong and problematic term; talk of crisis can be self-fulfilling and is best avoided. • Develop public conversation about the private funding of universities and research organisations. • Ensure transparency and accountability : public money requires accountability, and the university must be transparent about how that money is being spent

Unsurprisingly, an overview of these recommendations reveals a number of differences, some of which are related to differences in the institutional environment. Some countries, for example, have established research integrity advisors and regularly revised their best practice guides. Others are still waiting for these roles and guides to be established.

But beyond these expected differences, it is interesting to see that certain priorities are widely shared, including the 15 detailed below:

- o Implement clear guidelines, codes of conduct and promote shared research integrity standards across institutions and countries.
- o Increase administrative support throughout the research process, covering areas such as budget management, external collaboration and relations, and data management.
- o Encourage scientific institutions to address the organizational tensions, conflicting imperatives they contribute to generate.
- o Ensure science independence and develop public conversation about the private funding of universities and research organisations.
- o Continuous, career-long training and education programmes for students, scientists, but also other professionals working in the institution.
- o In-depth revision of the performance evaluation system: Towards more qualitative measures.
- o Ensure a culture of transparency regarding the institutional handling of misconduct.
- o Provide scientists with the necessary knowledge and resources to engage in a sustainable and meaningful process of social integration.
- o Protect own members, and particularly scientists, from external attacks.
- o Promote collaborative spaces and buildings: When citizens are invited for the physical space of institutions, buildings should be designed and built to favour this openness.
- o Develop and consider new ways of consulting the citizens at a local and regional level such as assemblies for citizens or other specific groups.
- o Insofar as the battle for scientific information is being waged at both global and local levels, act at both levels, combining comprehensive participation with mass dissemination.
- o Use institutional communicators to make citizens aware of research in the early stages.
- o Implement the inclusion of scientific knowledge in school curricula - the only moment in life when all societal groups

- can be reached simultaneously - but also foster life-long learning opportunities in this regard.
- o Avoid assuming a "crisis of trust", it is a strong and problematic term: talk of crisis can be self-fulfilling and is best avoided.

4. Concluding remarks

The research findings presented in this global report were produced as part of workpackage 3 of the POIESIS project, a WP coordinated by the project's CNRS partner in France.

The global aim of this task was to define, at the European level, to what extent and how institutions can provide policies and procedures that enable researchers to act in ways that are conducive to public trust in science.

Our consortium opted for a method that was both qualitative and participatory: qualitative, with 22 focus groups involving more than 130 participants; participatory, with 24 institutional stakeholders working with us as co-investigators. All partners were able to implement the research protocol and, where necessary, adapt it to local realities in order to obtain unprecedented qualitative data on how the various institutional actors involved in scientific integrity and social inclusion perceive both the current state of integrity and inclusion in their respective national contexts and the priority actions to be taken.

This report is the first comprehensive analysis based on the POIESIS WP3 data. Further developments will allow us to explore specific aspects in more depth. However, in the context of this conclusion, it is worth stressing the way in which the results discussed here shed light on the framework underlying the call for projects 'HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-44. Based on an initial assessment of a widespread crisis of trust between science and society, this call stipulated a set of three assumptions: 1) trust depends on scientists and engineers' capacity to demonstrate high standards of research integrity; 2) citizen and civil society's involvement in co-creating research agendas and contents makes research more relevant and responsive to society and strengthens co-ownership and trust"; 3)

institutions matter by enabling and supporting researchers to act responsibly in terms of integrity and social integration.

As we have seen, this report makes it possible, first of all, to question the initial observation on which the call is based, that of a supposed general crisis of trust between science and society. Our focus groups revealed a much more nuanced picture and a general recommendation that undoubtedly deserves some reflection. On the one hand, participants believe that there may be problems of trust between science and society, but that these problems are mainly limited to specific issues or areas. On the other hand, participants often felt that the question of trust was at least as much a question for society as for scientists themselves. A major challenge today is to ensure that scientists have full and unreserved confidence in scientific institutions. For this to happen, it is essential that the institutions meet their expectations. Finally, it was noted that the prevailing discourse of a generalized crisis of trust between science and society may not only be empirically false, but may also be counterproductive, in particular by artificially creating a growing distance between science and society. It seems critical that scientific institutions, by the simple classical logic of self-fulfilling prophecy, do not create the phenomenon they are trying to combat.

Regarding the link between public trust and scientific integrity, participants acknowledged that scientific misconduct can undermine trust in science. However, this effect is considered to be limited. Partly because cases of fraud or misconduct are considered either rare or difficult to measure. Participants emphasized the importance of the different actors in the mediation chain: the scientists themselves, when they expose their disputes on social media; the traditional media, which develop a sensationalist approach; and institutional communication, which too often cultivates an opaque approach in the name of protecting researchers.

Concerning social integration, it is striking that the participants were relatively divided on its effects, but that those who had the most detailed knowledge of it were also the ones who were able to describe its benefits, in particular its social relevance. From this point of view, the assumption that the involvement of citizens and civil society in the co-creation of research agendas and content makes research more relevant seems correct, but it depends on a long

list of factors that do not always come together. While participatory mechanisms have been praised for allowing, in principle, an in-depth dialogue between citizens and scientists, in practice this dialogue does not always take place. And when a participatory process fails to deliver on its promises, it can understandably generate public mistrust. More importantly, some actors believe that abandoning a dissemination strategy in favour of a participatory strategy is a mistake in the ongoing war for scientific information. This war is being fought on a large scale on social media, and participatory mechanisms only really work with small groups of participants. It is therefore necessary to promote a culture of participatory research, just as it is necessary to promote a culture of integrity, but this culture cannot replace a massive institutional communication strategy around scientific information on social media. Here too, the promotion of a culture of social integration requires the mobilization of all actors in the mediation chain: non-institutional actors in science communication are already involved, but other actors, especially institutional ones, should play a more active role in supporting the development of participatory projects by the scientific community.

This brings us to the third assumption, the idea that institutions matter when it comes to promoting social integrity and social integration. From this perspective, the focus groups allow us to describe the heterogeneity of the national institutional landscapes and the importance of expectations. Institutions clearly have an important role to play in creating roles, training, guidelines, etc. The long list of institutional recommendations presented in the previous section seems to clearly indicate the work that needs to be done. The idea that each scientific organization should be able to systematically identify the conflicting moral imperatives to which it subjects its staff seems to be an essential task. But it is important to stress that these institutional actions will remain ineffective if they are not coordinated at both national and European levels. In terms of integrity and knowledge of data sharing rights, the problem is not so much the absence of codes, but the proliferation of codes, which creates more and more confusion. There is a global need for standardization, harmonization and coordination that can only be achieved at the European or global level.

APPENDIX

Annex A: List of co-investigators

Country	Id.
Denmark	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . Marianne Gauffriau, research consultant at the IT university of Copenhagen and a specialist in research evaluation, peer review and bibliometrics; . Mia Ulvgraven, press- and communication consultant at School of Business and Social Sciences at Aarhus University (AU). Specialist in research communication and dissemination; . Lone Bredahl, senior consultant and assistant professor at the Library/University of Southern Denmark (SDU). Specialist in research ethics, research integrity and technology consumer acceptance. Lone is also responsible for courses on responsible conduct of research.
France	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . Antoine de Daruvar, former vice-president of University Bordeaux Segalen and initiator of the first MOOC on research integrity in France; . Caroline Strube, CNRS researcher in neurobiology and member of CNRS Mission à l'intégrité scientifique created in 2018 in charge of investigating misconduct cases and setting up training initiatives; . Olivier le Gall, senior research fellow at the Institut national de recherche pour l'agriculture, l'alimentation et l'environnement (INRAE), Olivier Le Gall has been INRAE Deputy Director in charge of the Institute's research programme. He has been President of the French Council for Scientific Integrity (COFIS), the scientific council of the French office for scientific integrity (OFIS).
Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . Marita Müller is an experienced senior professional who has been head of the Department for Public Relations at the university BTU Cottbus-Senftenberg from 1996 to 2022 and, since then, is the coordinator of the "BTU Präsenzstellen" . Pierre Schwidlinski is program director at the Volkswagen Foundation for media and communication studies, theology and religious studies.

	<p>. Tina Rotzal and Esther Reineke lead the Academic Integrity Competence Centre (AKIN) at the University Library of the Johannes Gutenberg University of Mainz.</p>
Greece	<p>. Pavlos P. Sotiriadis, at the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering of National Technical University of Athens (NTUA). He is an IEEE Fellow, the Director of the Electronics Laboratory of the NTUA and a governing board member of the Hellenic (National) Space Center of Greece.</p> <p>. Manolis Patiniotis, Department of Sociology, of Athens National and Kapodistrian University. He is a member of the academic committee of the postgraduate program Science Communication of the Hellenic Open University</p> <p>. Olga Tzortzatou, member the Legal department of the Biomedical Research Foundation of the Academy of Athens (BRFAA), external ethics expert of the European Commission; Co-Facilitator: Vasileios Zogopoulos, Biomedical Research Foundation, Academy of Athens</p>
Portugal	<p>. Maria João Leão, is the coordinator of Citizen Science and Active Citizenship Program at the IGC, ITQB NOVA and Oeiras Valley.</p> <p>. Rita Ferreira is part of IN2PAST - Associated Laboratory for Research and Innovation in Heritage, Arts, Sustainability and Territory.</p> <p>. Cristina Nobre Soares is a consultant in science communication and a copywriter who works at Claro. She writes the blog "Em Linha Recta"</p>
Spain	<p>. José-Félix Lozano has a strong professional profile and network in the field of moral philosophy and participates in institutional structures of REI</p> <p>. Luis Zurano brought a professional profile and network of contacts in science communication and dissemination in public universities as well as in citizen science practices.</p> <p>. Nuria Lloret has a diverse professional network, including in both the public and private sectors.</p>
United kingdom	<p>. Louise Jones, Head of Research Communications and Engagement; Communications Division; Knowledge Exchange and Impact (KEI) Integrated Service</p> <p>. Gemma Derrick, Associate Professor, Centre for Higher Education Transformation; academically interested in the topic</p> <p>. Samantha Oakley Research Governance and Integrity Manager, Governance, Policy and Integrity Team, Research Services, Research & Innovation</p>

	. Charles Shannon, Head of Research and Innovation; Quality and Policy; Research and Innovation
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Annex B: List of participants

Denmark

Participant Id.	Gender	Position	Institution
FG1_1	Female	Manager	RFO
FG1_2	Female	Research support manager	RPO
FG1_3	Male	Research administration senior consultant	RPO
FG1_4	Male	Science communication consultant and facilitator	Self-employed
FG1_5	Female	Manager	Open Access organisation
FG1_6	Male	Information and citizen science specialist	Library
FG2_1	Female	Communication manager	RFO
FG2_2	Male	Communication manager	RPO
FG2_3	Male	Manager	RFO
FG2_4	Female	Project manager	Private organisation involved in public engagement in science
FG2_5	Female	Communication manager	RPO
FG2_6	Female	Communication manager	RPO
FG2_7	Female	Communication manager	RPO
FG3_1	Female	Manager	Data Management organisation
FG3_2	Female	Manager	RFO
FG3_3	Female	Research support manager	RPO

FG3_4	Female	Associate professor, Responsible conduct of research teacher	RPO
FG3_5	Female	Manager	Hospital Research Support Unit

France

Participant Id.	Gender	Position	Institution
FG1_1	F	Manager	National public debate institution
FG1_2	M	Officer "science and society"	RPO
FG1_3	F	Former director	Public health institution
FG1_4	F	Manager of research and innovation committee	Association of RPO
FG1_5	M	Director	Scientific mediation organization
FG1_6	M	professor, Responsible conduct of research expert	RPO
FG2_1	M	Research integrity officer	RPO
FG2_2	F	Research Integrity and Ethics Officer	RPO
FG2_3	F	Research Integrity and Ethics Officer	RPO
FG2_4	F	Research Integrity and Ethics Officer	RPO
FG2_5	F	Research Integrity officer and pdt of national association of integrity officers	University
FG2_6	F	Research Integrity officer	RPO
FG3_1	M	Science journalist	Major French newspaper
FG3_2	F	Integrity and deontology officer	RFO

FG3_3	M	Head of the office integrity	RPO
FG3_4	M	Manager	European scientific mediation organization

Germany

Participant Id.	Gender	Seniority	Position	Institution
FG1_1	Female	Senior professional	Head of Science Communication and Strategy	University
FG1_2	Female	Senior professional	Chief Communication Officer	University
FG1_3	Male	Senior professional	Head of University Communications	University
FG1_4	Male	Senior professional	Managing Director	University
FG1_5	Male	Senior professional	Spokesperson	University
FG1_6	Female	Senior professional	Head of Communications	Non-University Research Centre
FG1_7	Female	Senior professional	Head of Communications	University
FG2_1	Male	Senior professional	Head of Division	Foundation
FG2_2	Male	Senior professional	Secretary General	Research Funding Organisation
FG2_3	Female	Senior professional	Head of Division	Federal Ministry
FG2_4	Female	Senior professional	Program Director	Foundation
FG3_1	Male	Senior professional	Managing Director	University
FG3_2	Female	Senior professional	Head of Ombudsoffice	University
FG3_3	Female	Senior professional	Coordinator Scientific Integrity	Non-University Research Centre
FG3_4	Female	Senior professional	Officer Early Career Researchers	University
FG3_5	Male	Senior professional	Head of Division	University
FG3_6	Female	Senior professional	Officer Department of Research and Knowledge Transfer	University
FG3_7	Female	Senior professional	Head of Ombudsoffice	University

Greece

Participant Id.	Gender	Age (approx.)	Position	Institution
FG1_1	Male	65+	Professor Emeritus	NTUA
FG1_2	Male	55-64	Professor, Vice-Rector	NTUA

FG1_3	Male	55-64	Professor/Archimandrite	NKUA/CHURCH OF GREECE
FG1_4	Male	40-50	Association President	MEDICAL LAW AND BIOETHICS ASSOCIATION
FG1_5	Male	55-64	Professor	NTUA
FG1_6	Male	40-50	Professor	NTUA
FG2_1	Male	45-54	Researcher, Science communication	Leibniz Institute for Astrophysics, Potsdam, Germany
FG2_2	Male	55-64	Professor	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens
FG2_3	Male	45-54	Professor	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens
FG2_4	Male	55-64	Responsible for communication	Democritos Research Center
FG2_5	Female	45-54	Professor	Panteion University of Social and Political Sciences
FG2_6	Female	45-54	Associate professor	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens
FG3_1	Male	65+	Bioethical Committee	BRFAA
FG3_2	Male	55-64	Bioethical Committee	BRFAA
FG3_3	Female	55-64	Professor/Bioethical Committee	NKUA/BRFAA
FG3_4	Male	55-64	Senior Lawyer at Medical Law	LEGAL ADVISORY TO THE STATE
FG3_5	Female	25-34	Researcher/Administration	BRFAA

Portugal

Participant Id.	Gender	Career stage	Position	Institution
FG1_1	Female	Mid-career	Research Data Steward	Research Support Office, Iscte
FG1_2	Male	Senior	Research Management and Science Communication	IN2PAST Associated Laboratory
FG1_3	Male	Mid-career	Science communicator, activist, and facilitator of citizen science	Lisbon University
FG1_4	Female	Initial	Communication and Outreach Manager	Institute for Systems and Robotics, Técnico
FG1_5	Female	Initial	Research and Quality Officer	Polytechnic Institute of Lisbon
FG1_6	Female	Mid-career	Science Communication Manager	Business Research Unit, Iscte
FG2_1	Female	Senior	Coordinator of the Science and Society Centre	Municipality of Oeiras
FG2_2	Female	Senior	Head of Science Communication Office	ITQB NOVA
FG2_3	Male	Mid-career	Events and Projects Officer/ Science Communication Officer	European Animal Research Association
FG2_4	Female	Senior	Director	Bioethics Institute of the Portuguese Catholic University
FG2_5	Female	Mid-career	Team member of RM Roadmap	NOVA IMS

FG3_1	Female	Mid-career	Member of the Board of Directors, responsible for Science Communication	MARE, University of Coimbra
FG3_2	Female	Mid-career	Science Manager	Research Centre LEAF, University of Lisbon
FG3_3	Female	Mid-career	Service Marketing and Community Outreach Officer	OPERAS Research Infrastructure
FG3_4	Male	Junior	Communication Officer	Centre for Functional Ecology, University of Coimbra
FG3_5	Female	Senior	Scientific consultant	European Science Foundation/ Green Media
FG3_6	Male	Senior	Principal Researcher	Centre for Functional Ecology, University of Coimbra
FG3_7	Male	Senior	Director of the Portuguese Journal of Social Science	Iscte
FG3_8	Male	Senior	Communication and project management officer	UC Exploratório - Centro Ciência Viva Coimbra
FG3_9	Female	Mid-career	Communications and Marketing Manager	FSC Portugal

Spain

Participant Id.	Gender	Age	Position	Institution
FG1_1	Female	45-55	Full professor / Natural sciences.	Public university

			Research integrity background or responsibilities	
FG1_2	Male	55-65	Full professor / Humanities. Research integrity background or responsibilities	Public university
FG1_3	Male	45-55	Professor / Natural Sciences. Research integrity background or responsibilities	Public university
FG1_4	Female	55-65	Manager. Research integrity background or responsibilities	Regional administration
FG1_5	Female	35-45	Researcher / Social sciences	Private university
FG1_6	Male	55-65	Professor / Humanities. Research integrity background or responsibilities	Public university
FG1_7	Male	35-45	Professor / Humanities. Research integrity background or responsibilities	Public university
FG1_8	Male	55-65	Full professor / Humanities. Research integrity background or responsibilities	Public university
FG2_1	Male	45-55	Scientist journalist	Public university
FG2_2	Male	45-55	Communication manager	Public university
FG2_3	Female	45-55	Communication manager	Public university
FG2_4	Male	55-65	Manager of research institute	Public university
FG2_5	Male	55-65	Communication manager	Public research performing organization
FG3_1	Female	45-55	Manager (PhD)	Public Official College of professionals

FG3_2	Male	45-55	Manager	Public Official College of professionals
FG3_3	Female	55-65	Manager	Business Association

United kingdom

	N participants	Gender	Departments and centres	N academics/professionals	Age	Names of job positions, language used at institutions
Glasgow	7	1 man 6 women	1 department 6 centres	1 academics 6 professionals	4 < 45 3 > 46	RI manager, RE manager, community engagement manager, RI advisor, ethics committee, grant support, head of governance policy
LSE	9	2 men 7 women	3 departments 6 centres	0 academics 9 professionals	5 < 45 4 > 46	Ethics committee, communications manager, knowledge exchange support, PhD manager, impact support, REF support, centre manager, impact manager, head of

						knowledge exchange
Bristol	6	3 men 3 women	3 departments 3 centres	1 academics 5 professionals	3 < 45 3 > 46	Research development, RI officer, RI reproducibility, UKRIO network, head of PE, meta-science academic
Loughborough	4	1 man 3 women	1 department 3 centres	0 academics 4 professionals	1 < 45 3 > 46	Ethics and RI officer, R&D officer, Research governance officer & PE, head of R&D REF
Total	26	7 men 19 women	6 departments 20 centres	2 academics 24 professionals	13 13	

Annex C: Guidelines for running the focus groups

1. OBJECTIVES

The overall goal of WP3 is to conduct participatory research with institutional stakeholders, ultimately generating insights and policy recommendations on how institutions can facilitate the establishment of conducive environments for responsible research practices.

WP3 is primarily designed to address this general research question: **To what extent and how can institutions provide policies and procedures that enable researchers to act in ways that are conducive to public trust in science?**

The questions or themes aligned with this question can be categorized into two primary groups: firstly, those pertaining to perceptions and attitudes, and secondly, those associated with actions and priorities.

Perceptions and attitudes: How do institutional stakeholders perceive, globally and locally, the level of public trust in science and technology and its implications? How do institutional stakeholders perceive the culture of research integrity and social integration in their own institutional and national environment?

Actions and priorities: To what extent do institutional stakeholders consider that responsible research practices and social integration could be fostered by institutional governance arrangements and policy environments? What kind of institutional governance arrangements and policy environments should be considered as key priorities?

WP3 is divided into two main segments: 1) focus group and 2) public deliberative roundtable. This document exclusively addresses the focus group. A dedicated document for organizing the roundtables will be prepared at a later date.

A focus group is a qualitative survey method carried out with a small group of targeted individuals with the objective to gain a deeper understanding of their attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors.

The four following research questions will guide the focus groups:

- How do institutional stakeholders perceive, globally and locally, the level of public trust in science and technology and its implications?
- How do institutional stakeholders perceive the culture of research integrity and social integration in their own institutional and national environment?
- To what extent do institutional stakeholders consider that responsible research practices and social integration could be fostered by institutional governance arrangements and policy environments?
- What kind of institutional governance arrangements and policy environments should be considered as key priorities?

The data collected through the focus groups will allow us to investigate at the institutional level:

- Perceptions of public trust, research integrity and social integration
- Concerns, hopes and expectations towards research integrity and social integration
- Procedures and policies translating research integrity and social integration into communicational or organizational processes - policies
- Expectations about the impact of these process and policies.

2. RECRUITMENT STRATEGY

As you all already know, the conduct of WP3 focus groups raises two recruitment challenges, firstly the identification, selection and training of co-investigators, and secondly the identification and selection of focus group participants.

Step 1. Co-investigators (reminder)

Each partner identifies three individuals in its national environment who belong to the two sets of institutional stakeholders already described:

Integrity	Social integration
[1] leaders and managers in research performing organizations	[7] open science policy advisers
[2] leaders and managers in research funding organizations	[8] communication and outreach officers in research performing organizations
[3] editors of peer-reviewed journals	[9] communication and outreach officers in research funding organizations
[4] members of the committee on publication ethics	[10] press officers
[5] research integrity officers	
[6] R&I policy makers	

Each potential co-investigator will be sent a Information sheet with a short description the POIESIS project, the focus group and its role in it.

Step 2. Participants (reminder)

Each co-investigator mobilizes his professional network to co-select 6-8 participants with the partner. For each partner, 3 focus groups should be set up: 2 out of the 3

groups will prioritize common professional background for most participants (with possible outsiders and an intra-diversity of age, gender and status), and 1 out the 3 groups will prioritize diversity in terms of professional background.

3. OVERVIEW OF THE EVENT

Participants will be sent a small information kit before the event (within the previous week). The information kit is the following:

- Information notice with short description of the project, focus group and participant's role in it;
- Consent form.

Participants will be asked to arrive 30 minutes before the start of the event.

Each focus group should last around **two hours max.** to maintain engagement.

There is no ideal time, morning or afternoon, to hold this type of group discussion. You just need to make sure that the **participants are available for the full duration of the focus group.** Don't underestimate participants' schedule constraints.

Choose a comfortable and neutral venue that fosters open communication. Ensure that the space allows for easy interaction and that participants feel at ease sharing their thoughts. If stakeholders are dispersed, consider hosting virtual focus groups using video conferencing tools. Ensure that participants have the necessary technology and a quiet space for participation.

For each focus group we envisage a sequence of 7 sections:

- 1) Introduction (10 min)
- 2) Ice breaker (10 min)
- 3) Opening question (10 min)
- 4) Understanding Perceptions: Trust in Science (20 min)
- 5) Exploring Social Integration (20 min)
- 6) Institutional Contributions to Trust in Science (30 min)
- 7) Card sort exercise (see excel) file (5 min)
- 8) Wrap up and next steps (10 min)

All these sections are detailed in the moderator guide with topics, questions and follow up.

A focus group coordination team typically consists of a moderator and note-taker. The co-investigator will have the role of the moderator and the partner the role of note-taker. The role of co-investigator should be to guide the discussion, encourage participation, and ensure that everyone has an opportunity to speak. The note-taker's intervention should be kept to a minimum, but if for any reason the moderator needs assistance, this should be provided from time to time and the dynamic of the discussion re-established.

The first 10 minutes of the discussion will be devoted to introducing the subject in a synthetic way and to lay down the terms and conditions of the collective discussion. The moderator should clearly articulate the ground rules for the discussion, emphasizing the importance of respectful communication, active listening, and confidentiality.

This introduction will be followed by quick introduction of the participants (Ice breaker). Once the general presentation has been made it will be possible to open the discussion with a simple, general, projective opening question (10min).

From there it will be possible to build on the general structure of the moderator guide adapted to the national context, allowing participants to move away from it if necessary. However, the moderator should be mindful of dominant voices and make an effort to involve all participants, even the quieter ones, to ensure diverse perspectives are heard. He should also ensure that all the planned topics are covered in some way. He has the possibility to periodically summarize key points raised by participants to ensure a shared understanding.

It is possible to allocate an average time for the most substantial sections of the guide (for ex. 20-30 minutes per section) and it will be up to the team to check that the time allocated to the session is respected. But of course, if an unexpected but relevant development occurs, it is preferable to let it develop rather than interrupting it to resume the moderator guide. The moderator guide should be viewed as a semi-structured guide: it should help to structure the discussions and assist with time management, but it should not be followed too mechanically.

An audio recording of the focus group will be made, complementing the notes of the note-taker.

At the end of each session, a quick exchange session will take place between the partner and the co-investigator.

Based on the notes taken during the session, but also the post-focus-group discussion, a short session report of maximum one page will be written that will highlight the important points of the focus group. It may also mention any difficulties encountered.

4. AFTER THE EVENT

All discussions in the focus groups will be recorded and transcribed. The WP3 coordinator will add to the moderator guide initially provided a coding guide designed to be adopted across all national contexts.

Based on the coding of the transcripts, each partner will conduct the analysis of the content of their focus group with the general objective to write a detailed country report on the main findings. These national reports will be integrated into one final deliverable. This final document will be an opportunity to highlight the similarities but also the differences according to the institutional actors enrolled in the research process, as well as the national contexts.

Annex D: booklet of information

poiesis
TRUST IN SCIENCE

AARHUS UNIVERSITY

LSE
THE LONDON SCHOOL
OF ECONOMICS AND
POLITICAL SCIENCE

wissenschaft : im dialog

National
Technical
University
of Athens

iscte
INSTITUTO
LUSOBRASILEIRO
DE CIÊNCIAS

CNRS
CENTRE NATIONAL
DE LA RECHERCHE
SCIENTIFIQUE

CSIC
CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTÍFICAS

In POIESIS, we explore **how public trust might be related to perceptions and evaluations of how science is conducted.**

POIESIS is a three-year project funded by Horizon Europe that strives to tackle societal mistrust in science by understanding how, and to what extent, societal trust in science, research, and innovation is affected by the aligning of research practices with principles of research integrity and by the integration of citizens and societal stakeholders in different phases of the research cycle.

Focus Group

A focus group is a qualitative research method used to gather insights and perspectives on a particular topic. It involves a small, diverse group of individuals whose reactions and opinions are studied to understand the wider population's viewpoint. Typically, a moderator leads the session, engaging the participants in an interactive discussion designed to delve into their attitudes, beliefs, and experiences concerning the subject matter.

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Funded by
the European Union

Why your participation matters...

Your contribution as **POIESIS co-investigator** is vital. By selecting focus group participants and animating the groups, you ensure the discussions are guided by a **deep understanding** of the institutional landscape, enhancing the depth and relevance of the insights obtained. Furthermore, this collaboration will empower us to **identify tangible institutional actions to bolster public trust in science**, helping to bridge the gap between science and society and foster a more engaged, science-literate community.

What your committing to...

Participating in POIESIS requires your commitment to undertake a **half-day training** designed to familiarize you with the intricacies of focus group methodologies. Your role extends beyond training, demanding effective collaboration with the POIESIS research team in **the identification of suitable focus group participants**. Additionally, your schedule must permit **co-facilitating** these enriching group discussions, a crucial element of our project.

Our support to your participation...

Engaging in the POIESIS project offers a remarkable opportunity to actively contribute to a large-scale participatory research initiative. As a valued participant, you will play a pivotal role in establishing and facilitating focus groups while actively participating in result analysis. Moreover, should you choose to take part, the subsequent phase of the research process involves engaging in thoughtful deliberations during round tables, building upon the insights gleaned from the focus groups. We deeply value your involvement, and to ensure your seamless participation, all expenses associated with these research activities will be fully covered by the project.

Annex E: Participation information notice

Participant Information Notice

Project Title:

Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science

POIESIS PROJECT

POIESIS consortium. POIESIS is a research consortium of seven partners: Aarhus University (Denmark), London School of Economics and Political Science (United Kingdom), Wissenschaft im Dialog (Germany), National Technical University of Athens (Greece), Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (France), Iscte - Instituto Universitário de Lisboa (Portugal), Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas (Spain)

POIESIS funding: The POIESIS project is funded with a grant from the European Commission (EC) coordinated by the Aarhus University. Grant agreement number: 101057253.

POIESIS IN FRANCE

This project is conducted in France by Michel Dubois, CNRS senior researcher and director of the GEMASS (CNRS - Sorbonne University) and Catherine Guaspere, CNRS Engineer and member of the GEMASS lab.

GENERAL OUTLINE OF THE PROJECT:

The POIESIS project aims to study the relationship between trust, science and research integrity and integration practices in a world where there is increasing need for clear and open scientific information. We aim to run a series of focus groups including various

institutional stakeholders to collect their views on scientific integrity, trust in science and scientific institutions.

Use of Data: Data collection will take the form of audio recording. The discussions will be audio recorded for exclusive use by the researchers. They will not be placed on a public platform. Recordings will be transcribed and anonymized for analysis.

PURPOSE OF THE FOCUS GROUP:

The purpose of this focus group is to gather diverse perspectives and opinions on how integrity of researchers and scientific institutions and integration of the public in research affect public trust in science. Your participation in the study is highly valued as it will contribute to the advancement of knowledge in this field of science. Your insights and experiences will contribute to the overall understanding of the issue.

WHAT PARTICIPATION INVOLVES:

Participation in the focus group involves attending a 2 hours max. session. During this time, you will be asked to share your thoughts, feelings, and experiences in relation to the topic at hand. The discussions will be audio recorded.

Your participation is voluntary. You can end your participation at any moment during the event. You may at any time demand removal of your data by a simple request to the coordinator of the study (Michel Dubois - michel.dubois@cnr.fr). However, data that have already been published, cannot be removed.

CONFIDENTIALITY:

We value your privacy and assure you that all information shared during the focus group will be kept confidential and anonymous.

The partners in the POIESIS consortium share the responsibility for the processing of your personal data that are collected and processed exclusively for the purposes of the study, legally based on Article 6(a) of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). A joint Data Controller Agreement was signed by all partners.

The study is conducted by Michel Dubois (CNRS GEMASS), who you may contact to clear up any doubts, share comments or exercise your rights in relation to the processing of your personal data. You may use the contact indicated above to request access, rectification, erasure or limitation of the processing of your personal data.

RISKS AND BENEFITS:

There are no significant risks involved in participating in this focus group. Your participation will contribute to the wider research on this topic and may lead to improved policies, understanding, or services.

EXPENSES:

The participants will be reimbursed by the project for any travel costs associated with taking part in the focus group.

Project website: More information about this project is available in the project website: www.poiesis.eu

Annex F: Consent form

Dear Participant,

This form is to seek your agreement to participate in a focus group for the European Project POIESIS funded by European Commission under the programme Horizon Europe (HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01).

Please read the details provided and confirm your consent by signing at the end.

PURPOSE OF THE FOCUS GROUP:

The purpose of this focus group is to gather diverse perspectives and opinions on how integrity of researchers and scientific institutions and integration of the public in research affect public trust in science. Your participation in the study is highly valued as it will contribute to the advancement of knowledge in this field of science. Your insights and experiences will contribute to the overall understanding of the issue.

WHAT PARTICIPATION INVOLVES:

Participation in the focus group involves attending a 2 hours max. session. During this time, you will be asked to share your thoughts, feelings, and experiences in relation to the topic at hand. The discussions will be audio recorded.

CONFIDENTIALITY:

We value your privacy and assure you that all information shared during the focus group will be kept confidential and anonymous. The partners in the POIESIS consortium share the responsibility for the processing of your personal data that are collected and processed exclusively for the purposes of the study, legally based on Article 6(a) of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). A joint Data Controller Agreement was signed by all partners.

The study is conducted by Professor [redacted], who you may contact to clear up any doubts, share comments or exercise your rights in relation to the processing of your personal data. You may use the contact indicated above to request access, rectification, erasure or limitation of the processing of your personal data.

The aggregated results of the questionnaires and the transcripts will be shared with the partners within the POIESIS consortium, one of which is located in the United Kingdom, where there is an adequacy decision by the European Commission, and as such implements protective measures and guarantees your rights just like the European Union.

RISKS AND BENEFITS:

There are no significant risks involved in participating in this focus group. Your participation will contribute to the wider research on this topic and may lead to improved policies, understanding, or services.

RIGHT TO WITHDRAW:

Participation in this focus group is entirely voluntary. You have the right to withdraw at any point during the discussion, or even after the discussion, without any consequences.

EXPENSES:

All expenses associated with your participation will be fully covered by the project.

If you agree to participate in the focus group for the European Social Science Project, please sign below.

I declare that I have understood the aims of what was proposed to me, as explained by the investigator, that I was given the opportunity to ask any questions about this study and received a clarifying reply to all such questions. I accept participating in the study and consent to my personal data being used in accordance with the information that was given to me.

Yes No

(Local), ____/____/2023

Name:

Signature:

Annex G: Card sort exercise

Could you please let us know how you would classify the following activities that you might deal with in your work environment? Please choose only ONE option.

No	Activities	PR Public Relations [stakeholders]	MR marketing [customers]	PA Public Affairs [government]	PE Public Engagement science communication	Don't know/not certain
1	Writing press releases					
2	Liaising with journalists					
3	Dealing with crisis communications/emergencies					
4	Organising media training for researchers					
5	Managing the university website					
6	Maintaining and monitoring a social media presence					
7	Training researchers to adhere to research integrity					
8	Fundraising					
9	Managing the university brand (logo, brand)					
10	Organising student fairs (welcome, recruitment)					
11	Advertising university events					
12	Cultivating an internal network of contacts at the university					
13	Creating campaigns					
14	Relating to and engaging Alumni					
15	Writing the integrity audit for our university/research unit					

Could you please let us know how you would classify the following activities that you might deal with in your work environment? Please choose only ONE option.

No	Activities	PR Public Relations [stakeholders]	MR marketing [customers]	PA Public Affairs [government]	PE Public Engagement science communication	Don't know/not certain
16	Producing university corporate publications (print and visual)					
17	Feeding research to and facilitating opportunities for academics to engage with policymakers					
18	Networking with groups representing universities					
19	Managing research integrity breaches for the institution					
20	Monitoring education and research policies					
21	Liaising with lobbyists (e.g. consultancies)					
22	Facilitating community engagement in research (e.g. Science shops)					
23	Facilitating university relations with stakeholders (co-creation, knowledge transfer)					
24	Producing research content for the university website					
25	Working with the senior management when integrity issues arise					
26	Supporting and encouraging academics to engage with civil society					
27	Organising university public events about research					
28	Assisting academics in grant writing (outreach plans)					

Which of the following most closely matches your job title/role? (Please choose ONE)

Communications role	<input type="text"/>
Management role	<input type="text"/>
Administrative role	<input type="text"/>
Academic role	<input type="text"/>
Research integrity role	<input type="text"/>
Other (please specify)	<input type="text"/>

For how long have you been working in this role?

Years	<input type="text"/>
-------	----------------------

In which focus group have you participated? Insert the code given by the moderator of your group.

Research Integrity (RI)	<input type="text"/>
Social Integration (SI)	<input type="text"/>
Research Integrity (RI) and Social Integration (SI)	<input type="text"/>

Annex H: National Report

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TRUST IN SCIENCE

National Report: Focus Groups - Denmark

**Project title: Probing the impact of integrity and
integration on societal trust in science**

Project acronym: POIESIS

Grant Agreement no.: 101057253

Lead partner for this deliverable: *Centre national de la recherche
scientifique (CNRS)*

*Contributors: Tine Ravn, Christina Løth Andersen, Mia Ulvgraven, Marianne
Gauffriau, Lone Bredahl*

Date: April 1st, 2024

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1 Introduction

1.1 Set up of the focus groups

The Danish focus group interviews were all conducted on-site on the 5th, 6th, and 8th of February 2024. The first two focus groups (FG1, FG2) were held at the IT University of Copenhagen, while the third interview (FG3) took place at the University of Southern Denmark in Odense. All interviews lasted two hours, from 1-3 pm. FG 1 was moderated by co-investigator Marianne Gauffriau, and FG 2 by co-investigator Mia Ulvgraven. Project member (TR) participated in both focus groups as a co-moderator and moderated the third focus group alone as the main moderator, as co-investigator Lone Bredahl was absent due to illness.

The three Danish co-investigators were recruited due to their key and varied expertise in research integrity, science communication, and research evaluation, respectively. They represent three different universities geographically dispersed across Denmark. The three co-investigators were invited via a formal invitation sent by email. The three co-investigators are:

- Marianne Gauffriau, research consultant at the IT university of Copenhagen and a specialist in research evaluation, peer review and bibliometrics.
- Mia Ulvgraven, press- and communication consultant at School of Business and Social Sciences at Aarhus University (AU). Specialist in research communication and dissemination.
- Lone Bredahl, senior consultant and assistant professor at the Library/University of Southern Denmark (SDU). Specialist in research ethics, research integrity and technology consumer acceptance. Lone is also responsible for courses on responsible conduct of research.

As all three co-investigators accepted the invitation, no further candidates were contacted. A first kick-off online meeting was held to discuss the focus group study and activities involved, followed by a second online meeting to discuss the moderator guide. In consultation with the co-investigators, the moderator guide was slightly adapted to better fit the Danish context. For example, the term 'social integration' was reviewed among co-investigators as it conveys a different meaning in the Danish context than originally intended. Instead, the Danish terminology for 'citizen involvement in science and technology' was applied to more accurately capture the operationalisation of the concept.

Co-investigators were provided with the information booklet and guidelines material provided by the study coordinator (CNRS). All co-investigators also participated in the online focus group training session conducted by study coordinator. Participants for each focus group were identified by each co-investigator, based on the sample criteria stipulated in the study research protocol. Formal invitation emails describing the objectives of the POIESIS study, with a particular attention towards the focus group study were sent out by the project member CLA.

Participants who accepted the invitation received a second follow-up email two weeks before the focus group session. The email included an information letter further detailing the aim of the POIESIS project and an explanation of what participation in the focus group interview involved. They also received a consent form, and an information sheet about Aarhus University's handling of personal data. Participants received a final reminder email the day before the focus group providing practical details such as the meeting room number and parking information.

Eighteen participants took part in the three focus group interviews. For details regarding the composition of the groups, please see section 1.2. One participant was absent from the third focus group interview. For additional information regarding the focus group compositions and interactions, brief accounts are provided in the sequential descriptions in section 2. The focus group interviews adhered to the flow and themes outlined in the moderator guide, which included an introduction, debriefing and exercise designed for the study. The exercise was primarily aimed at university employees, and a few participants had to adjust their responses or omit answers to better align with the activities specified in the exercise. All participants received a small gift bag as a symbolic token of appreciation, but none received financial compensation for their participation.

All focus group interviews were recorded and subsequently transcribed (by CLA). The focus group transcriptions were then coded in the software and data facilitation programme NVivo (by TR) by using the codebook provided by the study coordinator. The codebook was slightly adapted to align with the Danish version of the moderator guide. The coding process primarily utilized a deductive coding strategy to align with the comparative study design and the structure of the codebook. Emerging sub-topics and themes were inductively coded and added to the codebook. Co-investigators moderating focus group one and two have read, commented on, and validated the within-in analyses of the focus group interviews in which they participated. They have also reviewed the final report. The analyses reported in the subsequent sections include a within and across-case analysis of the three focus group interviews, following the report template structure of the collective focus group study.

1.2 Participants in the focus group

The following tables outline the composition of participants in the three Danish focus group according to gender, position, and institution. No detailed information is provided to maintain the anonymity of participants. RPO refers to research performing organisation and RFO to research funding organisation.

Focus group 1

Participant Id.	Gender	Position	Institution
FG1_1	Female	Manager	RFO
FG1_2	Female	Research support manager	RPO
FG1_3	Male	Research administration senior consultant	RPO
FG1_4	Male	Science communication consultant and facilitator	Self-employed
FG1_5	Female	Manager	Open Access organisation
FG1_6	Male	Information and citizen science specialist	Library

Focus group 2

Participant Id.	Gender	Position	Institution
FG2_1	Female	Communication manager	RFO
FG2_2	Male	Communication manager	RPO
FG2_3	Male	Manager	RFO

FG2_4	Female	Project manager	Private organisation involved in public engagement in science
FG2_5	Female	Communication manager	RPO
FG2_6	Female	Communication manager	RPO
FG2_7	Female	Communication manager	RPO

Focus group 3

Participant Id.	Gender	Position	Institution
FG3_1	Female	Manager	Data Management organisation
FG3_2	Female	Manager	RFO
FG3_3	Female	Research support manager	RPO
FG3_4	Female	Associate professor, Responsible conduct of research teacher	RPO
FG3_5	Female	Manager	Hospital Research Support Unit

2 Sequential description of the focus groups

The following section outlines a sequential description of each of the three Danish focus group interviews, hence presenting detailed within-case analysis aimed at describing the nature of topics, ideas, and perceptions as they were conveyed in each group. In addition to

reporting on the specific content of the various interviews, a brief overview of the group composition, interactions, and moderation is included. The within-case analysis will form the basis for the subsequent sections of the report, which present thematic findings on trust in science across the three individual discussions.

2.1 Focus group 1

In the initial focus group discussion, participants represented a wide range of professional stakeholders engaged in the broad areas of research integrity and social integration, as outlined in the focus group study research protocol (Dubois 2023). The group consisted of six participants employed in managing, specialist, self-employed and senior positions in relation to research funding and research support and organisation with expertise spanning the areas of science communication, citizen science, research evaluation, research administration, open science and open access infrastructures.

The composition of the group included three female and three male participants, in addition to the main moderator (MG) and co-moderator (TR). Along with a balance in gender and professional subject areas, the group was equally well-balanced in terms of high-level engagement and the very constructive exchanges of perceptions and professional experiences. The discussion was effectively moderated by the main moderator (MG), with a continuous flow in the topics addressed. All themes were fully discussed and explored, however, the main topic of research integrity led to particular in-depth discussions about current research integrity cultures, barriers to promoting research integrity, and the interrelations between RI and public trust in science.

Relationship between science and society

On the topic of immediate associations to the relationship between science and society, participants discussed the societal relevance of research, noting that research might not yield immediate impact to concrete problems, with a participant from a research funding organisation providing the example of basic research. Research was also highlighted for having its own internal 'logic' and the research system was compared to a 'cloud', with another participant highlighting the intersection between lifelong learning, citizen science and science communication as important for the science-society relationship. The application of **science-based knowledge in policy-making processes** was noted to be varied, with sectors like healthcare, food, and agriculture playing a larger role in policy-making than others. Later in the discussion, the same university

participant mentioned experiencing frustration among climate researchers, who do not feel that their research findings sufficiently influence policy-making in their field. Furthermore, they are advised by some politicians and research management to avoid engaging in research activism.

Addressing the complex science and society relationship, the same university participant also pointed out a concerning aspect of science communication - that an increasing number of **researchers receive threats**, making it challenging to encourage young researchers to engage in public debate.

Trust in science

A strong relationship of trust between science and society was emphasised as important. The example of Covid-19 was provided by several participants. One participant pointed out that a lack of trust could lead people to bypass scientific knowledge when seeking solutions, while another observed that the tensions witnessed during Covid-19 may have been somewhat alleviated. Conversely, another participant believed that the gap between science and society was narrowed during Covid-19, making science appear less 'unworldly' by demonstrating a rapid and direct impact of research, thereby increasing public trust in science. Nonetheless, there was a consensus among the participants that **trust in science is generally high in Denmark**. Participants exemplified this observation with 1) the overall pro-science sentiment among Danish politicians 2) the high social status and social capital connected to being involved in research 3) the strong support for science that have been constructed through the educational system 4) the extensive use of researchers as experts and commentators in the Danish media landscape, which is more prevalent compared to other countries. Nonetheless, this general view of use of researchers in the media was nuanced by two participants in the focus group; one participant, working in science communication, noted the potential negative effect of overshadowing other groups of specialists and practitioners. On the other hand, a participant from a funding organisation encouraged an even greater use of researchers to explain their research in the media.

In this regard, **participants did not identify any distinct crisis of trust**, highlighting that single incidents of misconduct are insufficient to significantly alter the overall confidence in science, metaphorically referred to as turning over the 'supertanker'. However, this does not preclude instances of mistrust. Participants provided several examples regarding AI innovations and health-care data related to life-expectancy or illness information that might be controversial and inadvertently instill fear among the public. A historical comparison was drawn with the birth of the first child conceived through assisted reproduction in Denmark in 1983 to illustrate the normalisation of technologies and likewise to

emphasize **the need for deeper reflection on the potential impacts and adverse effects of scientific advancements.**

Research integrity

In the discussion on research integrity, participants considered the current research system, emphasising the necessity for a system in regard to research career and funding that does not encourage misconduct. A participant specialising in open science drew attention to the problem of **high retraction rates** in relation to low quality and misinformation challenges. **Responsible research was seen as a means to bolster trust in research.** The Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) initiative was cited as an example of establishing shared rules that can enhance trust and promote research integrity. There was a consensus that - while many RI principles and policies are in place - implementing them effectively in practice remains challenging. It was noted that various actors and stakeholders - including research administrations, funders, and supervisors - play an important part in cultivating a strong culture of RI. Furthermore, principles of open science and reproducibility, for instance, should be integrated into the curriculum starting already from the bachelor level.

A participant from a funding organisation pointed out that the issue of authorships is gaining a lot of attention from researchers. While this participant emphasised the positive aspects of discussing this topic transparently, which the participant saw as being the case among authors, another participant highlighted the negative aspects of manipulating authorships to 'game the system', hence undermining the peer review process and the overall integrity of research.

A primary challenge in establishing responsible research cultures was identified as **the global nature of research.** As one participant mentioned, no one owns the system, and due to its organisation, competitiveness, publication structure etc., collective standards and actions are deemed necessary to introduce sustainable transformations. The widespread use of temporary positions is also mentioned as a particular challenge that increase the pressure to publish.

In addition to **recommending shared standards across institutions and countries**, the importance of informal training and counselling from senior researchers and supervisors is highlighted as key for socialising researchers into responsible research. The specific support structure of 'practice committees' at universities, which handles questions related to responsible research practices, is mentioned as a tangible initiative to discuss and rule on specific cases. The participant from a research funding organisation stated that while they generally rely on RI regulations and policies set by research performing organisations, there have been internal discussions around reproducibility and retraction issues, aiming to

contribute to increased awareness on these important attention points. Another issue mentioned is that of 'hyperprolific' authors, where the funding agency can play a role by explicitly inquiring into the reasons behind high-volume publication during grant application evaluations.

Public participation in science

Several participants noted a growing number of citizen science and public involvement initiatives across various universities. One university participant observed that many researchers have shown interest in citizen science apps for data collection that would otherwise be difficult to gather. This participant also mentioned that public involvement in identifying research topics for funding might lead to a more varied support. In this regard, a participant specializing in citizen science highlighted an initiative at a Danish university, where citizens can vote on projects, they wish to see funded. The same participant voiced most clearly a support for public involvement in science as a way to increase trust in science.

Generally, participants seemed to **support the idea of public participation in research, several however noting that some projects are more conducive to public engagement than others**. A participant employed in a university support unit pointed out that public participation is not equally relevant in all research projects. However, in some projects, public engagement can indeed introduce perspectives, diversity, and knowledge that enhance research quality and trust in science. At the same time, this participant felt that science communication efforts might generate more trust in science than public involvement in science. Echoing this sentiment, another participant working in science communication supported this viewpoint, arguing that while citizen science allows for deeper participation, science communication initiatives have the potential to influence a larger number of citizens.

The focus group discussion briefly touched upon recommendations to further support public engagement initiatives. The participant specialising in citizen science emphasized that we are **only utilising 'one percent' of the potential of citizen science**. The participant also suggested to develop an app that could provide citizens with an overview of all citizen science projects at Danish universities. Regarding the broader topic of increasing public trust, another participant expressed a wish for a greater breadth and diversity among the experts featured in the media. This would enable a wider identification with the relevant topics and generally increase trust.

2.2 Focus group 2

In the second focus group discussion, participants were primarily involved in the area of 'social integration' by representing managing communication and outreach positions in research performing and funding organisations as well as a private organisation involved in public engagement in science. Seven participants, five women and two men, took part in a very engaged, lively, and constructive discussion around the role of science communication and citizen involvement in building public trust in science. The relatively homogeneous composition of the group, in relation to a shared communication and outreach focus, supported in-depth discussions around the various pre-defined topics from a communicative approach to the subjects. Despite the relatively homogeneous nature of the group, (tacit) knowledge, opinions and ideas were made explicit and nuanced. The size of the group and the active participation of all members necessitated slightly more time management than in the other focus groups. Due to efficient moderation (by main moderator MU) all topics were explored and addressed.

Relationship between science and society

Participants took turns responding to the first open question about immediate science and society associations. From different viewpoints, they generally agreed on the key importance of **research as a societal institution and that research should be of relevance for the greater public good**, helping to develop and improve society at large. Consensus was also reached on the fact that research - both basic research and 'practice-related' research - should be discussed in dialogue with various part of the public and that **dialogue-based approaches can improve public trust in science**. Furthermore, it was noted that while research can and should be questioned, it plays an important role in 'democratic debates' within society.

Participants also highlighted the **complex relationship between science and society**. For instance, several participants working with science communication at research performing organisations pointed to the changed relationship between universities and the general society, emphasising that universities no longer possess a 'natural legitimacy' or authority and that there has been an increased focus on the relevance and utility of research. The participants underscored an increased awareness of maintaining legitimacy through close interactions with the surrounding society but noted that this could also pose challenges.

Another participant from a research funding organisation pointed out that the science and society relation should not be oversimplified and that researchers do not speak with one voice, but they disagree because contradictions are part of the nature of science. This participant pointed to an inherent challenge in communicating the fact that **disagreement within science does not necessarily imply that science is 'untrustworthy' to the public**. This challenge can pressure

the legitimacy of science and potentially increase mistrust in it, meaning that science communicators should be very aware of this challenge when communicating scientific results. Agreeing with this point, a participant from a different funding organisation emphasized that disagreement in science might also indicate a difference in research quality and that research should not be viewed as a 'viewpoint' but a 'well-founded point of view'.

Other challenges expressed in relation to the relationship between science and society included a **pressure on researchers** - particularly researchers from humanities and social sciences - due to an increase in media outlets, an increased politicization of these areas and in relation to research seen as activist, as well as a dilution of the 'expert' label. Furthermore, several participants problematized the fact that some researchers willingly speak on issues outside of their areas of expertise, which might make it more difficult for citizens to 'navigate' a diverse research landscape. When discussing this topic in relation to research integrity issues, the general opinion was further nuanced based on the discussion (see below).

Trust in science

When discussing the topic of general trust in research within Danish society, the **politicization of science** was again brought forward as a topic of concern. While participants generally pointed to a **high degree of public trust** - albeit media debate sometimes suggest the opposite - they also observed a downward negative trend among policy decision-makers. One participant identified this as an increased strategization over the last two decades, where politicians support research that aligns with their own ideologies and likewise attack opposing research. Other participants highlighted that there must be '**cracks**' in the general trust that can be exploited politically and are maintained within 'social media bubbles' that use facts very selectively.

In this regard, it was highlighted that **mistrust has found more fertile ground**. Another participant, working with communication for a funding agency, also traced this back to the flow of media assessments - as opposed to dissemination of facts - on the part of researchers, noting that science communicators also have a role to play in this context. From the participant's perspective, researchers often avoid engaging in accusatory discussions, leaving a void that politicians can exploit.

A participant working in communication at a Danish university also pointed to **the role of researchers in fostering public trust**, albeit from a distinct viewpoint. In the experience of the participant, researchers sometimes focus too heavily on possessing the 'right' and correct facts and having a precise understanding of how the world looks, which can be difficult for the broader society to relate to. In this context, another participant, involved in public

participation, noted that it can be equally rewarding for researchers – as well as for citizens – to engage in on-site dialogues with citizens within specific local contexts, learning about ‘people’s everyday lives and reality’.

Research integrity

On the topic of research integrity, the conversation continued on the **role of researchers in the media**. Although there were different views on the dissemination of facts versus assessments, participants seemed to agree that researchers can, while maintaining integrity, speak on research areas outside of their own if done transparently and with substantiation. Two participants emphasised that researchers have a unique opportunity to help ‘translate’ complex research findings for the public. Another participant, involved in citizen participation, added that effective research dissemination is not necessarily an inherent skill for researchers, highlighting that institutions and science communicators have a responsibility for educating researchers in this area that is not ‘credited’ in the academic system. In relation to barriers to professional RI standards, one participant noted that the sheer explosion of research articles – mirroring the abundance in media in general – puts pressure on the peer review system, potentially compromising research integrity.

Public participation in research

Participants generally expressed a **support for involving citizens in research processes**, and several mentioned a range of public engagement activities taking place within and outside of research performing organisations. Participants involved in science communication management at universities primarily mentioned the use of more broad science communication initiatives such as democratic festivals, science festivals, social media interaction and open talks, noting that resource capacities also pose limitations on their level of ambition. Several also highlighted an increased attention and inclusion of citizen science activities within their universities more broadly, with one participant mentioning efforts to not only include citizens in data collection processes or as research subjects but also engage **citizens as ‘co-producers of science’** in scientific knowledge production processes. Two other participants, one from a funding agency and the other from a private organisation engaged in citizen engagement, most distinctly expressed the benefits of public integration in research, based on their experiences with various formats of citizen engagement with science. In this context, the funding agency participant noted that citizen participation is especially relevant when debating the perspectives of emerging technologies, understanding diverse positions as a basis for formulating new research agendas and research questions. It was also mentioned that conducting public engagement activities poses

challenges due to their often cost-intensive nature, limiting participation to smaller samples if in-depth involvement is the goal.

Recommendations concerning research integrity

When discussing **efforts to promote institutional RI**, participants highlighted a number of existing and future awareness- raising points and set of initiatives to be considered.

Several participants in communication management positions highlighted their increased focus on providing **research support** throughout the research process, covering areas such as budget management, external collaboration and relations, and data management, among others. Additionally, it was noted that large grant projects are increasingly receiving public publicity, thereby prompting a greater need for administrative and communicative research support to help researchers to maintain high standards of research integrity and navigate a complex media landscape. One participant also highlighted that while researchers intensely focus on the core aspects of science, 'the engine room', they sometimes pay less attention to other areas. For instance, data may not be managed properly, and while the science itself might be of a very high quality, overall research integrity will suffer. It was also mentioned that some unfortunate incidents have led to the development and updating of university policies, along with an increased emphasis on implementing these measures through training and governance structures, among other strategies.

As part of the discussion, a participant from a funding agency noted that their trust as a fund has not been disappointed, emphasising that breaches of research integrity should be addressed in alignment with their relatively low frequency. A participant from a university echoed this sentiment, suggesting that such **breaches are more likely due to a lack of attention and awareness of their importance rather than outright 'cheating'**.

In this context, it was observed that academia operates on a high degree of trust, and it was noted by several participants that there may be occasions when **universities are somewhat 'starry-eyed'** and not necessarily fully prepared to address issues like research espionage and potential consequences of AI innovations.

For funding organisations, it was highlighted that codes of conduct are adhered to, but that they rely on institutional RI legislation and policies. It was suggested by one funding representative that as funders, they would like to enhance their support for the **'science of science communication'** to encourage cross-cutting research that could yield more empirical knowledge about the diversity of research debates and dissemination methods.

2.3 Focus group 3

The third focus group discussion involved five participants professionally engaged in the fields of research integrity and social integration. For the latter, several participants specialized in areas related to support and ethics in open science and data management. One participant joined the focus group 30 minutes late due to an already planned meeting, while a sixth participant was absent. Unlike the other two focus group interviews, this one had an all-female composition, resulting in a skewed gender balance.

The discussion was engaging, with all participants actively and equally involved in the discussion. It was characterised by a very pleasant, constructive, and somewhat calm atmosphere, with participants being very conscientious about the joint interaction and exchanges of opinions in terms of providing space for each other's responses. Perhaps attributable to this attentiveness, the size of the group and the fact that only one moderator was present, the moderator (TR) employed a few more probes to facilitate the discussion compared to the moderation in the remaining focus groups. Despite this, participants engaged in dedicated conversation among themselves, and the discussion was easily kept on track in alignment with the moderator guide.

In general, the discussion primarily revolved around the main topic of science and society in relation to trust and open science from the perspectives of research integrity and research security issues. Several enablers and barriers for fostering a robust research integrity culture was discussed, including current trends and initiatives to support institutional RI and data ethics infrastructures. The topic of how and when to involve citizens in research was debated to a lesser extent, yielding diverse opinions on the contexts in which public engagement in science and technology is beneficial.

Relationship between science and society

In response to the initial open question concerning immediate associations regarding the relationship between science and society, participants explored the role of research in the Danish society like in the other two focus groups. They discussed the **balance between strategic and basic funding** as well as between public and private funding in terms of 'agenda-setting' power. In relation to the latter, two participants emphasised the need to be wary of a potential 'distortion' of focus areas that could affect the 'growth layer' with one participant pointing out that growth and innovation also often stem from basic research.

Representing various research support units in their professional capacities, several participants highlighted their organisations' roles as mediators between science and society. They mentioned the provision of resources on both local, regional, and national levels aimed at enhancing the quality of research, assist with ensuring a proper use of research data and deliver equal access to support infrastructures.

As part of the initial open question, participants also discussed the **advantages and challenges of open science**, particular in terms of data sharing and international cooperation. Participants – representing research support structures within and outside of universities as well as a research funding organisation – all draw attention to an increased institutional awareness on actions to promote **research security**. After years dedicated to an open research agenda that emphasized data sharing and the development of international research partnerships, the participants considered the heightened focus on security and the trend towards 'closing down' as unfortunate. While participants mentioned continuous efforts to promote international research collaborations for its benefits to research and research quality, a majority of participants listed a number of protective measures and policies being initiated to manage risks of foreign interference and dual use concerns. Such actions include conducting university risk assessments, appointing a security manager and implementing specific guidelines within the funding organisation in question. Furthermore, a representative from a university support unit also specifically pointed out a current campaign from the Danish Security and Intelligence Service designed to caution against research espionage. This campaign, however, was noted by the participant as having the potential drawback of casting undue suspicion on existing university employees from countries such as China, Iran, and Russia.

Trust in science

On the topic of general perceptions of trust in science, participants continued to discuss openness and data sharing, focusing specifically on the effect of introducing the GDPR legislation in 2018. Despite examples of **GDPR** making data sharing more difficult, a representative from a university support unit also spoke to a positive shift in the discourse towards increased legitimacy internally among researchers – ensuring data are managed correctly – and externally – assuring the public that data security is in place in the case of research involving controversial technologies, for instance. Overall, participants expressed the view that there is a **high level of public trust in science in Denmark, which correlates with a general trust in key public institutions**. They acknowledged the presence and impact of several detrimental single cases but noted that such cases have not eroded a general trust in science. Instead, these cases typically

prompt the establishment of new 'supervisory bodies' and policies to prevent future misconduct.

The view that there is generally a high level of trust in the Danish society does **not preclude mistrust or scepticism towards certain technological innovations**, for instance, in the fields of health and climate technologies. It is suggested that such mistrust might partly be driven by fear. As one participant mentioned, based on professional experience within the area of health - it is difficult to predict a correlation between negative reactions and specific groups or parts of society.

Research integrity

Addressing the aspect of trust in relation to research integrity, participants expressed that they generally find the **professional standards to be high** and that this is also to be expected from researchers, research performing institutions and funding organisations alike. One participant from a regional support unit noted that her expectations extend beyond mere compliance with the law - for instance the GDPR - to include aspects of conducting responsible research. This encompasses adhering to high standards of research ethics and integrity. Several participants noted that the establishment of social science ethical committees have come late compared to other countries but that they are necessary to comply with high and international standards. **The global nature of research and data sharing** have also increased the risks of misuse according to several participants. Barriers to sound RI research cultures include current systems of merit and incentives, including 'pressure to publish' and the extent of non-permanent positions. The participant from a funding agency explicitly mentioned the 'Reforming Research Assessment' initiative as a very positive trend towards more qualitative assessments which is regarded to influence positively on RI standards and trust in science as well.

Public participation in science

On the topic of citizen involvement, participants generally **recognize the benefits but have varying opinions on when and how to engage the public in research-related processes**. One participant - engaged within the area of health care - has noted an increased awareness of systematically engaging citizens, patients and next of kin. She is also the one most 'on the champion side' of public engagement, advocating for the numerous benefits of participation in enhancing the quality of research. Conversely, other participants pointed out that citizen science may be better suited for certain types of research than to others, such as those related to basic research.

3 Building trust in science: from perception to institutional engagement

The following sections present the main findings across the three Danish focus group discussions, detailing participant perceptions of trust in science, cultures of research integrity, and public engagement in science within institutional and national contexts.

3.1 About science and society

When reflecting upon the **complex relationship** between science and society, participants generally seemed to agree that science is **one of the most important institutions** in our society and serves as a foundation for continuous societal development. Furthermore, participants emphasised the importance of research engaging in dialogue with its surroundings and the greater societal context.

“Research should be relevant, and research should be accessible, and research is, after all, one of the most recognised ways to understand something. That is, presumably, the main argument for research to be of value to society; it is a recognised way to possess knowledge or to document knowledge. So, it is. It should be given that research must be something for society, and society should trust research to some extent” (P2, male, RPO, FG2).

In addition, one main theme emerged as a cross-cutting topic in the discussions of all three focus groups: **the relevance of science**. While participants agreed on the societal importance of science, their opinions varied on when and how science is relevant, reflecting a divide between fundamental/basic research and problem-oriented research.

Two participants, in particular, each from different research funding organisations, highlighted the importance of **research being ‘curiosity-driven**. They noted, in particular, that basic research might not set out to explore or solve any current societal issues but could end up ‘solving problems that do not exist’ (P1, female, RFO, FG1) or that are ‘not yet highly topical’ and that may lead to important discoveries (P2, female, RFO, FG3). The latter participant mentioned that, as a research funding agency, they still prioritize communicating the practical value of research. The first participant noted that, as a research organisation, they experience pressure on researchers to focus on the societal relevance of science. The **relevance of science in terms of impact and application** were evident

in statements from a majority of participants. Overall, this stance can be summarised according to the following quotation:

"I know that I sometimes end up discussing things with basic researchers, but the idea that research should be used or created in relation with the surrounding society, or choosing one's research questions because they are relevant for the society to explore, because it's something we want to understand better, improve, develop, or whatever. And then afterwards - perhaps along the way - also collaborate with someone, and at least in the end, creating something with the goal of it going out to help develop our society and make it better" (P5, female, RPO, FG2).

The statements generally reflect a greater debate concerning strategic vs. 'blue skies research' as well as a current focus on societal challenges and the impact of science on society, not least promoted by the European Framework Programmes.

In response to the opening question regarding the relationship between science and society, the discussions closely intertwined with varying perceptions of trust in science. These perceptions are detailed in the following section.

3.2 Perceptions of trust in science

Participants across the focus groups generally agreed on a **high level of trust in science within the Danish society**. This consensus was supported by professional insights from trust surveys and general observations of supporting factors. These factors include significant public funding for research and innovation; the country's small size, high status and social capital associated with research, a general pro-science stance among political parties, and an educational system that emphasises science. Several participants compared the level of trust with their own experiences from other countries, highlighting a close intertwinement of science and society in Denmark. Furthermore, participants seemed to agree that this high level in trust in science is correlated with a relatively high level of confidence in key Danish national institutions.

While participants generally put emphasis on the importance of a high level of trust, several participants also stated that **we as a society should not trust researchers and research blindly**.

"We do not have a trust issue with research in Denmark, that is, if you look at the actual situation (...). I think you should have trust in research, but I don't know if you should have blind trust in researchers (...). You should trust what is being presented more than the one presenting it" (P3, male, RFO, FG 2).

Furthermore, disagreements are inherent in science, and participants expressed the view that research should be discussed and criticised – without necessarily reducing its trustworthiness. Additionally, researchers should be able to defend their findings in a transparent fashion.

“We talk about research and society, but perhaps it’s actually a somewhat oversimplified setup, because researchers do not agree, and there are really many disagreements among researchers. And how do we catalyse this disagreement out into society? Not us, but how is the population made to understand that research it not unreliable because researchers do not agree. Research is a process, it is a method, it is always two steps forward and one step back, different research designs will yield different results. It is the very essence of science to disagree with itself. Otherwise, we get nowhere.” (P1, female, RFO, FG 2).

This statement speaks to a broader theme of **contradictions vs. consensus in science** in relation to public understandings of science and their relation to fostering or reducing trust in science. This theme was primarily discussed from the perspective of researchers and their roles and responsibilities in term of fostering trust.

In this context, participants – primarily in the second group discussion – engaged in a nuanced debate on how researchers could contribute to decreasing trust by either offering personal assessments rather than evidence-based recommendations in the media or being overly intransigent in focusing on precise measures and isolated facts, which creates barriers to broader scientific and societal debates (see section 2.2).

“I believe that the trust relationship between society and researchers is on a journey. And I think you have a point in saying ‘research has high credibility’, but I also believe that enough researchers have been questioned so that the media is not shy – and should not be – to question whether the research is good enough, for the individual researcher” (P7, female, RPO, FG 2).

While participants generally agreed to the fact that research should be questioned, they also pointed to an **increasing pressure on the legitimacy of both researchers and universities**. This pressure relates to a loss of pre-given authority and increasing demands to demonstrate and communicate ongoing relevance. In the discussions in focus group 1 and 2, participants highlighted the negative aspects of political pressure on the legitimacy of science, particularly in relation to certain areas of research within the humanities and social sciences. Although opinions varied on whether the politization of research can be contributed to reduced trust in science among politicians, participants seemed to agree on the increased **politization and ideological instrumentalization of science** by politicians. In this context, participants’ concern about potential

manipulation of the public opinion reflects a more global trend of citizens worrying about the interference of governments in research (Gallup, 2019; Editorial, Nature, 2024).

Crisis of Trust?

While participants **could not recognise signs of a trust crisis in the Danish society**, they did identify **'cracks' in public trust** that may be exploited for manipulative purposes. They also noted that conditions for fostering distrust have improved. In relation to the political landscape, several participants highlighted the complex relationship between science and governance, particularly in terms of diverse use of evidence-based policy decision-making and the significant involvement of researchers in reform committees:

"(...) Politically, one relies on reform work that is actually done by researchers. So, sometimes research is given a lot of weight, and other times, we are kept at arm's length, so that's also an interesting dynamic with our decision-makers, one might say. But I believe that mistrust - at least has gotten better conditions than it has had before, and that is also part of the media conversation" (P7, female, RPO, FG 2).

Overall, participants across the three focus groups were of the perceptions that **single instances of detrimental research practices** might create ripples that may impact on reputations and trust to some extent. However, they believed these instances are not capable of overturning the 'supertanker' as a whole (see section 2.1.). The following quotation from a participant working in a research funding organisation, seems to capture the general perception of whether there is a crisis of trust in science:

"I experience it as somewhat isolated to individual cases or incidents that suddenly get a media run, more or less justified. But for some reason, my perception is certainly not that there is general mistrust, not at all, quite the contrary actually. But then there are those cases where it either becomes a media issue, or where there's a really messy case. Which is truly bad, isn't it, and had long lasting implications (P2, female, RFO, FG3).

Relatedly, another participant in the same focus group highlighted a development in the factors potentially challenging trust in science:

"The worries have become different over the last 20-30 years because technology has changed so much, hasn't it? So maybe. I mean, I don't know, I am not sure if trust is challenged, but of course, there are different discussions, and that's true. I find that it's difficult for people to understand and get to grips with what it means when they share their data, what it means when something is anonymized or

synchronized, right? And you can explain it as many times as you want, but it's just abstract" (P5, female, research support, FG3).

This perception is closely related to the issue of research integrity, as discussed in section 3.0, as well as it addresses public reactions to emerging technologies and scientific advancements.

Reactions to scientific advancements

While several participants mentioned varying levels of scepticism as a response to technological innovations, **none identified larger movements of opposition or mobilization against specific scientific advancement**. The case of Covid-19 is cited as an example that elicited diverse reactions in the Danish society. Across focus groups, participants also mentioned several technologies that may have sparked reactions of scepticism, for instance AI, healthcare algorithms, environmental issues, and healthcare robots. Participants did not attribute specific reactions of uncertainty, fear, or scepticism to particular groups. One participant has experienced that particular instances of mistrust, opposition or scepticism, for instance towards health care research and treatments, sometimes evolved from particular **'echo chambers'**. However, at the same time, the participant also noted the **difficulty of pinpointing certain groups or clear patterns** regarding different positionings among the public and that it – speaking from experience – is very challenging to predict specific responses to scientific advancements.

Another participant highlighted a similar observation:

"Sometimes I think, it can turn out that it's not necessarily those who are impacted by the research who are against it. In some cases, it can be surprising, for example, with health-care robots, it might not be the users or their relatives who are opposed, but rather someone far removed from ever needing any of this, who has some kind of resistance, right. So, it can be difficult to define. What exactly causes this resistance. What is it in the individual that stirs?" (P3, female, RPO, FG3).

3.3. Attitudes towards research integrity

Participants are engaged with the issue of research integrity through their professions and areas of expertise, demonstrating **high awareness and attentiveness towards identifying both enablers and barriers that support a research culture of integrity**, focusing on a range of topics related to research practices from data management, publication/communication and ethics structures. Based on the focus

group discussions, it seemed that participants perceived a general research culture characterised by a relatively high level of research integrity. Furthermore, they did not identify a widespread problematic culture marred by integrity breaches and detrimental research practices. They primarily talked about intentional **scientific misconduct cases as relatively rare**, with two participants explicitly noting that research integrity breaches and more questionable research practices (QRPs) often stem from a lack of awareness rather than intentional cheating. In relation to individual cases, participants across focus groups mentioned a number of detrimental research practice cases at different universities that have gained public attention. These examples were used to discuss current policies, practices, and issues of attention.

In general, participants highlighted the importance of fostering high standards of integrity practices to ensure high-quality research, transparency, credibility, and trust in science. The issue of **researcher independence** was also brought forward as a subject of importance. One participant working with research support spoke to the interrelationship between independence and credibility:

"But I mean - I also continue to think while we talk about - some of the things we have touched upon, the idea that - when I also - what's it called - listen to some researchers in the news or read some articles or watch a YouTube channel of a researcher. The importance of being able to trust what the person is saying is based on methods that are reliable. This is, well, a huge - what's it called - a huge counter to fake news, for example. The fact that I hear a researcher who is independent of politicians means a LOT to me and my impression of research. If I believe that someone is in the pockets of others, then that person loses their credibility. As long as I can believe that research is independent, then I can actually trust that - it's again a counterbalance against political currents and so on, but this places very large - what's it called - or high demands on research ethics, that it's in order" (P2, female, RPO, FG1).

In relation to a culture of research integrity, several participants mentioned a **shift towards open science** - including its principles of transparency, data sharing, fairness, and accessibility - as a positive development. The implementation and increased legitimacy associated with the EU general data protection regulation (GDPR) was also mentioned as a beneficial change, alongside the introduction of research ethics committees within the social sciences. While participants did not identify a general detrimental culture of research, they did identify a number of **barriers and factors posing challenges to research integrity**. Precarious employment in academia, a 'pressure-to-publish' mentality, a reproducibility crisis, lack of integrity training, gift authorships, insufficient time to open up and make data available, and potential conflicts of interests in term of private funding were some of the factors mentioned. Furthermore,

challenges related to the current publication and peer-review system were also identified as problematic. Issues such as expensive publishing, a high number of article retractions, and the difficulties of finding qualified reviewers were mentioned as important concerns:

"But one of the threats to credibility and integrity, I believe it's not just AI - there's also a huge peer-review crisis, because so much research is being produced, and then this - excuse me - open access monster has been created. Everyone talked about this 'open access.' 'We just need open access,' and now it's just - if you ask, many researchers think it's a nightmare. Because there are far too many journals and far too lax control over data, with the presentations (...)". Many of them [researchers] share this story. That they often say no to peer review or to reviewing, right? Because they don't get anything out of it. And the same happens when they themselves submit something, so it's extremely difficult for journals to actually find reviewers. And this just means that much, or some, will more likely get through without the proper quality stamp and without the proper processing before being published. And I just think we've seen the beginning of this. It's going to become a bigger problem moving forward" (P1, female, RFO, FG2).

From various perspectives, participants pointed to **the global nature of research as a challenge and facilitator of research integrity**. As to the latter, one participant mentioned the fact that worldwide research into the same topics help ensure consensus and quality. Another highlighted the need to maintain a high degree of integrity to maintain a strong international reputation and attract international collaborators:

"... But as a university, one also has an interest in ensuring that the research that is published is also well-regarded, if one wants to collaborate with others, right? Because when we sit down and start up projects and want to find partners, there are some universities we rule out, right? There are some where we think, 'Ah, we could probably find something better,' right? And I mean this on a global scale. That there are differences, and we as a university would also like, when they look at us and say, 'We need to find a partner, well, we can confidently collaborate with university [name of own university], because we know everything is in order" (P3, female, RPO, FG3).

In relation to challenges, the global nature of research also poses risks in terms of what it being shared and published. As the same participants also noted in the interview:

But there's also a greater risk today because it's just much easier to suddenly publish to the whole world on the internet and everything, isn't it, in ways that perhaps weren't possible before (P3, female, RPO, FG3).

In the first focus group interview, participants particularly identified the global nature of science as a barrier to implementing research integrity procedures and policies at national and institutional levels. **International standards** were perceived as essential to support greater research integrity transformations. Various initiatives were provided as examples, with the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) seen as an example of an exemplary international initiative capable of altering the current research integrity landscape.

"I think the publication or incentive structure in recent years has really had a huge influence on how research has been conducted and merited, and yes, it has been - what should I say - it has bitten its own tail, you could say. In several respects. (...) This thing about seeing very one-dimensionally what has been meritorious for the individual researcher in terms of funding, and also in terms of employment, how it has, well, yes. So, I think this confrontation with it, which also has - really received a huge amount of support. I mean, it has really come at the right time. There have been some attempts at it earlier, but which haven't really received the support that it suddenly has now. I think that's mega positive. So, it's something we are working on, among other things. I believe a majority of all Danish universities have joined in as well and several of the private foundations" (P2 ,female, RFO, FG3).

In addition, the research participant highlighted likely and associated impacts of the initiative in terms of greater transparency, increased trust, and enhanced quality and research integrity.

3.4. Attitudes towards social integration

Participants across the three focus groups are involved in public engagement in science and technology to varying degrees. As specified in the method section (please see section 1.1.), the issue of social integration in science was addressed in the focus groups as 'citizen involvement in science and technology' as this terminology better aligns with the Danish conceptualisation of the term. Public involvement in science was framed as citizen-science interrelations, emphasising two-way dialogue and interaction over more traditional one-way science communication formats, reflecting the movement 'from communication to deliberation' or 'from understanding to engagement' (Burgess, 2014; Stilgoe, Lock, and Wilsson, 2014). A few participants were actively engaged in projects applying participatory methods, whereas others were more indirectly involved through different research support functions (see section 1.2). Several participants,

particular in the second focus group, worked with science communication in relation to research performing organisations.

Participants commonly perceived a **growing number of initiatives being launched** to support the involvement of citizens into scientific knowledge production processes. This trend was observable both in universities, at large, and within individually funded research projects. Beyond traditional science communication formats, several participants referred to the use of participatory formats within their own organisations. These approaches include citizen science apps and initiatives, public consultations, user involvement in technological service innovations, and dialogue formats that emphasise deliberation and co-production of knowledge.

Citizens were seen as willing to participate in science dissemination events and lectures, and while it was acknowledged that it may primarily involve **specific segments of society**, it was emphasised that it indicates an interest in science and a general trust in scientific endeavours. At the same time, it was also mentioned by two participants that citizens are more likely to support research and researchers if they agree with the findings.

While participants generally agreed on the benefits of citizen involvement in research, it was evident that **those directly engaged in citizen science and public engagement generally held a more favourable view of the advantages**. For instance, they highlighted the educational potential of sparking an interest in science from a young age, improving data and research outcomes, and enhancing trust in science, at large:

"How do we ensure an informed basis for a qualified conversation, which also to a large degree involves mutual listening, and that the research becomes proficient at listening to those whom it also tries to communicate the research. So, I believe. At least, that's the starting point I come from, that trust often arises in the dialogue between researchers and citizens" (P4, female, private org., FG2).

"When you have citizens in the room, who are the ones to receive the service we actually produce, then you also make an extra effort. And I'm not saying that people don't make an effort already, but perhaps you make just a BIT more of an effort, and you're also more rigorously tested on whether you can defend and explain all parts of it" (P5, female, RPO, FG3).

"When you mentioned that thing about 'why are we actually doing this'. Well, it might be to get more funding, and we see that too. In my unit, we support researchers in writing good applications. And one of the mantras - there can be many good mantras from Brussels - and a less good one, is that about citizen involvement. Apparently, it's - what's it called - the key to everything, that research improves by involving citizens. Where we sometimes struggle to convince these

peer-reviewers that it doesn't really make much sense to involve citizens in this particular type of project, because what are those poor citizens supposed to think? On the other hand, citizen involvement is insanely good where it's about uncovering bias, uncovering researchers' biases, bringing some diversity and variety into this, making researchers say 'okay, I have some assumptions and hypotheses, but how do other people actually see this, and people who aren't so steeped in this research world, how do they perceive things and so on and so forth'. So for me, I see citizen involvement very much as something that can improve research. Create more trust." (P2, female, RPO, FG1).

The latter quotation in the textbox above also underscores that **citizen involvement are not equally relevant across all research projects** and cannot be seen as a universal solution for enhancing research quality. While participants may concur that some research projects - or specific aspects of research processes - could benefit more from public engagement than others, they offer diverse viewpoints on how and when to include citizens. Two participants pointed out that allowing citizens to influence the funding prioritization of research projects might be driven more by personal interests than by data. Conversely, two other participants noted concrete initiatives at a university and a funding organisation, where citizens have actively participated in the prioritization of research funding. Some participants also mentioned that very abstract research projects within basic research, such as research in 'nanotechnology' or 'dark matter', may not be as suited for citizen research compared to practice-oriented research.

On the issue on whether citizen involvement can positively impact the dissemination of scientific knowledge, two participants explicitly stated that science communication efforts have the potential to reach a broader public audience, whereas public engagement activities primarily address a smaller sample within the public population. In this context, it was also mentioned that implementing public engagement initiatives are often cost-intensive in terms of time, money, and personnel, which may limit the actual deployment of such engagement initiatives.

3.5. Institutional contributions to trust in science

While several participants highlighted the need for international standards and initiatives, many also mentioned institutional efforts initiated to promote research integrity such as increased research support throughout the entire research process, encompassing assistance with research dissemination, external collaborations, and data management, for example. In this context, it was also noted that

negative cases frequently prompt institutional self-examination and lead to increased efforts to up-date or employ new policies and measures. While not posed as a direct recommendation, one participant from a university explicitly emphasized the **difficulty of translating from policy to practice**, stressing that it is challenging to assess best practices and compare efforts.

In general, the discussions on promoting professional standards of integrity indicate an attention towards collective actions and a shared research culture of integrity, reflecting a shift within research communities from individual to collective actions (Mejlgaard et al. 2020).

Participants from research funding organisations generally expressed an adherence to the Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and emphasised their **reliance on research integrity policies and procedures at research performing organisations**. Several also explicitly mentioned an attention towards research integrity issues during research application evaluation processes, for instance, and while research funding agencies rely on university procedures. While research funding organisations depend on university procedures, two participants mentioned that topics of research integrity can be further addressed through courses or workshops, for example.

Given the significant variation in types of research projects, one participant from a funding organisation pointed to the difficulty of implementing uniform assessment criteria for citizen involvement in science at funding organisations.

Overall, participants highlighted an increased awareness and diversity of initiatives for public engagement in science, which could positively impact on social integration in science. However, the discussions on initiatives to promote public engagement in science were generally less extensive than those on actions to enhance research integrity at organisational levels. One participant suggested a need for **more systematic approaches to how and when citizens are involved in science**, noting that it currently appears to depend largely on individual and project-level efforts. Additionally, two other participants recommended greater **transparency in the supply of existing initiatives and options for involvement**. A fourth participant further emphasised the recommendation to create **organisational infrastructures and incentive structures** that enhance both research integrity efforts and public participation in research. The implementation of citizen councils was cited as one example of how to increase citizen engagement.

"One can do that by creating incentives in their organization, or by developing some infrastructure, right? I mean, I think [name of own organisation] is an example of wanting to create an infrastructure that provided secure frameworks for how to support research projects, and as a research leader, you could feel reasonably safe, right? And

so on, right? So, one can do a lot at the organizational level, in addition to cultural work and value work, and so forth, right? And those frameworks can also be created in relation to citizen involvement if one wanted to do so". (P5, female, RPO, FG3)

Similar to recommendations to support research integrity actions, participants highlighted systematic efforts at both macro and meso levels in order to improve citizen inclusion in science.

4. Conclusion

Across three focus group interviews, 18 professional stakeholders working in areas of research support, public engagement with science, research evaluation, research funding, science communication and open science discussed the current state of trust in science in relation to research integrity and citizen involvement within institutional and national contexts.

Overall, participants highlighted a complex relationship between science and society, emphasizing, among other things, a rising pressure on the legitimacy of both research performing organisations (RPOs) and researchers. While noting a general high level of trust in Denmark, and without identifying a distinct crisis of trust, several participants mentioned the emergence of 'cracks' in public trust, which they viewed as negatively influencing an increased politicization and ideological instrumentalization of science. Participants did not recognize any large movements of opposition or mobilization against specific scientific advancement but identified examples of mistrust and skepticism towards certain technological innovations.

Participants regarded research as one of the most important societal institutions, agreeing that research should help develop societies and be relevant for the greater public good. Different opinions were brought forward regarding the relevance of science, reflecting a division between fundamental/basic research and problem-oriented research.

Responsible research was perceived as a means to increase trust in research, with professional standards related to research integrity generally considered high. Based on the discussions, the global nature of research was found to offer both enablers and barriers to promoting a culture of research integrity. Participants recommended shared research integrity standards across institutions and countries and highlighted a set of principles and practices conducive to research integrity.

Participants generally supported the idea of citizen involvement in science and noted the potential of dialogue-based approaches to improve public trust in science. While taking a positive stance towards the advantages of citizen involvement in science, opinions varied on when and how to engage citizens, with several noting that not all research projects are equally conducive to such involvement. Participants identified a heightened awareness to engaging the public in research, particularly at research performing institutions. Some participants recommended more systematic approaches at national and institutional levels to increase participation and enhance transparency in the availability of existing engagement initiatives.

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poiesis
TRUST IN SCIENCE

National Report: Focus Groups - FRANCE

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integration on societal trust in science**

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1 Introduction

1.1 Set up of the focus group

The French focus group interviews were all conducted on-line on the 4th, 11th, and 14th of March 2024. All interviews lasted around two hours. FG 1 was moderated by co-investigator Antoine de Daruvar, FG 2 by co-investigator Caroline Strube, FG3 by co-investigator Olivier Le Gall. The three French co-investigators were recruited due for their key and varied previous expertise in research integrity, science communication, and research evaluation. The three co-investigators are:

- Antoine de Daruvar: former vice-president of University Bordeaux Segalen, former director of the doctoral school Bordeaux University, former member of the national "Corvol" committee on research integrity, Antoine de Daruvar, with his colleague Yannick Lung, is the initiator of the first french online training course on scientific integrity. The MOOC "Scientific Integrity in the Research" is a free training course open to anyone who wants to find out more about what it means to conduct research with integrity and responsibility. The MOOC has four main parts: 1) the challenges of scientific integrity, 2) what are scientific breaches or misconducts ?, 3) how can scientific misconduct be prevented?, 4) the regulation of scientific integrity.
- Caroline Strube: CNRS researcher in neurobiology, member of the Center for Research in Psychology and Neuroscience at Aix Marseille University, Caroline Strube is the research integrity officer of her lab , but also member of CNRS "Mission à l'intégrité scientifique" created in 2018 in charge of investigating misconduct cases and setting up training initiatives. Caroline Strube has been an active member of the CovETHOS project, funded by the ANR, looking, from 2021 to 2023, at the consequences of the covid crisis on scientific integrity and research ethics. During this previous project she has been trained to conduct individual interviews but also to moderate focus group.
- Olivier Le Gall : Originally trained in plant biology, senior research fellow at the Institut national de recherche pour l'agriculture, l'alimentation et l'environnement (INRAE), Olivier Le Gall has been INRAE Deputy Director in charge of the Institute's research programme, skills portfolio, infrastructure and partnerships. From 2017 to 2023, he has been

President of the French Council for Scientific Integrity (COFIS), the scientific council of the French office for scientific integrity (OFIS). Olivier Le Gall has also been an active member of the CovETHOS project, funded by the ANR.

Despite busy schedules, the moderators agreed to contribute to the research project without any notable difficulty. No further candidates were contacted. This relatively rapid agreement can be explained by our pre-existing mutual acquaintance, but also by our colleagues' interest in transforming the subject of their work as integrity officer into a research subject. As mentioned two of the moderators were part in a previous scientific project coordinated by the current project members and the third one was initially interviewed as part of an ongoing project on the social history of scientific integrity in France.

An individual online meeting was organised for each moderator/co-investigator to explain the general orientations of the project. Co-investigators were provided with the information booklet and guidelines material. All moderators were able to take part in a dedicated online training course in French, distinct from the collective training in english for moderators from other national partners.

The training course provided an opportunity to go through the interview guide line by line, and to adjust it as closely as possible to the national context. The notion of « social integration » developed in the European version Poiesis project was not considered sufficiently clear and was replaced by the french notion of « participation citoyenne » (public participation). After the focus groups sessions, the online sorting card exercise prepared by the English and Portuguese partners, also gave rise to a detailed reading, with fairly lengthy discussions on the national variations in interpretation around each term used.

For each focus group, the moderators were asked to propose a list of around fifteen possible participants. During an online discussion, each list was split up into three groups: contacts to be given priority, contacts to be used secondarily, and 'back-up' contacts if the others were not available. In most cases, the contacts in the first group, based on the sample criteria stipulated in the research protocol, agreed to make themselves available without too much difficulty. As in previous projects, this recruitment strategy of using the moderator's formal or informal professional network proved particularly effective.

Invitation emails were sent out by the moderator. Participants who accepted the invitation received a second email one week prior to the focus group, in which they received a letter of information describing the details of the POIESIS project and the focus group study, a

consent form, and an information sheet informing about CNRS/Sorbonne University's processing of personal data.

Participants in one of the three discussion groups asked for the opportunity to talk to the project members. An online meeting lasting about an hour was organised to answer their questions about the objectives of the research and any other related subjects.

All focus group interviews were recorded online and transcribed instantly by a member of the research team. Another member of the team reviewed the transcriptions to ensure accuracy.

The focus group transcriptions were then coded in the software and data facilitation programme NVivo (by TR) by using the codebook provided. The codebook matrix distinguishes between sociological notions (perception, attitudes, rationales and recommendations) and empirical issues (science, trust/distrust, integrity/misconduct, citizen participation, institution). Hence a theoretical total of 25 codes, but with a frequency that could vary considerably. Emerging sub-topics and themes were inductively coded and added to the codebook. The analysis reported in the subsequent sections includes a within and across-case analysis of the three focus group interviews, following the report template structure of the collective focus group study.

1.2 Participants in the focus group

The following tables outline the composition of participants in the three French focus groups according to gender, position, and institution. No detailed information is provided to maintain the anonymity of participants. RPO refers to Research performing organisation and RFO to research funding organisation.

It should be noted that two of the participants who had agreed to take part in the third focus group were unable to attend at the last minute, resulting in a smaller number of participants. Overall, the 3 focus groups brought together 16 participants with prominent positions.

Focus group 1 - Moderator: Antoine De Daruvar

Participant Id.	Gender	Position	Institution
FG1_1	F	Manager	National public debate institution
FG1_2	M	Officer "science and society"	RPO
FG1_3	F	Former director	Public health institution
FG1_4	F	Manager of research and innovation committee	Association of RPO

FG1_5	M	Director	Scientific mediation organization
FG1_6	M	professor, Responsible conduct of research expert	RPO

Focus group 2 - Moderator : Caroline Strube

Participant Id.	Gender	Position	Institution
FG2_1	M	Research integrity officer	RPO
FG2_2	F	Research Integrity and Ethics Officer	RPO
FG2_3	F	Research Integrity and Ethics Officer	RPO
FG2_4	F	Research Integrity and Ethics Officer	RPO
FG2_5	F	Research Integrity officer and pdt of national association of integrity officers	University
FG2_6	F	Research Integrity officer	RPO

Focus group 3 - Moderator: Olivier Le Gall

Participant Id.	Gender	Position	Institution
FG3_1	M	Science journalist	Major French newspaper
FG3_2	F	Integrity and deontology officer	RPO
FG3_3	M	Head of the office integrity	RPO
FG3_4	M	Manager	European scientific mediation organization

2 Sequential description of the focus groups

The following section outlines a sequential description of each of the three French focus group interviews, hence presenting detailed within-case analysis aimed at describing the nature of topics, ideas, and perceptions as they were conveyed in each group. In addition to reporting on the specific content of the various interviews, a brief overview of the group composition, interactions, and moderation is included.

2.1 Focus group 1

The first focus group, moderated by Antoine de Daruvar, had three main general features : a large proportion of participants living and working in the south west of France (near Bordeaux), a wide variety of profiles and professional experiences, a strong focus during the discussion on public participation in science.

The participants were, in turn, 1) a non academic member of a national commission responsible for public debate, particularly on scientific and technological issues, 2) a research integrity officer in a major University, 3) a former director of a national agency in charge of health policies during the Covid crisis period, 4) a research and innovation manager in the main association of

French universities, 5) the director of a major scientific mediation association, and 6) a historian of science with a strong expertise in science-society relations.

The composition of the group included three female and three male participants, in addition to the moderator (AdD). Along with a balance in gender and a high level of variety professional subject areas, the discussions demonstrated a high level of commitment from all the participants.

All themes were fully discussed and explored, however, due to the presence of two participants working in the field of scientific mediation, a great deal of time has been devoted to discussing the challenges of public participation. They all spoke freely for almost two hours, with a few follow-up comments from the moderator when necessary.

Science and society

For the opening question, participants were asked to name the words that came spontaneously to their mind when thinking about the relationship between science and society.

For both FG1_2 and FG1_4, the main words were "information", "democratization" and "empowerment".

Quote - French original version	Quote - English translation
FG1_2 : (...) le grand public a besoin d'être éclairé sur ces enjeux. (...) On a des défis qui s'offrent à nous, qu'ils soient sociétaux, environnementaux, climatiques et autres. On a besoin d'éclairer le débat public... (...) il faut "encapaciter" le citoyen à comprendre ces enjeux. Cela veut dire, lui donner les clefs pour qu'il soit en capacité de dépasser un peu ces enjeux partisans ou politiques...	FG1_2 : (...)The general public needs to be informed about these issues. (...) We're facing societal, environmental, climate and other challenges. We need to inform the public debate (...) we need to "empower" citizens to understand what is at stake. This means giving them the keys so that they can look beyond partisan or political issues.

FG1_1 and FG1_5 chose the words "méli-mélo" ("mishmash") and "grand bazar" (the "big mess"). These terms were used to describe how difficult it is today for non-scientists to distinguish between good science and bad science when scientists speak publicly, and how to distinguish between accurate information and false information.

Quote - French original version	Quote - English translation
FG1_5 : (...)j'ai bien aimé le méli-mélo (...) on a ce sentiment de grand bazar (...) Pour nous autour de la table la légitimité académique est une vraie légitimité. Ça n'est plus le cas pour beaucoup de gens. Aujourd'hui c'est souvent la légitimité affinitaire qui compte : mes potes disent que le vaccin est dangereux donc c'est dangereux...	FG1_5 : (...) (...) I liked the mishmash (...) you get this feeling of a big mess (...) For us around the table, academic legitimacy is a real legitimacy. That's no longer the case for many people. Nowadays, it's often affinity that matters: my mates say that the vaccine is dangerous, so it's dangerous....

Finally FG1_3 and FG1_6 underscored the notion of "trust," elucidating the prerequisites necessary for the public to have confidence in the scientific community, particularly regarding the dependability of scientific findings and the ethical conduct of scientists.

Quote - French original version	Quote - English translation
FG1_3 : (...)la confiance du public, c'est crucial en santé publique. Parce qu'on demande au public de renoncer à certaines de ses libertés (...) La fiabilité, mais aussi l'intégrité scientifique attendue des chercheurs : la question c'est celle de la responsabilité des institutions mais aussi des chercheurs eux-mêmes car dans la production de leur propre science, de leurs résultats, ils vont influencer des décisions en matière de santé publique, c'est crucial.	FG1_3 : (...) Public trust is crucial in public health. Because we are asking the public to give up some of their freedoms (...) Reliability, but also the scientific integrity expected of researchers: the issue is that of the responsibility of institutions, but also of the researchers themselves, because in producing their own science, their results, they are going to influence public health decisions, and that's crucial.

In the discussion on trust, it was stressed that the spread of false information or beliefs was not so much linked to a lack of education as to a lack of trust in the scientific community.

Trust in science

The participants agreed on the overarching idea of a general crisis of trust between science and society in France. According to them this crisis often stems from the perception that scientists lack autonomy from political or economic agendas, exacerbating the erosion of public confidence.

Quote - French original version	Quote - English translation
FG1_1 : (...)il y a indéniablement un problème de confiance parfois. Ça peut s'exprimer de façon différente : on peut entendre parfois ce scientifique n'est pas fiable parce qu'il a travaillé pour tel ou tel organisme. Ça peut être des organismes qui ont des activités économiques, ça peut être des organismes d'état, de gouvernement. Et ça mélange des aspects soit de science et business, soit de science et politique.	FG1_1 : (...)there is undeniably a problem of trust sometimes. It can be expressed in different ways: sometimes you hear that a scientist is not reliable because he has worked for such and such an organisation. This may be organisations that have economic activities, or state or government activities. And this mixes aspects of either science and business, or science and politics.

For some participants mistrust in science was fuelled not so much by science itself as by the negative perception of some of its direct or indirect consequences: climate change, pesticides, etc. The discussion also highlighted the role of the public's lack of understanding of the scientific process and the role of doubt in this process.

Quote - French original version	Quote - English translation
FG1_5 : pour la défiance il y a la mauvaise compréhension de ce qu'est la science établie et de ce qu'est la science en marche. L'amalgame entre les choses qu'on sait et les choses qu'on recherche... un exemple qui revient souvent c'est la question des bébés couchés ou sur le dos ou sur le ventre etc, « ça change tout le	FG1_5 : mistrust stems from a misunderstanding of what is established science and what is science in progress. The confusion between the things we know and the things we're looking for... an example that comes up a lot is the question of babies lying down or on their backs or stomachs etc., "it's changing all the time". the

temps ». la question de la science qui avance et change permet de douter...	question of science moving forward and changing allows doubt...
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Science during the Covid crisis

Participants emphasized the COVID-19 era as a challenging time for the scientists to convey a sense of the scientific process to the general public. But this period also starkly revealed the difficulties faced by science journalists in serving as mediators between scientists and the public. These difficulties were sometimes linked to the distrust of the general public: journalists are described as taking shortcuts, moving too quickly, which can lead to disappointment or corrections that fuel doubts about science itself.

Quote - French original version	Quote - English translation
FG1_2 : En général les collègues scientifiques qui publient prennent des précautions mais la traduction dans les médias prend des raccourcis et fait qu'on prend pour argent comptant des résultats qui restent à consolider... et donc ça crée de la défiance parce que finalement après... Les médias relaient parfois un peu trop vite, ou prennent des raccourcis. Quand le public n'est pas complètement averti sur la façon dont la démarche se déroule, finalement on prend peut être des raccourcis qui créent au final un peu de défiance à mon avis...	FG1_2 : In general, scientific colleagues who publish take precautions, but the translation in the media takes shortcuts and leads people to take at face value results that have yet to be consolidated... and so this creates mistrust because, in the end, afterwards... The media sometimes relay the results a little too quickly, or take shortcuts. When the public isn't fully aware of how the process works, we may end up taking shortcuts that ultimately create a bit of mistrust in my opinion...

Other participants offered a more nuanced perspective on the evolution of trust in science amid the COVID-19 era. In France, vaccination campaigns commenced in early 2021 amidst initial public skepticism toward vaccination policies. However, opinions swiftly shifted during the first half of the year. Faced with vaccine shortages, media coverage, and governmental pressure, a significant portion of the population quickly embraced vaccination. Hence, it's imperative to refrain from adopting a rigidly static viewpoint regarding our relationship with science during times of crisis.

This period coincided with the emergence of new players who complemented the traditional mediators: data scientists who did in-depth work on public health indicators, while accepting to transform themselves into influencers by taking up public health

Research integrity

In the discussion on research integrity, the participants divided themselves into two groups: on the one hand, those who felt that France had done what needed to be done on the subject (FG1_4), and on the other, those who felt that the issue remained unresolved despite the institutional efforts of the last 20 years (FG1_3).

Quote - French original version	Quote - English translation
FG1_4 Je pense qu'aujourd'hui c'est moins un sujet, j'ai l'impression que c'est mis en	FG1_4 : I think that today it's not so much a subject, I have the impression that it's

place dans les établissements. Il y a maintenant un réseau des référents intégrité... J'ai l'impression que le sujet se déporte plus sur les questions, sur les problèmes d'éthiques et de déontologie.	been set up in the research organizations. There's now a network of integrity advisors... I have the impression that the subject is more focused on ethical and deontological issues.
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In support of participants who consider that integrity is not a central problem anymore, participants working in the field of mediation stressed that the public never spontaneously raises the subject of scientific integrity. What the public does talk about is the supposed "instrumentalization" or "manipulation" of science by private or ideological interests. Very often what is at stake is not the scientist himself or his integrity but the use that may be made of his findings.

For a second group of participants, scientific integrity remains a major issue, both from the point of view of the behaviour of researchers and the changes taking place in scientific publishing.

Quote - French original version	Quote - English translation
FG1_3 l'intégrité scientifique, c'est un sujet majeur ! c'est un sujet absolument majeur ! (...) Il y a beaucoup à dire sur les revues prédatrices, sur les comportements des chercheurs eux-mêmes (...) je pense que l'intégrité scientifique a rapport avec l'honnêteté, le respect des citoyens (...) C'est un problème, il y'a un nombre de rétractions d'articles, pour conduite scientifique, qui a augmenté énormément (...) Il n'y a pas que les institutions qui peuvent agir... les scientifiques ont une responsabilité au sens où ils doivent rendre compte devant les citoyens de leurs propres comportements.	FG1_3 : scientific integrity is a major issue! it's an absolutely major issue! (...) There's a lot to be said about predatory journals and about the behaviour of researchers themselves (...) I think that scientific integrity has to do with honesty and respect for the public (...) It's a problem, and the number of retractions of articles for scientific misconduct has increased enormously (...) It's not just institutions that can take action... scientists have a responsibility in the sense that they have to be accountable to the public for their own behaviour.

Part of the discussion delved into the structural factors underlying integrity issues, which can be interpreted as sources of incentives or temptations by scientists. This includes the reliance on bibliometric indicators in evaluations, the pressure researchers feel to publish their work, the development of collaboration between public and private research. While social networks such as Twitter/X are often criticised for helping to spread false information, one participant stressed their positive role, which, by reporting misconduct, had helped to "advance the scientific process" and "cure some of the nosocomial diseases of the academic system".

Public participation in science

Several participants pointed out both the variety of participatory science formats and the relative slowness of France in this area compared to several countries, particularly in the North of Europe. In France, the situation differs between universities and research organisations. While universities are considered to be still 'ill-equipped' in terms of skills and staff, some research

organizations, particularly those focusing on environmental (INRAE) or public health (INSERM) issues, are more advanced. Experienced participants identified some obstacles within the scientific community: acceptance by scientists of the inclusion of a non-scientific point of view, the time needed to develop a complex survey system, the “goodwill” of funding agencies which generally want results within a limited timeframe, etc.

Quote - French original version	Quote - English translation
<p>FG1_3 On ne construit pas l'enquête sans que les citoyens concernés, ne participent au questionnaire. C'est pas facile, il faut que les scientifiques soient outillés pour ce dialogue avec les citoyens. Donc ça prend du temps. (...) On peut pas dire demain on sort les résultats. On se rend compte que les citoyens ont de très bonnes idées, il faut aussi du temps pour explorer ces sujets-là avec eux. C'est extrêmement riche (...) On évolue de plus en plus vers cette dimension de co-construction avec toute la complexité que ça représente, et notamment pour que les scientifiques s'approprient ces nouvelles manières de construire les études, et qui ce qui prend du temps... et c'est pas toujours évident de le faire comprendre aux financeurs, qui généralement veulent les résultats avant même que l'enquête soit commencée</p>	<p>FG1_3 : You can't carry out a survey without the citizens concerned taking part in the questionnaire. It's not easy, the scientists have to be equipped for this dialogue with the public. So it takes time (...) You can't say tomorrow we'll publish the results. We realise that citizens have some very good ideas, so it takes time to explore these issues with them. It's extremely rich (...) We're moving more and more towards this dimension of co-construction, with all the complexity that that represents, and in particular for scientists to appropriate these new ways of constructing studies, which takes time... and it's not always easy to make funders understand, as they generally want the results even before the survey has begun...</p>

Participants specialized in science mediation stressed the importance for the public of being able to have an open dialogue with the scientists. Various experiments were carried out, both in terms of size and environments, and the overall conclusion was that the quality of citizen participation depends closely on the scale of the participatory system adopted: beyond 7 or 8 people, citizen participation gives way to top-down scientific communication. It seems that paying attention to the size of the exchange group is an effective way of counteracting the effects of censorship or self-censorship that sometimes inhibit participants.

Quote - French original version	Quote - English translation
<p>FG1_5 On avait fait plein de protocoles rigolos... on les avait mis dans le noir et il y avait un échange absolument dingue... mais pour nous ce qui était important c'était de voir les modalités de l'échange. (...) Globalement dans une assemblée de 30 ou 40 personnes, ceux qui vont intervenir sont ceux qui veulent faire les marioles, ou ceux qui ont un avis, et pas le public lambda qui se sent exclu de la communication descendante... le chercheur va intervenir dans une forme non pas condescendante mais dans une forme où il est le sachant, où le public est en mode récepteur. Quand on est dans configuration plus petite, c'est beaucoup plus riche entre le public et le chercheur... je suis un défenseur de la massification,</p>	<p>FG1_5 : We'd done all kinds of funny protocols... we'd put them in the dark and there was an absolutely crazy exchange... but for us what was important was to see how the exchange worked. (...) Generally speaking, in an assembly of 30 or 40 people, those who are going to intervene are the ones who want to be the clowns, or those who have an opinion, and not the lambda public who feel excluded from top-down communication... the researcher is going to intervene in a way that is not condescending but in a way where he is the one who knows, and the public is in receiver mode. When you're in a smaller setting, there's a much richer relationship between the public and the researcher... I'm an advocate of</p>

mais là l'échelle micro permet l'inclusion du public...	massification, but in this case the micro scale allows the public to be included...
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Working on a small scale is described by participants as a way of developing the link between science and society, but also public trust in the scientific findings.

Quote - French original version	Quote - English translation
FG1_1 : j'ai été très surprise par les réactions des citoyens... tout coup il y avait une confiance... le fait de les impliquer, de les écouter, de revenir vers eux avec les résultats, cela a généré une confiance dans le protocole, mais aussi une confiance dans les résultats.	FG1_1 : I was very surprised by the reactions of the citizens... all of a sudden there was confidence... the fact of involving them, listening to them, coming back to them with the results, generated confidence in the protocol, but also confidence in the results.

What should be done?

Invited to develop proposals for positive action on public trust in science, the participants stressed in turn :

- developing scientific education and raising awareness of scientific research and critical thinking
- making good use of national service for the youngest part of the population with dedicated training modules
- developing a massive public communication strategy, with very substantial resources, on social networks, seeing them as an "informational war zone".
- moving institutions away from their minimalist communication on integrity and encourage them to display their values much more explicitly
- organising more small-scale events to create and cultivate the link between citizens and scientists
- encouraging research on research and on the various forms of trust in research, without assuming that it is necessary to systematically obtain the trust of the public

2.2 Focus group 2

The second focus group, moderated by Caroline Strube, had three main general features : all participants were research integrity officers or members of the same French network of integrity officers (RESINT), all participants came mostly from research organizations developing applied science, and finally a strong focus during the discussion on the diversity of factors related to scientific misconduct.

The participants were, in turn, 1) research integrity officer in a national research organization, 2) Integrity and Ethics Officer in a national research organization, 3) Integrity and Ethics Officer in a national research organization, 4) Integrity and Ethics Officer in a national research organization, 5) research integrity

officer in a university but also president of the french network of integrity officers, 6) research integrity officer in a national research organization

The composition of the group included 5 female and one male participants, in addition to the moderator (CS). Along with a strong imbalance in gender and a high level of specialization on research integrity, the discussions demonstrated a high level of commitment from all the participants.

All themes were fully discussed and explored, however, due to the professional experiences and interests of all participants, a great deal of time has been devoted to discussing the challenges of research integrity and scientific misconduct. They all spoke freely for almost two hours, with a few follow-up comments from the moderator when necessary.

Science and society

For the opening question, participants were asked to name the words that came spontaneously to their mind when thinking about the relationship between science and society.

The first words mentioned by FG2_2, FG2_4 and FG2_6 were "ignorance" and "disconnection" (« decalage »). The word refers to the alleged ignorance of the public with regard to the nature of the research process, but also that of politicians who ignore possible recommendations produced by the scientific community. The term "disconnection" is also used to describe the persistent discrepancy between what society expects from science and what science is able to provide to satisfy this social expectation. Politics is described as failing to act as a bridge between science and society.

Quote - French original version	Quote - English translation
FG2_2 : C'est embarrassant, car la société a envie de faire confiance à la science, mais comme elle est ignorante de ce qui fait la science, elle prend la science comme une croyance. Donc ce qui fait le statut différenciant de la science n'est pas perçu.	FG2_2 : It's embarrassing, because society wants to trust science, but since it is ignorant of what science is made of, it takes science as a belief. So what constitutes the differentiating status of science is not perceived.

FG2_1, FG2_3, FG2_4, and FG2_5 underscored the significance of enhancing "interactions" between the public and scientists, emphasizing terms like "dialogue," "pedagogy," and "mediation." The covid period was described as an opportunity for the general public to become more aware of the importance of public involvement by scientists.

Quote - French original version	Quote - English translation
FG2_3 : Il y a plus besoin que jamais que les chercheurs sortent de leur tour d'ivoire de technicité et se mettent au niveau du grand public pour qu'ils sachent d'où on parle, et sur quelle base fonctionne la	FG2_3 : Now more than ever, researchers need to get out of their ivory towers of technicality and get down to the level of the general public so that they know what we're talking about, and the basis on which

démarche scientifique, (...) Et ça c'est pas connu (...) on a bien vu pendant le Covid, que les attendus de la démarche scientifique n'était pas d'une connaissance générale. Il faut qu'on se relève un peu les manches parce que personne ne le fera mieux que nous. C'est quelque chose qu'on ne peut pas outsourcer, déléguer ça c'est une évidence.	the scientific process works (...) And that's not well known (...) we saw clearly during Covid that the expectations of the scientific process were not generally known. We need to roll up our sleeves a bit, because no one will do it better than us. It's something you can't outsource, you can't delegate, that's obvious.
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Finally FG2_3 mentioned the words “transparency” and “accountability”, emphasising that society gives to the scientific community a great deal of freedom, and that with this freedom comes a duty of “transparency” and “accountability”.

Trust in science

Rather than endorsing the notion of a widespread crisis of trust between science and society, participants offered various perspectives on problematizing the issue of trust in science. FG2_2 and FG2_6 initiated this discussion by highlighting the necessity for rigorous studies on the subject that surpass subjective impressions. Specifically, it's crucial to distinguish between trust in scientists themselves and trust in the outcomes of scientific research and their implications for social life.

FG2_5 stressed the need to understand the issue of trust in science from the point of view of the cultural or social characteristics of the population and, or the way in which people inform themselves about scientific and technological issues. Participants noted that science was often associated with complex knowledge that was not always easy to make accessible to the general public, particularly via the traditional media. The observation that scientists are not trained to communicate in the media was shared. Social networks were described as a possible source of information for the general public, but also as an area of unrestrained competition for knowledge. This competition may sometimes be associated with a form of generalised relativism when it comes to scientific knowledge.

Quote - French original version	Quote - English translation
FG2_5 : il y'a une concurrence des savoirs, qui a toujours existé, mais auparavant c'était plus entre la science et les religions (...) Maintenant elle est beaucoup diversifiée cette concurrence des savoirs, et les membres de la société peuvent avoir accès à des savoirs alternatifs, avec un phénomène de relativisation des savoirs où un peu « tout se vaut ». Avec des gens qui s'instituent « connaisseurs » sur des choses sur tel ou tel sujet, faisant un blog, des trucs sur youtube, et qui mélangent des connaissances scientifiques et d'autres choses... Il y a beaucoup de salmigondis dans la production publique autour de la science. Et c'est compliqué à gérer pour les scientifiques d'autant plus que les relais	FG2_5 : There has always been a competition of knowledge, but in the past it was more between science and religions (...) Now this competition for knowledge is much more diversified, and members of society can have access to alternative knowledge, with a phenomenon of relativisation of knowledge where 'everything is equal'. There are people who claim to be 'expert' on this or that subject, writing a blog or posting things on YouTube, and who mix scientific knowledge with other things... There's a lot of muddle in the public production of science. And that's complicated for scientists to manage, especially as the media aren't always there, and the political relays are lacking.

médiatiques ne sont pas toujours là, et les relais politiques sont défaillants.

FG2_5 pointed out that the public's supposed mistrust of the scientific community can sometimes be justified. In particular, she recalled the various health scandals in France in which scientists had been implicated. The growing power of the economic interests on which science depends is also cited by FG2_3 as a major factor in doubting the independence of researchers. The scientists are described as having sometimes contributed by their behaviour to fuelling the idea among the general public that "everyone is rotten" (« tous pourris »).

Quote - French original version	Quote - English translation
FG2_3 : (...)c'est vrai qu'il y'a eu des abus, il y'a eu des gens qui s'en sont mis plein les poches, qui n'ont pas révélé leurs conflits d'intérêt, c'est tout à fait vrai, mais c'est à nous de contrebalancer ça, de mettre les contre-feux, des outils, pour faire une recherche consciente des impacts qu'elle a sur la société, et qui se donne les moyens d'être plus intègre, plus équilibrée	FG2_3 : (...)It's true that there have been abuses, there have been people who have filled their pockets, who haven't revealed their conflicts of interest, that's absolutely true, but it's up to us to counterbalance that, to set up counter-fires, tools, to conduct research that is aware of the impact it has on society, and that provides itself with the means to be more honest, more balanced.

Crises are also important for FG2_1 : the covid crisis, like the climate crisis, may also have played a role in amplifying a form of social mistrust of science, in particular by highlighting the degree of uncertainty or doubt inherent to the scientific process.

Quote - French original version	Quote - English translation
FG2_1 : (...) le réchauffement climatique et la crise du covid (...) ça été un phénomène d'amplification pour le problème de la crise de confiance, car d'ordinaire les gens ne savent pas comment ça marche. Les gens ont toujours challengé les résultats de la science, parce qu'ils ne savent pas comment ça fonctionne (...) ils se sont aperçus que ce qui était affirmé par un scientifique à un moment donné pouvait être contredit dix mois après (...)	FG2_1 : (...) global warming and the covid crisis (...) have amplified the problem of the crisis of trust, because people don't usually know how it works. People have always challenged the results of science, because they don't know how it works (...) they have realised that what a scientist says at a given moment can be contradicted ten months later (...)

Finally, FG2_4 noted that sometimes scientists also lose confidence in society or politicians because they feel that they are not sufficiently heard. This can sometimes lead them to radicalise their views or practices.

Social acceptance of technological innovation

Discussions between participants focused on technological innovations and how they are perceived by the general public. FG2_2 observed that research establishments have come a long way on this subject and have stopped playing the "sorcerer's apprentice": in most research organizations there is an internal strategic reflection that takes into account the costs, benefits, ethical and

regulatory dimensions. FG2_6 tempered this observation by noting that most of the technological innovations now reaching the general public come not from public research organisations but from private companies. And so the responsible frameworks and social dissemination strategies used by public organisations are hardly relevant to private companies, which are driven primarily by commercial considerations. FG_2-3 observed that the reception of technological innovations often depended on marketing and communication effects.

Quote - French original version	Quote - English translation
FG2_3 : (...)ce qui m'a toujours laissée songeuse, c'est la différence de perception dans l'oeil du public de choses qui sont très voisines... Le téléthon, ça sauve des enfants, c'est bien dans l'oeil du public... vs les ogm animaux et végétaux dans votre assiette et nouvelles techniques de génome editing, c'est mal. C'est fascinant parce que du point de vue technique pure, de la biologie moléculaire, c'est la même chose. C'est extraordinaire la différence marketing entre les deux...	FG2_3 : (...)What has always left me wondering is the difference in public perception of things that are very similar... The telethon, which saves children, is good in the public eye... versus animal and plant GMOs in your plate and new genome editing techniques, which are bad. It's fascinating because from the purely technical point of view of molecular biology, it's the same thing. The marketing difference between the two is extraordinary...

Factors behind the scientific misconducts

When asked to describe the very notion of scientific integrity, participants used the words "reflexivity", "transparency", "resisting (external pressures)", "doubting", "acting collectively", "humility", "avoiding (conflicts of interest, bias)", etc.

The participants agreed on the importance of disciplinary variations in defining scientific integrity as the normative status of practices that could potentially deviate from integrity.

Quote - French original version	Quote - English translation
FG2_5 : (...)ce qui m'a frappé, c'est la grande variation ou variabilité selon les disciplines de la conception de l'intégrité scientifique. Même s'il y a des points communs, il y a des pratiques qui dans une discipline sont considérées comme normales, et dans une autre discipline peuvent être considérées comme un manquement à l'intégrité. Je pense par exemple à l'autorité, pour les articles, c'est très clair.	FG2_5 : (...)What struck me was the great variation or variability between disciplines in the conception of scientific integrity. Even if there are points in common, there are practices that in one discipline are considered normal, and in another discipline may be considered a breach of integrity. I'm thinking, for example, of authorship of articles, which is very clear.

Drawing on their detailed knowledge of the cases they have dealt with in their role as integrity officers, they explored the various factors that are regularly associated with scientific misconduct. They stressed that misconducts are frequently linked to situations of tension between contradictory principles, dilemmas associated with the conduct of ordinary research. They also point out that it is often difficult to know the exact extent of misconduct, not least because scientists may have reasons for not reporting what

they see. For example, for a doctoral student to report the misconduct of his thesis supervisor is inevitably to undermine his own position.

- 1) The first factor mentioned during the discussion relates to the tension between the timeframe of research and the timeframe of funding (FG_2_6). Scientists are very often subject to pressure or injunctions to complete their research "on time"; they have to deliver results "on time" in line with the duration of a contract, which is generally limited to 3 - 5 years max. And this pressure to finish on time can sometimes compromise the quality of the research.
- 2) A second recurrent factor mentioned in the discussion is the predominant place given by the organisation of science, as well as research and higher education policies, to competition and rivalry.

Quote - French original version	Quote - English translation
FG2_5 : (...)c'est lié à des choix politiques et des modes d'organisation de la science. Et c'est pour gagner dans la compétition que les collègues sont amenés à mordre le trait. D'autant plus quand ils ne sont pas régulés dans le cadre d'un collectif qui peut être un garde-fou par rapport à ces logiques et, comment dire... [il faut] rassurer les plus jeunes mais pas qu'eux, sur le fait qu'on peut produire de la science valable, sans être forcément toujours dans la "course des petits chevaux". Cela rejoint le fait de prendre son temps	FG2_5 : (...)it's linked to political choices and ways of organising science. And it is to win in the competition that colleagues are driven to bite the line. All the more so when they are not regulated within the framework of a collective that can act as a safeguard against these logics and, how can I put it... [we need to] reassure young people, and not just them, that we can produce valid science without necessarily always being in the 'small horse race'. This goes back to the idea of taking one's time, which is very clear.

The scientific competition is described as having a negative impact on publication and evaluation practices, particularly through the search for high-volume or high-profile publications that promise more than they can deliver. The unbridled competition between researchers is described as fuelling a 'sentationalist' logic that makes it almost impossible to publish negative results. Young PhDs are considered to be particularly exposed: to be recruited, they usually need a strong publication that makes a difference, at the risk of being prepared to do anything to get the publication accepted (FG2_1).

- 3) A third factor mentioned by the participants relates to research training, the ability of scientists to acquire and pass on "good methods" and "good practice". Training methods should be revised to ensure that colleagues start their careers on the right footing. But training should not just be aimed at young colleagues. Participants pointed out that researchers who are well advanced in their careers are sometimes not even aware that they are in a situation of

misconduct. They were described as too often not asking themselves enough questions about their own behaviour.

- 4) Fourth factor, the participants emphasised the importance of the immediate work environment and the difficulty for some of breaking out of a situation of professional isolation while struggling with a heavy mental burden.

Quote - French original version	Quote - English translation
<p>FG2_3 : (...)Les fraudeurs, il y a un portrait-robot qui émerge de quelqu'un avec un gros ego, et une pression de la performance, qui passe par-dessus tout le monde... okay très bien. Mais tous et toutes les autres, c'est des histoires très différentes, mais au cœur de tout ça, y'a un jour quelqu'un qui a une énorme charge mentale sur les épaules, qui est plus ou moins en isolement, qui est plus ou moins bien formé, et qui d'un coup, dans un moment de fatigue peut être, se demande « tiens si je me facilitais la vie ». Et qui commence à prendre des raccourcis, à glisser de plus en plus loin de ce que l'on appelle l'intégrité scientifique.</p> <p>FG2_5 : (...)il peut y avoir des rares profils psychologiques déviants, mais la plupart ce sont des gens qui sont coincés aussi, dans des conditions de travail, dans des relations professionnelles qui les amènent à un moment donné à mordre le trait...</p>	<p>FG2_3 : (...)The fraudsters, there's a portrait that emerges of someone with a big ego, and pressure to perform, who goes over everyone's head... okay fine. But all the others have very different stories, but at the heart of it all, there's one day someone who has an enormous mental burden on their shoulders, who is more or less isolated, who is more or less well trained, and who suddenly, in a moment of tiredness perhaps, wonders "well, if I made life easier for myself". And they start to take shortcuts, to slide further and further away from what we call scientific integrity.</p> <p>FG2_5 : There may be some rare deviant psychological profiles, but most people are trapped in working conditions and professional relationships that lead them to bite the line at some point...</p>

- 5) Another significant factor discussed is technology itself. FG2_6 stressed the influence of generative artificial intelligence, which is already shaping new forms of scientific misconducts. Tools like ChatGPT may discourage researchers from thoroughly examining articles or generating their own comprehensive reports on a specific topic.

- 6) The last general factor discussed relates to the culture of secrecy of French scientific institutions, i.e. their historical tendency not to favour transparency and openness in dealing with misconduct. Non-transparent integrity management is describe as problematic in terms of fostering the development of a shared culture of integrity.

Quote - French original version	Quote - English translation
<p>FG2_3 : (...)j'ai l'impression qu'on n'a pas totalement en France franchi le pas de se dire « il y a un moment il vaut mieux révéler et traiter les problèmes frontalement, en transparence, plutôt que de les balayer sous le tapis ». On n'a pas encore, en tout cas pas partout et sur tous les sujets franchi ce pas... il y a encore vachement la tentation de se dire « n'en parlons pas », comme les secrets de famille finalement... n'en parlons pas et ça cessera d'exister.</p>	<p>FG2_3 : I have the impression that in France we haven't completely taken the step of saying "there comes a time when it's better to reveal and deal with problems head-on, in a transparent way, rather than sweep them under the carpet". We haven't yet taken that step, at least not everywhere and on all issues... there's still a real temptation to say "let's not talk about it", like family secrets in the end... let's not talk about it and it will cease to exist.</p>

A critical view of public participation

Public participation is a subject that divided the participants. FG2_6 and FG2_1 questioned the composition of the audiences, their degree of representativeness, their objective and their real capacity to understand the issues at stake in the research in which they were participating. FG2_2 stresses the highly variable degree of progress made in France regarding citizen participation, depending on the research organisations concerned, but emphasises its scientific and social productivity when carried out under the right conditions :

Quote - French original version	Quote - English translation
<p>FG2_2 : (...)en santé il y'a de très belles expériences de recherche participative, incluant dans les projets de recherche des associations de patients, avec bien sûr des gens qui détiennent le savoir scientifique (...) la robustesse était garantie par la présence des gens qui ont la maîtrise de la démarche scientifique, mais la pertinence... la pertinence des résultats obtenus et leur caractère de transférabilité, d'innovation, d'opérationabilité, etc, avaient été significativement enrichis par la présence d'un autre regard, d'utilisateur potentiel, de gens qui étaient vraiment concernés d'une autre manière par ça. Il ne faut pas jeter le bébé avec l'eau du bain, il faut être prudent, c'est pas facile, on y va à petits pas, mais c'est extrêmement intéressant, y compris car c'est un autre moyen de tisser le lien entre science et société.</p>	<p>FG2_2 : in biomedical science, there have been some very fine experiments in participatory research, including patient associations in research projects, with of course people who possess the scientific knowledge (...) the robustness was guaranteed by the presence of people who have mastered the scientific approach, but the relevance... the relevance of the results obtained and their transferability, innovativeness, operability, etc, were significantly enriched by the presence of another perspective, of potential users, of people who were really concerned in another way by this. It's not easy, we're taking it slowly, but it's extremely interesting, not least because it's another way of forging the link between science and society.</p>

The participants emphasised the risk of public participation being used as a superficial device. All too often, citizens are involved in the downstream phase of research without being involved in the design of the research. They do not have access to the initial discussions that help to shape the participatory research process or the type of questions asked.

What should be done?

Invited to develop proposals for positive action on public trust in science, the participants stressed in turn :

- renewing science teaching at school and increasing the number of cultural events involving the scientific community (FG2_6)
- moving away from a culture of secrecy by encouraging scientific institutions to speak out publicly about their values and how they deal with situations of scientific misconduct or fraud (FG2_2)

- handling cases of misconduct correctly and ensure that there are no significant discrepancies in treatment between different research organisations. Any disparity between research organisations can only weaken respect for scientific integrity (FG2_5)
- reinforcing existing training courses, involving all researchers and not just the younger generation of scientists; once the population has been trained, include scientific integrity in the evaluation criteria for career progression (FG2_2). Training must also take into account the management of research staff, as integrity problems are frequently associated with poor management of research staff(FG2_3)
- changing the evaluation culture in science by giving priority to collective success over individual success (FG2_3 ; FG2_4 ; FG2_5)
- encouraging scientific institutions to address the tensions, conflicting orientations, and moral quandaries they inadvertently or intentionally contribute to generate. (FG2_2)

FG2_2 : (...)ça c'est le job de l'institution, « tricoter » à tous les endroits de l'institution pour limiter les tensions. Que ce soit sur les processus d'évaluation, que ce soit sur les processus de reconnaissance, sur les accompagnements RH de collectifs... moi c'est la mission que je me suis assigné (...) traquer avec toutes les directions de l'institution tous les endroits où leurs processus pouvaient mettre en tension avec l'intégrité scientifique, l'éthique et la déontologie. Et ça c'est vraiment le job de l'institution. Alors le monde extérieur est ce qu'il est, on n'a pas forcément de prise dessus (...) par contre ce qui est dans nos mains, je veux dire celles de nos institutions, c'est de construire un environnement au sein de l'institution qui soit le plus favorable, le plus propice, et donc le moins en injonctions paradoxales pour ce qui concerne les valeurs.

FG2_2 : (...) That's the institution's job, to work in all areas of the institution to limit tensions. Whether it's evaluation processes, recognition processes, HR support for groups... that's the job I've given myself (...) to work with all the departments in the institution to track down all the places where their processes could come into conflict with scientific integrity, ethics and professional conduct. And that's really the job of the institution. So the outside world is what it is, we don't necessarily have any control over it (...) but what we do have control over, and by that I mean our institutions, is to build an environment within the institution that is as favourable as possible, as conducive as possible, and therefore as free from paradoxical injunctions as far as values are concerned.

2.3 Focus group 3

The third focus group, moderated by Olivier Le Gall, had three main general features : a wide variety of profiles and professional experiences, a limited number of participants (4) due to the late impossibility of two participants to join the group, a moderator taking an active part in the discussion and playing the role of a participant.

The participants were, in turn, 1) science journalist in a major French newspaper, 2) ethics and research integrity officer in a major research funding organization, 3) a chief editor of a journal

in the field of anesthesiology and director of an office of research integrity in research performing organization, 4) member of European association for citizen science and expert of public participation

The composition of the group included three male and one female participants, in addition to the moderator (OLG). Along with a imbalance in gender and a high level of variety in terms of professional areas, the discussions demonstrated a high level of commitment from all the participants. One of the participants apologised in advance for his difficulty to speak in French. Indeed, his participation was partly limited by his limited fluency in French.

All themes were fully discussed and explored. All participants spoke freely for almost two hours. One of the participants had to leave the group before the end of the session, due to a professional obligation.

Science and society

Just like for the two previous focus groups, participants were at first asked to name the words that came spontaneously to their mind when thinking about the relationship between science and society.

FG3_1 and FG3_2 spontaneously referred to the words "trust" and "distrust" wondering whether the links of trust and mistrust between science and society were unilateral or reciprocal. FG3_4 used the terms "advancement" or "progress". FG3_3 preferred the words "misunderstanding" or "ignorance" using the covid crisis as an illustration.

<p>FG3_3 : (...) on l'a bien vu pendant la crise Covid, puisqu'on a mis en balance des pseudo experts avec des savants d'envergure internationale, qui avait des données qui étaient non contestables. On a comparé des opinions d'individus sur tweeter avec des études randomisée en double aveugle, incluant 25 000 patients. On a mis en question les vaccins sur des arguments qui étaient non scientifiques. On a l'impression qu'il manque un savoir sur l'approche scientifique. Il manque, il manque vraiment une connaissance et les scientifiques, du coup, comme diraient les jeunes, ont beaucoup de mal à se défendre : parce qu'on est totalement désarmé vis à vis de quelqu'un qui vous assène un argument d'autorité</p>	<p>FG3_3 : (...) We have seen this clearly during the Covid crisis, when pseudo-experts were weighed against internationally renowned scientists, who had data that could not be challenged. We compared the opinions of individuals on Twitter with randomized, double-blind studies involving 25,000 patients. Vaccines were challenged on unscientific grounds. There seems to be a lack of knowledge about the scientific approach. There's a real lack of knowledge, and as a result, as young people would say, scientists have a lot of trouble defending themselves: because you're totally helpless when someone makes an authoritative argument against you.</p>
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Regarding ignorance, FG3_1 observed that scientists sometimes exhibit ignorance towards citizens or society at large. Scientists were described as "not grasping that citizens may not comprehend," despite their own relative ignorance regarding the complex functioning of society. FG3_4 considered that the distance between science and society is also due to the complexity of scientific

language and the lack of training of scientists to communicate with the public.

Lessons from the Covid crisis

The exchange between participants continued around the lessons to be learned from the Covid period. Opinions turn out to be divided between the participants. For FG3_3, the period has seen a rise in conspiracism, with a highly critical public discourse on the role of Big Pharma, blamed for all evils. OLG considers that this public discourses is not very different from the one he personally experienced at the time of the GMO crisis in France, when he was at INRAE: he was called a "militant" and "corrupt" by the big companies in the sector.

FG3_2 felt that public criticism was sometimes justified: during the covid crisis some experts didn't behave as they should have. Scientists didn't always do everything necessary to be heard or properly understood by the general public. The journalistic processing of information is also important: citizens usually read something in the newspaper and then, depending on what they want to see, what they like, their interests and also their motivations... they'll believe one thing more than the other, but they don't know which is truer, which is statistically stronger (FG3_4). Finally, despite all these limitations, according to FG3_1, this crisis period may also have had a pedagogical role: it helped bring science into everyday conversation.

FG3_1 : (...)Moi j'ai toujours en tête le vieux rêve de Jean Marc Lévy Leblond qui disait que voilà... que les relations entre science et société changeront lorsque au café du commerce, on causera des résultats de foot et du dernier vaccin ARN. Eh bien ça a eu lieu. Je sais pas à si c'est si c'est bien ou pas, mais je retiens quand même que cette période était aussi unique pour ça.

FG3_1 : (...)I'm still thinking about Jean Marc Lévy Leblond's old dream, when he said that... the relationship between science and society would change when the latest soccer results and RNA vaccine were discussed at the café du commerce. Well, it happened. I don't know whether it's a good thing or not, but I can't help remembering that this period was also unique in that respect.

Research integrity and scientific misconducts

When asked to define scientific integrity, participants used the following terms: "responsible", "reflexivity", being able to "anticipate" consequences (FG3_2), "transparency and honesty", "respect", "trusting colleagues" (FG3_3), an attribute that should be "given", a characteristic that is supposed to be naturally present among all scientists (FG3-1).

The conversation progressed to address the guidelines and codes provided to the French scientists. FG3_2 expressed the view that these documents do not effectively clarify the concept of scientific integrity or differentiate it from ethics. She found them somewhat perplexing, prompting her to seek additional coursework at university for clarification. FG3_3 observed that

although codes have multiplied in recent years, nobody really knows them. At the head of his scientific organization, no one had taken the time to look at them.

While France has recently adopted the principle of a doctoral oath, participants questioned the effectiveness of this oath in developing a culture of scientific integrity. FG3_1 saw the doctoral oath as a way of stating discussion on integrity at the university, but also as a way of protecting doctoral students from illegitimate demands coming from their supervisors. One participant drew a comparison between the doctoral oath and the hypocritical oath.

<p>FG3_3 : (...)le serment d'hippocrate est très simple (...) Ils ont la toge et ils ont la main sur la tête d'Hippocrate. Formidable! Et puis ils disent qu'ils tairont ce qu'ils voient dans les intérieures, ils ne se taisent pas du tout... qu'ils ne feront pas payer, mais il y en a plein qui sont cupides et qui deviennent... il faut voir les dérives du secteur privé à l'hôpital... Enfin, le serment d'Hippocrate, il n'est pas suivi, mais alors c'est très beau et c'est très bien. C'est indispensable, il faut pas le supprimer, mais il ne faut pas être naïf. Et le serment doctoral, ce sera la même chose. C'est une étape, c'est mieux, c'est mieux qu'il y ait ça, mais il ne faut pas en attendre trop non plus...</p>	<p>FG3_3 : the hippocratic oath is very simple (...) They have the robe and they have their hand on the head of Hippocrates. How wonderful! And then they say they'll keep quiet about what they see inside the hospital... they don't keep quiet at all... they say they won't charge, but there are plenty who are greedy and become... you have to see the excesses of the private sector in the hospital... Finally, the Hippocratic oath is not followed, but then it's very beautiful and it's very good. It's essential, we mustn't eliminate it, but we mustn't be naive. And the doctoral oath will be the same thing. It's a step, it's better, it's better that it's there, but we shouldn't expect too much either...</p>
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Participants also questioned the ability of institutions to act once a misconduct has been identified. They agreed that while public debate in France revolves around the Didier Raoult case in Marseille, this should not mask a more general problem, which is described as a form of institutional "cowardice" (FG3_3). FG3_1 emphasized the institutional tension between the desire, on the one hand, to correct scientific literature and the desire, on the other, to protect the staff. This tension can generate a form of immobility that is harmful to scientific integrity.

<p>FG3_2 : (...)effectivement, les établissements et les institutions ont du mal à prendre leur part de responsabilité... et souvent les chercheurs ou les chercheuses se retournent vers nous en disant : « S'il vous plait, aidez-nous, sortez nous de ces difficultés » (...)parce que justement il y a un constat de manquements de la part de collègues. Et je dois dire aussi, qu'il y a beaucoup de juniors, de doctorants, un doctorants qui nous contactent parce qu'ils sont en difficulté, parce qu'ils constatent que des chercheurs seniors ont des pratiques qui ne sont pas tout à fait intègres. Et c'est vrai qu'en étant dans le réseau des référents intégrité je constate aussi c'est un peu tabou que de dire ça... Il faut aussi faire tout un travail de sensibilisation, de</p>	<p>FG3_2 : indeed, research organizations and institutions find it hard to take their share of responsibility... and researchers often turn to us and say: "Please, help us, get us out of these difficulties" (...) precisely because there is an observation of shortcomings on the part of colleagues. And I have to say, too, that there are a lot of juniors, doctoral students and PhD students who contact us because they're in difficulty, because they see that senior researchers are engaging in practices that are not entirely honest. And it's true that, being part of the network of integrity referents, I've also noticed that it's a bit taboo to say this... We also need to do a lot of awareness-raising and training work with senior researchers.</p>
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<p>formation auprès des seniors, des chercheurs seniors</p> <p>OLG : (...)on aura sans doute beaucoup progressé quand les institutions s'honoreront d'avoir suivi les affaires de manquements à l'intégrité et d'avoir amélioré leur science de cette façon. Pour le moment, elles en ont honte et donc, comme elles en ont honte, elles essaient de le cacher.</p>	<p>OLG : (...)we will undoubtedly have made a lot of progress when the institutions will take pride in having followed the cases of integrity breaches and improved their science in this way. For the moment, they're ashamed of it, and so, because they're ashamed of it, they try to hide it.</p>
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During their discussions, participants highlighted several others factors that may contribute to generate misconducts:

- the search for recognition from peers,
- the principle of confraternity which prevents people from reporting problematic situations,
- the growing use of calls for proposals to fund research, which encourages researchers to develop an economy based on promises that are sometimes unrealistic,
- the lack of transparency in the institutional handling of scientific misconduct,
- the pressure to publish,
- the necessity to be visible in high-impact journals,
- and the pressure from department or laboratory leadership.

They also acknowledged some progress in the institutional bodies responsible for evaluation, particularly the french National University Council (CNU), which has formally disavowed conducting evaluations solely based on bibliometric criteria (FG3_3).

Finally FG3_1 emphasised the difficulty journalists have in dealing with breaches of scientific integrity without fuelling an anti-science discourse.

<p>FG3_1 : (...)Mon état psychologique, ne vous ne vous intéressera pas trop, mais je vous assure que c'est pas facile pour nous d'aborder ces questions d'intégrité parce que on pourrait chaque semaine raconter une histoire, parce que dans le monde entier, il y a des chercheurs qui font vraiment du mauvais travail et donc on pourrait raconter ça toutes les semaines ou tous les mois (...) on s'interroge sur quelle affaire nous va nous intéresser. Et on essaye de parler de celles qui auront un intérêt pour le public, c'est à dire celles qui mettent en évidence un dysfonctionnement de réglementation en vigueur par exemple, ou celles qui mettent en évidence une triste nouvelle tendance dans la recherche. Parce que ça, c'est quelque chose qui a une grande portée, ou évidemment aussi si c'est une vedette ou un ou un responsable managérial de la recherche. Mais parce que j'entends certains commentaires qui disent qu'on fait du mal à la science en exposant ses mauvais côtés et ses travers.</p>	<p>FG3_1 : (...) You won't be too interested in my psychological state, but I can assure you that it's not easy for us to tackle these issues of integrity, because every week we could tell a story, because all over the world there are researchers who are doing a really bad job, and so we could tell that story every week or every month (...) we ask ourselves which cases will interest us. And we try to talk about the ones that will be of interest to the public, i.e. those that highlight a malfunction in the regulations in force, for example, or those that highlight a sad new trend in research. Because that's something that's very far-reaching, or obviously also if it's a star or a research manager. But because I've heard some comments saying that we're hurting science by exposing its bad sides and its shortcomings.</p>
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Public participation

Asked to comment on the value of developing citizen participation in science, participants noted that scientists need to be properly trained, so that they can be as precise about their objectives as they are about how to achieve them. Citizen participation is described as an effective way of familiarizing the general public with the general principles of the scientific approach (FG3_4).

In the field of biomedical science, the presence of citizens or citizens' representatives is described as a useful but still largely undeveloped step forward.

FG3_3 : (...)on a on a un représentant des usagers qui est d'ailleurs très actif, très présent. Et moi je suis ravi parce que c'est quelqu'un qui lit tout ce qu'on écrit et qui fait des remarques auxquelles on n'avait pas pensé et qui prend beaucoup de plaisir à ça. Et je me dis que dans les commissions recherche des universités, les commissions recherche des hôpitaux, les commissions recherche des grandes institutions, il pourrait y avoir des usagers... et pour l'instant il n'y en a pas. Mais c'est vrai que ça serait très utile parce que d'abord il permettrait de réorienter éventuellement les politiques de recherche en disant mais « attendez là, vous travaillez là dessus, mais ça n'a plus aucun intérêt »... Ou alors « vous vous engeulez entre vous sur des sujets qui n'auront aucun débouché pour nous »... Je pense que, c'est même indispensable. Mais on n'est même pas au début, hein...

FG3_3 : (...)we have a very active, very present patient representative. And I'm delighted because he's someone who reads everything we write, who makes comments we hadn't thought of, and who takes great pleasure in doing so. And I say to myself that in university research commissions, hospital research commissions, the research commissions of major institutions, there could be users... and for the moment there aren't any. But it's true that it would be very useful, because it would make it possible to redirect research policies by saying "wait a minute, you're working on this, but it's no longer of any interest"... Or "you're arguing amongst yourselves about subjects that will have no outlet for us"... I think it's essential. But we're not even at the beginning, are we?

What should be done?

Invited to develop proposals for positive action on public trust in science, the participants stressed in turn :

- profoundly changing the institutional culture for dealing with breaches of scientific integrity to encourage transparency and the display of positive values (OLG)
- reinforcing the training in scientific integrity for all members of the scientific community (FG3_3)
- Increasing media coverage of the institutional handling of scientific misconduct (FG3_1)
- pursuing the transformation of research evaluation methods by emphasising qualitative rather than quantitative aspects (FG3_2)
- providing journalists with more in-depth training to improve their coverage of scientific and technological subjects (FG3_4)
- encouraging the scientific community to be more open to society, particularly with regard to environmental issues (FG3_1)

3 Building trust in science : from perception to institutional engagement

After describing precisely the content of the three French focus groups in the previous section, this final section provides an overall analysis based on the project's main research questions:

1. How do institutional stakeholders perceive, globally and locally, the level of public trust in science and technology?
2. How do institutional stakeholders perceive the culture of research integrity?
3. How do institutional stakeholders perceive public participation?
4. What kind of institutional governance arrangements and policy environments should be considered as key priorities?

3.1 Public trust in science

Two recent surveys (Dubois, Guaspere, 2022 ; Dubois, Guaspere, 2024) conducted in two French research performing organizations (CNRS, INSERM), have underscored scientists' perception of a crisis of trust between science and society. Between 7 and 9 out of 10 scientists respondents to the surveys consider that the relationship between science and society is currently in a problematic state.

The discussions in the focus groups do not challenge this overarching observation; rather, they contribute to its refinement. French society exhibits a high degree of heterogeneity in its relationship with science and technology, as well as with scientific culture more broadly. It was noted that more research into attitudes towards science would be useful in order to better understand the issue of trust in science from the point of view of the cultural or social characteristics of the population, or the way in which people inform themselves about scientific and technological issues.

Some participants emphasized the necessity of rebuilding the trust between science and society by reforming the way science is taught in school. Promoting scientific literacy as early as possible in school and offering a deeper comprehension of the scientific process, was described as a possible way to narrow the growing gap between science and society.

Other participants questioned the way in which recent transformations in science could fuel a critical discourse in the general public. The covid period was the occasion for a highly critical discourse on the supposed lack of independence of

scientists from private interests. Some participants emphasized that French scientists had not always been exemplary in the past, potentially contributing to a degree of mistrust.

Participants were divided regarding the impact of the COVID-19 crisis: while some viewed it as a valuable educational opportunity to enhance scientific literacy, others believed that the crisis had made the inherent uncertainty of the scientific process more apparent, consequently undermining the credibility of science in the eyes of the general public.

3.2 Research integrity and scientific misconducts

When asked to define the concept of scientific integrity, most of the participants stressed the difficulty of grasping its precise meaning from the various institutional codes or guidelines available in France. One integrity officer even took the decision to go back to university before taking up her duties in order to gain a clearer understanding of the distinction between integrity and ethics.

There was no general consensus among participants on how to describe the state of scientific integrity in France. In an understandable way, those who have been involved in the various reforms carried out in France over the last 20 years considered that the bulk of the reforms have been carried out and that we should now wait for them to bear fruit. Recent reforms include the inclusion of integrity in the research code and the doctoral oath.

Others argued that while these reforms are beneficial, they fell short of addressing the remaining challenges of scientific integrity. Notably, significant emphasis was placed on the institutional culture surrounding the management of scientific misconduct. France was described as lagging behind other countries due to its "shameful" and "opaque" approach to addressing misconduct. Participants advocated for a shift in institutional culture, viewing the handling of misconduct as an opportunity to uphold the positive values of scientific integrity.

Throughout their discussions, participants underscored the various factors linked to what they perceived as a potentially significant volume of scientific misconduct. Once the importance of scientists' egos acknowledged, participants focused on the cultural, organizational, structural or material dimensions associated with science. These factors are already well identified in the available scientific literature on scientific misconduct : the quest for visibility and recognition at all costs, the constraints of contractual research, the culture of competition, the emphasis on individual success, the lack of training, scientists transformed

into managers without the necessary skills, the institutional culture of secrecy, etc.

The discussion also shed an interesting light on how research organizations were confronting scientists with conflicting imperatives: on one hand, they were encouraged to be virtuous and cautious in their approach, while simultaneously being pressured to secure highly competitive funding and gain visibility in journals that occasionally favored a sensationalist approach. Some participants acting as integrity officers claimed that it was central to their work to develop organizational analyses aimed at identifying these conflicting imperatives. They emphasized the importance of conveying to organizational management the necessity of minimizing these contradictions as much as possible. From a sociological point of view, this observation could be an interesting starting point for renewing, on an organisational scale, the fairly old sociological tradition of analysing the forms of ambivalence or normative dissonance present in the scientific community.

3.3 Public participation in science

The participants agreed that France is lagging considerably behind other European countries when it comes to participatory science. Even if the situation is different between research organisations and universities, the few initiatives mentioned during the discussions were into two main areas: biomedical science and environmental sciences.

The factors that explain this relative slowness have been described as having to do in part with the complexity of participatory schemes: once the idea of public participation accepted, scientists have to be trained, funding agencies have to allow sufficient time to develop original research protocols. However, training courses are not often available and funding agencies have only very recently become involved in participatory science.

Some participants were quite critical of the very principle of “social inclusion”, judging it to be relatively demagogic and acting as if citizens were capable of understanding scientific issues without being trained. Others emphasized the risk of public participation being superficially implemented. Frequently, citizens are engaged only in the later stages of research without being involved in its initial design.

On the contrary, the few participants who had had the opportunity to conduct or supervise participatory research emphasised the benefits associated with this approach: the ability to create links between science and society and to add a form of social relevance to the robustness of the scientific results.

3.4 Institutional key priorities

The discussion groups identified a number of institutional key priorities, the main ones being:

- developing scientific education in school as early as possible
- developing a massive public communication strategy to promote science and critical thinking on social networks, seeing them as an "informational war zone".
- organising small-scale events to create and cultivate the link between citizens and scientists
- radically change the culture of research organisations when it comes to the handling of scientific misconduct: from secrecy to transparency
- changing the evaluation culture in science by giving priority to collective success over individual success, to quality over quantity
- training the entire scientific community in the values of scientific integrity, including senior researchers
- encouraging research on research and on the various forms of trust in research
- encouraging scientific institutions to address the tensions, conflicting imperatives they contribute to generate.

4. Conclusion

The COVID-19 period in France provided an occasion to scrutinize the interplay between science and society. Since 2020, the public controversy surrounding the work of the team led by Professor Didier Raoult in Marseille has heightened awareness of the crucial role of scientific integrity in fostering public trust in science. It has also underscored the significance of social networks as both a means of disseminating information but, regrettably, spreading misinformation.

In this post-COVID context, there is a particular interest in developing a qualitative research approach focusing on the perceptions of various institutional stakeholders involved in scientific and technological matters. Our three focus groups were made possible through the collaboration of three co-investigators: Antoine de Daruvar, Caroline Strube, and Olivier Le Gall. Through their experience and in-depth knowledge of the issues surrounding scientific integrity and the opening up of science to society, all

three played pivotal roles in organizing and facilitating these discussion groups.

As indicated by the rich content of the previous sections of this report and the numerous excerpts, the adoption of this participatory research approach, wherein institutional players collaborate with researchers, presents an opportunity to deepen our understanding of institutional mechanisms and avenues for transformation. This approach had already proved its worth as part of the French CovETHOS project, and given the quality of the exchanges gathered during the discussion, its extension to the European level with the POIESIS project appears to be a very positive step towards to develop efficient institutional recommendations as well as innovative research perspectives.

The collection and analysis of qualitative data pave the way for two avenues of exploration: firstly, a comparative examination at the European level of the outcomes derived from the discussion groups; and secondly, the potential utilization of the qualitative material to uncover new areas of sociological investigation within research institutions and organizations.

National Report: Focus Groups - *Germany*

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1 Introduction

The three German focus groups on the role of institutions in the POIESIS 3i4t model have been conducted between the 6th and 14th of February 2024 with the help of four Project Co-Investigators (PCIs). Institutional actors with different professional backgrounds discussed questions on trust in science, research integrity and the integration¹ of citizens in the research process. Most importantly, they formulated recommendations how to strengthen the role of institutions and improve conditions for research integrity, integration and ultimately also trust in science - not only in the public but also among researchers themselves.

1.1 Set up of the focus groups

As a first step for the organisation of the focus groups, even before recruiting the PCIs, Wissenschaft im Dialog (WiD) defined the desired **target groups for the three focus groups** in a brainstorming session. It was decided to organise one group with university communicators (social integration), one with research integrity officers from universities and other research institutions (research integrity), and the third one with research funders (social integration & research integrity)². With this variety of profiles, WiD aimed for a maximum of institutional perspectives on the questions to be discussed.

Further, it was decided to hold all focus groups as **2-hours online events**. This appeared to be an easier, more time-efficient and also more realistic solution than on-site meetings, for several reasons: first of all, to have a chance of gaining the best and most interesting perspectives of PCIs and focus group participants, it was clear that members from the same focus group would have to be recruited from all over Germany. Organising an on-site event with people having to travel from all over the country for a two-hours exchange would have led to many declines - as much from PCIs as potential focus group candidates. Additionally, in the last years, and especially since the coronavirus pandemic, short meetings like this one have been increasingly organised online as it is much more time efficient for all participants. It was to be expected (and confirmed) that this had no negative consequences for the dynamics of the discussion as all participants are largely used to and familiar with exchanging in an online room.

For the **recruitment of the PCIs**, the invitation material prepared by the WP3 team was translated and adapted (see Appendix 2) and an additional invitation letter was drafted. It was important for us to keep it short and clear and to provide a realistic overview over the timeline and the requested efforts implied in the role of the PCIs.

Two of the PCIs, the ones for the focus groups of university communicators and research funders, were recruited via the vast personal network WiD has built over the years in the science communication community. The third one was contacted after a desktop-research on institutional research integrity structures and relevant networks in this regard. All PCI-candidates were contacted individually and with personalised messages including the prepared material. Individual calls followed the written invitations in order to discuss open questions and the exact procedure of the focus groups. All PCIs accepted to be part of the project and to independently manage the recruitment of the participants of their focus groups.

After the initial contact, that had been established in the month of December 2023, all PCIs independently made a list of potential **participants for the focus groups**. They tried to achieve a good representation of participants from different kinds of institutions, with several years of experience in the field, and with an interest

¹ The term "integration" is used here under the definition of the POIESIS project: *Increased inclusion of citizens and societal stakeholders throughout the different phases of research and innovation cycles.*

² The participants of the focus groups work in different positions in their institutions. To facilitate speaking about the different focus groups, they are summarised under the terms 'university communicators', 'research funders' and 'research integrity officers'. This is by no means meant in a downgrading way.

in science communication in the larger sense. It was agreed that PCIs could independently contact the participants they had in mind and an adapted version of the PCI-invitation material was made at their disposal in this regard.

The PCIs started recruiting participants in January 2024 with overall very positive feedback from the contacted people. They kept in touch and informed the WiD team about the advancement of the recruiting. Several possible dates and times were offered to the participants for the realisation of the focus groups that had been agreed on between the WiD team and the individual PCIs before. After confirmation of the respective participants, PCIs provided a list of names and email addresses to the WiD team.

One week before each focus group, the participants received an email from the WiD team with a reminder of the time and date of the focus group, a link to a Zoom room in which the focus group would take place, an additional information sheet and the **informed consent form**, all of them were asked to read, sign, and send back before the date of the respective focus group. This worked very smoothly, all participants sent back their signed consent sheets in time. Participants did not have any further questions addressed to WiD beforehand: except for the mentioned email, there was no further contact between the participants and the WiD team before the events.

As none of the German PCIs was available at the date of the common **PCI-training** provided by WP3, individual 2-hour meetings were scheduled with each of the PCIs a few days before their respective focus groups. A member of the WiD team participated in the common PCI-training provided and also prepared the **moderator guide** for each focus group. To this aim, the original moderator guide was translated, discussed among colleagues, as especially the translation of the term "social integration" and some of the questions were quite challenging, and then slightly adapted to each of the focus groups. This individual modification concerned however only the questions Q3. and Q5. where we added the question "*What role does scientific integrity / social integration play in your professional daily life? How often do you deal with the concept/its application?*" for the groups, where the answer was not evident (e.g. for social integration in the case of research integrity officers).

During the **individual meetings with the PCIs**, the general objective of the focus groups and the role of the moderators were presented to the PCIs as none of them had ever moderated a focus group before. Then, the moderator guide was discussed in detail, going through all questions, explaining the objective of the questions, and checking whether there were any doubts or questions from the PCIs left.

It was agreed that the WiD member present during the focus group (Anne-Sophie Behm-Bahtat) would hold a short presentation of the POIESIS project in the beginning of the focus group and lead the exercise in the end, but rather be a 'silent spectator' in between, only intervening if necessary.

The **realisation of the three focus groups** was very similar: all of them took place online in a Zoom room provided by the WiD team. All were led and moderated by the PCIs with a short introduction on the POIESIS project held by the WiD member in the beginning. All focus groups were audio-recorded using the according Zoom function to do so. All participants had agreed to the recording in the informed consent form but were asked again whether this was okay before the recording was started. The PCIs and the WiD member communicated via the chat function of Zoom during the focus group, for example when the WiD member indicated to jump to the next question. Such interaction was however not necessary very often. At the end of the focus group, the WiD member provided a short overview regarding the next steps to happen in WP3, namely the national analysis, international comparison, and an open invitation to participate in the round table in autumn with the promise to provide further information on that as soon as possible.

All groups lasted for 2 entire hours, followed by a short debriefing only between the PCI and the WiD member, where the PCIs could share their impressions and thoughts after the focus group. These exchanges were very valuable and also important for the PCIs themselves.

One day after the focus group all participants received an email signed by the WiD team and the respective PCIs **thanking the participants** for their time and efforts.

The **feedback** in all three focus groups was very positive and enthusiastic regarding the topics discussed and the perspective to contribute to recommendations with regard to trust, integrity and integration. All participants also expressed great interest to participate in the roundtable in order to deepen the discussions and also to hear more about the international comparison. It was promised to circulate the results of the analysis as soon as they are available.

In the following, the PCIs and the composition of their focus groups are described in more detail:

Focus Group 1: University Communication

The PCI: Dr. Marita Müller is an experienced senior professional who has been head of the Department for Public Relations at the university BTU Cottbus-Senftenberg from 1996 to 2022 and, since then, is the coordinator of the "BTU Präsenzstellen", attendance centres which have the objective to make the university more accessible to prospective students, companies and society in the region.

She is very engaged in the field of science communication and is for example Member of the Steering Committee of EUPRIO (European Universities Public Relations and Information Officers) and Member of the Board of the Bundesverband Hochschulkommunikation ("Federal Association of University Communication"). The Bundesverband Hochschulkommunikation is the association for university communicators in Germany. It is committed to the profession's strategic development and to quality assurance in all areas of university communication. It plays a very important role in the sector of university communication.

The focus group: Marita Müller has a very strong network of spokespersons and other professionals working in the field of university communication. From this network, she recruited the initially eight participants of her focus group. One participant had to cancel her participation due to illness, so the focus group had seven participants in the end.

All of them are experienced senior professionals and have many years of experience as leading members of the communication departments in different universities. Participants came from universities from all over Germany and with very different sizes. One of the participants has recently changed to lead the communication department of a research centre outside university. It was however underlined that the participants should not see themselves as representatives of their institutions during the focus group but that the project would rather benefit from collecting their rich individual experiences in the field of university communication throughout their careers. The group consisted of four female and three male participants. One member had to leave the discussion after one hour for another appointment.

All members of the group (except the one who had to leave early) and also the PCI completed the exercise on different functions of activities realised by university communication departments. They were very quick in doing so and did not have any further questions.

Focus Group 2: Research Funding Organisations

The PCI: Dr. Pierre Schwidlinski is program director at the Volkswagen Foundation for media and communication studies, theology and religious studies. The Volkswagen Foundation is an important foundation in the field of science and technology in Germany and exists since 1961. As part of Team "Exploration", which promotes and encourages risk-taking and innovative research ideas, Pierre Schwidlinski is in charge of a funding program for unconventional and explorative research in the humanities and cultural sciences and is co-responsible for the topic of science communication.

He is further engaged in and member of the advisory board in the program "Development and Management of Research Projects (EMF)", an initiative of the University of Kassel and Marburg addressed to PhD students and post-Docs on their way to successful applications for external funding.

The focus group: The idea behind organising a focus group with people working in research funding organisations was to offer perspectives on trust, integrity and integration from inside institutions which do not conduct research themselves but have an important influence on how research is conducted - through their agenda setting, guidelines, processes for granting financing, and oversight. Pierre Schwidlinski has a great network across different kinds of research funding organisations and foundations and, in a very short amount of time, succeeded to recruit four participants from different institutions with varying sizes and profiles. The participants also came from very different positions within these institutions, making this focus group the most heterogeneous one in terms of the participants' profiles.

All of the participants are highly engaged in the field of science communication but nevertheless had very different, however complementary perspectives on it due to their respective backgrounds. The institutions represented in the focus group ranged from a rather small foundation, that develops own projects and programmes to encourage science communication in all facets but also finances scholarships for example, to a German Federal Ministry with numerous research funding programs. The group consisted of two female and two male members.

The participants of this group were not asked to complete the exercise on different functions of communication activities as it really did not fit the context of the debate and seemed to be completely out of scope for them. In agreement with the PCI, the ongoing deep discussion about potential ways to improve conditions for integrity and integration from an outside-university institutional perspective was prioritised here.

Focus Group 3: Good Scientific Practice

The PCIs: Tina Rotzal and Esther Reineke lead the Academic Integrity Competence Centre (AKIN) at the University Library of the Johannes Gutenberg University of Mainz. The Centre provides confidential advice with regard to Good Scientific Practice but also offers and organises numerous workshops and provides self-learning as well as teaching materials in this regard. Prevention strategies to avoid misconduct and a general strengthening of Good Scientific Practice at all levels in the university are the main objectives of AKIN.

Both are also part of the "Network for Good Scientific Practice" under the umbrella of the German University Association of Advanced Graduate Training (UniWiND/GUAT). The network brings together trainers of Good Scientific Practice all over Germany and Austria and ensures ongoing dialogue between them. Beyond the exchange of experiences on formats and methods, the network also aims to push common standards of Good Scientific Practice and the professionalisation of relevant actors in the field of research integrity further. Tina Rotzal and Esther Reineke decided to take over the role of PCI together and shared the task of recruiting participants but also the moderation during the focus group. This worked perfectly well and could even be seen as a further enrichment of the participatory method.

The focus group: From the lively UniWiND network, the PCIs recruited eight participants, of which one had to cancel last minute due to illness. Therefore, there were seven participants in the focus group. All of the participants have many years of experience in the field of research integrity and Good Scientific Practice, and they all work in different positions related to integrity, mainly at universities all over Germany. One participant is currently the coordinator for research integrity at a non-university research centre but has worked at universities for many years before.

The structures of ensuring research integrity and Good Scientific Practice at German universities are very diverse which is why it is difficult to directly compare the participants' individual positions. They are however all in one way or another responsible for pushing forward standards of Good Scientific Practice in their professional environment and they are all very engaged in this regard beyond their

actual positions. Several of the participants are trainers for Good Scientific Practice themselves and provide workshops to different target groups. The group consisted of five female and two male members. One member had to leave the discussion for 45 minutes in the second half of the debate for another appointment but joined the debate again in the end.

The participants and also PCIs of the focus group of research integrity officers all completed the exercise on different functions of activities realised by university communication departments. They were however much more puzzled and needed more time for it than the participants of focus group 1. They also had a more critical view on the exercise than the university communicators.

In view of the **analysis**, the audio-recordings of the three focus groups were first transcribed automatically using a software and then revised by a WiD team member. In a second step, the transcripts were coded in Atlas.ti using a codebook closely related to the chapters of this report (see Appendix 1). The main arguments of the participants were extracted from the numerous pages of coded material and supported with citations. Attention has been paid to the different ways in which participants from different groups discussed the single topics. The analysis does not follow the linear progress of the focus groups in chronological order. Instead, for all topics and especially regarding the recommendations, the contributions of participants throughout the entire debates in the focus groups have been taken into account. On the basis of this qualitative analysis, chapters 3 and 4 of this report have been authored.

1.2 Participants in the focus group

The following tables list the participants in each focus group and their age, seniority, position and the kind of institution they work in. In order to ensure anonymity, the information remains rather general. Senior professionals are considered professional who have been working for 10+ years in a science- and research-related context, which applies to all participants of the German focus groups.

Focus Group 1: University Communication

Participant Id.	Gender	Seniority	Position	Institution
FG1_1	Female	Senior professional	Head of Science Communication and Strategy	University
FG1_2	Female	Senior professional	Chief Communication Officer	University
FG1_3	Male	Senior professional	Head of University Communications	University
FG1_4	Male	Senior professional	Managing Director	University
FG1_5	Male	Senior professional	Spokesperson	University
FG1_6	Female	Senior professional	Head of Communications	Non-University Research Centre
FG1_7	Female	Senior professional	Head of Communications	University

Focus Group 2: Research Funding Organisations

Participant Id.	Gender	Seniority	Position	Institution
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FG2_1	Male	Senior professional	Head of Division	Foundation
FG2_2	Male	Senior professional	Secretary General	Research Funding Organisation
FG2_3	Female	Senior professional	Head of Division	Federal Ministry
FG2_4	Female	Senior professional	Program Director	Foundation

Focus Group 3: Good Scientific Practice

Participant Id.	Gender	Seniority	Position	Institution
FG3_1	Male	Senior professional	Managing Director	University
FG3_2	Female	Senior professional	Head of Ombudsoffice	University
FG3_3	Female	Senior professional	Coordinator Scientific Integrity	Non-University Research Centre
FG3_4	Female	Senior professional	Officer Early Career Researchers	University
FG3_5	Male	Senior professional	Head of Division	University
FG3_6	Female	Senior professional	Officer Department of Research and Knowledge Transfer	University
FG3_7	Female	Senior professional	Head of Ombudsoffice	University

2 Sequential description of the focus groups

2.1 Focus group 1: University Communication

All participants of the focus group knew each other very well already before the meeting, and this was noticeable in the very familiar and supportive atmosphere of the discussion. The participants went deep into the questions but mostly complemented rather than contradicted each other. They had more thoughts about social integration than about research integrity, with the latter not being perceived as a very problematic issue by them. The topic of social integration however led to controversial debates about whether the ongoing increase of integrating citizens in the scientific process was actually something positive, and also what 'participation' actually means and should look like. On top of that, the problematic and often unclear interrelation of science and politics (non-transparent policy advising, instrumentalisation of scientists by politics especially during and since the pandemic, independence of science, unclear roles) was a recurring and rather dominant topic during the two hour-debate as much in relation to research integrity as to trust in science more generally.

2.2 Focus group 2: Research Funding Organisations

The second focus group was much more heterogenous than the first and third one in terms of institutions and positions of the participants. The participants partly knew each other before but not as well as the participants of the other groups. There were only four participants in this focus group which allowed for very deep discussions and extensive speaking time for everybody.

In very general terms, the discussions in this group were often held on a meta-level and very centred around large questions of 'science as a system', the role of science in society, and the (public) understanding of the scientific method - and why the latter is crucial for trust, for integrity considerations, and also for integration. In the same vein, the recommendations formulated in this group referred very much

to overarching topics like thinking research and science communication together, rethinking collaboration within research but also with 'external' actors for example from industry, and also strengthening an actual 'culture of error'.

2.3 Focus group 3: Good Scientific Practice

As in the first focus group, all participants of this focus group knew each other before, and the entire discussion had a very familiar atmosphere. The participants were very passionate about the topics of the debate, and it was clear that it was not the first time they discussed similar issues among them: they are all part of the UniWiND network which regularly organises meetings for such an exchange.

Among all groups, this one had the strongest focus on the institutional dimension - the roles and responsibilities of institutions - when discussing the questions. Not surprisingly, their main focus in the debate were the different facets of research integrity. They provided a very clear insight into the dynamics of 'integrity' within institutions and also took the perspective of scientists: Can scientists actually still trust in institutions? What mechanisms exist to support them facing the ambivalent expectations they are confronted with? Another important topic in their focus group was the (loss of) the 'authority of science'.

The group very clearly identified structural problems on the institutional dimension in regard to integrity but also integration and offered recommendations in this regard throughout the entire discussion - not only at the end. Interestingly, their view on social integration was rather classical and uncontroversial compared to especially the first focus group where it was the other way around (controversial discussion on integration, rather uncontroversial discussion on integrity).

Altogether, the three focus groups were extremely rich in their discussions but also highly different in their approaches of the topics discussed. The different professional backgrounds of the participants clearly led to very different perspectives on the topics, which is very valuable but also needs to be kept in mind when reading the analysis. Some arguments were recurring across the focus groups, but others should be analysed from the different viewpoints they have been approached from in the different focus groups. It could - by the way - be a particular strength of the international analysis if similar patterns are found across similar professional groups.

3 Building trust in science: from perception to institutional engagement

The following chapter presents the main lines of argumentation determined in a cross-sectional analysis of the three focus groups. The arguments are supported and illustrated by direct quotes from the participants of the different groups. The chapter starts with answering the question how participants perceive the general relation of science and society today, which role science plays in society and how important the 'system of science' is in this regard (section 3.1). It continues by elaborating on the current state of trust in science and reasons and influencing factors for trust but also potential distrust in science (section 3.2). Sections 3.3 and 3.4 present the main arguments of the debate on the current state and future development of research integrity and social integration from an institutional perspective. In section 3.5. two other themes which emerged during the debates in different focus groups are discussed, namely the relation of science and politics and science and industry.

This entire analysis leads over to chapter 4, presenting the different recommendations the focus groups formulated for institutions and other stakeholders to improve conditions for research integrity, social integration and, ultimately, trust in science.

While no systematic differences were identified in the discussions about science and society and public trust in science between the different focus groups - even though opinions were of course diverse - the groups' approaches to the topics of research

integrity and social integration were partly very different. The analysis aims to account for that by clarifying in the beginning of the respective sections from which angle the topic was mainly discussed in the different focus groups.

3.1 About science and society

This section is dedicated to the participants' perception of the general relation between science and society. Asked about the first key words that come to their mind, participants had a wide range of associations in this regard relating to dimensions such as the interaction of science and society ("ivory tower", "mutual interest", "exchange", "transfer", "science communication"), feelings of the public towards science (from "fascination" to "disenchantment", "high expectations", "trust" vs. "decreasing trust") and basic principles to discuss when thinking about the relation of science and society ("mutual dependency", "normativity", "basis for democratic processes").

In and beyond these first impressions, two main themes were discussed across focus groups in view of the relation between science and society: on the one hand, the perception of science by the public (section 3.1.1), and on the other hand, science as a system and its definitions and challenges (section 3.1.2).

3.1.1 About the public perception of science

Participants of the three focus groups see clear ambivalences in the relation between science and society and much of this seems to stem from a partly distorted public perception of science. On the one hand, there is still a lot of fascination for science, especially in disciplines that are completely out of reach for the own understanding.³ People love fascinating facts, new insights into topics like astrophysics and outer space that have no direct and obvious link to their daily lives. At the same time, there seems to be a process of disenchantment, people understand that 'science' is not all-powerful and cannot make any problem disappear with the snap of a finger.

According to the participants, the coronavirus pandemic has played a very important role in this regard: expectations towards science and scientists to 'solve' this crisis quickly and in a lasting manner skyrocketed in the beginning of the pandemic. At the same time, the - within science totally common - topic of scientific uncertainties entered the public perception at a new level. People, scared and highly affected by the virus and the measures taken for its restriction, wished for clear, easy, and unambiguous answers to their questions (for a more extensive discussion about public expectations towards science, see section 3.2.2). Scientists were however not able to provide these, because there are barely any clear and totally unambiguous answers in science. This huge discrepancy and mismatch between the expectations towards science and the actual way science works is not new as such but reached new dimensions throughout the pandemic and is, according to the participants, among others due to a lack of scientific literacy in the public (see also section 3.2.2).

3.1.2 About the system of science

Participants of the focus groups described science as an important and inherent subsystem of society and everyday life. It is the basis for factual opinion-forming and democratic processes and therefore has a crucial importance for the functioning of society. However, they also discussed important fundamental principles and challenges regarding the system of science.

³ For reasons of readability, perceptions and opinions of focus group participants are not always explicitly labelled as such in this report ("participants think / perceive / argue" etc.). But of course, all statements presented here are not given facts, but perceptions expressed by the focus group participants.

Basic principles of science

One important point in regard to the system of science is the distinction between basic - open-ended - research ("Grundlagenforschung") and applied research. Often it seems as if in public discourse but also in communication coming from within science, applied research was held above basic research in underlining the direct link to everyday life and the direct applicability research findings should have. However, basic research - coming without necessarily directly applicable findings - is as important as applied research.

Another aspect discussed about the system of science was the often wrongly invoked 'objectivity' of science. Participants underlined that science is not objective but rather very much dependent on the humans conducting it. However, science is self-conscious about that and has implemented strong mechanism of inner-science scrutinizing and peer-review to account for human-made mistakes and also various forms of scientific uncertainties.

Related to that was a discussion mainly in the focus group of research funders on the desire for a change of the internal scientific culture towards an actual 'culture of error' ("Fehlerkultur"), in which it would not only be accepted but supported and encouraged to make mistakes and learn from them. Currently, the high pressure to publish as much as possible - also because obtaining external funding very much depends on it - hinders scientists from a) going new and unexplored ways in their research because they cannot be sure that the former will work out and b) to openly address mistakes or uncertainties with regard to their research. This is very strongly related to persisting structures of power within institutions and science in general.

Challenges for the system of science

This last point already leads over to the next main theme discussed in relation to the 'system of science', namely current and future challenges it faces. In two of the three focus groups (university communication and research funding), science was pictured as a 'driven' rather than a driving force. It was described as passive, only re-acting - as opposed to acting - and having little offense. This is the case for example in current debates about scientific misconduct, which are driven from the outside of academia by companies that have specialised in the search for plagiarism. Instead of pro-actively countering scientific misconduct, research only reacts once there are allegations. The same seems to be true in the currently heated debate about the positioning of universities and research institutions in the political discourse, for example in relation to the Middle East conflict. 'Science' is perceived as hesitant and then reacting hectically instead of acting proactively in a united and considered manner. The same has already been observed during the pandemic, for example when individual scientists have been played off against each other.

Another current challenge for the system of science, and especially for scientists themselves are the conflicting expectations scientists are confronted with. Science becomes more and more specialised, and scientists are required throughout their career to specialise in one very small part of their topic in order to fulfil the criteria of 'excellence'. At the same time and answering the public call for more transparency and 'science outside the ivory tower', funding calls nowadays include requirements for science communication, participatory science and public engagement formats. Suddenly, scientists are supposed to communicate and exchange about their highly specialised scientific topics at a low-threshold level with citizens without ever having received an appropriate training and also without appropriate resources for it.

The double-edged sword of science communication

This leads to the last important aspect discussed regarding science as a system and this is the double-edged sword of science communication. Playing an important part in the discussion about social integration and public engagement, the topic of science communication will also be discussed later in the chapter (see section 3.4.) but some system-related arguments shall already be presented here.

Many participants argued that science as such does not face a crisis, but that a crisis arises from the way society currently deals with scientific uncertainties: there is a crisis of communication and an important problem in the representation of scientific processes in science communication. This applies especially to the communication of scientific findings in the media, whose role in the linkage between science and society, for example during the pandemic, is seen very critically. In search of the strongest headlines, media is perceived to rather polarise than contextualise, thereby increasing uncertainty and fears or even distrust in science among the public.

While science communication as such has the huge potential to bring science and society closer together, to increase transparency, dialogue, mutual exchange, and interest, according to the participants, it can also have the opposite effect as when media provides a platform for pseudo-scientific news and misinformation. Science communication is also a challenge in the sense that many scientists have no training in this regard and do not know how to successfully communicate about their research. Increasing attacks and hate campaigns, on- and offline, increase the hesitancy of scientists to go public with their work.

Altogether, participants clearly perceive the relation between science and society as multi-faceted. It is not all bad - fascination and also a feeling of use- and helpfulness of science prevail in large parts of the society. Nevertheless, one could say by coming out of its ivory tower, science and scientists have also become more vulnerable. Having very high expectations about the problem-solving capacity of science, the public has been disappointed during the pandemic as it became increasingly aware of scientific uncertainties and the fact that science can only very rarely provide easy and straightforward answers. What is needed in the relation between science and society is an increased open exchange and dialogue (see also chapter 4).

The current role of science as a system in society is also not seen uncritically by the institutional actors of the focus groups. 'Science' is perceived as driven rather than driving, passive, re-acting and only very little pro-active system not very successfully positioning itself in the current heated political and social debates.

3.1 About Science and Society

„Inter-Esse: dazwischen sein. Und ich denke, das Interesse auch in der Gesellschaft, bei den Bürgerinnen und Bürgern ist groß und letztlich auch bei den Wissenschaftlerinnen und Wissenschaftlern selber. Und da [ist] eben auch die Überlegung, wie kann das gut genährt werden und sich gegenseitig befruchten.“

"Inter-Esse: being in between. And I think there is a great deal of interest in society, among the general public and ultimately also among the scientists themselves. And there [is] also the consideration of how this can be well nourished and cross-fertilise each other."

Focus Group Research Funding Organisations

„Wissenschaft fasziniert weiterhin stark in der Gesellschaft. Ich glaube, das kann man in jedem Newsportal immer wieder sehen. Irgendwelche Anekdoten, irgendwelche neuen Erkenntnisse, sei es Weltall, sei es merkwürdige Befunde in der Flora oder Fauna auf der Erde.“

"Science continues to fascinate society. I think you can see that again and again in every news portal. Any anecdotes, any new findings, be it space, be it strange findings in the flora or fauna on Earth."

Focus Group Research Funding Organisations

„[...] , aber dass manche Wissenschaft auch im Elfenbeinturm verhaftet bleibt und nicht wahrnimmt, dass sie eigentlich eine wichtige Rolle hätte, das der Gesellschaft zu vermitteln.“

"[...] but that some science remains stuck in the ivory tower and doesn't realise that it actually has an important role to play in communicating this to society."

Focus Group University Communication

„Wissenschaft ist eben nicht objektiv, sondern sie ist von Menschen gemacht, die alle in ihren Hintergründen forschen und arbeiten.“

"Science is actually not objective, it is made by people who all research and work based on their backgrounds."

Focus Group Research Funding Organisations

„Was mir noch einfällt ist, dass die Wissenschaft ja immer spezialisierter wird und [es] ja für den Außenstehenden immer schwerer wird, irgendwie überhaupt nachzuvollziehen, was da passiert. Und deswegen ist es vielleicht auch oft so schwer, Informationen aus der Wissenschaft irgendwie einzuordnen und zu werten für Außenstehende. Und mit Außenstehende meine ich schon fast Menschen, die in einem anderen Wissenschaftsgebiet arbeiten.“

"Another thing that comes to mind is that science is becoming more and more specialised, and [it] is becoming increasingly difficult for outsiders to understand what is happening. And that is perhaps why it is often so difficult for outsiders to somehow categorise and evaluate information from science. And by outsiders, I almost mean people who work in a different scientific field."

Focus Group University Communication

„Nun glaube ich, hilft es vielleicht auch noch mal zu schauen, wie äußern sich eigentlich wissenschaftliche Diskurse innerhalb der Wissenschaft und außerhalb der Wissenschaft? Und ich würde sagen, da gibt es so leichte Akzentverschiebung. Also innerhalb der Wissenschaft ist eigentlich der gängige Diskursmodus Kritik. Kritik an scheinbar gesicherten, an scheinbaren Erkenntnissen. Also wenn irgendein neuer Forschungsaufsatz kommt, dann ist der Modus eher ‚Stimmt das?‘, ‚Stimmen die Parameter?‘, ‚Ich habe hier Zweifel, ich habe da Zweifel und das ist nicht berücksichtigt worden‘. [...] Das macht Wissenschaft ja aus, permanente Kritik an dem, was sozusagen methodisch da an Hintergrund ist. Tritt man in die Öffentlichkeit [...] dann wird eher dieser Aspekt der gesicherten Erkenntnis in den Vordergrund geschoben.“

"Now I think it might also help to look again at how scientific discourses are actually expressed within science and outside of science. And I would say that there is a slight shift in emphasis. Within science, the usual mode of discourse is actually criticism. Criticism of seemingly certain, apparent findings. So, when any new research paper comes out, the mode tends to be 'Is it true?', 'Are the parameters right?', 'I have doubts here, I have doubts there and this has not been taken into account'. [...] That is what science is all about, permanent criticism of the methodological background, so to speak. When you go public [...], then the aspect of reliable knowledge tends to be pushed to the fore."

Focus Group Research Funding Organisations

*„Aber es sind eben auch widerstreitende Anforderungen, denen Wissenschaftler*innen da ausgesetzt sind.“*

"But there are actually conflicting demands that scientists are exposed to."

Focus Group Good Scientific Practice

3.2 Perceptions of trust in science

It has already become clear that participants do not see the relation between science and society as unproblematic. Based on this, the discussion about trust in science, whether there is a crisis of public trust and where it derives from, has been deep and complex in all three focus groups. Section 3.2 first of all presents the main arguments brought forward by the participants when discussing whether there actually is a crisis of trust in science and how one might differentiate such a crisis, and then secondly, the main reasons observed for trusting or rather distrusting science in today's society.

3.2.1 A crisis of trust?

Participants across the groups were rather reluctant to talk about a crisis of trust in science in general. A crisis would imply a sudden occurrence of particular circumstances, and this has not been the case. Rather the increasingly difficult relation between science and society is seen as a gradual process.

Many participants raised the fact that data of the "science barometer"⁴ shows that there is no overall loss of trust in science among the public in Germany. At the same time, the overall perception of the participants was that trust is declining. It appeared however that the perceived decrease in trust in science might not apply to 'science' in general, but rather to different dimensions of it and also concern particular segments of the society more than others. Additionally, there might not only be a problem of public trust in science but also a loss of scientists' trust in science and its institutions (see also section 3.1.2).

Discussing the matter of trust in science, participants referred to different dimensions of trust but also different dimensions of science: people can of course trust in 'science' as a cognitive system, the scientific method etc., but beyond that, participants also identified science as a social system and people's trust in scientists and scientific institutions as very important.

Trust among different social groups

Participants have argued that while, according to surveys, trust levels are relatively stable across time, the same data shows that it is important to take a more differentiated look at different societal groups in this regard: trust levels vary importantly across groups with different levels of formal education with those having lower levels of formal education trusting much less in science than others. As science becomes increasingly complex, people are torn between high expectations and incomprehension. *Science literacy* is an important key concept often discussed by the participants in this regard (see also section 3.2.2).

More generally, participants also observe a feeling of being overwhelmed and powerless in view of the complexity of current world events which is also transferred to science. In this same vein, an increased polarisation within society, in social and political terms, is seen to have an influence on science as well: because science is a fundamental subsystem of society it is not exempt from these polarisations.

Science as a cognitive system – varying trust in different scientific disciplines

As already stated, participants did not perceive an overall loss of trust in science, but clearly noted that there are differences across varying scientific disciplines. They underlined that there is not 'one science' but that one should speak of 'the sciences'. A potential crisis of trust would rather concern the scientific disciplines that have a direct – or for the public directly visible – impact on current societal transformations and political decisions. A strong example for this is of course the field of virology during the pandemic. But the same is true for other disciplines dealing with currently controversial social topics that might have an influence on the political agenda and / or on people's daily lives. The

⁴ The Wissenschaftsbarometer, an annual representative survey of the German population on perceptions of science and research, organised by Wissenschaft im Dialog.

participants mentioned gender studies, climate research and health studies as examples for such disciplines.

Science as a social system – personification of science and the role of scientific institutions

However, the discussion about trust and a crisis of public trust in science focussed much more on science as a social system and the role different actors have within this system than on science as a cognitive system. This might be the case because trust is a relational concept – we always need someone else to trust in, we cannot trust 'alone' – and it is easier to trust in people than in complex cognitive systems. Therefore, participants underlined that trust in science very often means **trust in scientists** but also trust in the people communicating science. This implies a huge responsibility for the actors implied but also a huge vulnerability of the individuals' trust in science as it is dependent on the scientific actors they turn to.

A related aspect when thinking about trust in science as a social system is the **role of institutions**. Across all focus groups, participants agreed that there is a decrease of trust in institutions in Germany today. Compared to others, such as political institutions, but also journalism for example, scientific institutions are seen to be still in a good position but also at risk of losing public trust. As a possible explanation, participants argued that many discussions that formerly took place within academia, for example about free speech, are now widely discussed in public. Science or academia are no longer a self-contained space, and this changes the way science and institutions (need to) act. As a concrete example, the group of university communicators discussed the fact that scientific institutions and especially universities are increasingly torn into political debates, and that, for example, it is expected from them to position themselves in debates about the Middle East conflict. In reaction to that, participants once again invoked the image of institutions being driven and just re-acting, often in an uncoordinated and rushed manner. The negative public impression arising from this reaction was perceived as being transferred to the image of the university as a whole with no differentiation between the university as an 'institution', with a board of directors and a communication department etc., and the university as a place of science.

It was underlined that institutions can build trust but that they can also lose it very quickly and that scandals, such as a failed political statement but also cases of scientific misconduct, can cause severe damage to trust in single institutions but also the system of scientific institutions as a whole. This applies not only to public trust in institutions, though, but also to scientists who might lose trust in their institution.

Altogether, the participants' tenor was that the public already does and increasingly will question scientific institutions as they question other fundamental institutions in society. Based on that, in the group of research integrity officers, theoretical questions about the role of universities emerged: can they, following Giddens, serve as an access point for people where trust in science can be built? Can universities still act as the 'neutral' and trusted third party?

The 'authority of science' and the instrumentalisation of scientific content

Related to the decrease of trust in institutions, comes another observation participants across different focus groups made in the debate on trust in science: a new dimension of 'dealing with' institutions and their actors in public discourse and action, characterised by total delegitimisation, contempt and even violence. The group of research integrity officers argued that this is due to a **loss of the authority**, that science and scientific findings had to some degree in the public view before. One characteristic of this loss of authority is the fact that there is no more unquestioned trust in the 'old white man with the lab coat'. But participants also see a certain loss of trust in the benevolence and orientation towards the common good of science in general. It was argued that such 'demystification' and

'disenchantment' are also desirable to some degree because blind trust is not what science should desire, either. However, the expression this 'loss of authority' takes with the emergence of alternative facts, false information, doubts about climate change, and direct attacks of scientists, who defend unwanted opinions is very dangerous and alarming.

The **instrumentalisation of scientific content**, mainly by actors outside the scientific system, plays an important role in this regard. One can increasingly observe the use of scientific half-truths to create pseudo-scientific discourses as well as clearly targeted disinformation campaigns, increasing insecurity and doubts about science and scientific findings in the public. This is certainly partly due to the loss of the authority of science but at the same time it also reinforces the increase of mistrust in science among the public. It is therefore as much an expression of a crisis as a reason for it and science has not found an adequate answer to it (yet).

3.2.2 Reasons for trust and distrust in science

When discussing the matter of trust in science, one should always keep in mind what trust in science is actually for. Trust is a mechanism of complexity reduction in an always more complex world. It means giving up control and being okay with someone or something else having this control. We cannot know everything, especially not when it comes to scientific findings, so acknowledging someone else's expertise is crucial in trust in science.

The questions that participants in the group of research integrity officers raised were: what has led to the fact that people think they cannot confidently give up control in scientific matters anymore? And what are the consequences if they cannot or are not willing to do so anymore?

Participants discussed very different answers to these questions in all three groups. The main arguments presented here relate to the system of science and the relation of science and society rather generally. Aspects concerning research integrity and social integration are discussed in the respective thematic sections (see sections 3.3 and 3.4).

Increased relevance of science in daily life

A first factor that has contributed to trust in science being a clearly more debated topic than it was before is the increased relevance of science in people's daily life. New scientific findings and technological developments have a huge impact on our lives, and this was the case already before the coronavirus pandemic. With this increased influence or at least the increased visibility of the direct influence of science, people have started to ask more questions, for example about the actual usefulness and benefit of science for oneself, the potential threat of scientific findings (keyword 'dual use'), and in how far one should be able to influence the direction of science as it is one's tax money spent on it. This leads to an interesting evolution: as long as there are no points of contact with science, it is easy to trust. But as soon as science touches upon our daily life, our bodies, our decisions, questions arise. This is as such very positive: healthy mistrust or critical trust is better than unfounded, unchecked enthusiasm. Questioning can lead to further thinking - among the public but also among scientists. To take this positive direction, however, some pre-conditions need to be met - among them a true understanding of the way science works.

(False) Expectations towards science

With the increased relevance of science in daily life also comes the increased awareness of our dependence on science - society needs science and scientific findings, and nothing has been a better demonstration of this than the coronavirus pandemic. According to the participants, there was an important ambivalence in the public's approach to science during the pandemic. On the one hand, one could observe a loss of authority of scientific findings and the realisation that science is not

a saviour (see 3.2.1), and on the other hand, there were huge expectations towards science to immediately 'solve' the virus and with it the pandemic.

All focus groups agreed that society has actually truly wrong expectations towards science and scientists, expecting 'clear and easy answers' from it, which science is very rarely able to provide. Such huge expectations obviously bear a high potential of frustration and when they are not met, scepticism towards science logically increases.

There is however another aspect of expectations towards science that causes frustration among especially young people according to the groups of research funders and university communicators: the lack of action in the fight against climate change despite the fact that we know it exists for already quite some time. One needs to differentiate between the obligations of science and politics in this regard, but there clearly is the expectation towards science to raise its voice and defend the cause of stopping climate change. Having the impression that not enough is done in this regard can equally decrease trust in science.

Scientific uncertainties and a lack of "scientific literacy"

Coming back to false or misguided expectations towards science, participants in all focus groups report a mismatch between public expectations of what science *should* be able to do and actual knowledge of what science *is* able to do and how the scientific method works. This mismatch is even stronger in educationally disadvantaged population groups and is often argued to be due to a lack of "scientific literacy".

Maybe the most important aspect in this regard is the different understanding of scientific uncertainties in science and in the public. While uncertainties are an intrinsic part of the scientific method, they might appear as a weakness and as frightening to the public. A participant of the group of research integrity officers argued that due to its centuries-long success, and some very 'certain' scientific facts everybody learns about at school, expectations towards science are too high today, and people have difficulties to understand why not all scientific findings are as certain as the fact that the earth is not flat. As disputes between scientists do increasingly happen in public, on social media, and accessible for everyone, the public is much more exposed to scientific uncertainties as it has been before. However, not everybody has the same access to information or informs themselves to the same extent. During the pandemic, this has led to what has been called a 'pandemic of different information levels' and in consequence to very different risk perceptions. It is also very difficult to understand from the outside, whether a dispute between two scientists is due to methodological uncertainties or whether it is actually a personal matter.

Related to the understanding of scientific uncertainties is also the temporality of scientific findings and the fact that some scientific 'evidences' may change over time - when new discoveries are made, new technologies developed etc. In this regard, the group of university communicators raised the question how much transparency the communication of scientific findings actually needs and whether it would really be a good idea to clearly state with each scientific finding that it might be obsolete two years from now.

Altogether, participants of the three focus groups agreed that there is no general crisis of 'trust in science' and that most people still trust in science and see its usefulness for their lives. But they all also observed problematic developments, namely when 'healthy questioning' of institutions and the authority of institutions turns into systematic delegitimation and even hate and violence. Participants identify an ambivalence in the public stance towards science as on the one hand, the authority of scientific findings is called into question, and on the other hand, expectations towards scientists to immediately be able to solve problems are extremely high, which became very clear during the pandemic. They see the reason for this ambivalence in a mismatch between what people expect science to do and their knowledge of what science is actually able to do. Independently from another, all groups agreed that the only solution for these challenges and ultimately also the

solution to strengthen public trust in science is to explain and raise awareness for the way science and the scientific method work in all parts of the society. This also includes knowledge on how to manage today's constant overflow of information, how to recognise disinformation campaigns, and how to deal with the systematic sowing of doubts ('manufactured doubts'), for example by lobby groups with specific economic and political interests in mind. Without such knowledge, one is much more susceptible to fall for fake news and pseudo-scientific discourses destroying the actual image of science in society.

3.2 Perceptions of trust in science

A crisis of trust?

„[...] und auf der anderen Seite aber auch, dass letzten Endes Wissenschaft vielleicht als Teilsystem von Gesellschaft nicht allein jetzt von so einem Vertrauensverlust heimgesucht wird, sondern dass es eher ist: es gibt einen Vertrauensverlust in Institutionen und von dem ist Wissenschaft nicht unberührt.“

"[...] and on the other hand, that in the end, science as a subsystem of society might not be the one to be affected by a loss of trust alone, but that it is rather: there is a loss of trust in institutions and science is not unaffected by this."

Focus Group Research Funding Organisations

„Ich sehe auch keine Krise der Wissenschaft, sondern ich sehe [...] die Instrumentalisierung von Wissenschaft oder von außerwissenschaftlichen Äußerungen, um seine Position zu legitimieren, in einem noch nicht gekannten Ausmaß mittlerweile im öffentlichen Diskurs. Die Wissenschaft selber hat keine Krise, aber der Umgang und wie wir mit unwissenschaftlichen, als Wissenschaft verbrämten Thesen umgehen, da haben wir eine Kommunikations-, eine Legitimations- oder eine Politikkrise.“

"I don't see a crisis in science either, but I do see [...] the instrumentalisation of science or non-scientific statements to legitimise one's position to an unprecedented extent in public discourse. Science itself does not have a crisis, but how we deal with unscientific theses that are dressed up as science, in this regard we have a crisis of communication, a crisis of legitimisation or a crisis of politics."

Focus Group University Communication

*"JA, Einrichtungen können Vertrauen gewinnen, aufbauen, aber auch verlieren."
"YES, institutions can gain trust, build trust, but they can also lose it."*

Focus Group University Communication

*„Wissenschaft steht im Vergleich zu anderen Institutionen und Berufsgruppen noch ziemlich gut da nach wie vor, aber sie ist natürlich auch massiv und gezielt unter Druck, wenn es um Desinformationskampagnen oder eben so Hate Speech-Attacken oder so geht, wenn einzelne Wissenschaftler*innen versucht werden, mundtot gemacht zu werden.“*

"Compared to other institutions and professional groups, science is still in a pretty good position, but of course it is also under massive and targeted pressure when it comes to disinformation campaigns or hate speech attacks or the like, when individual scientists are tried to be silenced."

Focus Group Research Funding Organisations

„Vertrauenskrise im Sinne von: Welchen Status hat wissenschaftliche Erkenntnis überhaupt in der Gesellschaft? Wird wissenschaftliche Expertise noch anerkannt? Alternative Fakten, Verdrehungen von Informationen, Bezweiflung von Klimawandel, auch Anfeindungen von Wissenschaftlerinnen und Wissenschaftlern, die unliebsame Positionen vertreten.“

"Crisis of trust in the sense of: What status does scientific knowledge even have in society? Is scientific expertise still recognised? Alternative facts, distortions of information, doubts about climate change, even hostility towards scientists who take unpopular positions."

Focus Group Good Scientific Practice

Reasons for trust and distrust in science

"Wenn die Leute nichts mit Wissenschaft zu tun haben, dann ist es leicht zu vertrauen. ‚Es ist mir egal, was die da machen.‘ So, ne? Aber in dem Moment, wo es in den Alltag rein diffundiert, muss ich irgendwie dazu Stellung nehmen. Also ich glaube ja, dass wir alle komplett überfordert sind gerade, also alle. Und einige fühlen das als Ohnmacht und das kann ich auch total gut nachvollziehen."

"If people have nothing to do with science, then it's easy to trust. 'I don't care what they do.' Like that, right? But the moment it diffuses into everyday life, I have to take a stand on it somehow. I actually think we're all completely overwhelmed right now, really everyone. And some perceive this as powerlessness, and I can totally understand that."

Focus Group University Communication

„Also die Suche nach den einfachen Antworten, die Wissenschaft in aller Regel im laufenden Prozess so nicht liefern kann.“

"The search for simple answers that science can generally not provide in the ongoing process."

Focus Group Good Scientific Practice

„Und da ist so eine Ambivalenz, [denn da ist] einerseits dieser Autoritätsverlust, also sie ist eben die Wissenschaft und ist keine Heilsbringerin. Sie kann uns keine Antworten liefern. Auf der anderen Seite aber eine totale Überhöhung von Wissenschaft, also die Erwartung in der Coronakrise, die Wissenschaftler sollen es richten. Und ich glaube, in dieser Ambivalenz bewegt sich das.“

"And there is this ambivalence, [because on the one hand there is] this loss of authority, i.e. it is science and is not a saviour. It can't provide us with answers. On the other hand, however, there is a total exaltation of science, i.e. the expectation in the corona crisis that scientists should fix it. And I believe that this ambivalence is a crucial point."

Focus Group Good Scientific Practice

„Eben fiel das Stichwort ‚scientific literacy‘. Ich glaube, dass Vertrauen [...] nicht dadurch gestärkt wird, zu sagen: ‚es ist so‘, sondern ‚es ist WAHRSCHEINLICH so‘ und da gibt es aber auch Zweifel und den müssen wir auch deutlich machen.“

"The keyword 'scientific literacy' was just mentioned. I believe that trust [...] is not strengthened by saying: 'it is like this', but rather 'it is PROBABLY like this', but there is also doubt, and we have to be clear and transparent about this doubt."

Focus Group Research Funding Organisations

„Auf der anderen Seite würde aber Transparenz an der Stelle auch nicht unbedingt zum Vertrauen beitragen, wenn wir jedes Mal einen Disclaimer dahinter schreiben: ‚Dieses Forschungsergebnis hält nur für zwei Jahre‘.“

"On the other hand, transparency in this regard would also not necessarily contribute to trust if we were to write a disclaimer behind it every time: 'This scientific result only lasts two years'."

Focus Group University Communication

*"Aber ich würde das auch fett unterstreichen, dass es eben viel wichtiger ist, über das Erkenntnisinteresse und dann die Methoden, die Wissenschaftler*innen anwenden [zu sprechen] als Ergebniskommunikation. Also da würde ich auch drei Ausrufezeichen hinter machen."*

"But I would also highly emphasise that it is much more important to [talk] about the research interest and then the methods that scientists use than doing 'results communication'. I would put three exclamation marks behind that."

Focus Group Research Funding Organisations

3.3 Attitudes towards research integrity

Having reviewed different perspectives on the relation of science and society and trust in science that participants brought forward in the discussion, the following section deals with research integrity. While the main arguments presented here have come up in one way or another in different focus groups, it is necessary to underline that the three groups actually had pretty different perspectives on the topic and different focal points during their discussions.

In the focus group of university communicators, integrity was discussed as a not very controversial topic, pretty well 'taken care of' at the institutional level by existing guidelines. Important points of the discussion here were the relation of science and politics (see also section 3.5.1) and also the question whether integrity standards should be applied to the field of science communication as well.

In the group of research funders, integrity was already discussed before being introduced by the moderator. Scientific misconduct did however not become an important topic of the debate - even after specifically asking about it. The debate focussed on superordinate themes in relation to integrity rather than the concrete implementation of integrity in institutions. One point of discussion was the relation of science and industry (see also section 3.5.2), but participants also raised questions on the functioning of the peer-review process, of dependencies and power relations, and of more diversity in science, and how this might be related to integrity.

In the group of research integrity officers, research integrity was obviously the most discussed topic. It was very clear that this topic is at the heart of the participants' daily work which was expressed through a very targeted and at the same

time comprehensive discussion. Participants had a strong focus on the role of institutions and what they need to do better, also on a structural level.

The following section presents in three parts first of all what research integrity means in the eyes of the participants (section 3.3.1), what framework conditions it needs to 'work' (section 3.3.2), and what they think about the extent and incentives for scientific misconduct (section 3.3.3).

3.3.1 What is research integrity?

On the initial question of what research integrity actually means, participants had rather similar associations. They described it as a system of norms and values one has to adhere to and underlined the crucial importance of independence and transparency. In the current German discourse, one rather talks about 'Good Scientific Practice' than about research integrity which is seen as a more comprehensive approach with less negative connotations. This term was employed mainly in the group of research integrity officers.

A 'system of norms and values'

Very generally said, research integrity can be defined as a system of norms and values that exists for already a long time and has been shaped and further developed by many theorists. Integrity today means knowing about and complying with these norms and values in our behaviour.

A term often used by the participants in association with integrity was 'attitude'. Research integrity means an attitude that one should internalise early, constantly reflect on, and that needs to be developed and passed on. While in the group of university communicators it was described as a professional attitude, in the group of research integrity officers it rather appeared to be a personal attitude as well. Two important ingredients of research integrity are responsibility and a sense of responsibility.

It was also underlined, that the 'right' behaviour in terms of research integrity is not set in stone and has to some extent a temporal dimension: what has been right 30 years ago, might now be seen as wrong or not up to the standards of integrity anymore. This is why the constant reflection on this system of norms and values is so important.

Independence and autonomy

One crucial aspect of integrity is independence. Scientists should - in an ideal world - work truly independently, freely conducting research and developing ideas without being influenced or pushed into a certain direction by anyone. Participants underlined that public trust in science is very much related to the fact that it should be independent. And that the suspicion that one is not independent (anymore), can very quickly lead to mistrust in science. An example for this is the field of policy advice: when providing political actors with scientific advice, participants perceive it as important that the scientists defend their own findings with determination even if they do not correspond to what 'politics' wants to hear. This is seen as having the potential to strengthen public trust in the integrity of science.

From another perspective, it has also been brought up, that science however also needs to own up to its own cooperations. This is particularly the case when working together with the private industry: in case of failures or mistakes, science is still very quick to shift the responsibility to the economic actors.

Transparency

Closely related to the aspect of independence is the importance of transparency that has been discussed in all three focus groups. Transparency is underlined as a crucial part of integrity, that needs a comprehensive understanding: in scientists' daily work, it basically means stating all the facts, archiving them, keeping a lab diary,

displaying conflicts of interest, not accepting any 'authorship of honour', and being transparent about who financed the study they are working on. But there is also a dimension of transparency that is much more directed towards the outside: participants expressed the need for more transparent communication also concerning doubts, mistakes and failures, leading back to the keyword 'culture of error' (see 3.1.2). It was argued that currently, it is not actual failures one talks about, but only those that in the end turned out to be great learnings and moments of change. This leads to scientists being afraid of transparently communicating doubts in the public, even more because of the increasing danger of these doubts being instrumentalised by external actors. Participants also see it as a responsibility of the institutions to communicate transparently and comprehensively about cases of misconduct. Instead of trying to get out of it with the least possible damage, as it is most often the case today, they should proactively communicate about what happened but also about what happens afterwards and what is done to improve a culture of integrity within the institution (see also 3.3.2).

3.3.2 Framework conditions for integrity

While participants' perspectives on what research integrity actually means were rather similar, very different aspects of the framework conditions needed to implement research integrity were discussed in the three groups. The scope ranges from written guidelines to a 'culture of research integrity' at all institutional levels and also includes questions on the pitfalls of peer-review, science's internal mechanism of quality assurance.

Guidelines

The standard reference work for German institutional actors when thinking about research integrity are the "Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice" of the DFG (German Research Foundation). These guidelines have first been published in 1998 but have recently been updated and "as of 1 August 2019, all universities and non-university research institutions will be required to implement the 19 guidelines in a legally binding manner to be eligible to receive DFG funding".⁵ As DFG funding is crucial for all kinds of scientific institutions in Germany, the obligation to implement these guidelines has had an important influence on the institutional landscape. Interestingly, while being the first association of university communicators and research funders, the research integrity officers did not mention these guidelines explicitly in their debate. One participant of the university communicators group also referred to the European Charter for Researchers as important document of reference and the general wish that the German discourse would orientate itself more towards the European one.

A culture of integrity

Participants in all groups underlined the necessity to understand that integrity is an integral part of research and the research process. In order for it to become a 'living culture' it needs more than guidelines one needs to follow in order to obtain money: it needs an implementation at all levels of the research process and within institutions.

Indeed, participants see institutions in the duty of establishing, living, and communicating a 'culture of integrity' at all levels. The most obvious aspect in this regard is that Good Scientific Practice should be a compulsory part of every student's and young researcher's training, but this is not enough: the groups of university communicators and research integrity officers - therefore the actors dealing with this aspect regularly in their work - underlined that the topic of research integrity is often not very present at the executive level in universities. They notice a clear unwillingness of executives to inform and train themselves in Good Scientific Practice. On the one hand, participants see the reason for this in the idea of senior executives that training on Good Scientific Practice is supposed

⁵ For more information, see the official homepage of the DFG: <https://www.dfg.de/en>.

to be for the younger generations 'who still need to learn'; and on the other hand, that when hearing Good Scientific Practice, people directly have the reflex of thinking about actual scientific misconduct and that they do not want to be associated or in touch with that.

Participants underline that there is also a huge problem of power structures within universities: even if young researchers have a good basis of training and knowledge about Good Scientific Practice, they are powerless when it comes to decisions taken by their superiors which they themselves perceive to be against the standards of Good Scientific Practice.

What would be needed from the executive levels of universities in order to implement a comprehensive culture of integrity, is on the one hand to change communication to the outside: research integrity officers currently observe a differentiation between the institution and individual scientists in communications related to research integrity. As soon as there is a success story, this is thanks to the institution, and as soon as there is a mistake or a failure, the responsibility is shifted entirely to the individual concerned. On the other hand, communication to the inside about topics related to integrity needs to change as well: rooms for open and transparent exchange need to be provided, Good Scientific Practice should not happen entirely behind closed doors, because as long as it does, it keeps its unwanted and even 'dirty' connotation.

Another aspect discussed by the university communicators in relation to a culture of research integrity - in a very self-reflexive way - is in how far the process of communicating science (at universities, but also in journalism) should adopt the same rules and standards as the process of conducting science. This would imply to critically read and question papers and scientific findings that are to be communicated. But it would also mean to rethink the way university communication currently works. One participant stated that such communication is often led by own interests - at least to some extent - and consciously employs framing that attracts attention, for example with future funding in mind. Instead, it would be important to communicate about research and its findings in a truly transparent and honest way.

In the group of research funders, the question was discussed in how far issues of diversity and the reproduction of educational inequalities could not also be seen as part of integrity as a culture and how research funding organisation might be able to influence developments in this regard.

Instruments of quality assurance and control

The last aspect discussed in the context of necessary framework conditions for research integrity are instruments of quality assurance and control. The probably most obvious aspect in this regard and most often mentioned by the participants were continuous trainings and awareness measures for young researchers as well as the implementation of the above-mentioned guidelines, for example through compliance offices etc. Participants made clear that they perceive prevention measures as more important than direct control. Anyhow, the use of plagiarism software for students' works and also severe punishments for cases of scientific misconduct serving as deterrent measure for others were still seen as important.

Especially in Germany, plagiarism regularly plays an important role in public discourse, however mostly not related to students but rather to important public or political figures. Discovering cases of plagiarism in scientific works, it could be seen as an important instrument of control related to research integrity. However, this plagiarism industry has been discussed very critically by participants as it is organised completely outside the scientific system and with clear financial interests in mind. On the one hand, this leads to science always just 're-acting' when accusations are made (see section 3.1.2 and the image of science as the 'driven force'), and on the other hand, cases of plagiarism are often instrumentalised to harm a public figure, very often based on the initiative of, for example, political opponents. Additionally, very often, such cases of plagiarism relate to fairly old scientific works, for which standards at the time were not the same. This plagiarism industry therefore mostly serves specific interests of individual parties but has the potential to cause a lasting damage to the image of science.

The most important mechanism of internal quality control in scientific work – and the basis of many selection and funding allocation processes – is peer-review. Peer-review is generally seen as working well and ensuring high quality of scientific work, especially when it comes to journal publications. Nevertheless, participants also discussed the pitfalls of peer-review: it is a system very much driven by personal and power relations, creating strong dependencies and penalising people who are not or do not want to be part of such dependency networks. Participants in the research funders group underlined that they further support these dependencies with their processes of funding allocations, which are equally based on peer-review but that for the moment, they do not have found better ways to proceed.

In the group of research integrity officers, the question was raised whether science would not also need external monitoring and mechanisms of quality assurance. It was stated that in fields like occupational safety or animal protection, nobody would come up with the idea of letting institutions regulate themselves exclusively from the inside.

As a last important instrument of control related to research integrity but also scientific content in general, participants discussed the high responsibility of science journalism and other mediators between science and society. They need, among many other things, to make sure not to encourage and allow the increase of 'false balance', meaning not to give a platform to opinions with weak evidence or pseudo-scientific discourses in trying to be overly 'transparent' about scientific uncertainties as this further increases insecurity and mistrust in science among the public.

3.3.3 Extent and incentives for scientific misconduct

From a general point of view, the topic of concrete scientific misconduct played a much smaller role in the discussions than expected. All groups came back to more general and comprehensive questions of research integrity relatively quickly. Nevertheless, the most important aspects of the discussion on scientific misconduct are presented here.

Participants in all groups were rather reluctant to give estimations on the extent of scientific misconduct. It seemed to be the general tenor that the majority of scientists are honest, and that genuine misconduct is rather rare. One university communicator stated that he experienced actual cases of scientific misconduct less than five times in 14 years. A research integrity officer reported that in his conflict counselling, he is confronted with more cases related to research integrity today – maybe due to an increased awareness for the topic – but that the number of severe cases has decreased. Another one stated that nevertheless, in his seminars, regularly 10-20 percent of young researchers report that they have already been aware or part of breaches of research integrity. Therefore, it should be seen as part of the reality in the life of young researchers.

Participants of different groups stated that 'misconduct' within the grey areas might be more often the case than one might think, for example regarding the recycling of own scientific content in new publications. However, one participant also underlined that he perceives extensive misconduct by large companies, targeted disinformation campaigns and large-scale fraud as much more important and heavier in weight than 'small-scale' misconduct such as unclear citations in a PhD thesis from 30 years ago.

Regarding the incentives for scientific misconduct, once again most arguments presented here were brought up during the general discussion and not so much in direct response to the explicit question about it. The most often and recurring argument in the three groups was the general pressure under which scientists are working. This pressure has several dimensions, mainly time, money, and resources. Especially among young researchers, there is the pressure to publish and to climb the career ladder very quickly as at least in Germany, there is barely any job security before reaching tenured professorship. Further, in academia a lot depends on the individual reputation of a scientist, which needs to be built in an environment of strong competition, but that can easily be destroyed as well – a reason why accusations of misconduct need to be treated with caution and care.

Several participants underlined that the strong competition prevailing within the scientific system is externally driven and amplified through financial incentives (funding allocations based on reputation and publications etc.), and that as long as there is no change in this competition, pressure will not decrease.

At the same time, one participant also raised the thought that 'pressure' is also a socially desirable explanation: we all know and experience pressure and are therefore willing to understand and forgive mistakes happening in this context. It is therefore even more important to differentiate between mistakes and misconduct (in German: "Fehler" vs. "Fehlverhalten") in regard to research integrity.

Coming back to the role of institutions, the group of research integrity officers emphasised the institutions' responsibility not to pass the buck to individual scientists and blame them in cases of scientific misconduct, but to acknowledge that there are systemic reasons and incentives for misconduct and that they - as an institution - have their part to play in this regard as well. Such responsible communication from the institutional side could support and strengthen scientists and their position in the public discourse beyond individual cases of misconduct.

Altogether, the discussion on research integrity and Good Scientific Practice has revealed complex and partly divergent perspectives of the different institutional actors in the three focus groups. All of them pretty much agreed on the main 'ingredients' of research integrity, meaning norms and values, independence, and transparency. The practical implementation of research integrity was however discussed at different levels, leading to a comprehensive picture of the current 'integrity landscape' in Germany.

It can be stated that the DFG "Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice" are definitely the standard reference work when it comes to integrity guidelines in Germany. Regarding a 'culture of integrity', particularly the research integrity officers but also the university communicators group perceived it as crucial that Good Scientific Practice 'enters the executive levels'. There can only be a culture of integrity when it reaches all institutional levels and is led by example by the executives. Coming to the instruments of quality assurance within science, participants repeatedly underlined the importance of peer-review processes, but at the same time also discussed the pitfalls of this system creating strong dependencies and power imbalances. These, in combination with a high pressure on scientists to 'succeed' - to present successful research, to publish, and nowadays also to engage with the public - can also be seen as incentives for scientific misconduct or at least to operate in the grey area between Good Scientific Practice, scientific mistakes and misconduct.

All participants agreed that research integrity can clearly have an influence on public trust in science - as much in a positive as in a negative way. Increased transparency, communication about research processes and pro-active management of cases of misconduct have the potential to strengthen trust. On the opposite, arising doubts about the independence of researchers or entire research institutions, for example when cooperating with private companies, as well as disregard of scientific standards, scandals and resignations can increase mis- and even distrust in science.

3.3 Attitudes towards research integrity

What is research integrity?

„Haltung. Also, das war auch der erste Begriff, der mir durch den Kopf schoss. Aber ich denke tatsächlich, dass es etwas ist, was zwar früh angelegt werden sollte, aber dass es sich tatsächlich auch über die Zeit immer neu definiert. Also es ist auch das wiederkehrende Thema, das einen durch die ganze Profession begleitet. Das heißt, diese Haltung auch ständig zu reflektieren, anzureichern, weiterzugeben, so diese ständige Beschäftigung damit im Hinterkopf [...].“

"Attitude. That was also the first term that popped into my head. But I actually think that it is indeed something that should be established at an early stage,

but that it also redefines itself over time. It's also a recurring theme that accompanies you throughout your entire profession. That means constantly reflecting on this attitude, enriching it, passing it on, keeping it constantly in mind [...]."

Focus Group Good Scientific Practice

„Unabhängigkeit. Also dass man dann auch wirklich sagen kann, egal in welche Richtung, Finanzierung oder irgendjemandem einen Gefallen tun oder so, das ist für mich ein ganz wichtiger Baustein.“

"Independence. So that you can then really say no matter in which direction, funding or doing someone a favour or something, that is a very important component for me."

Focus Group University Communication

"Warum? Weil die Wissenschaftler möglicherweise glauben, wenn wir unsere Zweifel in die Öffentlichkeit tragen, dann kommen die ganzen ja die ganzen Fake News und sagen, ‚guck mal, da gibt es Zweifel. Und diesen Zweifel, den werden wir jetzt noch mal ordentlich bespielen.‘ Also man hat Angst davor, das, was man eigentlich als interne Praxis vollzieht, in die Öffentlichkeit zu bringen."

"Why? Because scientists may believe that if we discuss our doubts in public, then all the fake news will come and say, 'look, there are doubts. And these doubts, we're going to play on them extensively'. Therefore, people are afraid of doing in public what is actually an internal practice."

Focus Group Research Funding Organisations

Framework conditions for research integrity

"[...], dass die Institutionen selbst auch ein hohes Maß an Verantwortung für wissenschaftliche Integrität tragen, weil sie ja die Rahmenbedingungen dafür schaffen, dass diese Haltung, über die eben gesprochen worden ist, auch gelebt werden kann."

"[...] that the institutions themselves also bear a high degree of responsibility for research integrity, because they create the framework conditions to ensure that this attitude, which has just been discussed, can also be practised."

Focus Group Good Scientific Practice

„Es geht sehr stark von der Leitung aus, jeweils. Also wie die Leitung das Thema selber kommuniziert, wie konsequent die Leitung ist.“

"It comes very much from the management, in each case. In other words, how the management communicates the topic itself, how consistent the management is."

Focus Group University Communication

"Ich nehme in der Kommunikation immer die Ebene [wahr], wenn es darum geht, sich als Institution zu positionieren. Was man positiv macht, ist auf die Institution bezogen war und wenn etwas negativ ist, ist es sehr personen- oder fallbezogen. Und das finde ich insofern eigentlich ganz interessant, dass man sagt: Okay hier ist ein positives Beispiel, da ist es unsere Institution, das ist ein negatives Beispiel, das ist diese Person, dieser Fall."

"I always notice the level of communication when it comes to positioning oneself as an institution. What you do positively is related to the institution and if something is negative, it is very person- or case-related. And I actually find that quite interesting in the sense that you say: OK, here is a positive example, this is our institution, this is a negative example, this is this person, this case."

Focus Group Good Scientific Practice

„Ich würde gerne ergänzen, dass eben zur Integrität auch gehört, dass ich nach denselben Kriterien kommuniziere, wie ich forsche. Also eben genauso selbstkritisch, genauso die Grenzen auch nach außen transparent mache, genauso versuche, unabhängig zu bleiben. Also das ist ja unsere Forderung, [...] die GWP muss sie sozusagen umschließen, die Kommunikation. Und bisher wird da sehr oft

noch einfach da getrennt: also ich bin Wissenschaftler und dann habe ich da meinen PR-Fuzzi, der macht da was Schönes draus."

"I would like to add that integrity also means that I communicate according to the same criteria as I do my research. In other words, being just as self-critical, making the limits just as transparent to the outside, and trying to remain just as independent. So that's our demand, [...] the [Good Scientific Practice] must, so to speak, encompass it, the communication. Until now, there has very often been a simple separation: so I'm a scientist and then I have my PR-guy who makes something nice out of it."

Focus Group University Communication

Extent and incentives for scientific misconduct

"Also Druck in allen Varianten. Zeit, Karrieredruck usw. Gerade auf höheren Karrierestufen: Zeitdefizit. Fächerkultur und damit verbundene Erwartungshaltung. Oder auch sprich klassisches Medizin-Klischee, vielleicht auch hohe starke Hierarchien, Abhängigkeiten durchgängig bis quasi zur finalen Karrierestufe und auch antizipierte Erwartungshaltungen sowie Kommunikation und die Konfliktkultur."

"Pressure of all kinds. Time, career pressure, etc. Especially at higher career levels: Time deficit. Particular cultures in disciplines and the associated expectations. Or the classical medical cliché, perhaps also strong hierarchies, dependencies right through to the final career stage, and also anticipated expectations as well as communication and the culture of conflict."

Focus Group Good Scientific Practice

"Ich meine, da müssen wir über Wettbewerb reden beim Thema Integrität. Also wir stehen unter einem starken, von außen angezogenen Wettbewerb. Der nicht generisch ist. Und der Wissenschaftler*innen natürlich zum Beispiel in Richtung Exzellenz treibt. [...] Aber der Wettbewerb bezieht sich ja auf alles, auch auf Drittmittel, auch auf Publikationen usw. Und natürlich gibt es da Anreize, eben gegen die gute wissenschaftliche Praxis zu verstoßen."

"I think we need to talk about competition when it comes to integrity. We are facing a strong competition, amplified from the outside. Which is not generic. And which naturally drives scientists towards excellence, for example. [...] And the competition relates to everything, including third-party funding, publications, etc. And of course, in this context, there are incentives to violate good scientific practice."

Focus Group University Communication

"Druck ist die sozial erwünschte Erklärung. Wir stehen alle unter Druck und deshalb finden wir es sehr nachvollziehbar, dass einem unter Druck Fehler passieren. Ich würde dann aber doch differenzieren zwischen den Fehlern und dem Fehlverhalten, und sagen, da ist dann der Druck eben vielleicht noch erklärungsfähig, aber nicht mehr legitimierend."

"Pressure is the socially desirable explanation. We are all under pressure and therefore we find it very understandable that mistakes happen under pressure. However, I would differentiate between mistakes and misconduct and say that [in the latter case], pressure can perhaps still be the explaining, but no longer be the legitimising argument."

Focus Group Good Scientific Practice

3.4 Attitudes towards social integration

The next section presents the main arguments and results of the participants' debate about social integration. As the term 'social integration' is difficult to directly translate in German, participants have been offered a definition in the beginning of the focus group, explaining that 'integration' is to be understood as the involvement of citizens and other stakeholders in the research process, comprising classical forms of participation but also all kinds of dialog-oriented science communication⁶.

Just as for research integrity, there were rather different approaches to the concept across the different groups. The group of university communicators had the most controversial discussion about social integration, its practical implementation ('what is actual participation?') and potential undesired consequences ('expectation management').

The group of research funders also critically discussed the concept of social integration but with a stronger focus on science communication. They further reflected on the question how the overall process of social integration could be improved to have a positive impact on the general relation of science and society, and to make it beneficial for both ('rethinking the entire concept of exchange').

The group of integrity officers had the least controversial discussion about social integration - maybe because of time constraints, as their debate about integrity had been long. Their view on the topic was mainly positive and their definition of it rather classical. Various forms of public engagement were seen as having a clear potential for increasing trust in science.

In the following, first different forms of social integration, namely dialog-oriented science communication and participative formats, such as citizen science are discussed (section 3.4.1). Then, and in more depth, the participants' main arguments regarding advantages and potentials of social integration but also its pitfalls and challenges are presented (section 3.4.2).

3.4.1 Forms of social integration

Even though the initial definition of social integration given to the participants also included the integration of other stakeholders, the focus of the participants' discussions in all three groups was citizens' involvement in the research process. Within the examples of social integration the participants discussed, one can differentiate between forms of dialog-oriented science communication and participative project, e.g. in the field of citizen science but also in medical research. The discussed forms of social integration are however only to be seen as

⁶ For reasons of readability, the term 'dialog-oriented science communication' is sometimes shortened to 'science communication' in this report. It is however always to be understood as communicative measures with a focus on interaction and exchange.

examples and not as an exhaustive list: as several participants underlined, there are countless formats of public engagement in the research process today.

Dialog-oriented science communication

When asked about different forms of communication, participants invoked a large range of formats that one could sum up under the concept of dialog-oriented science communication. Some of these examples were open house days of institutions, long nights of sciences, citizen/school universities, nights of museums, podcasts, social media activities, 'science in residence', open bars, scientists going into school classes, scientists visiting their hometowns, Fuckup Nights, and film series with panel discussions and questions from the audience. Additionally, innovative formats such as a 'true or fake' event were mentioned. During the latter, scientists discuss topics, and the audience needs to guess whether these are actually true. Such events might increase the critical thinking and questioning of the public. Social media is an important and difficult variable in dialog-oriented communication today. In the context here, it was however discussed entirely positively as a mean to invite people but to make the content of such events available afterwards as well.

Participants generally had a rather positive view on these formats. They perceived them as reaching many people and as an opportunity for scientists to present their own research, explain research processes, provide an insight into actual scientific work but also into topics such as Good Scientific Practice. They were also being described as a room for exchange with scientists one can ask questions to. Scientists in turn can use such events to receive feedback from the public. Through an increased transparency of the scientific process reached via such events, the latter could lead to a better public understanding of how science works. Through the personal contact established with scientists, public trust and a feeling of accessibility could be built.

However, also more critical points concerning formats of dialog-oriented science communication were discussed. Participants mentioned the sometimes kind of low involvement of the audience, without any lively discussions or an actual reflection of what the scientist tries to convey. From a more general point of view, it was emphasised that these events often 'preach to the converted' mainly attracting a public already interested in science. In order to reach all segments of the society, one needs to go towards them and not only wait them to come. This is meant physically, for example through activities in malls or city centres, houses of science, and also going into schools to reach the youngest generation.

From the scientists' perspective, science communication also has its difficulties: they are not trained to be communicators, they might not know how to reach which target group, and they often also experience a certain uncertainty in what they are allowed to communicate. For a long time, institutions were reluctant to anyone but their communication departments communicating, scientists were not allowed to do so. This has been change, something that can, on the one hand, be seen as a proof for the high trust institutions place in their scientists, but on the other hand, it also comes with new high responsibilities for the scientists.

Participation and citizen science

Another form of social integration going beyond formats of science communication are participative projects. The most often mentioned examples in this regard are citizen science projects and the participation of patients in medical research. Citizen science projects often exist in natural sciences, consisting of citizens' contributions for example to soil samples and the monitoring of animal species ('bird counting'). Another field in which the public is already very much involved in the research process, and which was also mentioned in several groups, is patient participation in medical research. One could however ask whether this is truly a form of participation. Indeed, one participant raised the necessity to differentiate between people's 'normal' involvement in research projects, particularly in medicine, psychology but also, for example, in case of interviews in social sciences, and actual participation.

Two other and newer forms of participation have also been discussed by participants, namely citizen committees and panels on the one and funding decisions for research projects taken by citizens ('playing DFG') on the other hand. Participants described a concrete case, in which a university organised a 'speed dating' of citizens with different research projects. There was money only for realising one of the projects and after the speed dating, citizens could decide which one of them would get the funding. This was perceived as a certainly stimulating but also very dangerous form of public participation in the research process (see 3.4.2).

As a last potential form of participation in the research process, participants also discussed donations and crowdfunding campaigns for research projects. A participant raised a concrete example of a research project in the medical field to develop an alternative therapy for a disease of the nervous system. As there was no public financial support and also no support of the pharma industry for the project, money was needed, and a crowdfunding campaign started. This was also perceived as a form of participation in and contribution to research.

To some extent - already visible in the different formats of participation invoked - there was disagreement in the groups about what 'participation' actually means. In one group, participants argued that participatory spaces in research projects can be either small or big, meaning that the participative dimension does not need to comprise the entire project. From this perspective, mainly discussed in the group of research funders, the most important objective of participation in the research process was perceived to be the mutual benefit of it - for the public, but also for science itself. For science, the objective of citizen science defined here was to make participation truly contribute to the research process. This means making citizens' knowledge and resources usable for research and encouraging the evolution of new research questions based on perspectives from the outside.

In the group of university communicators, on the other hand, it was underlined that 'participation' is a comprehensive process. It was underlined that it does not just involve 'using' citizens to collect data but that in its true form, it means to implicate them in all stages of the research project - from the definition of the research question to the communication of the results. In this form, participation is highly time-consuming and cost-intensive, which is why it does not happen often. These two approaches to participation have similar objectives in mind but imply different scopes of citizen involvement in individual projects.

3.4.2 What role for social integration?

As it has already become clear, formats of dialog-oriented science communication and participation have been discussed positively but also controversially in the focus groups. All participants agreed that integrating citizens in the research process is important and bears many chances, but they were also very aware of difficulties and challenges in this regard. The main arguments for both sides are presented in the following.

Chances of social integration

The most often mentioned chance of social integration in all focus groups was the increase of public understanding and trust through experiencing science oneself. Various forms of social integration can lead to an increased public knowledge about scientific findings but also scientific processes, something seen as crucial by the participants (see also 3.2.2). The personal contact to scientists can increase a feeling of closeness and relatability to science. Active participation in scientific projects, for example in citizen science, has also been proven to strengthen the feeling of self-efficacy among the participants.

The participants however also discussed advantages for science that emerge from involving citizens in the research process at various stages: Social integration makes it possible to include diverse perspectives in the research process and therefore enriches it from the outside. It enables totally new forms of studies and contributes to the advancement of science. It was underlined that citizen science is actual science and brings added value to science. It should not just be perceived as something 'one must do nowadays'. The participants of the research funders group underlined that this thought of participation being beneficial for science could and should be pushed forward even further by increasing the systematic collaboration

between science and citizens on a much larger scale. However, they also underlined that for this to happen, public trust in science – and in the scientific use of their data – must be very strong.

One participant in the group of university communicators compared the current development in social integration to the general opening of scientific institutions a few decades ago. At the time, universities were entirely governed by the president and some professors, who alone took all important decisions. With an increasing demand of co-determination rights, this has changed in many regards since then. In the same vein, the participant argued that to keep public trust in science, science needs to respond to demands of increased social integration – even if this cannot mean that the entire field of science should or would be organised in a participative way.

Challenges of social integration

Next to the many chances and opportunities social integration means for science and society alike, it also brings numerous challenges and difficulties, that have been discussed extensively in the focus groups.

The first and most practical aspect in this regard are **resources**, mainly time and money. While this has been primarily discussed from the perspective of scientists, it is equally true for most scientific institutions. Both are increasingly supposed to engage with the public (or other stakeholders), and this lack of resources applies to all forms of social integration. At first sight, mainly participatory research comes to mind as particularly resource-intensive, requiring lots of time and money to be designed, accompanied and evaluated. However, also formats of science communication need a lot of resources, which are already scarce in the life of scientists. Indeed, scientists are increasingly 'invited', but also expected to participate in these kinds of activities, but no one takes over any of their other obligations. Participants raised the question, *when* scientists are actually supposed to do communication – and even more good communication – next to teaching, conducting research, and fulfilling their administrative tasks. In this regard, the demand for a comprehensive recognition of science communication activities for researchers including the necessary institutional support was formulated (see chapter 4).

Another challenge for social integration could be summed up under the keyword **impact**. From a very general point of view, it was argued that there is a lack of studies on the impact that forms of social integration actually have, for example on public trust. Some participants expressed the feeling that formats such as open bar events only reach few – and already interested – people and do not have a systematic impact on society. In this regard, the question was raised how to reach 'the unreachable' and what formats one would need for that.

It was further argued that the impact of social integration can also be negative. In case of citizen science projects, participants might have the feeling of being 'used' when only involved in the data collecting process and this can lead to a loss of trust. For science communication formats, it was discussed that scientists are asked to engage in such activities on a voluntary basis and that it is generally always the same scientists who agree to participate. These are however not necessarily the ones who might be best suited for the task, as they might not have the appropriate training but also sometimes pass on stereotypes of their research disciplines, which is not desirable when aiming to improve the public image of science.

Impact is further important in the sense of who actually benefits from social integrity and in which way. It has been discussed that science communication and participative activities bear the chance of increasing closeness to science and strengthen a feeling of self-efficiency for the public. When being counted under the keyword 'participation', potential benefits are even higher or more concrete in medical research projects, where patients and society as a whole might actually come closer to a working therapy when participating in relevant projects. Nevertheless, these benefits do not come automatically with social integration, especially in the field of participation. They are difficult to achieve, and it must be ensured that participants of participative projects are taken seriously and are not only 'used' for data collection as this can lead to important frustration and also mistrust. On the other hand, science should also benefit from social integration with actual contributions to research projects in terms of data but also new perspectives and

reflections. This is not guaranteed in relevant projects either, they might cost more than they earn. It is therefore crucial to differentiate between good collaborative knowledge production between science and the public and 'pseudo participation processes'.

In this regard, participants discussed that social integration measures should be used in a meaningful way and not be imposed on each and every scientist and research project. It should become an integral part of the research process, meaning that the reflection on social integration should be part of every research project. However, it also needs to be possible that this reflection comes to the conclusion that, for example, it would not contribute to the project to communicate about its findings at an early stage. The group of research funders raised the important question, how to deal with this precise role of social integration - as an integral part of the research process, but without an obligation to do so because this would make it meaningless - for example in funding calls. Participants agreed that they wanted social integration to be a part of each funding application but in an appropriate and individually reflected way. Creating the right incentives for this to happen was identified as a difficult task for the funders. One participant emphasised that she sees science communication as a long way to go. She argued that a kind of trial-and-error process in this regard should be supported by funders as well - leading back to the argument of a necessary 'culture of error' also from this perspective.

The next challenge for social integration is the status of **scientific expertise**. Trust in science serves the need of complexity reduction in an ever more complex world. It means that we trust in scientific experts to have more knowledge on a specific topic than we do. Participants expressed the doubt that if all parts of a scientific project are partly done by laypeople - in contrast to scientists - now, why should people still believe in the need of scientific expertise? It is therefore very important to make clear, that even if everyone might be able to contribute to science in one way or another, not everyone directly becomes a scientist. It is crucial to uphold the status of scientific expertise, because if not, and if everyone thinks to know as much as scientific experts on a certain topic, this might ultimately be detrimental for public trust in science. The 'loss of authority' of science comes to mind here again (see 3.2.1).

This reflection on the importance of scientific expertise in the scientific process also applies to decisions about scientific funding: entrusting citizens with making decisions in this regard would imply that they actually know what research is needed and how particular research objectives can be achieved. Participants expressed that this could be dangerous and that long-developed institutions, guidelines, and expertise are needed for this.

The last challenges for social integration are its own **limits**, and very closely related to that, public **expectations** that might come with an increased overall process of social integration.

The idea of citizens making funding decisions, but also deciding on research questions, methods etc. bears a risk for academic freedom and is, in its most extreme form, in contrast with the idea of independent research which is crucial for research integrity (see 3.3.1). If, for example, the public decides on what research is conducted, how can one ensure that the decision has been taken based on reflections for the common good? Should research not be independent from outside influence? Participants raised these questions but underlined at the same time, that research is obviously not independent today, either: it needs to reply to funding calls which set the agenda of the next framework programme etc. However, the current selection process in funding decisions is mainly based on peer-review and therefore at least on an inner scientific mechanism (even if this is not without its difficulties either, see 3.3.2). Additionally, not all kinds of research and research disciplines are suitable for participation. Basic research ("Grundlagenforschung"), for example, is as important as applied research but does not offer the same opportunities for social integration. This is totally fine as such, as social integration should be implemented only where it makes sense, but these differentiations need to be emphasised stronger in the public discourse.

Participants agreed that social integration cannot comprise the entire scientific process and all scientific decisions at all times. They underlined that it is crucial to emphasise and be clear about such limits of integration from the beginning in order to avoid fuelling false public expectations towards science (which are already

a problem from another perspective, see 3.2.2). In making publicity for formats of citizen science for example, participants expressed the fear that citizens might develop the expectation to become a decisive actor in all research processes and projects, and that they might start claiming this influence beyond what research is able to offer. Media might function as a fuelling source in this regard. As stated before, an overall integration of citizens in the research process is not possible, but if such expectations emerge in the public and they are not met, this might lead, once again, to strong frustration and mistrust, but also even to active resistance against research projects. This does not mean that active resistance against research projects is something negative as such. One participant just expressed the fear that the claim to be involved gets a systematic dimension and that no research decision can be taken without such (unfounded) resistance anymore.

In the same way as research integrity, social integration proves to be a complex topic with many different dimensions to consider when reflecting on its potential influence on trust in science. It might be even more controversial than research integrity, as pushing it forward was not seen as entirely desirable in especially one of the focus groups.

In the discussion about different forms of social integration, comprising forms of dialog-oriented science communication and participation, both with its advantages and pitfalls, it became clear that there is no positive influence of social integration on public trust in science per se. The influence it might have depends strongly on the organisation and framework conditions of integration measures. Spaces of exchange between science and the public and personal contacts can increase trust. Participants – also the critical ones – agreed that increased social integration is needed in today's society, but that the implementation as a comprehensive and still to some extent limited process is very difficult. Social integration should also be beneficial for science itself and not exclusively be directed towards the benefit of the public.

However, if done 'wrong' and not handled well, social integration might also backfire and ultimately be detrimental for trust in science. This concerns pseudoparticipation processes, in which citizens are only used as data collectors⁷, a decrease in the recognition of actual scientific expertise that might follow from 'too much participation' and citizen science, as well as false and unreachable public expectations concerning their involvement in all kinds of scientific decisions.

Participants in all focus groups agreed that social integration, such as research integrity, need to become more than an 'add-on' but an integral part of the research process. But they also underlined that this implies to think and rethink these concepts comprehensively. To successfully implement social integration as an integral part of science it would need big changes in the scientific system, the political approach to science, and also in the public thinking.

3.4 Attitudes towards social integration

Forms of social integration

⁷ There is an interesting parallel to the discussions in the public deliberative workshop here, which took place in Berlin in June 2023 in the frame of the POIESIS project.

"[...] ich finde auch die Räume, in denen dann über Wissenschaft ins Gespräch gekommen werden kann, total wichtig. [...] Und das finde ich auch einen Raum, der zum Vertrauen in Wissenschaft beitragen kann. Wenn ich die Erfahrung mache, dass Personen dahinterstehen, ich kann die befragen auf ihre Annahmen hin usw. Ich kann etwas erfahren über die Prozesse."

"[...] I also think the spaces in which people can talk about science are really important. [...] And I also perceive this as a space that can contribute to trust in science. When I experience that there are people behind it, I can question them about their assumptions and so on. I can learn something about the processes."

Focus Group Research Funding Organisations

"Und Partizipation ist ja mehr als nur Daten für Menschen zu sammeln. Wenn der Mensch nur als Forschungsobjekt genutzt wird, das ist ja keine Partizipation. Partizipation ist, wenn Menschen an der Fragestellung in einem Projekt teilhaben, an der Methodik teilhaben, an der Datenauswertung teilhaben, an den Interpretationen zu Daten. Braucht natürlich abhängig vom Fach enorme Fachkenntnis."

"And participation is more than just collecting data for people. If people are only used as research objects, that's not participation. Participation is when people are involved in the research question of a project, involved in the methodology, involved in the data analysis, involved in the interpretation of the data. Of course, depending on the subject, this requires enormous expertise."

Focus Group University Communication

"Das, was bei Citizen Science ja wirklich der relevante Aspekt ist, ist es das Wissen der Vielen letztlich produktiv nutzbar machen für den wissenschaftlichen Erkenntnisprozess. [Es wäre wichtig], dass eben genau die Frage am Anfang steht, was denn das Erkenntnisinteresse und das Ziel des kommunikativen Austauschs-Akt ist, sage ich mal. Und idealerweise ist es ja nicht irgendwie nur was, das man eben auch noch mit erledigen muss, sondern weil es hoffentlich auch vielleicht ja Forschungsfragen letztlich evozieren kann oder durch interessante Rückfragen Aspekte reinbringt, die vorher nicht so gesehen worden sind."

"What the truly relevant aspect of citizen science is, is that it ultimately makes the knowledge of the many productively usable for the scientific process. [It would be important], I would say, that the initial question was precisely what the research interest and the goal of the communicative exchange act are. And ideally, it's not just something that you have to do, but [something you do] because it can hopefully evoke research questions or bring in aspects through interesting questions that were not previously seen in this way."

Focus Group Research Funding Organisations

What role for social integration?

"Ja, also auf jeden Fall ein Verständnis für den Wissenschaftsprozess, also wie Wissenschaft funktioniert."

"Yes, definitely an understanding of the scientific process, i.e. how science works."

Focus Group Good Scientific Practice

"Eröffnung von Perspektiven. Ich glaube, da kommen diverse Perspektiven mit rein, die vielleicht so nicht auf dem Schirm gewesen sind."

"Opening up perspectives. I think various perspectives come into play that may not have been on the screen before."

Focus Group Good Scientific Practice

"Es gibt doch Entwicklungen in der Wissenschaft, die eigentlich zu mehr Kollaboration führen müssen, damit sie Wissenschaft vorantreiben."

"There are developments in science that MUST actually lead to more collaboration in order to drive science forward."

Focus Group Research Funding Organisations

"Also, wenn wir jetzt von Partizipation reden, ist es ja mehr als nur Kommunikation oder Dissemination. Da brauchen dann die Hochschullehrenden noch mal neben der Kommunikationsfähigkeit noch mal ein ganz anderes Training. Ich will damit sagen:

wie viel Jobs wollen wir denn den Profs noch aufdrücken? [...] Alles zusammen werden wir nicht leisten können."

"I mean, when we talk about participation now, then this is much more than just communication or dissemination. In addition to communication skills, university lecturers would need completely different training for this. I'm saying: how many more jobs do we want to impose on the professors? [...] We won't be able to do everything together."

Focus Group University Communication

"Die Erfahrung ist: Man spricht ein sehr akademisches Klientel an, das sowieso schon...also das ist ‚preaching to the converted‘ sozusagen. Und ich sehe noch nicht, wie man da so richtig rauskommt. Das ist eine andere Frage. Wahrscheinlich sind diese Bildungsprogramme noch am ehesten der Ansatz. Also ein Junior Campus. Also näher in die Schulen reingehen, da wo die Entscheidung noch nicht getroffen ist, ob jemand akademisch geprägt wird oder nicht. [...] Alle anderen Programme sehe ich sehr kritisch. Die haben viel mit Marketing zu tun und relativ wenig mit gesellschaftlicher Wirkung."

"The experience is: You appeal to a very academic clientele that is already...this is ‚preaching to the converted‘, so to speak. And I don't see how we can really get out of that, yet. That's another question. Probably, these educational programmes are the best approach. For example, a junior campus. In other words, going more into the schools, where the decision has not yet been made as to whether or not someone will be academically shaped. [...] I am very critical of all other programmes. They have a lot to do with marketing and relatively little with social impact."

Focus Group Good Scientific Practice

"Ich glaube, wenn wir über öffentliche Beteiligung, Citizen Science was auch immer reden, ist mir ganz wichtig dann auch zu akzeptieren, es gibt Expertinnen und Expertentum, um das wir ja auch nicht drum herumkommen. Also wir können ganz viel versuchen, Disziplinen zu erklären oder der Bevölkerung klarzumachen, wo sie sich beteiligen kann. Es gibt dann [aber trotzdem] auch noch Gründe, warum in manchen Spezialdisziplinen Leute sich 20 Jahre spezialisieren, um dann erst auch Forschung voranbringen zu können."

"I think that when we talk about public engagement, citizen science, whatever, an important point for me is to accept that there are experts and expertise, and that we cannot do without that. Of course, we can extensively try to explain disciplines or make it clear to the public where they can participate. But there are still reasons why people specialise in some disciplines for 20 years in order to then be able to advance research in this field."

Focus Group Research Funding Organisations

"Manchmal habe ich den Eindruck, dass wir uns selber schaden. Mit zu viel. Mit der Idee, dass eine umfassende Partizipation eigentlich auch nur Gutes sein kann. Weil ganz ehrlich, niemand kann in der Art von Wissenschaft, wie wir sie jetzt betreiben heutzutage, [niemand] kann da irgendwie mitreden. Das ist unheimlich schwierig. Also keine Chance. Und so zu tun, als könnten wir das, was ja einige Formate irgendwie auch suggerieren, finde ich sehr schwierig."

"Sometimes I have the impression that we harm ourselves. With too much. With the idea that comprehensive participation can actually only be a good thing. Because quite honestly, nobody can have any say or participate in the kind of science we do nowadays. It's incredibly difficult. There's no chance. And I find it very difficult when some [participative] formats somehow suggest that we can."

Focus Group University Communication

"Erwartungsmanagement. Also die Erwartung, einbezogen zu werden bei Themen, die ist ja heute schon da. Und die füttern wir natürlich auch damit. Das färbt ab, auch auf andere. ‚Wir sind ja nie gefragt worden.‘ ‚Wir haben es aus der Zeitung erfahren, dass er da jetzt ein Maushaus baut, dass er da jetzt mit Gen- weiß ich nicht Genmais rummacht‘ usw."

"Expectation management. I mean, the expectation of being involved in issues is already there today. And, of course, we also feed it [with by pushing for more participation]. That rubs off, also on others. ‚We've never been asked.‘ ‚We found

out from the newspaper that he's now building a mouse house there, that he's now, I don't know, messing around with genetically modified maize', etc."

Focus Group University Communication

"Wir haben eine wahnsinnige Angst davor, die Wissenschaftsfreiheit darüber irgendwie zu verlieren, die uns ja super heilig ist, dass wir aus der Wissenschaft selber die Fragestellungen generieren. Aber die ist ja eh schon perdu durch die ganzen Anreizsysteme. Also ,es ist ja alles freiwillig'. Du kannst es mit freiwilligen Themen machen, wenn mal irgendwo Geld über ist - dann machen wir halt so ein Partizipationsformat."

"We are terrified of somehow losing our academic freedom, which we hold so sacred, meaning that we generate questions from within science itself. But that's already gone anyway because of all the incentive systems. Of course, 'it's all voluntary'. Yes, you can do voluntary topics if there's money left over somewhere - and then we'll just do a participative format."

Focus Group University Communication

3.5 Other themes

In two of the focus groups, the group of university communicators and research funders, two additional topics had an important influence on the discussion throughout the debate. These were the relation between science and politics on the one, and science and industry on the other hand. Interestingly, these two topics were also discussed as crucial influencing factors for trust in science in the POIESIS public deliberative workshop, organised with a group of citizens in Berlin in June 2023. Without aiming to develop the arguments on these topics in too much detail, they were important enough in the discussion to be sketched here shortly.

3.5.1 Science and Politics

With the increased relevance of scientific findings in everyday life (see also 3.2.2), scientific findings have also increasingly found their way into political decision-making - or at least, this process has become increasingly visible. Many political decisions are triggered or to some extent influenced by scientific findings. This has a strong and direct influence on people's daily lives and social transformations and might be perceived by some as limiting their freedom to some extent. There are three main aspects that have been discussed in the focus groups in this regard, mostly in the group of university communicators:

First of all, it has been noted that the process of scientific policy advice is, at least in Germany, not transparent at all and therefore fuels mistrust among the public but also fellow scientists. Which expert is consulted when, why and based on which legitimisation?

Once asked to provide policy advice, scientists are often instrumentalised by politics. Pursuing the objective to legitimise the own decisions with scientific expertise, politicians however want to hear only opinions desirable to their political interest. And in case that political decisions turn out to be controversial or facing important public opposition, the responsibility is quickly assigned to science and scientists. This phenomenon is particularly strong in situations of strong scientific uncertainty, such as in the coronavirus pandemic but not alone. Finally, one can also observe that the spheres of politics and science get increasingly mixed up in the public discourse: political demands and political activism often refer to scientific arguments, in turn making science and scientists the target for attacks by political opponents. Another challenge in this regard are political actors who specifically promote the delegitimisation and instrumentalisation of science. "Merchants of doubt" have been mentioned in this context, applying however not only to political but also all other kinds of actors, for example from industry.

Another consequence of the increasing intermingling of science and politics and a rather recent development in Germany is the expectation of scientific institutions

to position themselves politically. This point has been raised several times by the university communicators who are currently very often confronted with this topic in their daily professional life. They describe the universities as struggling and 'driven' in this regard and expressed the impression that communications going 'wrong' in this context could affect the overall reputation of the institution (see also 3.2.1).

3.5.2 Science and Industry

The second cross-sectional topic discussed in the focus groups was the relation of science and industry. It has however been approached from two very different perspectives: on the one hand, science-industry relation were discussed very critically in the sense that there might be interest-led influence on research from the outside, for example in form of lobbyism etc., and that the plagiarism industry puts scientific institutions under pressure for reasons that are not related to the common good; on the other hand, it was discussed from the perspective that collaborations between science and industry should be increased because only through comprehensive cooperation, society's current challenges can be tackled.

While the first point is a rather common argument and has also been analysed in various studies (see deliverable D1.2 for more details on trust in industry research and section 3.3.2 of this report for a short discussion on the role of the plagiarism industry in Germany), the main arguments in favour of a stronger collaboration between science and industry shall be discussed here to some more extent.

The opinion in favour of more cooperation between industry and science has been raised in the group of research funders who expressed that science might miss out on crucial developments and risks to be left behind when it does not cooperate with industrial actors. Indeed, important technological and societal innovations are developed in the industrial sector and not in academia. An example for this is ChatGPT, but similar evolutions can also be observed in the field of life sciences, genetic food etc. Additionally, many topics need both, the more theoretical expertise of academia and the more applied expertise of the industry to reach reliable and successful research findings. Therefore, such collaboration should be fostered instead of avoided. Especially the scientific sector still hesitates to reach out for cooperation with the industry - obviously because they are afraid to be confronted with increasing public mistrust if they do so. In this sense, some participants in the group of research funders clearly called for an increased cooperation between science and industry at eye level and on a basis of transparency, mutual trust, and benefit. This would however imply that industry-based research also adhered to standards of responsible research practice and increased its efforts in the fields of social integration. This might lead to an increased public trust in this sector and would therefore also favour the framework conditions for an increased cooperation of science and industry.

3.5 Other themes

Science and Politics

"Ja, also einerseits trägt Wissenschaft ihre Erkenntnisse in die Politik rein und dann wird es kompliziert und umgekehrt. Wenn Politik dann auf den Campus kommt, wird es auch nicht gerade konfliktfrei."

"Yes, on the one hand science carries its findings into politics and then it gets complicated and vice versa. When politics comes to the campus, it's not exactly conflict-free either."

Focus Group Research Funding Organisations

"[Es gibt ja] im politischen Prozess mittlerweile Akteure, die ganz aktiv so eine Delegitimierung der Wissenschaft betreiben, aus unterschiedlichen Gründen, beispielsweise weil die Erkenntnisse der Wissenschaft unliebsam sind. Oder weil man halt sich nicht vorschreiben lassen möchte, was naheliegende Handlungsoptionen"

für die Politik wären. Und das hat eine neue Qualität bekommen. [...] Und die Wissenschaft hat schlecht darauf reagiert. Also die ist nicht geschlossen aufgetreten, sondern hat sich da auch treiben lassen. Und das hat, denke ich, dazu geführt, dass es einen Vertrauensverlust schon feststellbar gibt."

"[There are] actors in the political process who are now actively delegitimising science for various reasons, for example because the scientific findings are unpopular. Or simply because one doesn't want to be told what the obvious options for political action would be. And that has taken on a new quality. [...] And science has reacted badly to this. It didn't act united but allowed itself to be driven. And I think that has led to a noticeable loss of trust."

Focus Group University Communication

"Also ich glaube, dass es auch mittlerweile in der Öffentlichkeit einfach auch verwechselt wird. Was macht eigentlich die Wissenschaft oder was machen wissenschaftliche Bereiche und was macht die Politik oder was machen politische Bereiche? Also ich glaube, dass Personen, die jetzt keinen Bezug zur Wissenschaft haben - so wie wir oder halt auch weniger, aber trotzdem noch irgendwie einordnen können und auch wissen, was sind eigentlich Akademien, was machen Unis - dass die das vielleicht auch wirklich mittlerweile durcheinanderbringen? Und das ist alles dann irgendwie eins. Und wenn sie dann irgendwie gerade unzufrieden sind mit der Ampelregierung und dann steht da ein Wissenschaftler daneben, dann wird das sozusagen alles irgendwie vermischt."

"So, I believe that both are actually often confounded and intermingled in public discourse. What does science actually do or what do scientific fields do, and what does politics do or what do political fields do? I think that people who have no connection to science - like us or even less, but who can still somehow categorise it and also know what academies actually are, what universities do - that they might really get increasingly confused now? And it's all somehow one single thing. And if they are then somehow dissatisfied with the [current] government and then there is an academic standing next to them, then it is all getting mixed up somehow."

Focus Group University Communication

Science and Industry

„In dieser Zusammenarbeit zwischen Wirtschaft und Wissenschaft gibt es auch immer so [...] eine Zögerlichkeit auf der Wissenschaftsseite. Einerseits wissen sie, man muss mit den Unternehmen zusammenarbeiten, bei bestimmten Dingen, gerade in der Gesundheitsforschung ja, also ohne die Zusammenarbeit mit Unternehmen können Sie ja keine Medizinprodukte entwerfen. Aber andererseits ist das immer auch so ein bisschen ‚bäh‘. Und immer, wenn dann irgendwie ein Skandal aufkommt, dann meldet sich die Wissenschaft und sagt: ‚oh ja, das ist die Wirtschaft‘. Aber dass man diese Kooperation dann auch offensiv verfolgt, das passiert ja auch nicht. Das gehört aber auch zur Frage von Integrität und Proaktivität usw.“

"In this collaboration between industry and science, there is always [...] a hesitancy on the scientific side. On the one hand, they know that they have to work with companies on certain things, especially in the health sector, I mean, they can't design medical products without working with companies. But on the other hand, it's always also a bit 'ugh'. And whenever a scandal somehow arises, science says: 'oh yes, that's the industry'. But pursuing such cooperation proactively, this does not happen. And that is also part of the question of integrity and proactivity, etc."

Focus Group Research Funding Organisations

„Dieses Gefühl, du sagtest eben so: ‚ah, das ist so ein bisschen bäh‘, so etwas wird mit einer gewissen Skepsis letztlich verfolgt. Aber die Themen sind ja letztlich ganz, ganz ähnlich. Und wenn ich noch mal daran anknüpfe, dass wir eben ja für diese großen Herausforderungen in der Transformation letztlich alle Sphären

brauchen, ist, glaube ich, eben eine Haltung, die von mehr Kollaboration geprägt ist, da tatsächlich entscheidend und führt dann wiederum auch, glaube ich, zu mehr Vertrauen."

"This feeling, you just said: 'ah, that's a bit ough', something like that [science-industry cooperations] is pursued always with a certain degree of scepticism. But the topics at stake are actually very, very similar. And if I go back to the fact that we ultimately need all spheres for these major challenges in the transformation, I believe that an attitude characterised by more collaboration is actually crucial and, in turn, will lead to more trust."

Focus Group Research Funding Organisations

4 Recommendations on Trust in Science

The following chapter presents the recommendations participants have made during the debates in the three focus groups. They have not necessarily been made towards the end of the focus group when the precise question about recommendations was asked, but already throughout the entire discussion before.

The recommendations are structured along target groups - most of them concern scientific institutions and their umbrella organisations (section 4.1), some recommendations have been formulated addressed to other stakeholders, namely research funding organisations and politics (section 4.2), and finally, there are also some short recommendations for scientists themselves (section 4.3) with the aim to contribute to strengthening trust in science in view of research integrity and social integration. Some of the recommendations directly address either integrity or integration, but others are more overarching and apply to both.

After an extensive analysis of the discussions throughout the focus groups (chapter 3), the recommendations aim to be as precise and short as possible. The relevant arguments and context information can all be found in the analysis.

4.1 Trust in Science: what scientific institutions⁸ should do

Many participants observe a decreasing trust in institutions in Germany today, not necessarily addressed to scientific institutions in the first place but having an impact on them as well. Such a decrease of trust in institutions is not only noticeable in the public but also among scientists themselves, which is why the following recommendations clearly also have the latter's perspective in mind.

For integrity as much as integration, participants agreed that comprehensive approaches are needed in order to make a lasting and more than superficial change, which is why they recommend developing a culture of integrity but also a comprehensive concept of integration within and beyond individual institutions. Before going more into detail about how these should look like, in all focus groups, one crucial cross-sectional recommendation has been made, that is the basis of all institutional change: a self-reflexive and coherent self-definition process.

1) Be self-reflexive and coherent in your self-definition process!

⁸ Scientific institutions are to be understood as research-performing institutions in the following.

Institutions should systematically reflect on themselves and their role. They need to develop a strong and comprehensive vision and attitude of who they want to be and which role they want to play in society - kind of a 'corporate identity' with anchoring values that all members of the institutions can represent confidently. Once they have entered this continuous process, institutions would and should no longer allow themselves to drift or be driven but find an appropriate way of dealing with challenges and also mistakes, and act in a self-determined manner. Such a process needs to be supported and lived by everyone in the institution, in case of a university from the student to the president. Values and norms of the institution must be upheld by everyone - and also defended together from the outside. This implies for example clear support for the own members in case of attacks or allegations.

2) Implement a 'culture of integrity'!

To successfully and sustainably deal with topics related to research integrity and Good Scientific Practice at institutions, there is a need develop a comprehensive culture of integrity. Such a culture of integrity implies a continuous reflexive process that needs to permeate all institutional levels. Different dimensions and structures of the institutions are affected by a comprehensive culture of integrity, but it is important to think them all together, not separately from one another.

Ensure independence.

One of the crucial elements of research integrity is independence - financial and also ideological independence. Independence needs to be maintained, even under pressure, and protected against intervention from the outside, for example in the defence of sound scientific findings against political influencing.

Live transparency.

Transparency is another crucial element of research integrity. It applies to power structures within institutions but also to research processes in general, doubts, errors, and failures. Regarding the latter, it is essential that when engaging in science communication activities, not only research findings, but also the research process and potential scientific uncertainties are communicated. It is however equally important that such transparency is also encouraged within institutions without fear of reputation or career losses in case of mistakes or failures. Transparency must be lived in external relations with society and stakeholders as much as to the inside within the institution.

Communicate pro-actively - externally and internally.

Another aspect of a comprehensive culture of integrity with an external and internal dimension is pro-active communication. To the outside, actively engaging in discussions and showing self-reflexion about the own decisions and acts can counter attempts of instrumentalisation. It might also reinforce the public's believe in scientific expertise by acting against the image of science as a passive, uncertain and driven system.

However, pro-active communication is also crucial to the inside: institutions need to create room for open, continuous exchange and open up spaces to work on problems on its roots instead of trying to conceal its consequences. In the particular case of scientific misconduct, institutions should not (only) show an attitude of minimising the damage but proactively and systematically address mistakes and learn from them. An actual and working 'culture of error' should be lived internally and externally, serving as a role model for others.

Provide your employees with the necessary tools.

Implementing a culture of integrity does not only mean to pursue certain norms and values but also to provide the own members with the necessary tools to be able to act in accordance with this culture. The most important aspect in this regard is continuous, career-long training and education programmes for students, scientists, but also other professionals working in the institution, such as communicators. It is essential to also include the executive and management level in this regard,

which is often particularly reluctant to participate in training but have the most important function as role models within the institutions. Awareness and prevention are the most important objectives that should be pursued by the institutions. Beyond that, it is however also necessary to implement clear guidelines, codes of conduct and structures that allow for these guidelines to be followed: qualified contact persons for counselling, but also clear consequences and sanctions in case of misconduct applied systematically and in a transparent way. Regarding research integrity, the academic internal self-control mechanism might not always be sufficient, therefore there should be a system-wide debate about external quality control and monitoring mechanisms in science.

Once again, the most important aspect on the way to a culture of research integrity is that the different dimensions are thought and tackled comprehensively and at all levels of each individual institutions and that institutions also work together in this.

3) Implement a comprehensive concept of social integration!

The need for a comprehensive approach is not limited to research integrity but equally applies to social integration. Integration should not be seen as an add-on or a nice-to-have, but as an integral part of scientific work and the further development of the system of science. This can be seen from several perspectives: from the public perspective, it is for example essential not to misuse participation as a way of obtaining cheap data collectors. In order to avoid this from happening, one however needs to take over the scientists' perspective: institutions need to develop - and implement - a comprehensive concept of social integration providing scientists with the necessary knowledge and resources to engage in a sustainable and meaningful process of social integration. There is no 'one size fits all' approach in social integration.

Provide systematic qualification and training.

For all forms of social integration (science communication, participation and all in-between) to be improved, there needs to be more training and qualification methods for researchers. This involves communication training, but also learning about the definition of objectives, target groups, evaluations, and the various ways one can involve citizens and other stakeholders in the own research process. Such training should be updated continuously and - once again an important emphasis - offered to scientists at all stages of their career.

Recognise and support the effort.

For social integration to work and to become an integral and constantly reflected part of the research process, scientists need to be equipped with the necessary resources, time, and money. Engaging in social integration needs to be recognised as part of the scientific work, therefore it should be evened with the scientists' obligations in research and teaching.

Prizes for good communication and comparable incentives are indeed nice-to-have. What is actually needed, though, are more systematic incentives for scientists to 'invest' in social integration, most importantly the recognition of social integration efforts in the dominant academic reputation system. Investing resources and energy into science communication and participative projects needs to pay off in the career. One institution cannot act alone on this, it is the umbrella organisations that need to work together in this regard.

Recognising efforts with regard to social integration does however not mean making it mandatory. Participation in particular is not possible and also not desirable in all scientific projects at all times. The tricky part of social integration is to ensure that it becomes an integral part of each reflection on the scientific process of a project but without mandatory requirements of how it should look like.

Collaborate.

One important objective of social integration is common knowledge production. There is an important need for more joint and systematic collaborations for knowledge production within the system of science but also with actors outside the system.

This implies involving citizens in the research process, but it also means the integration of other stakeholders, for example associations, industrial actors, journalists etc.

Part of this collaborative thought is also to make research more accessible: institutions should foster open access publications and provide help and support for their members in this process.

Just like for research integrity, it is crucial to act on these different aspects together and in a comprehensive way. The different fields - e.g. transfer, participation and science communication - should be thought together in a holistic way to make social integration a success for all involved: citizens, stakeholders, scientists, and institutions alike.

4) Be a good employer!

When working towards the implementation of a culture of integrity and a comprehensive concept of social integration, institutions must keep the interests of their members in mind. This implies providing them with the necessary institutional structures and support to adhere to rules of Good Scientific Practice and to develop measures of social integration. But it also means to protect the own members, and particularly scientists, from external attacks - a topic which has become more important than ever in recent years.

'Being a good employer' is crucial because only with the actual support of the institutions' members, research integrity and social integration can become a living reality. Institutions and their executives need to act as role-models and live and work up to high standards - in research but also in communication and administration.

5) Work together across institutions!

Most of the recommendations made above can be addressed by individual institutions for a start. The most crucial element for them to be successful in developing a culture of integrity and a comprehensive concept of social integration is however working together across institutions. Such cooperation is particularly relevant for scientific institutions as scientists move in-between institutions and in order for integrity- and integration- incentives to work, the latter must exist and be recognised across all institutions.

Institutions need to stand and work together closely as a system of science that wants to improve itself. One single actor cannot change a culture.

In Germany, this represents a big challenge as institutional structures in its federal system are particularly complex, but there are ways to cooperate and take common decisions that need to be explored further.

4.2 Trust in Science: what politics and funders should do

Not only scientific institutions need to work towards a culture of integrity and a comprehensive approach of social integration, but other institutional stakeholders - among them political and research funding institutions - play an important role in this process, too.

1) Foster life-long learning opportunities on science!

A crucial variable for citizens being able to trust in science - and also even being able to recognise efforts in regard to integrity and integration that might increase trust - is knowledge about the way science works. The pre-condition to understand what scientific findings are able to provide, the meaning of scientific uncertainties, the necessity of academic actors collaborating with non-academic actors, and also the limits of social integration ('expectation management') is a basic understanding about the scientific method and science as a system. Therefore, it is crucial to implement the inclusion of such knowledge in school curricula - the only moment in life when all societal groups can be reached simultaneously - but

also foster life-long learning opportunities in this regard. Politics plays a crucial role in this regard, but research funding organisations can also contribute to this process by supporting relevant initiatives.

2) Live up to your own expectations!

In public discourse, institutional stakeholders beyond scientific institutions are often quick to request the latter to act and take initiatives in regard to research integrity and social integration. That is however not enough. Other stakeholders, such as political and also research funding institutions, need to integrate the same norms and values, the same principles in their daily work as scientific institutions. Not only 'science' is affected by issues related to integrity, integration and especially trust, but many other actors play an important role in this regard as well. The same recommendations made for scientific institutions therefore apply to other institutional stakeholders as well.

In addition to that, research funding organisations should be aware of their subjective perspective when making decisions and be self-reflexive on the processes of funding allocations. Their actions and decisions should also be directed towards the reduction of inequalities and an increase of diversity in science. Political institutions need to have the same reflections in mind, but additionally need to actually allow for a lasting cultural change by amending relevant legislation such as Higher Education Acts at the federal and national level.

3) Encourage a 'culture of error'!

The pressure on scientists and also scientific institutions is high. External funding is needed in order to realise most innovative research projects. To obtain funding, in form of grants, excellence initiatives⁹ etc., scientists and institutions need to perform and need to succeed in their performance. The criteria for this performance are very strict and create a climate of continuous and strong competition in the entire academic sphere. Aiming to achieve a true culture of integrity and a comprehensive concept of social integration, institutional stakeholders need to encourage a 'culture of error' and integrate it in their funding requirements.

This means on the one hand to encourage new and innovative formats and research projects with no guarantee whether they will work. Innovation can only be achieved when walking new paths. However, it must be acceptable that these might lead nowhere in the end. At the same time, the pressure of performance in regard to publishing, teaching and conducting research must be altered in a way that scientists are allowed to have doubts and make mistakes. These should be discussed openly and constructively in order to either learn from them or sometimes also just leave them behind.

Actual and conscious scientific misconduct however needs clear consequences, in which institutional stakeholders from outside academia need to support universities and other scientific institutions.

4) Integrate a reflexive and comprehensive concept of social integration in funding calls!

In order to realise a comprehensive approach to social integration as an integral part of the reflection on each research project, the concept must be mapped accordingly in all kinds of funding calls. This means that there should not be 'additional' funds for measures of science communication in calls, but that reflections on science communication and social integration more generally should be required as part of every project proposal. There should also be possibilities to ask for financial support for training and qualification measures in funding calls. Projects for which the involvement of citizens or other stakeholders does not make sense must not be punished for this, but an increased innovative thinking towards more social integration should be fostered.

Additionally, public and private funding initiatives should not only concentrate on increasing the involvement of citizens but also other stakeholders in the research

⁹ For more details on the so-called Excellence Strategy in Germany, see: https://www.bmbf.de/bmbf/en/academia/excellence-strategy/excellence-strategy_node.html.

process. Collaborations between scientists, institutions and all kind of societal but also economic actors should be encouraged. This would lead to an increase in the scope of project applications and also increase diversity in science in a larger sense.

Just like for scientific institutions, it is obviously great to have (financial) recognition for good science communication or successful participatory projects, for example in form of prizes. Comprehensive support for structural change is even more needed, though.

4.3 Trust in Science: what scientists should do

The clear focus of the recommendations formulated here is on the institutional level. However, scientists themselves can equally contribute to the success of research integrity and social integration and to increased public trust in science as well. As for all institutional recommendations before, the following recommendations are based on the fundamental assumption that scientists are willing to adhere to standards of Good Scientific Practice and are at least interested in measures of social integration.

1) Dare to communicate!

Social integration is the most direct way for scientists to enter into interaction with the public and such interaction is crucial for public trust. Therefore, there is a lot of responsibility on scientists' shoulders in this regard. Nevertheless, scientists should start and try. By engaging with the public, scientists are able to contribute to a more realistic and diverse image of science, showing that research is more than 'the old white man in the lab coat'. In their communicative activities, scientists should include information about the scientific process behind their findings, reflections, methods, and uncertainties. It is also crucial to make clear that there is not one science but many sciences.

2) Train yourself continuously!

Social integration and research integrity are difficult and complex topics. For science communication, for example, one needs to know how to affectively address target groups, how to transparently but not confusingly talk about scientific uncertainties etc.; for participative projects one needs to be able to reflect on when and how involving citizens and other stakeholders in the research process is useful and how to do it. Regarding research integrity, current standards and guidelines may change, it is not always obvious what is expected from one as a scientist, technological developments such as AI mean new challenges and new ways of working that one needs to adapt to. Continuous training and qualification are crucial in order to navigate these challenges - at all stages of a scientist's career.

3) Collaborate!

Collaboration is not only crucial for institutions but also individual scientists. One cannot save the world alone. Scientists should seek for more collaboration in all directions. Many chances and opportunities lie in working together with people from other scientific disciplines but also from outside academia, for example societal stakeholders and economic actors.

4) Seek support!

Just like one is not able to save the world alone, one should also not try to improve it on their own. Aiming to implement standards of research integrity and a comprehensive concept of social integration in their work, scientists need support and should seek for it.

Regarding integrity, in case scientists have doubts about applicable rules or appropriate behaviour, they should reach out to the institution's research integrity officer or someone in a comparable position. In case they are hindered to adhere to rules of Good Scientific Practice by supervisors or they observe scientific misconduct, they should not remain silent about it but seek support within or also outside the institution.

In relation to social integration, scientists should try to get advice when being unsure, for example about how to successfully realise a participative project or how to perform activities of science communication. Beyond that, and very importantly, scientists should also seek support in case they are victim of an attack, for example following any kind of public statement. Help can be provided within the own institutions but also from the outside as there are more and more projects to support scientists that have been victims of hate speech or similar attacks.

Altogether, scientists are encouraged to engage in a living culture of integrity and in forms and formats of social integration. However, the necessary pre-condition for that is that institutional structures exist which allow the scientists to act in the recommended way.

5 Conclusion

The three focus groups, organised with institutional actors from different institutions and positions, have all discussed trust in science, research integrity and social integration as complex and to some degree controversial concepts. Certainly influenced by their different professional backgrounds, they had clearly different approaches to the topics which have been taken into account in the analysis. Regarding the recommendations, one can however say that they may have been different in their emphases but rather similar in their core. This conclusion does not have the objective to discuss all arguments that have been extensively made before, but just to raise some last important points that seemed to be crucial to the authors.

Trust in science is a mechanism of complexity reduction that means for citizens to give up control. Trust also means having certain expectations towards the actors one places the own trust in. As a dynamic process, trust – not only trust in science – needs time to be built but can be destroyed very quickly. Participants all agreed that one important problem in the ambivalent relation between science and society today, leading to increasing mistrust, is the existence of wrong public expectations about how science works. They see the core of this problem in a lack of education ('scientific literacy') in the public but also in a distorted self-display of science and scientists in the public discourse. Tackling this problem should be at the core of improving the trust-relation between science and the public.

Beyond that fundamental challenge in the public-science relationship, participants of the three focus groups expressed the clear opinion that research integrity and social integration may have an influence on public trust in science, but that this influence can be positive as much as negative. Regarding integrity, being perceived as integer and aware of the own responsibility, scientists and institutions can contribute to public trust in science. On the other hand, doubts about scientists' independence or scandals of scientific misconduct can have important and very quick negative consequences on trust in science as a whole.

In the same vein, successful forms of social integration may increase a feeling of closeness and accessibility among citizens. With a better understanding of scientific processes and methods, it might also give them the feeling of 'gaining back control' to some extent. However, social integration can also be detrimental to public trust in science, for example when citizens feel 'used' as data collectors, but also – when being pushed too far – by fuelling wrong assumptions about future involvement of citizens in scientific decision-making or the importance of scientific expertise.

We therefore do not need just 'more' of research integrity and social integration in order to increase public trust in science. Instead, both alike must become more than 'add-ons' to normal scientific life. Working towards a positive influence of integrity and integration on public trust in science, both concepts need to be thought and re-thought as comprehensive and integral parts of the research process. For this to happen, there need to be comprehensive, and one could say cultural changes within institutions but also within the system of science as a whole, including all relevant stakeholders in this process. This requires lasting and innovative forms of collaboration between scientific, political, and societal actors following the guiding principle of 'learning from and with each other' in order to strengthen public trust in science.

Appendix

1 Codebook of the German focus group analysis

German: Wissenschaft	English: Science
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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1.Wissenschaft&Gesellschaft_Schlagworte ● 2.Wissenschaft_Strukturen und strukturelle Probleme ● 3.Wissenschaft&Politik ● 4.Wissenschaftsfreiheit ● 5.Wissenschaft_Recommendations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1.Science&society_keywords ● 2.Science_structures and structural problems ● 3.Science & politics ● 4.Academic freedom ● 5.Science_recommendations
Vertrauen	Trust
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1.Vertrauen_Krise ● 2.Vertrauen_Gründe ● 3.Vertrauen_Integrität ● 4.Vertrauen_Beteiligung ● 5.Vertrauen_Institutionen ● 6.Vertrauen_Recommendations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1.Trust_crisis ● 2.Trust_reasons ● 3.Trust_integrity ● 4.Trust_integration ● 5.Trust_institutions ● 6.Trust_recommendations
Integrität	Integrity
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1.Integrität_was ist das ● 2.Integrität_Fehlverhalten ● 3.Integrität_strukturelle Faktoren ● 4.Integrität_Rollen ● 5.Integrität_Recommendations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1.Integrity_what is that ● 2.Integrity_misconduct ● 3.Integrity_structural factors ● 4.Integrity_roles ● 5.Integrity_recommendations
Beteiligung	Integration
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1.Beteiligung_Formen und Farben ● 2.Beteiligung_Vorteile ● 3.Beteiligung_challenges ● 4.Beteiligung_Recommendations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1.Integration_shapes and colours ● 2.Integration_benefits ● 3.Integration_challenges ● 4.Integration_recommendations
Institutionen	Institutions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1.Institutionen_Rolle ● 2.Institutionen_Recommendations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1.Institutions_role ● 2.Institutions_recommendations
Recommendations	Recommendations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Wissenschaft_Recommendations ● Institutionen_Recommendations ● Integrität_Recommendations ● Beteiligung_Recommendations ● Vertrauen_Recommendations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Science_recommendations ● Institutions_recommendations ● Integrity_recommendations ● Integration_recommendations ● Trust_recommendations

2 Invitation material for PCIs:

poiesis
TRUST IN SCIENCE

National Report: Focus Groups - *Greece*

**Project title: Probing the impact of integrity and
integration on societal trust in science**

Project acronym: POIESIS

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1 Introduction

1.1 Set up of the focus group

Three Focus Groups (FGs) were organised in Greece; all three FGs took place in Athens, on the 19th (Research Integrity & Societal Integration - FG1), 21st (Societal Integration - FG2), and 23rd (Research Integrity - FG3) of February 2024. The FG1 was held by physical presence of the participants at a hotel close to the center of Athens, while the FGs 2 and 3 took place via online participation. Online means were used, because universities in Greece were closed during the period from the middle of January until beginning of March 2024; the reason was that the Greek government was trying to pass a law that institutionalised private universities (in Greece the tertiary education is carried out only by public universities, according to the Greek constitution). This raised considerable criticism among the Greek academia and massive riots from the Greek students; actually, the Greek Universities were “occupied” by the Greek student’s unions and held closed within the above-mentioned time period, which varied among different Greek universities.

This disruption caused considerable barriers for the planning of the FGs by physical presence, for the following reasons: (a) the participants were full-time employees at Greek universities and the obvious meeting places were supposed to be university campuses which were closed; (b) non-academic participants were scattered geographically throughout the metropolitan area of Attica and the online means were facilitating their participation.

The strategy used to recruit national co-investigators was by reaching out to experts from our professional network. This strategy was essential, since in Greece there are no institutionalized bodies that deal explicitly with Research Integrity (RI) or individuals that act as official spokesmen of universities for issues of science communication. The people we reached out gather all necessary characteristics of the expertise needed to run their specific FGs. This nuanced and “eclectic” expertise would be challenging to describe if we would proceed with an open invitation for co-investigators. Such an approach would, most possibly, delayed the recruitment of country co-investigators. We did not encounter any difficulties in involving these co-investigators in the project, since they all gladly accepted to participate as facilitators of their FGs.

The descriptions of the national co-investigators follow:

- o **FG1:** Professor Pavlos P. Sotiriadis, at the [School of Electrical and Computer Engineering](#) of [National Technical University of Athens \(NTUA\)](#). He is an IEEE Fellow, the Director of the

Electronics Laboratory of the NTUA and a governing board member of the [Hellenic \(National\) Space Center of Greece](#).

- o **FG2:** Professor Manolis Patiniotis, Department of [Sociology](#), of [Athens National and Kapodistrian University](#). He is a member of the academic committee of the postgraduate program [Science Communication](#) of the [Hellenic Open University](#). He was also active by writing the editorial at a public science bi-monthly magazine called PRISMA that was released as an inset by a Greek newspaper of national circulation, until the end of 2023.
- o **FG3:** Olga Tzortzatou, member the Legal department of the [Biomedical Research Foundation of the Academy of Athens](#) (BRFAA), external ethics expert of the European Commission.
Co-Facilitator: Vasileios Zogopoulos, Biomedical Research Foundation, Academy of Athens

The participants were recruited by the co-investigators. The invitations were sent by the co-investigator to experts whose needed expertise had been discussed with the NTUA researchers, in order to avoid invitations of experts that were not relevant to the needs of each specific FG. All co-investigators made an effort to achieve attendance by a gender-balanced group; that was not possible for FG1, where people from the higher levels of hierarchy participated. This reflects the under-representation of female researchers at such positions in Greek Universities.

FGs 1 and 2 were attended by six participants; FG3 was attended by five participants. All participants that had accepted the invitation showed up to the FGs, except in the case of the FG1, where 4 experts that had accepted the invitations did not show up. No special incentive strategy had to be developed to ensure the attendance of participants.

There was no need for local adaptations of the moderator guide. The coverage of the anticipated discussions points and the flow of the discussions during all three FGs is considered satisfactory. FG1 focused on trust in science and its parameters. FG2 put more focus on the societal aspects of the discussion, with regard the other two FGs. This was due to the fact that the participants were faculty members and science communicators with a background on Social Sciences and Humanities. It worths mentioning that despite four out of six participants had a bachelor degree in Physics, none of them followed an academic career in Physics. FG3 focused on RI and the link between science communication and trust. FGs 1 and 2 lasted 2.5 hours and FG3 lasted 80 minutes. Information meetings were organised with the co-investigators of FGs 1 and 2, before the conduct of the FGs.

The recordings of the FGs were transcribed using the Amberscript software, which is GDPR-compliant. The transcript was proof-read by LA and PK, authors of this report, by comparing the recording and the

transcript, in order to ensure that the latter was verbatim to the former. After proof-reading the transcript, in the Greek language, was coded by using the commenting function of Microsoft Word software. The codes used were developed *a priori* by CNRS (deductive approach); there was not need for additional codes, based on the reading of the transcripts (inductive approach). Coding was applied to the original transcript in the Greek language; the codes, whenever that was essential, were translated in Greek. However, in most cases the codes were descriptive of the content of the discussion, so it was not essential to translate all codes contained at the code book developed by CNRS.

No travel assistance was provided to the participants of the FG1, which was held via physical presence, while at this FG dinner was provided to the participants after the end of the discussion.

1.2 Participants in the focus group

FG1

Participant Id.	Gender	Age (approx.)	Position	Institution
FG1_1	Male	65+	Professor Emeritus	NTUA
FG1_2	Male	55-64	Professor, Vice-Rector	NTUA
FG1_3	Male	55-64	Professor/Archimandrite	NKUA/CHURCH OF GREECE
FG1_4	Male	40-50	Association President	MEDICAL LAW AND BIOETHICS ASSOCIATION
FG1_5	Male	55-64	Professor	NTUA
FG1_6	Male	40-50	Professor	NTUA

FG2

Participant Id.	Gender	Age (approx.)	Position	Institution
FG2_1	Male	45-54	Researcher, Science communication	Leibniz Institute for Astrophysics, Potsdam, Germany
FG2_2	Male	55-64	Professor	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens

FG2_3	Male	45-54	Professor	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens
FG2_4	Male	55-64	Responsible for communication	Democritos Research Center
FG2_5	Female	45-54	Professor	Panteion University of Social and Political Sciences
FG2_6	Female	45-54	Associate professor	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens

FG3

Participant Id.	Gender	Age (approx.)	Position	Institution
FG3_1	Male	65+	Bioethical Committee	BRFAA
FG3_2	Male	55-64	Bioethical Committee	BRFAA
FG3_3	Female	55-64	Professor/Bioethical Committee	NKUA/BRFAA
FG3_4	Male	55-64	Senior Lawyer at Medical Law	LEGAL ADVISORY TO THE STATE
FG3_5	Female	25-34	Researcher/Administration	BRFAA

2 Sequential description of the focus groups

2.1 Focus Group 1

FG1 was the only of those that took place in Greece that was conducted by physical presence. This factor, along with the co-Investigator's capacity to effectively facilitate the discussion helped the conversation to evolve, with the engagement of every participant. All topics were thoroughly discussed and while the group was pretty much uniform, in terms of academic background (4 out of 6 were engineers), each participant added a unique view on the debate. Especially regarding Social Integration (SI) some of participants expressed very interesting and diverse opinions, while the matter of Trust and how this is affected by private interests, and the competition in academia - as the main factor for research misconduct - seemed to be the focal points of the debate.

The diversity of opinions and the occasional disagreements - especially on aspects of SI - were handled by the participants and

the co-Investigator in an excellent, delicate, and gentle way and that was one of the features that made this FG really interesting. Despite the fact that the problem-solving part on the SI was somewhat generic, the depth and diversity of the general discussion confirms that this FG has achieved its objectives.

2.2 Focus Group 2

The discussions of FG2 followed the sequence of the questions as they appear at the moderator guide. There were cases where specific questions were not asked to the participants, since the discussion of previous questions provided sufficient information to cover them. The questions not brought to discussion were Q2, Q4, and Q6 (according to the numbering of the moderator guide).

The main topics discussed at the beginning of FG2 were how the perceptions for science evolved during the course of the 20th century and the interaction of science and society. For the former topic, the participants expressed the opinion that the geopolitical situation after the end of the 2nd World War resulted to the dissolution of the more "relaxed" atmosphere within which science had been conducted until then. For the latter topic the participants agreed that both science and society affect each other, in a sense they are dialectically entangled.

The discussion then focused on the (dis)trust in science that was the theme that attracted - especially the rationales question - the highest number of comments. This topic seemed to be very relevant with the discussions about science; this smooth transition, possibly, helped the participants to think within the most appropriate context.

For the topic of RI/Misconduct the participants brought into the discussion two different and quite opposing perspectives for the sources of misconduct: systemic factors and the responsibility of the individual researcher, specifically the quality of his character traits. The discussion for the institutions focused (a) on the role of formal education in universities and the effects it has on the way researchers do research and (b) on the role of (science) museums on SI.

Due to the background of the participants, the discussion quickly departed from superficial arguments and was fertilised by deeper reflection, related to the socio-economic structure of modern societies and science. The facilitator did a great job by providing almost equal time for all participants to express their opinions. The facilitator was opening the discussions on the various different topics by initiating the discussion with a different participant, each time. The facilitator was "facilitated" by the willingness all participants showed to contribute to the discussion. Overall, the objectives of the study were met by this FG, especially on the data

collected and idea generation, while the problem-solving opinions were of a more generic character.

2.3 Focus Group 3

In this FG the discussions focused mainly on the topics of RI and research misconduct, as well as on the issue of SI of Science. Particularly, regarding the latter aspect, most of the participants expressed their concerns about the communication of science to the public from the beginning of the discussion, considering it a major aspect of the relationship between science and society. From the start of the conversation communication of science was linked with Trust in Science.

The topic of RI and the reasons behind research misconduct was the most popular of FG3, as all participants were fully engaged in the discussion.

The discussion was facilitated smoothly, most of the participants were engaged in the conversation and there was a very interesting exchange of ideas in a friendly and collegial atmosphere. Despite the fact that FG3 had the lowest attendancet, it achieved its targets as many interesting ideas, recommendations and data were recorded. Another positive aspect is that one of the POIESIS research cases (Covid-19) was a particular focus of the debate.

3 Building trust in science : from perception to institutional engagement

3.1 About science and society

The following words were used by the participants, per FG, to describe or give meaning to the notion of science and society (in alphabetic order): Accountability, communication (in simple terms), contribution, development, diffusion, dissemination, enlightenment of people, ethics, exploitation of results, fruitful encounter, honesty, improvement of quality of life, inclusion, innovation, mediation of science in society through technology, misunderstanding of results, morality, nice encounter, openness, politics (the handling of common affairs), prediction, progress, reciprocation of needs, reciprocal relationship, representation, respect, responsibility, social construction, social good, social responsibility of the scientist, suggestions for further exploration of these needs, two-way interaction, understanding the world.

3.2 Perceptions of trust in science

Speaking about the issue of Trust in Science, FG1_6 stressed that there is a gap between science and the public because the former is incomprehensible to the latter. There was a general agreement about this gap but not about its extent with FG1_1 in particular, insisting on that the crisis exists mainly on the implementations of science and not to science at large. FG1_4 stressed that this crisis might provide an opportunity just like the one at the aftermath of World War II, when bioethics appeared first at USA. One participant in FG2 (FG2_2) expressed a view of a "periodization" on the development of the feeling of trust or distrust among non-scientists. Specifically, "in previous times", FG2_2 mentioned, that science was connected to reliability and authority; in those times there were no issues of a trust crisis. Science was expressing an authoritative view that enjoyed the acceptance from society, because it was connected to political power. The real issue of trust crisis, during the last decade, was a result of the discussions around the vaccination.

The discussion about trust and distrust in science was linked with the effectiveness - or ineffectiveness for that matter - of science communication and mainly revolved around that matter. The fact that uncertainty and constant doubt is a vital part of the scientific process complicates the issue of trust according to FG3_4.

Concerning the reasons of this gap and distrust in general, the main reason according to the participants (everyone mentioned it as one of the reasons) is the question if science is serving humanity or financial and political interests. The perception of the participants, with regard the state of public trust in science, was heavily influenced by the notion that science is governed by political and economic interests, which are responsible for the crisis in the relation between science and society. According to their view, society is more distrustful of science (or less trustful), if the comparison is made with middle 20th century.

FG1_1 and FG1_6 pointed out that the crisis of trust in science is part of the wider crisis of trust in institutions at large. FG2_5 mentioned that this overarching crisis in trust is the result of a more general societal "deregulation" and the coming of the era of information. The constant bombardment of citizens with information makes it difficult to discern what is scientific and what is not or how scientists work. Another participant (FG2_4) related the crisis in trust with the sentiment produced from the arrogance with which sometimes scientists address to their audience, whether this is their peers or society. Another notion is that trust should be seen as a

two-way relation; if scientists wish to be trusted by society, they should also reciprocate this trust to society.

FG1_2 stressed that it is not absurd for people to be suspicious of the sources of research funding and while the crisis of trust in the past probably had to do mostly with a lack of understanding on behalf of the public now is more complicated, and the main reasons are that: a) research is conducted for profit, b) war industry interests, c) the unemployment and job insecurity that is created because of technology progress, d) the segregation in society according to each people views about science, e) fake news and pseudoscience, f) the fact that competition on research industry sometimes produces poor quality results. Other factors identified by the rest of the group included g) religious beliefs that may be contradicted with the technological progress, h) the speed of this progress in modern societies and i) the conflict with tradition that was previously mentioned.

In FG1 the conversation revolved around the concepts of enthusiasm and uncertainty. Each participant starting from a different point - which sometimes was relevant to their scientific background - substantially agreed that they are connected to each other and are common reactions to everything new science and society has or had to offer. According to most of the participants the tensions finally "tend to balance and the society finally progresses" (FG1_5). FG1_1 also stated that the hesitation is more documented to the more educated portions of the society, and it might turn into fear when it comes to faculties like biomedicine and its potential findings.

Some of the participants suggested specific measures to improve the society's trust in science: FG1_4 stressed that the major factor for the evaluation and promotion of a scientific breakthrough should be its social impact, while FG1_3 proposing a management and understanding of ethics that derives from the legislature and the human rights

The participants of FG2 did not directly mention whether they trust science, but a positive view was implied throughout the discussion. One participant (FG2_4) expressed a more complex view. Namely, the participant believes that the crisis of trust is possibly an intermediate stage of the process of maturation of the relation between societies and science. This maturation process reveals that science is not the bearer of the "absolute truth", but a partner who helps humanity to seek the truth. Science's view has, of course, its own particularities, tradition, and prestige to this process. So, this crisis of trust is one stage in the process of the assessment of science's activities.

Participant FG2_5 elegantly described the way science practice is communicated to non-experts with the following metaphor:

“Τους λέμε ότι μέχρι τώρα στα πανεπιστήμιά σας, στις περισσότερες περιπτώσεις ή κυρίως στα σχολεία, βλέπατε την σάλα της επιστήμης όπου τα πιάτα έρχονται έτοιμα, έρχονται καλώς σερβιρισμένα, έτοιμες θεωρίες, έτοιμες απαντήσεις κτλ. Στα ερευνητικά κέντρα και σε κάθε εργαστήριο επιστημονικό μπαίνετε μέσα στην κουζίνα της επιστήμης που παράγεται η επιστήμη, όπου εκεί γίνεται ένας μικρός χαμός και εκεί υπάρχουν οι ερωτήσεις, υπάρχουν οι πολλές απαντήσεις, υπάρχουν οι δοκιμές, υπάρχουν τα λάθη, υπάρχουν όλα αυτά.”

“We tell them that until now in your universities, in most cases or mainly in schools, you saw the hall of science where the dishes come ready, they come well-served, ready theories, ready answers etc. In the research centers and in every scientific laboratory you enter the kitchen of science where science is produced, where there is a little mess and there are the questions, there are the many answers, there are the tests, there are the mistakes, there are all these.”

Another participant (FG2_5), with a background in Social Sciences, expressed - during the discussions about trust - the view that the integrity in Social Sciences is mostly related to subjectivity, which is characteristic of the methods of this discipline. The participants implied that integrity is more related to positivism and not with qualitative research, where subjectivity is important.

Another interesting aspect of the conversation was the example (brought by FG3_4) of the 6 Italian seismologists that were accused of manslaughter for misleading the public about the potential risk of an earthquake at the town of L' Aquila in 2009. This helped to somewhat widen the conversation to aspects such as the fear that the scientists sometimes might have in communicating their findings (FG3_3), to the interrelation between science and politics and played a key role to turn the conversation towards the topics of RI and SI. Other examples revolved around Covid-19, while climate change wasn't specifically mentioned.

3.3. Attitudes towards research integrity

The participants of FG2 perceive the notion of RI as the *modus operandi* for producing scientific outputs. By *modus operandi* they mean the rules a scientist has to follow during her/his practice and the responsibility she/he should have with regard the ethical issues related to the results of someone's research. Honesty, reproducibility, vigorous scientific methodology, social impact, impartiality, disclosure of potential conflicts of interest, connection of morality and legitimacy, research in service of humanity are the main concepts that the participants in FG1 used to describe a scientist who is working with RI.

The main characteristics of RI are: adherence to the highest methodological standards, being transparent and sincere (do justice) to our research results, follow a professional culture that presupposes collegial norms of communication with our collaborators (irrespective of their relative placement at the hierarchy of a research performing organisation), following evidence-based arguments when addressing to an audience that transcends the scientific community. This last point is related with one scientist's integrity towards her/his peers, by avoiding manipulation of information, hype, as well as adhering to transparency, by revealing all dimensions of a research problem.

Some of the participants (FG1_1 and FG1_5) noted that misconduct rarely happens nowadays (maybe except for countries such as China) and when they do, academia expels those "bad apples", especially when the peer reviewers are adequate. Some other participants disagreed with that view, stating that it is not that rare as it seems to be, and by bringing up some examples from the Greek and the international scientific community. FG1_1 seemed to be receptive of those opinions. Proposed measures to improve RI and to reduce misconduct included the decrease of pressure to researchers for citations and the introduction of alternative methods of evaluation, more concrete Codes of Conduct for scientists and the development of mechanisms to expel the violators.

The participants of FG2 presented the following as causes for breaches of integrity: personal ambition, work insecurity, lack of personal life due to continuous change of institutes, cities, countries, and pressure to publish. As previously mentioned, there were two participants that highlighted, as a cause for misconduct, the character traits of the individual researcher that are reflected to her/his work. For example, participant FG2_6 said:

"Νομίζω ότι είναι κυρίως τα προσωπικά χαρακτηριστικά του καθενός από εμάς που κάνουν τη διαφορά. Μπορεί όλοι να είναι καλοί ή καλοί επιστήμονες, αλλά νομίζω το παράπτωμα σχετίζεται με το άτομο"

"I think it is mainly the personal characteristics of each of us that make the difference. They may all be good or good scientists, but I think the offense is related to the individual"

And, on a similar note, participant FG2_3 said:

"Σίγουρα η ακεραιότητα θέλει την επιστημονική κατάρτιση, αλλά για μένα η ακεραιότητα του επιστήμονα είναι απόλυτα συνυφασμένη με την ακεραιότητα του προσώπου του επιστήμονα. Δηλαδή αν το πρόσωπο το συγκεκριμένο έχει ένα, δύο, τρία, τέσσερα προβλήματα, αυτά θα εμφανιστούν και στην επιστήμη"

“Certainly integrity requires scientific training, but for me the integrity of the scientist is completely intertwined with the integrity of the scientist's person. That is, if the specific person has one, two, three, four problems, these will also appear in science”

The most “popular” reason behind research misconduct was the pressure and competition between researchers, labs and perhaps institutions. As participant FG2_1 said, commenting on the sideeffects of pressure to publish to non-tenured researchers:

“Όμως καθίσταται και υπαρξιακή για ανθρώπους σαν και μένα που είμαι, που δεν έχω μόνιμη θέση και οι άνθρωποι που ζούμε σε αυτό το λίκμο μεταξύ διδακτορικού και μόνιμης θέσης, είμαστε σε ένα κυνήγι μιας εξασφάλισης και αναγκάζομαστε να παίξουμε με κανόνες παραγωγικότητας (...) Βλέπεις την αγωνία και σε νεότερους συναδέλφους από μένα να βγάλω ένα paper στο οποίο θα ανακαλύψω. Θα βάλω ένα όνομα σε κάτι. Που μπορεί να μην έχει ονομαστεί από κάποιον προηγουμένως. Διάφορα τέτοια.”

“But it also becomes existential for people like me who am not tenured and people who live in this limbo between PhD and tenure, we are in a hunt for a security and are forced to play by the rules of productivity (...) You can see the anxiety among younger colleagues to produce a paper in which I will discover. I'm going to put a name on something. Which may not have been named by someone before. Various such things.”

The metrics of evaluation (h-index was repeatedly mentioned) play a leading role in intensifying this pressure according to most participants of FG3. Other factors included engagement of private interests in science and ideology. In FG3, participants identified the independence of scientific research from private interests, the overcome of personal ideas and ideology systems, the willingness to serve science and society in general and not only to satisfy personal ambitions, the reproducibility of research and its openness as key factors that determine the Integrity of the research process. Most of them mentioned the pressure for publications and results as one of the main reasons for Integrity breaches. Lack of knowledge of the RI principles by young researchers was also mentioned.

Participant FG3_1 stated that the risk for research misconduct is quite big, but participants FG3_2 and FG3_4 expressed their fears about the extent of the aforementioned misconduct in scientific community and the difficulties in ensuring the independence of research, especially regarding financial factors. FG3_5 proposed the disclosure of potential conflicts of interest as a way to solve such “problems” while other recommendations included a more creative interaction between science and society based on the principles of

accountability, effective training of young researchers on RI principles and an attempt to lower the pressure on researchers not only from the academic community but from society as a whole.

With regard to the participants' familiarity with existing integrity guidelines and codes, there were generic remarks about the existence of institutional research ethics and deontology committees. However, there were also mentions that the adherence of Greek academia to RI standards is, in some cases, suboptimal. As a result, the participants perceive that the culture of scientific integrity needs to be further promoted, especially in the context of how senior researchers treat young researchers.

3.4. Attitudes towards social integration

SI was probably the most diverse topic, in terms of the opinions expressed during the discussions. Many group members expressed their scepticism or even their disagreements with some tools for SI such as citizen science and popularisation. FG1_1 for example stated that:

“θέλει να συνδέσει το πόσο καλά βλέπει ο κόσμος και την εμπιστοσύνη που έχει στην έρευνα, στα αποτελέσματα της έρευνας, με το να συμμετέχουν... και να συμμετέχουν περισσότεροι lay men στην έρευνα. Ε, δεν νομίζω ότι ισχύει!”

“it wants to link the view of the public about research and the publics' trust in research, in the results of a research, with the participation... and the participation of lay men in research. Well, I don't think it is true!”

additionally on another part:

“Το πόσο καλό θα είναι μια τεχνολογία και πόσο ηθική θα είναι δεν εξαρτάται από το αν θα έχουμε 2 ή 500 ανθρώπους να συμμετέχουν σαν παρατηρητές, σαν χρήστες στην έρευνα. Αυτό το οποίο θα συμβάλει στην ακεραιότητα είναι η δημοσιοποίηση των αποτελεσμάτων και η συνεχής στο χρόνο αποτίμηση της ορθότητας της.”

“How good a technology is or how moral it is, does not depend on having 2 or 500 people to participate as observers, as users in the research. What will contribute to its integrity is the publication of the results and the continuous assessment of its correctness over time.”

Concerning popularisation, FG1_2 (who partially agreed with FG1_1 on the latter subject) said:

“Η εκκλαΐκευση νομίζω ότι έχει πολλούς κινδύνους. Εγώ αυτό νιώθω ότι μπορεί να θεωρείται θεμιτό κλπ για να γίνουν όλοι κοινωνοί κάποιων πραγμάτων, αλλά κατά

βάθος δουλεύει αρνητικά, γιατί μερικά πράγματα ισχύουν κάτω από ορισμένες συνθήκες και μόνο τότε. Και όταν εκλαϊκεύουμε γενικεύουμε και μπορεί να τελικά να οδηγήσει σε αντίθετο αποτέλεσμα από αυτό το οποίο... από την αλήθεια και να καταλάβει ο κόσμος, κάτι το οποίο κατά βάθος δεν ισχύει γιατί δεν καταλαβαίνει όλη τη λογική, αυτό που περιγράφεται. Προσωπικά έχω μια ψιλοαπέχθεια για την εκλαϊκευση."

"I think popularisation has many dangers. I feel that it can be seen as legitimate etc. to make everybody aware of certain things, but in fact it works negatively, because some things are valid under certain circumstances and only then. And when we popularize, we generalize and it can ultimately lead to the opposite result from what... from the truth and so people will understand something which is fundamentally not true because they don't understand all the logic, what is being described. I personally have a slight dislike for popularization."

FG1_5 agreed with the two aforementioned participants, but they left the door open for citizen science activities in humanities. FG1_3 and FG1_4 on the other hand seemed to be more open on such endeavours not only in humanities but also in other sciences. They also stressed that popularisation is essential, but it needs to be handled carefully and that mediators play an integral part in it. FG1_3 noted that SI should be as inclusive as possible, but if someone had to choose, he should choose the middle class as it has a perception that can better cover all layers of the society, while FG1_4 commented that "lay people" can participate in some phases of research, as long as they also follow a Code of Conduct. They both agreed that this enhances trust in science.

The popularization of scientific results, informing people of what Science has achieved over the years and how it bettered the quality of everyday life (an aspect that the scientists could have done better in the past according to FG3_1), the training of researchers in science communication were among the main factors and recommendations of the participants. Other features of SI identified were that of Committees and Unions of patients at Medicine and their inclusion on Bioethical Committees (if they have received proper training before).

Conclusively, most group members recommended that the participation of "lay people" in research should be mainly or exclusively limited to a consulting role if not any. Particularly useful according to them is the participation in such consulting committees in Medicine (patients, doctors, nurses etc.), exceptionally in groups like people with disabilities, where their advice on the design of a scientific product is crucial as they know better what they need (FG1_2). FG1_6 also noted that at the research process we need to take feedback also from those who might be

negatively affected by a scientific breakthrough, like people who might lose their jobs etc.

The following opinion was expressed about the current state of SI in science and technology:

“Το επιστημονικό προϊόν ενσωματώνεται στο πλαίσιο του νεοφιλελευθερισμού ως εμπόρευμα. Άρα, ζούμε σε αυτή τη φάση που ο νεοφιλελευθερισμός, ως κυρίαρχη ιδεολογία, έχει επικρατήσει όχι μόνο στην πολιτική, αλλά και στην οικονομία και στην εκπαίδευση και παντού. Το δεύτερο. Και αυτό δεν είναι μόνο εμπόρευμα, αλλά είναι και υπηρεσία. Έτσι για να πιάσουμε ένα ευρύτερο τομέα. Αλλά αν ως υπηρεσία μπορεί να πουληθεί, έχει αξία και ενσωματώνεται. Γιατί η κοινωνία για τον νεοφιλελευθερισμό είναι η αγορά.”

“The scientific product is incorporated into the context of neoliberalism as a commodity. So, we are living in this phase where neoliberalism, as a dominant ideology, has prevailed not only in politics, but also in the economy and in education and everywhere. The second. And this is not only a commodity, but also a service. So to catch a wider field. But if as a service it can be sold, it has value and is integrated. Because society for neoliberalism is the market.”

The level of SI was not directly addressed, in FG2, but there were comments that expressed the need of society to be reflected into the way science is conducted, something that has to be also applied to all other institutions. The effects of such an approach would be to have, not only an open communication of science with society in its entirety, but to also have an inclusive research workforce.

One participant (FG2_5) expressed the opinion that SI of science means to interpret social phenomena, in the following way:

“Για μένα η κοινωνική ενσωμάτωση της επιστήμης σημαίνει πρώτα απ' όλα μια ερμηνεία των κοινωνικών γεγονότων, ερμηνεία της κοινωνικής πραγματικότητας. Αναστοχασμό πάνω σε ένα κοινωνικό γεγονός. Τη δυνατότητα μιας ανάπτυξης, μιας κριτικής, της κριτικής στάσης απέναντι στο κοινωνικό γεγονός, απέναντι στην επιστήμη και εν τέλει τη δυνατότητα πρόνοιας ή πρόβλεψης, αν θέλετε”

“For me the social integration of science means first of all an interpretation of social events, an interpretation of social reality. Reflection on a social event. The possibility of a development, a critique, a critical attitude towards the social event, towards science and finally the possibility of providence or prediction, if you like”

The perceived benefits of public involvement in science, as expressed in FG2, are: (a) to educate young people and young

scientists about our current uncertainties and (b) to help scientists to reflect on the ways citizens perceive science.

One participant used one example to present how SI can benefit dissemination of scientific knowledge and innovations to the general public. That example was about an exhibition that had been created by mathematicians, scientists, social scientists, IT experts, and graphic designers, to present the scientific dispute on genetically modified products. This example was put into the framework of a theory of museology that is being currently discussed, according to which science has to be presented as a process, through the visualisation of the work of a researcher.

Such kind of SI can help professional researchers to uncover the misrepresentation of research from mass media. Informing society about the research community's disputes and why they come into being is important for citizens to comprehend the process of scientific progress.

Taking up the case of Covid-19, three participants (FG3_1, FG3_2, and FG3_3) stood on the importance of good science communication, acknowledging that we had both good and bad examples and how relieving or damaging was that for the people on either case. All three participants noted also the importance for scientists to be trained in science communication, linking science communication and SI with Trust in Science as well. Another factor that all of the three participants mentioned was that science communication is often conducted by journalists and while some of them are act with integrity, some others are mainly interested in publicity, damaging both science communication and Trust In Science as a result.

3.5. Institutional contributions to trust in science

With regard ways with which institutions can have a positive impact on SI, the participants of FG2 mentioned two examples: (a) the post-graduate course on Science Communication, of the Greek Open University, that provides the theoretical framework and the tools to the students to communicate science, either through science museums or through other initiatives and (b) the Natural History Museum of the University of Crete. The participants of FG3 stressed the need to create and strengthen their Bioethics Committees, to take care of science communication and not leave it to the Mass Media, to investigate and disclose potential conflicts of interest, to train their researchers according to the principles of RI and to promote Open Science practices.

One participant (FG2_6) mentioned that one model that could be imported is an exhibition that presents science not as something

standard or still, but as something that changes constantly. Research practice is this exactly process of change; this is something that must pass to the visitors of these type of exhibitions (i.e. exhibitions that highlight the scientific process and not the scientific product).

The recommendations focused on the role of formal education. Specifically, despite the fact that such education exists for the teachers of elementary schools, there is a lack of such education for teachers of secondary education (in Greece secondary education covers the ages from 12-18). All educational levels should have lessons about science communication and this expands also to tertiary education (i.e. Universities). It was implied that formal education has a more important role than targeted seminars, since science communication has to become part of the "consciousness" of citizens, some of which will become researchers. Another recommendation was that faculty members and researchers staff of research performing organisations should be guided on how to use social media.

"Κάποιες φορές έχω σκεφτεί ότι θα πρέπει να κάνουμε σεμινάρια στους ερευνητές και στα μέλη ΔΕΠ και σε όσους επιστήμονες ανήκουν σε οργανισμούς, πώς θα πρέπει να χρησιμοποιούν τα μέσα κοινωνικής δικτύωσης ή καλύτερα πως να μη χρησιμοποιούν τα μέσα κοινωνικής δικτύωσης."

"Sometimes I have thought that we should give seminars to researchers and faculty members and those scientists who belong to organizations, how they should use social media, or rather how not to use social media."

The conversation about SI was reflected in the subsequent one about the role of institutions in promoting it in FG1. Most of the participants identified a lack of mechanisms and activities on behalf of their institutions, which according to some of them was not a particularly bad thing, concerning at least the citizen science factor. Others stressed that it is important for Universities to develop SI activities for a number of reasons: (a) whether that would be their obligation as publicly-funded institutions, so the public has to have a saying, (b) because it will enhance the transparency of research, (c) because it would promote their wider interests, e.g. it could serve as a promotional opportunity for people who will participate in research to later send their children to study there (FG1_6). Moreover, according to FG1_3 this osmosis that will come as a result of the consulting process not only with the public but also with other stakeholders, might provide some suggestions to policy makers in a wider spectrum, whether this will concern government or entrepreneurial practices. FG1_4 also stated that this consulting committees are no strangers in Medicine, and he also was part of one as a legal advisor.

Regarding the role of Institutions on strengthening RI practices, recommendations varied from stiffer penalties to violators in Greece (students and researchers) like the ones that apply on the other side of the Atlantic, to the creation of role models which are more efficient than punishments most of the times (FG1_2), the introduction of training programs on RI and to the modernisation of the existing (or non-existing for that matter) Code of Conduct. A very popular recommendation among the participants were that the evaluation should be done not according to h-index and citations but to the wider reputation of the candidate (the IEEE Fellow candidacy example was mentioned and was very well received by all) and the social impact of his research. The British example of the evaluation of universities faculty staff was exceptionally mentioned (FG1_1) and was met positively by the majority of the group members.

3.6. Other themes

In FG2 criticism on the pressure to disseminate was articulated by one participant. This pressure to disseminate the research results via to schools, to academia does not allow for scientists that produce the research to self-reflect on their research.

In FG2 there was one participant (FG2_2) that raised the point that although openly disseminating research results it may be a transparent and democratic process, sometimes there is a need to customize the dissemination content according to the gender, race, religion, when your target audience is students. In this case the particularities are important, as Multicultural Science Education has pointed out. This is especially pertinent, since there seems to be information that has been left without communication in favour of Citizen Science education. We include below the words, since we believe are interesting:

“Σε κάθε περίπτωση νομίζω ότι. Μάλλον να κάνω ένα φλας μπακ. Υπήρχε ένα ωραίο paper του Jürgen Renn στο Centaurus το 2014 όπου έλεγε το εξής ότι το history of science θα πρέπει να το αντικαταστήσουμε. Το λέω χοντρικά με το history of knowledge. Εννοώ ότι η επιστήμη είναι ένα σύνολο από knowledge systems έτσι, σε παγκόσμια κλίμακα έχουμε διαφορετικά γνωσιακά συστήματα και τελικά θα πρέπει να λάβουμε υπόψη μας τα διαφορετικά γνωσιακά συστήματα τα οποία έχει κάθε εθνότητα. Λοιπόν, δεν θέλω να μακρηγορήσω. Μπορούμε να συνεννοηθούμε έτσι νομίζω, γιατί είμαστε ώριμοι να μην κάνουμε αναλύσεις, αλλά θεωρώ ότι υπάρχουν ζητήματα στο ζήτημα της αποδοχής, της κοινωνικής αποδοχής. Θα πρέπει να λάβουμε υπόψιν πού απευθυνόμαστε, αν λάβουμε υπόψη ότι αυτή η κοινωνία δεν είναι ότι απευθύνομαι στην κοινωνία στο σύνολό της. Αλλά υπάρχουν κοινωνικές ομάδες οι οποίες συνδέονται μεταξύ

τους όχι κατ' ανάγκην με σχέσεις ευθύγραμμες, αλλά με σχέσεις καθετοποίησης, γνωστά πατριαρχικά, των decolonising science. Γι' αυτό σταματάω, γιατί το θεωρητικοποιούμε πολύ"

"In any case I think so. I should probably do a flashback. There was a nice paper by Jürgen Renn in Centaurus in 2014 where he said the following that the history of science should be replaced. I mean it roughly with the history of knowledge. I mean that science is a set of knowledge systems so, on a global scale we have different knowledge systems and ultimately we should take into account the different knowledge systems that each ethnicity has. Well, I don't want to be long. We can come to an agreement like this, I think, because we are mature enough not to analyze, but I think there are issues in the issue of acceptance, social acceptance. We should consider where we are addressing, if we consider that this society is not that I am addressing society as a whole. But there are social groups which are connected to each other not necessarily with straight relationships, but with vertical relationships, known as patriarchal, of decolonising science. That's why I stop, because we theorize it a lot."

4. Conclusion

The influence of financial and political interests on public trust in science and competition between researchers and possibly RPOs on RI are two main factors identified by the majority of the participants of all three Focus Groups conducted in Greece. SI proved to be a topic that gathered more diverse views, but even when participants rated it high and even linked it directly with the issue of trust (FG3), their recommendations mainly focused on issues of communication and dissemination rather than citizen science. This, most probably, reflects the fact that initiatives, like citizen science, are not still that popular in Greece. Overall, the Focus Groups were very fruitful, involving engaged participants and in-depth conversations, representative of the local paradigm and peculiarities.

poiesis
TRUST IN SCIENCE

National Report: Focus Groups - *Portugal*

**Project title: Probing the impact of integrity and
integration on societal trust in science**

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1 Introduction

In this report, we describe three focus groups, which took place in Lisbon, in February 2024, with 20 institutional stakeholders. The aim of the focus groups was to discuss stakeholders' views on research integrity, social integration and public trust in science. In what follows, we describe the events including the set-up, the characteristics of the participants and the discussions that took place.

1.1 Set up of the focus groups

The three focus groups engaged 20 participants and three co-investigators (one per group), recruited beforehand to moderate the discussions.

Focus group 1 (FG1) involved 6 participants and took place face to face at Iscte - Instituto Universitário de Lisboa in Lisbon, on 8th of February of 2024 (Thursday), from 14:30 to 16:30hrs. Focus group 2 (FG2) involved 7 participants and took place face-to-face at Iscte - Instituto Universitário de Lisboa on 9th of February of 2024 (Friday), during from 14:30-17:00, lasting two and a half hours. Focus group 3 (FG3) took place online via zoom on 16th of February of 2024 (Friday), lasting two hours from 16:00 to 18:00hrs.

All three focus groups were moderated by one co-investigator and co-moderated by the POIESIS national team. All discussions were recorded, and notes taken during the sessions. Informed consent was asked to participants before the sessions started. After the focus groups, a thank you email was sent to participants to express our gratitude for their contribution to the project and to share photos of the sessions. Participants were given a gift bag as a welcome and thank you for their participation.

Recruitment strategy of co-investigators

POIESIS Institutional Co-investigators were selected with the aim of moderating the focus groups. These were selected from a wide range of roles related to communication of science and management roles. For the selection and recruitment of the co-investigators, several criteria were taken into account to look for some heterogeneity (e.g., type of institutional functions, experience), and a list of potential co-investigators and participants was compiled. From this list, we identified three co-investigators and sent invitation emails.

In the invitation email, we introduced the aim of the POIESIS project, basic information about the focus groups such as date and duration, and a short description of their format, and we kindly requested the

co-investigators to identify 5 to 6 potential participants from their networks to be part of the focus groups.

The process of recruiting the co-investigators was smooth. One co-investigator expressed great interest and accepted our invitation immediately. One did not think she was qualified to perform the role of the co-investigator, but kindly accepted to get involved as a participant in one of the focus groups. A second invited co-investigator did not accept but recommended a colleague. Another targeted co-investigator never responded so we identified another contact who accepted.

The recruitment phase is often one of biggest challenges in such kind of projects. The most common mentioned reasons to reject an invitation had to do with the lack of time and their perception of lacking in skills to perform the role.

Training

The three co-investigators attended a training session online given by the French POIESIS team (CNRS), coordinator of the focus groups (WP3). After the training session, the national team sent the co-investigators a moderator's guideline (translated from POIESIS materials in English to Portuguese, provided by the partner coordinator of the focus groups), which had been presented and discussed in the training session, jointly with basic information about the project and their role. We also sent to each co-investigator the list of participants who had confirmed their presence in focus groups.

The co-investigators

The three co-investigators in the Lisbon focus groups were Maria João Leão, Rita Ferreira, and Cristina Soares.

Maria João Leão, is the coordinator of Citizen Science and Active Citizenship Program at the IGC, ITQB NOVA and Oeiras Valley. For 10 years, she was Executive Director of Marathon da Saúde and coordinated an awareness and fundraising program at IGC, where she established innovative partnerships with Everything is New / NOS Alive and Vista Alegre. Maria João Leão studied in Universidade de Coimbra, Universität Heidelberg and University of Leicester for her high education, all with specialization of biology, and she had a PhD from Imperial College, London, through the Gulbenkian Doctoral Program in Biology and Medicine (PGDBM). She is also part of the citizens panel of the European project IMPETUS.

Rita Ferreira is part of IN2PAST - Associated Laboratory for Research and Innovation in Heritage, Arts, Sustainability and Territory. Before that, she had a year and a half as Communications Manager at

the InnovPlantProtect Collaborative Laboratory (CoLAB) in Elvas, and a year in a similar role at IPRI-NOVA (Portuguese Institute of International Relations). With a bachelor degree in Communication Sciences, one of Journalism variant (pre-Bologna), Rita worked in media as diverse as *Diário Económico*, (new) *Vida Mundial* magazine, *Público* (Science and Technology editor) or *Quero Saber* (science magazine), as well as in other initiatives and roles, such as the project "Engenho e Obra: Engenharia em Portugal no século XX". She has extensive experience in content production and editing (planning, writing, editing, translation, proofreading, basic image and multimedia skills) and managing digital platforms (websites, social media, newsletters). In 2020, she taught the Science Journalism module of Iscte's Postgraduate Diploma in Journalism, involving in a Synthetic Biology project for the international iGEM competition, and co-organised and moderated a session on scientific uncertainty at the European Federation of Science Journalism conference. After more than 20 years in science and technology journalism, she turned to focus on non-journalistic Science Communication, then she got a Master's degree in Science Communication from NOVA FCSH/ ITQB NOVA in 2022.

Cristina Nobre Soares is a consultant in science communication and a copywriter who works at Claro. She writes the blog "Em Linha Recta" and is currently working on the "Clear abstracts in Portuguese" project at LEAF - Linking Landscape, Environment, Agriculture and Food. Cristina Nobre Soares graduated in Forestry Engineering and Natural Resources Management and worked at the Institute for Nature Conservation and Forests. She also taught cartography and remote sensing at the Polytechnic Institute of Tomar. She dedicates her life to stories, language, and communication. More than 400 researchers and technicians from various Portuguese universities, institutions and companies are estimated to have passed through her science communication courses.

Recruitment of participants for the focus groups

Due to the purposeful sample for our focus group, the snowball strategy was very useful and effective in recruiting other participants besides co-investigators. Our co-investigators suggested potential participants, which we combined with our own contact list. We contacted about 43 institutional stakeholders to participate in the focus groups. Of these, 21 accepted our invitation; 16 rejected referring lack of interest or no availability. Participants were distributed by the focus groups according to their professional background (research integrity and science communication), gender and experience to guarantee some heterogeneity.

There was no absence of participants for the focus groups, even despite the extreme weather with wind and heavy rain. And, we did not

have any special incentive strategies to ensure participants attended also suggesting a strong interest in the project and discussions to take place.

All participants received an eco-friendly bag from Iscte, a pen, a notebook, a bookmark and a brochure about CIES-Iscte. No monetary incentives were provided to participants.

The discussions

The terms 'public engagement' and 'involvement in science' were used instead of social integration, as these are the commonly used terms among the community of practitioners. The coordinator of POIESIS project in Portugal played the role of the co-moderator, supporting the co-investigator with the moderator guideline.

The three co-investigators all mentioned challenges in moderating these discussions concerning time management and control, how to use diplomatic language to keep the process flow, how to avoid group influence or bias, how to keep flexibility, and how to encourage all participants to contribute.

Recording the sessions

We used two audio recorders to secure the quality of 2 hours of recording for each face-to face focus group. During each focus group, we also took notes about the discussions. The audio recordings were transcribed, coded using a codebook scheme provided by the coordinators of the focus groups (CNRS), and analysed using the software MAXQDA. The qualitative analysis focused on five main dimensions: science and society, perceptions of trust in science, attitudes towards research integrity, attitudes towards social integration, institutional contributions to trust in science.

1.2 Participants in the focus group

The three focus groups involved 20 participants, moderated by the three co-investigators. Table 1 to 3 show the characteristics of the participants in the three focus groups (FG1, FG2, and FG3).

Table 1. Composition of FG1

Participant Id.	Gender	Career stage	Position	Institution
FG1_1	Female	Mid-career	Research Data Steward	Research Support Office, Iscte

FG1_2	Male	Senior	Research Management and Science Communication	IN2PAST Associated Laboratory
FG1_3	Male	Mid-career	Science communicator, activist, and facilitator of citizen science	Lisbon University
FG1_4	Female	Initial	Communication and Outreach Manager	Institute for Systems and Robotics, Técnico Polytechnic Institute of Lisbon
FG1_5	Female	Initial	Research and Quality Officer	Polytechnic Institute of Lisbon
FG1_6	Female	Mid-career	Science Communication Manager	Business Research Unit, Iscte

Table 2. Composition of FG2

Participant Id.	Gender	Career years	Position	Institution
FG2_1	Female	Senior	Coordinator of the Science and Society Centre	Municipality of Oeiras
FG2_2	Female	Senior	Head of Science Communication Office	ITQB NOVA
FG2_3	Male	Mid-career	Events and Projects Officer/ Science Communication Officer	European Animal Research Association
FG2_4	Female	Senior	Director	Bioethics Institute of the Portuguese Catholic University
FG2_5	Female	Mid-career	Team member of RM Roadmap	NOVA IMS

Table 3. Composition of FG3

Participant Id.	Gender	Career years	Position	Institution
FG3_1	Female	Mid-career	Member of the Board of Directors, responsible for Science Communication	MARE, University of Coimbra
FG3_2	Female	Mid-career	Science Manager	Research Centre LEAF, University of Lisbon
FG3_3	Female	Mid-career	Service Marketing and Community Outreach Officer	OPERAS Research Infrastructure

FG3_4	Male	Junior	Communication Officer	Centre for Functional Ecology, University of Coimbra
FG3_5	Female	Senior	Scientific consultant	European Science Foundation/ Green Media
FG3_6	Male	Senior	Principal Researcher	Centre for Functional Ecology, University of Coimbra
FG3_7	Male	Senior	Director of the Portuguese Journal of Social Science	Iscte
FG3_8	Male	Senior	Communication and project management officer	UC Exploratório - Centro Ciência Viva Coimbra
FG3_9	Female	Mid-career	Communications and Marketing Manager	FSC Portugal

2 Sequential description of the focus groups

In this section, we briefly describe the main topics discussed, the dynamics of the discussion, and the facilitation process in each focus group. Our purpose is to provide a comprehensive understanding of how participants interacted with each other and how the discussion was guided and managed by the moderator to achieve the goals.

2.1 Focus group 1

In this focus group, all the topics in the moderator's guide were discussed, although more superficially than in the other groups. The discussion focused particularly on ways of involving the public in science, what is already being done by institutions and what can still be done.

The co-investigator took an assertive stance in conducting the conversation and managing time, ensuring that all questions were asked and steering the discussion back on track whenever necessary. There were two dominant voices in this group. Participants agreed on almost all the topics discussed, and the atmosphere was respectful.

2.2 Focus group 2

In this group, conversation about scientific integrity was considerably longer than that of the other groups and with the deeper insights. Some participants disagreed on the role of individual characteristics (vs. institutional pressures) in misconduct, but there was an attempt by the co-investigator to build consensus.

The co-investigator showed a flexible attitude and gave the participants complete latitude to answer the open-ended questions, without guiding the discussion. There were two to three dominant voices in all the topics, and there was one quieter individual who participated considerably less than the others.

2.3 Focus group 3

In this focus group, most of the conversation was around the relationship between science and society and on social integration. Participants also spent much of their time talking about the different publics of science, how to reach them and attract them to science, including using new voices.

The co-investigator took a more directive stance when approaching the participants, by calling their name and asking their opinion about the topic being discussed. By encouraging their participation, all

participants answered to all questions. The tone was conducive to open communication and an inclusive environment.

3 Building trust in science: from perception to institutional engagement

To what extent and how can institutions provide policies and procedures that enable researchers to act in ways that can foster public trust in science? In this section, we answer to the main four questions of this study, presenting a summary of the results emerging from the three focus groups in Portugal. The original quotes are in Annex B.

3.1 About science and society

All participants in the three focus groups answered to the question “What words do you spontaneously associate with the relationship between science and society?”. We organise the list of words in two dimensions, according to its meaning. The first dimension embraces the **characteristics** of this relationship, including positive, negative, and neutral characteristics. Examples of words mentioned are openness, accountability, co-construction, and collaboration. The second dimension refers to the (possible) **outcomes** of the relationship science-society and examples of words are impact, transformation, risk and benefits. The full table with all the words mentioned by the participants are in Annex A.

Besides mentioning the words, FG2 and FG3 also discussed more deeply this relationship, exploring the meaning of some of the words. In participants’ view, there is a **gap between what scientists think that society needs and what society really wants and/or needs**. Thus, they argued that listening to people and involving citizens in the definition of the projects’ goals are a moral **responsibility** of scientists – science must give an answer to the real problems of society and **transform people’s lives** in a positive way. According to the participants, this level of involvement, based on **co-construction/co-creation** methodologies, will allow a true **partnership, connection** between science/scientists and society, **strengthening** their relationship.

3.2 Perceptions of trust in science

Participants in the three focus groups believed that **trust in science** and scientists is **high** in Portugal. However, they pointed out that there is, on the one hand, a **growing questioning of how science is done** and, on the other, an expectation that science will **discover definitive truths**, which can sometimes be perceived as a lack of trust, but is not necessarily so.

No crisis of trust in science

Most participants were of the opinion that, in Portugal, there is **no crisis of trust in science** from the general public. Some participants mentioned that there is even data (e.g., Eurobarometer) showing that scientists are respected and more trusted than other institutions such as the Government or people like politicians. They highlighted that there is no systematic distrust in science, particularly when compared to countries like the United States of America (USA), and the mistrust is punctual, isolated, and more related to institutions – sometimes related to the political power – and not specific to science. Even when there is false information circulating, such as false scientific studies, science is not generally discredited, in participants' beliefs.

Science under scrutiny: more questioning by the public

In FG3, most participants agreed that there is **increasing scrutiny of science by the public**, which might convey the feeling of greater distrust in science. However, this is a false idea in participant's perspective since more questioning cannot be understood as a generalised breach of trust ("Questioning is not a general breach of trust." – FG3_8). In fact, participants suggested that this should be interpreted in a positive way, meaning that more people critically analyse scientific information, and they perceive that science communicators are taking on an increasingly important role in the relationship between science and society.

"Our aim is also to give people the tools to ask questions. Working on literacy is also about that." (FG3_4)

Science is not an absolute truth forever

Participants stated that distrust might be, instead, **misunderstanding of how science works, lack of knowledge of the scientific process**, its **uncertainty, mutability**, and underlying philosophy of 'trial and error', aggravated by the lack of consensus among researchers on scientific findings. In participants' views, this is understandable as society expects science to have all the solid answers it does not always have and there is always unpredictability, a characteristic

that stands out in some contexts like the COVID-19 pandemic. For example, participants in FG2 mentioned the pandemic as an example of science's uncertainty and, despite that, they believe that the pandemic reinforced people's trust in science.

"On the one hand, science is expected to have all the answers... And now with the pandemic, it has been very curious to see this whole process play out in the public sphere and show what we all know, that it [the scientific process] is not a straight line. (...) I think the pandemic has helped to strengthen the image of science to some extent. (...) The scientific process is not made up of certainties, it's made up of trial and error." (FG2_2)

The same points are seen in other participants' voices:

"Researchers take a topic that has already been researched, continue researching it and then come up with different results... Or even controversial situations (...). The Earth used to be flat and now it's round. Because someone questioned it." (FG3_9)

"The question of science being something that one day is true, another day is not... (...) And for scientists that's the advancement of science and for other people that might be what leads to greater mistrust." (FG3_6)

In this regard, participants saw **science communication** having a relevant role in public understanding of science, by explaining the **process** and not only the results from scientific studies, helping people to understand what science is and what is not (e.g., it is not pseudoscience). Laypeople need to have scientific literacy to know how to interpret information, evaluate its quality and avoid manipulation, for example: *"This sample is representative of this context."* (FG2_4). Furthermore, science communication can be used to **situating scientific knowledge**, defining who the target audience of the communication is and what information should be shared.

"When I want to show, for example, what is being done in zootechnics, the researchers themselves are very afraid... For example, the photographs have to be taken from a certain angle because they want to convey to the outside world the idea that there is no mistreatment of animals - and there isn't, of course. (...) They are very careful about how the message can be captured and then passed on. Because they want to avoid misinterpretations of what is being done." (FG3_2).

Even though the participants believe there is no crisis of trust in science, they identified a few situations and contexts that might

lead to distrust. One of these situations refers to cases of **lack of integrity**, usually when a scientist shows misconduct, and the other to the context of certain groups that show **radical and denialist views** about science.

Scientific integrity: transparency and openness

The basis of trust in science seems to be shaken, in the view of the participants in FG1, when an **authority figure who represents science shows misconduct** and, because of their notoriety, the episode can affect science's image. Still, in participants' opinion this is interpreted as an isolated, not common case for most people. One participant pointed out that perhaps it is the scientific community itself that gives more importance to these wrong behaviours than the public.

"I think there may be some mistrust on the part of the public, but I think there's a lot of mistrust on the part of scientists towards themselves, towards each other."
(FG1_2)

Furthermore, two participants from FG1 and FG2 mentioned that research funding organisations have been investing some efforts to foster transparency and open science practices (e.g., sharing data, open access publications) to extend the network of people that can access the information. In this way, funding institutions can contribute to maintain and increase people's trust in science.

"From the perspective of funders, there has been an effort to define requirements so that knowledge can be opened up, so that these practices are transparent, open and anyone can replicate, have access, can be the scientist themselves." (FG1_1)

"Not in my backyard" and the radical movements

Participants in FG3 commented that there seems to be more mistrust in science when the subject is close to us - the **"not in my backyard" effect**: *"For example, in relation to incinerators. That's ok, but if it's not in the space that concerns me."* (FG3_2). Environment, particularly the role of humanity in climate change, and health were the two topics that participants in the three focus groups mentioned as more sensitive for most people because they generate fear or make people feel they are at risk. These topics also attract more *"irrational perspectives"* and *"radical movements"* in society (FG3_7). Agriculture was also a 'hot topic' in the FG3 debate, considering the farmers protest across Europe at the time.

"There is no reason to think that there is mistrust in science. However, there are certain attitudes, increasingly present in contemporary society, that are blatantly anti-

science. And I think it's very difficult to fight such attitudes with the weapons of science.” (FG3_7)

3.3. Attitudes towards research integrity

Despite receiving less attention in the discussions, integrity was an important topic for the participants and often came up in connection with the impact of science on society and public trust in science. Participants mostly addressed the **definition of integrity**, described as both **individual characteristics and actions**, such as being honest, rigorous, and respectful throughout the scientific process, giving credit to all authors, acknowledging mistakes, and **institutional actions**, such as creating procedures and structures to foster integrity. They also shared their views on the **motives to engage in misconduct**, highlighting **the pressure to publish** associated to performance evaluation and career progression of researchers.

The conceptualization of integrity

In the three focus groups, participants defined integrity as both an **individual** characteristic of ethical virtues of “doing good” and an **institutional** requirement for an ethics culture. For most participants, it was also easier to state what integrity is not (i.e., to use the definition in the negative) than what integrity is.

“There are also personal positions in relation to ethics. (...) There are things that aren't written in codes, but which have to do with our ability to respond [publicly] to others.” (FG1_3)

“There has to be a surrounding environment for the person to put these [ethical] principles into practice.” (FG2_3)

“A researcher with integrity is careful in their processes, respectful of their objects of research, and careful in ethical terms. (...) They are careful when disseminating the products of their research with very strict ethical guidelines. This involves (...) publishing in open access, different types of communication products to achieve conversations with different audiences. And also, be very strict with those who are defining public policies.” (FG3_7)

Individual actions and characteristics

As individual actions and characteristics, participants thought that integrity is what **should be done** instead of what can be done, a responsibility of the researcher to be **honest**, to be careful with their words so as **not to make empty promises** or **assert certainties**

with total confidence. Accountability, care, and rigour throughout the research process (from defining goals to communicating results with society and funders), and respect for the objects of investigation were also pointed out as important characteristics of integrity. Lack of integrity also includes failing to **give due credit** to all authors, publishing in predatory journals, which are known to facilitate the peer review process and the respective publication, and not **acknowledging mistakes** if they have made them.

"Publications that researchers make and that sometimes it happens that a paper appears with just the teacher's name and then the student says "that was my work"." (FG1_6)

"[Integrity] is showing what you are doing without seeming like it is more than what it is. Say "Be careful, I only went this far. Let's differentiate what this could be for, where we are." (FG2_2)

"[A scientist with integrity is] someone who is open to scrutiny and, if there are mistakes, is willing to own them." (FG3_3)

In participants' words, a scientist with integrity is one who **follows the codes of conduct** of the institution and the European Commission, the ALLEA Code – the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity. However, some participants were not sure if all the scientists would know these European guidelines.

Few participants also mentioned that a scientist with integrity is also someone who **integrates younger researchers** into the lab, **provides support, distributes funding** according to fair and transparent rules, who answers to others when questioned about a particular subject.

"The concept of integrity is new and never completely fixed. (...) The lack of integrity can range from publishing in one's own name without crediting others to limiting funding... For example, at the institute we realised at some point that the way the group coordinators distributed the money was always by twos or threes, and the rest received a "no". It wasn't transparent at all... Until we changed the rules." (FG1_2)

Although less discussed in the three focus groups, **providing** the necessary **information to enable the replication** of studies (i.e., replicability) and **disclosing conflicts of interest** were also mentioned as important individual actions for scientific integrity.

"With regard to the funding of research to a researcher working in a public institution, in the case of the medical sciences, this question is often raised by conflicts of interest and the suspicions that exist because certain

studies are paid for by pharmaceutical companies. This can generate some mistrust.” (FG3_2)

It is interesting to note that participants agreed that **misconduct is not common** and sometimes it results from mistakes or ignorance. Therefore, it is necessary to humanise the scientist, to show that they are not perfect, they are not magicians but also, they are not evil geniuses or villains, they are human.

“I don't think lack of integrity is that common. I honestly think that most people do research with integrity.” (FG1_5)

Institutional actions

Institutions have the duty to create an ethics culture that should be more than rules. In one participant's words: *“Ethics is not aesthetics of the discourse” (FG2_4)*. However, participants suggested that creating **internal procedures and structures** for ethics may be the easiest way to develop this culture. They suggested specifically elaborating a document with ethical guidelines for researchers and creating an Ethics Council or Committee, but also guarantee that their staff are aware of this code. Some participants shared that these already exist in their institutions, but other participants were not certain about existed in their organisations. Offices for reporting misconduct do not appear to exist in most the participants' institutions.

“In my institution, I don't know what the procedure is when there's a more complex [ethical] situation. I'd say you'd have to go to the management [of the research centre] for the management to see how to handle things.” (FG2_2)

The rules for **giving authorship credit** for a publication was mainly discussed in FG2, considering that some journals and publishers already have very specific rules for this attribution and that there is sometimes confusion between the research team and the authorship of a publication. For some participants, it is still not clear what criteria should be used for recognising authorship, especially considering that it greatly depends on the scientific areas and the methodological processes. This topic deserves, in their opinion, more discussion at the institutional level.

“The point is to define from the beginning who will appear as the author of this publication. (...) It could be a way to solve this problem from an organizational point of view. (...) But it's often case by case.” (FG2_4)

Views on motives for misconduct

Participants' discussions also went on to justify why they thought scientists engage in misconduct. In their perspective, there are a number of factors that interact to explain misconduct in research, but some seem more relevant than others and **institutional aspects** assumed particular relevance in the discourse of participants from the three focus groups. Particularly, the **pressure to publish** was emphasised as one of the main motives for misconduct. Still, few participants argued that researchers can never avoid being held individually responsible for their misconduct: *"Individually giving in to [institutional] pressure has an impact on science, trust in science, and what science is."* (FG2_4). Thus, individual character and personality also play a role in misconduct: *"The perception of integrity is different from person to person. It depends on the personality."* (FG2_5).

"If I'm already a person who doesn't prioritise professional ethics, I'll always find a way round it."
(FG3_2)

Pressure to publish and performance evaluation

The **pressure to publish**, and a **performance evaluation and career progression** of researchers **based on metrics**, constitute an environment that is not conducive to integrity, one of the factors most mentioned by participants in the three focus groups. This "publish or perish" philosophy may *"justify the dubious practices, which may increase distrust in science"* (FG1_1). Furthermore, research funding depends heavily on the researcher's CV and values the quantity (vs. quality) of publications.

"There's a lot of pressure for researchers to have CVs with lots of papers, lots of papers, the number. It's the number that counts. Quality, at a certain point, was no longer relevant." (FG3_1)

Error tolerance in the institutional context can affect people's behaviour: *"The pressure on a person not to make mistakes can lead to misconduct"* (FG2_3). Misconduct can also be explained by **ignorance** due to the lack of institutional norms or structures for ethics or due to lack of training.

Predatory journals

Participants also talked about **predatory journals** and their aggressive practices as a seduction mechanism for researchers to publish a lot, very quickly and in open access. This subject was discussed further in FG3. However, one participant in this group highlighted that it is not only predatory journals but also some top journals facilitate the publication by certain researchers because

of their names and friendships with journal editors. Besides predatory journals, this one participant also mentioned the huge number of **retracted articles** in top journals in some scientific areas. In her opinion, this

"There are also top journals that, regardless of peer review, find it easier to publish when they are friends of friends. And I know this from personal experience." (FG3_5)

3.4. Attitudes towards social integration

In the three focus groups, participants considered that, in Portugal, there are already a number of interesting activities that promote public involvement in science, but they still identified some gaps: a) in the **type of publics** that get involved and those that are still left out, b) in the different **phases of the scientific process**, with the initial phases still not taking the public's voice into account, c) the (temporal) **continuity** of activities. Participants also briefly mentioned that journalism is losing its importance in science communication and other means of communication and voices need to be considered.

The type of publics: need to go beyond the 'converted'

Regarding the different publics of science, several participants in the three focus groups mentioned that scientific institutions and scientists keep "**preaching to the converted**" and it is difficult to engage the *other public*, those who do not attend events such as the European Night of Researchers, science fairs, and do not go to museums, etc. For example, in participants' opinion it is common to see adults accompanied by children and teenagers (i.e., families) at various science events, but it is less common to see only adults. There are many events aimed at children and young people, especially in the school context, such as science clubs, where the researcher and the students jointly present their projects.

"The school public is an audience that is, in a way, easy to work with because they are captive in the sense that they are captive in a classroom, with a teacher who is going to make that decision. (...) And science reaches a large group. (...) Citizen science projects are very good for involving adult audiences, we can reach adult audiences much more easily. (...) I feel that there is a certain embarrassment on the part of adults to take part, or to step in front of a child to, I don't know, look under a microscope." (FG2_2)

In the opinion of the participants, it is therefore important to rethink the 'general approach' to public involvement in science,

starting by asking: **who is the public?** What are the specific groups we want to communicate to? Answering to these questions can be very helpful for institutions to be able to contribute to trust in science.

"There is no general group. We have to work for groups, define our audience, who it is, this is very difficult and then try to evaluate it, which is also very difficult."
(FG3_4)

In the discourse of most of the participants, the idea of the public was usually **people in general**, but sometimes other groups were highlighted, such as companies. Some participants suggested that research is important to respond to real business problems.

Participation in the scientific process: need for involving the public in all phases of research

One of the recurring ideas in the three discussions was that the public cannot be mere recipients of information like in a traditional top-down approach: *"We produce our research, we find a way to wrap it up and deliver it, but I think the most interesting thing is not to deliver the information already prepared, but to involve people from the beginning"* (FG3_2). Participants advocated that a deeper involvement from people in science requires **co-design methodologies**, with the identification of society's needs, interests, goals, and priorities for science, moving away from the idea that the citizen is just an executor of a task.

"Citizen science projects are a good example. It's not just a way of publicising science, but also of involving citizens and turning them into scientists. They learn by doing."
(FG2_1)

"Researchers in the field of diabetes are working hard to lower glucose levels, to control glucose levels. But often patients already have that part sorted out and what they want is solutions for other things in their lives, such as sexual impotence, being able to do sport. And researchers don't know this." (FG2_3)

This full participation in the scientific process also includes **giving the results back** to the participants, which will contribute to demonstrate the social impact of projects - i.e., the **social value of research** (e.g., behaviour change, strategies for promoting care, etc.). This already happens in health projects, where patients and/or patients' families have a say in the course of research, including the **distribution of funding**. However, in other scientific fields is not that common and could be difficult to implement.

"In the case of a research centre that works only with Parkinson's, we could have someone from civil society,

someone who represents Parkinson's patients, a patients' association, for example, present on a scientific council, and who actually dictates the institute's research policies and which projects should be submitted for funding." (FG2_3)

This collaboration can take different forms, such as being a member of a citizens' council or assembly, inviting people to attend meetings of scientific institutions or research groups. In such events, researchers can listen to the public's ideas, understand their problems, and having a voice can trigger more motivation and enthusiasm for science. Non-profit organizations can be important partners for academia in involving the public in science.

"Promoting scientific literacy shouldn't just be about "sitting down" science, like talks or conferences. It is not productive." (FG2_1)

One of the questions raised in the three focus groups was about the **representation of citizens** in assemblies or other citizens' groups. Participants questioned which individuals should be invited to participate in the scientific process, how citizen participation in debates and decision-making can be democratic.

Scientists can have very different roles in citizen science projects. One participant in FG1 mentioned that in some scientific areas like archaeology, public integration in science should be careful and supervised by the researcher.

Continuity of the activities: need for long-term collaboration

The proximity between science and society requires a process of **long-term collaboration**, which takes time to establish but pays off. This ongoing dialogue is what makes it possible to create an **open-door environment** all year round, breaking barriers and being accountable.

"This closeness of relationship takes time to create. We moved here [Figueira da Foz] exactly to get closer to society. It was a long process, but it bore fruit. We now work with several companies and not just in the context of: they come and ask for a service, we do it, they pay. It really is a process of total collaboration. Often, they have an idea, they ask if we can bring that idea to life (...) and the process evolves." (FG3_1)

In FG1, one of the participants questioned the place of fundamental science in this discussion about public involvement in science.

Voices of science: need for clarification who should communicate science

One of the topics discussed in FG2 was **science journalism** and the **media crisis**. Participants considered that the space for science in the media has decreased in recent years, and that there are few newspapers and journalists specialising in this topic. The newspaper “Jornal Público” is an exception and its journalists know how to reach people using simple language, such as infographics. However, for participants, it is not clear who are the actors responsible for communicating science in Portugal. Some participants questioned whose role this should be in different channels (e.g., newspapers, TV programmes) and who the audiences of these different channels are.

“Often in prime-time news, when there is news that corresponds to pseudo-science, we need to have a scientist, a science communicator who comes to present it in a way “for geeks”, that we can understand.” (FG2_4)

In FG2, few participants suggested that popular books written by scientists to the general public, using plain, clear language, cartoons, etc., are important for communicating science. One participant commented that she was in the presentation of the book “The End of the World in Underpants” where several experts and science communicators in Portugal describe different apocalyptic scenarios in a scientific but also entertaining way, with illustrations and organisation by one communicator and social media influencer. Following this example, some participants asked who the **new voices of science** communication are and what the role of “influencers” can be. They left the question unanswered but suggested that this should be further discussed in the future.

3.5. Institutional contributions to trust in science

Breaking the barriers between scientific institutions and the public is key for participants, enhancing the accountability of scientists, institutions, and science in general. Institutions can implement some measures to foster integrity and social integration and, ultimately, increase trust in science. The promotion of an **ethics culture** should prioritise, according to participants, a) **training** researchers in integrity, b) fostering **discussions** on integrity, c) encouraging a **culture of open access**, d) **discouraging** publication in **predatory journals**, e) **revising** the performance **evaluation system** of researchers, and f) **creating** a **new** institutional **role** such as an **ethics officer**.

Social integration requires, in the opinion of the participants, a well-defined strategy to **bring the public closer to science**, using **science communication** and investing in the development of truly **participatory projects** in a bottom-up approach.

Scientific integrity

Training researchers in integrity

Initial and continued **training** researchers in integrity was the first measure proposed by participants in the three focus groups, from junior researchers such as master students to senior researchers. Training researchers, **organising workshops**, seminars and conferences about integrity in research for capacity-building of researchers and the staff who supports these people will contribute to a culture of scientific integrity, where everyone is responsible for compliance with the institution's **code of conduct**. In FG2, participants even suggested that formal education should prepare young people for integrity, starting in primary school and teaching, for example, basic rules for searching for information and referencing sources.

"I very much associate integrity with information literacy. From the first years of school, students must learn the basic rules of research, citation, referencing, and communication." (FG2_1)

In these events to promote scientific integrity, people should discuss the institutions' code of ethics, identify their personal ethical values and principles, and find out the individual and institutional responsibilities.

"When we see a lot of projects with the same [ethical] problem, we organise a workshop to build capacity, to clarify things." (FG2_4)

Foster (continuous) discussion on integrity

For participants, it is also important to foster a continued discussion on integrity, creating **forums** where people can read documents with guidelines from the European Commission or scientific national institutions, debate these and their application. Institutional representatives can then update their institutional guidelines and plans and communicate these to their staff (officers, researchers, students, etc.). This would contribute for a better understanding of why it is important to implement practices in the institution and what benefits could be extracted from such practices.

"When I went to work on the data, the presentation was "We have to do this because it's FCT policy". That's a terrible thing to say to someone! Let's say why it's worth doing this, what the benefit is, why people will gain from the records, then how they can take advantage of them." (FG1_2)

Encourage a culture of open access

Encouraging **open access publishing** through agreements such as with b-on and making **data available** can contribute to trust in science. Also, one participant stated that **Diamond Open Access Hub** is an important way to boost the visibility and openness of scholarly publications to other scientists - who might not have access to it - and to the public. As these journals do not charge fees to readers, all interested people can access scientific information. Also, by eliminating the fees in Diamond Open Access journal, authors can widen their publication opportunities, considering more and new alternatives. of these measures can increase transparency and openness in the scientific process, which will strengthen trust in science.

"In Portugal, there are transformative agreements by b-on in which there is the possibility of publishing in open access, but in journals that are not in this group considered potentially predatory." (FG3_2)

However, because cultures are difficult to change and resistance could be high, **funding agencies** can catalyse a change of perspective on ethics, at the individual level (i.e., researchers who seek funding for their projects) and at the institutional level (i.e., research centres that receive funding).

"Research funding today requires open science. Open science practices are now a requirement in European funding and increasingly in national funding." (FG3_3)

In the view of the participants, a starting point could be the creation and implementation of concrete measures by funding agencies such as the European Commission or, in Portugal, the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT). The FG1 participants gave the example of the obligatory data management plan, a deliverable in European projects, and soon also a **requirement for obtaining national funding**.

"The institutions are part of larger institutions, and these larger institutions are part of the Ministry of Science and Technology and an FCT that has always had in mind, lately, the question of statistics, rankings, etc, compared to the European ones." (FG3_5)

Discourage publication in predatory journals

Institutions should also **discourage publication in predatory journals**, identify publishers that are not recommended for publication and provide a list of journals that would not be considered for awards or performance evaluation.

"This year we changed the rules for awarding research prizes to make researchers aware of the aggressive practices of publishers, journals, conferences. (...) There is no

database yet, but common procedures have already been identified for all these predatory publishers and journals.” (FG1_1)

“In my research centre, there are certain editorial groups which, although not closed to researchers, are strongly discouraged.” (FG3_2)

Evaluation system of researchers (re)considered

Considering the central role that the pressure to publish played in the participants' discourse to justify misconduct, participants in the three focus groups suggested a **revision of the performance evaluation system of researchers and professors**, which should be less focused on metrics or quantitative indicators and more focused on impact and benefits of research for society. In FG3, participants also suggested that all scientific outputs should be valued such as open access books and not only scientific papers. Few participants in the three focus groups mentioned their participation in the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (COARA).

“We're in COARA, a European group where research evaluation models are being questioned, particularly to deal with this “publish or perish” pressure. (...) Today there's also a lot of talk about the impact that research has on society.” (FG1_1)

Moreover, some participants suggested that **rewarding researchers** who comply with the ethical principles of research could also be a starting point to promote a culture of integrity.

“There's a lot of talk abroad, in the Netherlands and perhaps the UK, about data champions. Basically, it rewards the researcher with the most datasets deposited or... (...) It helps with the cultural change that is so slow and so difficult to achieve.” (FG1_1)

Need for an officer on ethics/integrity

Furthermore, participants in FG2 suggested that research projects should be discussed between the research team and a procurer for ethics in the institution, which would imply to create a new role in most institutions - an **ethics officer or procurer**. These officers would also be responsible for receiving and handling allegations of unethical behaviour in the institution.

“An ombudsman in the area of ethics and integrity to whom these situations of suspected deviation, misconduct or harassment are reported (...) And to be able to subject the situations to scrutiny.” (FG2_4)

"Last year, we set up the researcher ombudsman to try to understand the reasons why researchers behave the way they do, like misconduct in research." (FG3_1)

Social integration

Increase proximity between scientists and the public

In participants' view, to increase public's trust in science institutions should **Increase the proximity between the public and scientists**, using different tools and mediators such as science communication by communicators and scientists, participatory projects, citizens' assemblies, popular books, among others.

Moreover, it is crucial to open the scientific space to communities. When citizens are invited for the physical space of institutions, buildings should be designed and built to favour this openness without walls, more collaborative spaces, desacralizing the university or research institute.

"Our institution wants to bring citizens closer to space. It is not necessarily about research, teaching, but about space. Desacralize the space, to show that it's the citizen's space." (FG1_2)

"A few years ago, this was seen as a temple of science. Kids come here and see the great wonders that science has produced, and they worship them. The idea of the Church metaphor. And now we become a forum. It is a place where either a businessman, a scientist or a citizen can come together." (FG3_8)

One important idea is **questioning who the public is** we want to communicate to and defining its characteristics to prevent science from reaching only those who already know about it and are involved in its projects. The biggest challenge of social integration is, in the view of the participants, to attract new people to science-related events and activities, create networks and establish new partnerships.

In this sense, one challenge identified by FG2 was the 'coastality' in Portugal (i.e., regional inequality between the coast and the interior) and the difficulty in reaching people in the interior, where there are much less universities, research centres, laboratories and other scientific infrastructures. For example, the European Researchers' Night should be geographically expanded to other regions of Portugal.

Science communication as key

Science communication was one of the most mentioned mediation channels in this process of bringing science and society closer together, and science communicators played a leading role. Most participants identified the need for reinforcement of the **capacity building** of science communication offices in institutions, providing **more resources** to each and **creating synergies** between them. For example, research centres can work together with other entities whose purpose is to promote science and scientific culture (e.g., UC Exploratório - Centro Ciência Viva). According to participants, this would help to define a medium and long-term strategy for science communication.

"Communication offices that are more effective, more complete, more complementary, and less precarious, more consolidated. So that they [the offices] can do more medium- and long-term work." (FG3_6)

Moreover, science has to find different, **simple and attractive ways of communicating results**, and here researchers can use new tools. In the FG3, participants suggested video-abstracts and clear abstracts as two interesting tools for dissemination. Video-abstract is an educational tool to create bridges between academia and schools, where video is seen as a new language for communicating science, with a very appealing graphic side. Clear abstracts are summaries of scientific articles in simple, plain language and in Portuguese, which makes it easier for many people to understand the subject.

Increase participatory projects

Participatory projects, in the sense of a truly empowered participation of the public in science, should also be a priority for researchers and institutions in participants' views. These are co-creation projects, where the **public has an active role**, is willing and capable to do research, and available to engage in a dialogue with scientists, and both parties can use this space to clarify doubts, share concerns and indecisions. Public and scientists can exchange experiences and knowledge to find solutions to real problems. One participant shared information about a platform where scientists can meet people from civil society and other associations, they can collaborate, they can create a project and see funding opportunities for the project.

"A citizen science that does not involve a top-down approach, but that sees others in society as a true partner. (...) Thinking together the scientific problem is one of the things we have to do, this collaboration has to be from the beginning." (FG3_3)

This could be understood from the Social Movement Perspective (Ryan, 2006) that considers that people can participate in society in different ways, be interested in different topics (e.g., economy, culture, human rights), and that this participation should empower people to influence the direction of their lives. For example, the public should decide what should be achieved in science and how.

In this sense, participants suggested that researchers should **develop and consider new ways of auscultating the citizens** at a local and regional level such as assemblies for citizens or other specific groups (e.g., teachers, parents, people living in specific neighbourhoods). Thus, cooperating with local institutions/municipalities and organised movements (i.e., local associations) is imperative.

"During the pandemic, we held an online teachers' assembly. and out of that came I don't know how many projects, which were done at their request. They'd say to us "We need this" and we'd say "OK, let's do this". Now we have plans to work with parents' associations and neighbourhoods." (FG2_2)

One participant suggested that, for example, scientific institutions can cooperate with senior universities to attract older adults to science activities. Another participant gave an example of collaboration between science and society, **VERA**, which is an online collaboration platform where professionals, practitioners and researchers can build social sciences and humanities research projects together.

"Listening to people's needs is one way to start. Meeting what is actually a real problem in society and needs to be solved." (FG2_1)

"One of the ways to do this is to invite society to be part of a council, a group of citizens (...) who can be an external eye, provide input, point the finger, encourage the advancement of research." (FG3_9)

3.6. Other themes

There were no other themes to report here.

4. Conclusion

The three focus groups that took place in Lisbon, Portugal, involved 20 participants who shared their views as practitioners in science integration and integrity in Portuguese institutions and/or projects.

Participants generally agreed that the level of public trust in science is high in Portugal. They do not consider that there is a crisis of trust in science, but they do think that there is growing questioning of the scientific process by a more informed and educated public – to which science communication has been contributing. This is seen in a positive light and as a result of the gradual opening up of science (e.g., more transparency, open science).

In Portugal, from the participants' perspective, **integrity has a long way to go**: we need to put this topic on the public agenda, discuss it with different actors and make it concrete through guidelines for institutions. This need can be seen in the **general lack of human resources** working specifically on integrity in scientific institutions in Portugal. In the case of institutions that have an ethics committee, it is common for researchers and teachers to be involved as members, accumulating this task with their other duties. The **pressure to publish** associated to the performance evaluation and career progression of researchers was one of the most mentioned determinants for misconduct.

Training on integrity issues, well-defined and useful **guidelines**, and communication of such can contribute to develop a **culture of open science** and **good research practices**. Also, the creation of **new roles** for integrity officers and the inclusion of integrity as a requirement for national and international funding were seen as priorities by the participants, which may ultimately lead to a culture of ethics in scientific institutions.

While integrity is seen as needing more developments and measures, **social integration needs better** ones. Participants argued that there are already many initiatives to involve the public, but these do not seem to be effective for all: some types of publics are still not interested or do not participate in science, some regions of the country do not have access science initiatives, and often the most appropriate channels or language are not used to capture the public's attention. In this context, participants discussed the need to increase the **proximity between scientists and society** by using new tools to **communicate science**. One group raised the question who are the **new voices in science**? In addition to scientists and science communicators, there are other mediators between science and society: In the future it will be interesting to consider who these actors are, what channels they use to communicate and how effective their communication is.

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Appendix

Annex A

List of words about the relationship between science and society

Table A. List of all the words used to describe the relationship between science and society in the three focus groups

Characteristics	Outcomes
Openness	Impact
Trust	Transformation
Insufficiency, (being) far behind	Potential
Bridges	Salvation
Strengthening the relationship	Service
Indicators	Hope
Narrative	Better decisions
Co-creativity	Sharing benefits
Co-construction/co-creation	Risk
Collaboration	
Participation	
Inclusion	
Citizen/citizenship	
People	
Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)	
Transparency	
Partnership	
Connection	
Responsibility	
Accountability	
Power	
Sharing	
Reluctance	
Knowledge vs. Ignorance	
Education	
Barrier	
Subsidiarity	
Integrity and ethics	
Technical	
Difficult	
Clarity	
Emotions	

Annex B

Quotes presented in the original language and the English translation

Table B. Quotes presented in the original language and the English translation

Original quote (PT)	Translated quote (EN)
<i>Perceptions of trust in science</i>	
O nosso objetivo também é dar às pessoas as ferramentas para fazerem perguntas. Trabalhar na literacia também tem a ver com isso. (FG3_4)	Our aim is also to give people the tools to ask questions. Working on literacy is also about that. (FG3_4)
Por um lado, espera-se que a ciência tenha todas as respostas... E agora, com a pandemia, tem sido muito curioso ver todo este processo na praça pública e mostrar aquilo que todos sabemos, que ele [o processo científico] não é uma linha direita. (...) Acho que a pandemia ajudou a fortalecer a imagem da ciência até certo ponto. (...) O processo científico não é feito de certezas, é feito de tentativa e erro. (FG2_2)	On the one hand, science is expected to have all the answers... And now with the pandemic, it has been very curious to see this whole process play out in the public sphere and show what we all know, that it [the scientific process] is not a straight line. (...) I think the pandemic has helped to strengthen the image of science to some extent. (...) The scientific process is not made up of certainties, it's made up of trial and error. (FG2_2)
Os investigadores pegam num tema que já foi investigado, continuam a investigá-lo e depois chegam a resultados diferentes... Ou mesmo situações polémicas (...). A Terra era plana e agora é redonda. Porque alguém o questionou. (FG3_9)	Researchers take a topic that has already been researched, continue researching it and then come up with different results... Or even controversial situations (...). The Earth used to be flat and now it's round. Because someone questioned it. (FG3_9)
A questão de a ciência ser uma coisa que um dia é verdade, outro dia não é... (...) E para os cientistas isso é o avanço da ciência e para as outras pessoas isso pode ser o que leva a uma maior desconfiança. (FG3_6)	The question of science being something that one day is true, another day is not... (...) And for scientists that's the advancement of science and for other people that might be what leads to greater mistrust. (FG3_6)
Esta amostra é representativa deste contexto. (FG2_4)	This sample is representative of this context. (FG2_4)
Quando eu quero mostrar, por exemplo, o que se faz na zootecnia, os próprios investigadores têm muito medo... Por exemplo, as fotografias têm de ser tiradas de um determinado ângulo, porque eles querem passar para o exterior a ideia de que não há maus-tratos aos animais -	When I want to show, for example, what is being done in zootechnics, the researchers themselves are very afraid... For example, the photographs have to be taken from a certain angle because they want to convey to the outside world the idea that there is no mistreatment of

<p>e não há, claro. (...) Eles têm muito cuidado com a forma como a mensagem pode ser captada e depois transmitida. Porque querem evitar interpretações erradas do que está a ser feito. (FG3_2)</p>	<p>animals - and there isn't, of course. (...) They are very careful about how the message can be captured and then passed on. Because they want to avoid misinterpretations of what is being done. (FG3_2)</p>
<p>Penso que pode haver alguma desconfiança por parte do público, mas penso que há muita desconfiança por parte dos cientistas em relação a si próprios, em relação uns aos outros. (FG1_2)</p>	<p>I think there may be some mistrust on the part of the public, but I think there's a lot of mistrust on the part of scientists towards themselves, towards each other. (FG1_2)</p>
<p>Do ponto de vista dos financiadores, tem havido um esforço para definir requisitos para que o conhecimento possa ser aberto, para que estas práticas sejam transparentes, abertas e qualquer pessoa possa replicar, ter acesso, ser o próprio cientista. (FG1_1)</p>	<p>From the perspective of funders, there has been an effort to define requirements so that knowledge can be opened up, so that these practices are transparent, open and anyone can replicate, have access, can be the scientist themselves. (FG1_1)</p>
<p>Por exemplo, em relação às incineradoras. É OK, mas se não estiver no espaço que me diz respeito. (FG3_2)</p>	<p>For example, in relation to incinerators. That's ok, but if it's not in the space that concerns me. (FG3_2)</p>
<p>Não há razão para pensar que existe desconfiança em relação à ciência. No entanto, há certas atitudes, cada vez mais presentes na sociedade contemporânea, que são claramente anti-ciência. E penso que é muito difícil combater essas atitudes com as armas da ciência.</p>	<p>There is no reason to think that there is mistrust in science. However, there are certain attitudes, increasingly present in contemporary society, that are blatantly anti-science. And I think it's very difficult to fight such attitudes with the weapons of science. (FG3_7)</p>
<p>Attitudes towards research integrity</p>	
<p>Há também posições pessoais em relação à ética. (...) Há coisas que não estão escritas em códigos, mas que têm a ver com a nossa capacidade de responder [publicamente] aos outros. (FG1_3)</p>	<p>There are also personal positions in relation to ethics. (...) There are things that aren't written in codes, but which have to do with our ability to respond [publicly] to others. (FG1_3)</p>
<p>Tem de haver um ambiente envolvente para a pessoa pôr em prática esses princípios [éticos]. (FG2_3)</p>	<p>There has to be a surrounding environment for the person to put these [ethical] principles into practice. (FG2_3)</p>
<p>Um investigador íntegro é cuidadoso nos seus processos, respeitador dos seus objetos de</p>	<p>A researcher with integrity is careful in their processes, respectful of their objects of</p>

<p>investigação e cuidadoso em termos éticos. (...) É cuidadoso na divulgação dos produtos da sua investigação com orientações éticas muito rigorosas. Isso implica (...) publicar em acesso aberto, diferentes tipos de produtos de comunicação para conseguir dialogar com diferentes públicos. E também, ser muito rigoroso com quem está a definir as políticas públicas. (FG3_7)</p>	<p>research, and careful in ethical terms. (...) They are careful when disseminating the products of their research with very strict ethical guidelines. This involves (...) publishing in open access, different types of communication products to achieve conversations with different audiences. And also, be very strict with those who are defining public policies. (FG3_7)</p>
<p>Publicações que os investigadores fazem e, por vezes, aparece um artigo apenas com o nome do professor e depois o aluno diz "isto era o meu trabalho". (FG1_6)</p>	<p>Publications that researchers make and that sometimes it happens that a paper appears with just the teacher's name and then the student says "that was my work". (FG1_6)</p>
<p>[Integridade] é mostrar o que se está a fazer sem parecer que é mais do que aquilo que é. Dizer "Cuidado, eu só fui até aqui. Vamos diferenciar para que é que isto pode servir, onde estamos." (FG2_2)</p>	<p>[Integrity] is showing what you are doing without seeming like it is more than what it is. Say "Be careful, I only went this far. Let's differentiate what this could be for, where we are." (FG2_2)</p>
<p>[Um cientista com integridade é] alguém que está aberto ao escrutínio e, se houver erros, está disposto a assumi-los. (FG3_3)</p>	<p>[A scientist with integrity is] someone who is open to scrutiny and, if there are mistakes, is willing to own them. (FG3_3)</p>
<p>O conceito de integridade é novo e nunca está completamente definido. (...) A falta de integridade pode ir desde publicar em nome próprio sem dar crédito a outros até limitar o financiamento... Por exemplo, no instituto apercebemo-nos a dada altura que a forma como os coordenadores dos grupos distribuían o dinheiro era sempre por dois ou três, e o resto recebia um "não". Não era nada transparente... Até que mudámos as regras. (FG1_2)</p>	<p>The concept of integrity is new and never completely fixed. (...) The lack of integrity can range from publishing in one's own name without crediting others to limiting funding... For example, at the institute we realised at some point that the way the group coordinators distributed the money was always by twos or threes, and the rest received a "no". It wasn't transparent at all... Until we changed the rules. (FG1_2)</p>
<p>No que diz respeito ao financiamento da investigação a um investigador que trabalha numa instituição pública, no caso das ciências médicas, esta questão é muitas vezes levantada pelos conflitos de interesses e pelas</p>	<p>With regard to the funding of research to a researcher working in a public institution, in the case of the medical sciences, this question is often raised by conflicts of interest and the suspicions that exist because</p>

<p>suspeitas que existem pelo facto de certos estudos serem pagos por empresas farmacêuticas. Isto pode gerar alguma desconfiança. (FG3_2)</p>	<p>certain studies are paid for by pharmaceutical companies. This can generate some mistrust. (FG3_2)</p>
<p>Não creio que a falta de integridade seja assim tão comum. Sinceramente, penso que a maioria das pessoas faz investigação com integridade. (FG1_5)</p>	<p>I don't think lack of integrity is that common. I honestly think that most people do research with integrity. (FG1_5)</p>
<p>Na minha instituição, não sei qual é o procedimento quando há uma situação [ética] mais complexa. Diria que é preciso ir à direção [do centro de investigação] para que a direção veja como lidar com as coisas. (FG2_2)</p>	<p>In my institution, I don't know what the procedure is when there's a more complex [ethical] situation. I'd say you'd have to go to the management [of the research centre] for the management to see how to handle things. (FG2_2)</p>
<p>O ponto é definir desde o início quem vai aparecer como autor desta publicação. (...) Pode ser uma forma de resolver este problema do ponto de vista organizacional. (...) Mas muitas vezes é caso a caso. (FG2_4)</p>	<p>The point is to define from the beginning who will appear as the author of this publication. (...) It could be a way to solve this problem from an organizational point of view. (...) But it's often case by case. (FG2_4)</p>
<p>Ceder individualmente à pressão [institucional] tem um impacto na ciência, na confiança na ciência e no que é a ciência. (FG2_4)</p>	<p>Individually giving in to [institutional] pressure has an impact on science, trust in science, and what science is. (FG2_4)</p>
<p>A perceção de integridade é diferente de pessoa para pessoa. Depende da personalidade de cada um. (FG2_5)</p>	<p>The perception of integrity is different from person to person. It depends on the personality. (FG2_5)</p>
<p>Se já sou uma pessoa que não dá prioridade à ética profissional, encontrarei sempre uma forma de a contornar. (FG3_2)</p>	<p>If I'm already a person who doesn't prioritise professional ethics, I'll always find a way round it. (FG3_2)</p>
<p>Justificar as práticas duvidosas, o que pode aumentar a desconfiança na ciência. (FG1_1)</p>	<p>Justify the dubious practices, which may increase distrust in science. (FG1_1)</p>
<p>Há uma grande pressão para que os investigadores tenham currículos com muitos artigos, muitos artigos, o número. É o número que conta. A qualidade, a certa altura, deixou de ser relevante. (FG3_1)</p>	<p>There's a lot of pressure for researchers to have CVs with lots of papers, lots of papers, the number. It's the number that counts. Quality, at a certain point, was no longer relevant. (FG3_1)</p>
<p>A pressão exercida sobre uma pessoa para que não cometa erros pode conduzir a uma má conduta. (FG2_3)</p>	<p>The pressure on a person not to make mistakes can lead to misconduct. (FG2_3)</p>

<p>Há também revistas de topo que, independentemente da avaliação pelos pares, têm mais facilidade em publicar quando são amigos de amigos. E eu sei-o por experiência própria. (FG3_5)</p>	<p>There are also top journals that, regardless of peer review, find it easier to publish when they are friends of friends. And I know this from personal experience. (FG3_5)</p>
<p>Attitudes towards social integration</p>	
<p>O público escolar é um público que é, de certa forma, fácil de trabalhar porque é cativo no sentido em que está cativo numa sala de aula, com um professor que vai tomar essa decisão. (...) E a ciência chega a um grupo grande. (...) Os projetos de ciência cidadã são muito bons para envolver o público adulto, podemos chegar ao público adulto muito mais facilmente. (...) Eu sinto que há um certo constrangimento por parte dos adultos em participar, ou em passar à frente de uma criança para, sei lá, olhar para um microscópio. (FG2_2)</p>	<p>The school public is an audience that is, in a way, easy to work with because they are captive in the sense that they are captive in a classroom, with a teacher who is going to make that decision. (...) And science reaches a large group. (...) Citizen science projects are very good for involving adult audiences, we can reach adult audiences much more easily. (...) I feel that there is a certain embarrassment on the part of adults to take part, or to step in front of a child to, I don't know, look under a microscope. (FG2_2)</p>
<p>Não existe um grupo geral. Temos de trabalhar para grupos, definir o nosso público, quem é, o que é muito difícil, e depois tentar avaliá-lo, o que também é muito difícil. (FG3_4)</p>	<p>There is no general group. We have to work for groups, define our audience, who it is, this is very difficult and then try to evaluate it, which is also very difficult. (FG3_4)</p>
<p>Nós produzimos a nossa investigação, encontramos uma forma de a embrulhar e entregar, mas penso que o mais interessante não é entregar a informação já preparada, mas envolver as pessoas desde o início. (FG3_2)</p>	<p>We produce our research, we find a way to wrap it up and deliver it, but I think the most interesting thing is not to deliver the information already prepared, but to involve people from the beginning. (FG3_2)</p>
<p>Os projetos de ciência cidadã são um bom exemplo. Não se trata apenas de uma forma de publicitar a ciência, mas também de envolver os cidadãos e de os transformar em cientistas. Eles aprendem fazendo. (FG2_1)</p>	<p>Citizen science projects are a good example. It's not just a way of publicising science, but also of involving citizens and turning them into scientists. They learn by doing. (FG2_1)</p>
<p>Os investigadores na área da diabetes estão a trabalhar arduamente para baixar os níveis de glicose, para controlar os níveis de glicose. Mas muitas vezes os doentes já têm essa</p>	<p>Researchers in the field of diabetes are working hard to lower glucose levels, to control glucose levels. But often patients already have that part sorted out and what they want is</p>

<p>parte resolvida e o que querem são soluções para outras coisas nas suas vidas, como a impotência sexual, poder praticar desporto. E os investigadores não sabem isso. (FG2_3)</p>	<p>solutions for other things in their lives, such as sexual impotence, being able to do sport. And researchers don't know this. (FG2_3)</p>
<p>No caso de um centro de investigação que trabalhe apenas com a doença de Parkinson, poderíamos ter alguém da sociedade civil, alguém que represente os doentes de Parkinson, uma associação de doentes, por exemplo, presente num conselho científico, e que dite efetivamente as políticas de investigação do instituto e quais os projetos que devem ser submetidos a financiamento. (FG2_3)</p>	<p>In the case of a research centre that works only with Parkinson's, we could have someone from civil society, someone who represents Parkinson's patients, a patients' association, for example, present on a scientific council, and who actually dictates the institute's research policies and which projects should be submitted for funding. (FG2_3)</p>
<p>A promoção da literacia científica não deve ser apenas uma questão de ciência "sentada", como palestras ou conferências. Não é produtivo. (FG2_1)</p>	<p>Promoting scientific literacy shouldn't just be about "sitting down" science, like talks or conferences. It is not productive. (FG2_1)</p>
<p>Esta relação de proximidade leva tempo a criar. Mudámo-nos para aqui [Figueira da Foz] exatamente para nos aproximarmos da sociedade. Foi um processo longo, mas que deu os seus frutos. Agora trabalhamos com várias empresas e não é só no contexto de: eles vêm e pedem um serviço, nós fazemos, eles pagam. É de facto um processo de colaboração total. Muitas vezes, eles têm uma ideia, perguntam se podemos dar vida a essa ideia (...) e o processo evolui. (FG3_1)</p>	<p>This closeness of relationship takes time to create. We moved here [Figueira da Foz] exactly to get closer to society. It was a long process, but it bore fruit. We now work with several companies and not just in the context of: they come and ask for a service, we do it, they pay. It really is a process of total collaboration. Often, they have an idea, they ask if we can bring that idea to life (...) and the process evolves. (FG3_1)</p>
<p>Muitas vezes, nos telejornais do horário nobre, quando há notícias que correspondem a pseudociência, precisamos de ter um cientista, um divulgador de ciência que venha apresentá-las de uma forma "para totós", para que possamos compreender. (FG2_4)</p>	<p>Often in prime-time news, when there is news that corresponds to pseudo-science, we need to have a scientist, a science communicator who comes to present it in a way "for geeks", that we can understand. (FG2_4)</p>
<p><i>Institutional contributions to trust in science</i></p>	
<p><i>Scientific integrity</i></p>	

<p>Eu associo muito a integridade à literacia de informação. Desde os primeiros anos de escola, os alunos devem aprender as regras básicas de pesquisa, citação, referenciação e comunicação. (FG2_1)</p>	<p>I very much associate integrity with information literacy. From the first years of school, students must learn the basic rules of research, citation, referencing, and communication. (FG2_1)</p>
<p>Quando vemos muitos projetos com o mesmo problema [ético], organizamos um workshop para capacitar, para esclarecer as coisas. (FG2_4)</p>	<p>When we see a lot of projects with the same [ethical] problem, we organise a workshop to build capacity, to clarify things. (FG2_4)</p>
<p>Quando fui trabalhar para os dados, a apresentação foi "Temos de fazer isto porque é a política da FCT". Isso é uma coisa terrível para se dizer a alguém! Vamos dizer porque vale a pena fazer isto, qual é o benefício, porque é que as pessoas vão ganhar com os registos, e depois como podem tirar partido deles. (FG1_2)</p>	<p>When I went to work on the data, the presentation was "We have to do this because it's FCT policy". That's a terrible thing to say to someone! Let's say why it's worth doing this, what the benefit is, why people will gain from the records, then how they can take advantage of them. (FG1_2)</p>
<p>Em Portugal, existem acordos transformadores da b-on em que há a possibilidade de publicar em acesso aberto, mas em revistas que não estão neste grupo considerado potencialmente predatório. (FG3_2)</p>	<p>In Portugal, there are transformative agreements by b-on in which there is the possibility of publishing in open access, but in journals that are not in this group considered potentially predatory. (FG3_2)</p>
<p>Atualmente, o financiamento da investigação exige ciência aberta. As práticas de ciência aberta são atualmente um requisito para o financiamento europeu e, cada vez mais, para o financiamento nacional. (FG3_3)</p>	<p>Research funding today requires open science. Open science practices are now a requirement in European funding and increasingly in national funding. (FG3_3)</p>
<p>As instituições estão inseridas em instituições maiores, e essas instituições maiores estão inseridas no Ministério da Ciência e Tecnologia e numa FCT que tem tido sempre em mente, ultimamente, a questão das estatísticas, dos rankings, etc., comparados com os europeus. (FG3_5)</p>	<p>The institutions are part of larger institutions, and these larger institutions are part of the Ministry of Science and Technology and an FCT that has always had in mind, lately, the question of statistics, rankings, etc, compared to the European ones. (FG3_5)</p>
<p>Este ano, alterámos as regras de atribuição de prémios de investigação para sensibilizar os investigadores para as práticas agressivas de editoras, revistas,</p>	<p>This year we changed the rules for awarding research prizes to make researchers aware of the aggressive practices of publishers, journals,</p>

<p>conferências. (...) Ainda não existe uma base de dados, mas já foram identificados procedimentos comuns a todas estas editoras e revistas predatórias. (FG1_1)</p>	<p>conferences. (...) There is no database yet, but common procedures have already been identified for all these predatory publishers and journals. (FG1_1)</p>
<p>No meu centro de investigação, há certos grupos editoriais que, embora não estejam vedados aos investigadores, são fortemente desaconselhados. (FG3_2)</p>	<p>In my research centre, there are certain editorial groups which, although not closed to researchers, are strongly discouraged. (FG3_2)</p>
<p>Nós estamos no COARA, um grupo europeu onde os modelos de avaliação da investigação estão a ser questionados, nomeadamente para fazer face à pressão do "publish or perish". (...) Atualmente, fala-se também muito do impacto que a investigação tem na sociedade. (FG1_1)</p>	<p>We're in COARA, a European group where research evaluation models are being questioned, particularly to deal with this "publish or perish" pressure. (...) Today there's also a lot of talk about the impact that research has on society. (FG1_1)</p>
<p>Fala-se muito no estrangeiro, nos Países Baixos e talvez no Reino Unido, dos "data champions". Basicamente, recompensa o investigador com o maior número de conjuntos de dados depositados ou... (...) Ajuda na mudança cultural que é tão lenta e tão difícil de conseguir. (FG1_1)</p>	<p>There's a lot of talk abroad, in the Netherlands and perhaps the UK, about data champions. Basically, it rewards the researcher with the most datasets deposited or... (...) It helps with the cultural change that is so slow and so difficult to achieve. (FG1_1)</p>
<p>Um provedor na área da ética e da integridade a quem sejam reportadas estas situações de suspeita de desvio, má conduta ou assédio (...) E que possa submeter as situações a um escrutínio. (FG2_4)</p>	<p>An ombudsman in the area of ethics and integrity to whom these situations of suspected deviation, misconduct or harassment are reported (...) And to be able to subject the situations to scrutiny. (FG2_4)</p>
<p>No ano passado, criámos o provedor do investigador para tentar compreender as razões pelas quais os investigadores se comportam da forma como se comportam, como a má conduta na investigação. (FG3_1)</p>	<p>Last year, we set up the researcher ombudsman to try to understand the reasons why researchers behave the way they do, like misconduct in research. (FG3_1)</p>
<p><i>Social integration</i></p>	
<p>A nossa instituição quer aproximar os cidadãos do espaço. Não se trata necessariamente da investigação, do ensino, mas do espaço. Dessacralizar o espaço, para mostrar que é o espaço do cidadão. (FG1_2)</p>	<p>Our institution wants to bring citizens closer to space. It is not necessarily about research, teaching, but about space. Desacralize the space, to show that it's the citizen's space. (FG1_2)</p>

<p>Há alguns anos, isto era visto como um templo da ciência. Os miúdos vêm aqui e veem as grandes maravilhas que a ciência produziu, e veneram-nas. A ideia da metáfora da Igreja. E agora tornámo-nos um fórum. É um sítio onde um empresário, um cientista ou um cidadão se podem reunir. (FG3_8)</p>	<p>A few years ago, this was seen as a temple of science. Kids come here and see the great wonders that science has produced, and they worship them. The idea of the Church metaphor. And now we become a forum. It is a place where either a businessman, a scientist or a citizen can come together. (FG3_8)</p>
<p>Gabinetes de comunicação mais eficazes, mais completos, mais complementares, menos precários, mais consolidados. Para que eles [os gabinetes] possam fazer um trabalho mais a médio, longo prazo. (FG3_6)</p>	<p>Communication offices that are more effective, more complete, more complementary, and less precarious, more consolidated. So that they [the offices] can do more medium- and long-term work. (FG3_6)</p>
<p>Uma ciência cidadã que não implica uma abordagem top-down, mas que vê o outro na sociedade como um verdadeiro parceiro. (...) Pensar em conjunto o problema científico é uma das coisas que temos de fazer, esta colaboração tem de ser desde o início. (FG3_3)</p>	<p>A citizen science that does not involve a top-down approach, but that sees others in society as a true partner. (...) Thinking together the scientific problem is one of the things we have to do, this collaboration has to be from the beginning. (FG3_3)</p>
<p>Durante a pandemia, fizemos uma assembleia de professores online. E dali saíram não sei quantos projetos, que eram assim a pedido deles. Eles diziam-nos "Precisamos disto" e nós dizíamos "Ok, então vamos fazer isto". Agora temos nos nossos planos fazer com as associações de pais e trabalhar com os bairros. (FG2_2)</p>	<p>During the pandemic, we held an online teachers' assembly. and out of that came I don't know how many projects, which were done at their request. They'd say to us "We need this" and we'd say "OK, let's do this". Now we have plans to work with parents' associations and neighbourhoods. (FG2_2)</p>
<p>Ouvir as necessidades das pessoas é uma forma de começar. Ir ao encontro do que é de facto um problema real na sociedade e que precisa de ser resolvido. (FG2_1)</p>	<p>Listening to people's needs is one way to start. Meeting what is actually a real problem in society and needs to be solved. (FG2_1)</p>
<p>Uma das formas de o fazer é convidar a sociedade a fazer parte de um conselho, um grupo de cidadãos (...) que pode ser um observador externo, dar o seu contributo, apontar o dedo, incentivar o avanço da investigação. (FG3_9)</p>	<p>One of the ways to do this is to invite society to be part of a council, a group of citizens (...) who can be an external eye, provide input, point the finger, encourage the advancement of research. (FG3_9)</p>

poiesis
TRUST IN SCIENCE

National Report: Focus Groups - *Spain*

**Project title: Probing the impact of integrity and
integration on societal trust in science**

Project acronym: POIESIS

Grant Agreement no.: 101057253

Centre national de la recherche scientifique (CNRS)

T3.3

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1 Introduction

The POIESIS Focus Groups in Spain were organised following the methodology and using the tools prepared in Deliverable 3.1 "Protocol for participatory research actions with institutional stakeholders". This Protocol ensured a consistent methodological approach between the POIESIS consortium members. In Spain, the focus groups were organised by INGENIO (CSIC-UPV).

1.1 Set up of the focus groups

The three national focus groups organized in Spain were held on the 5th, 12th, and 26th of March respectively and were all held online. The "Guidelines for running the Focus Groups", a complement to Deliverable 3.1, proposed a purposeful sample design to recruit the participants in the focus group. Participants were selected primarily through the institutional network of the POIESIS Institutional Co-Investigators in collaboration with the local POIESIS team. The three Co-investigators selected in Spain belonged to category 1 (FG1 and FG3) and category 8 (FG2) in Table 1.

Table 1. Profiles for selecting Poiesis Institutional Co-Investigators

Integrity	Integration
[1] Leaders and managers in research performing organizations	[7] Open science policy advisers
[2] Leaders and managers in research funding organizations	[8] Communication and outreach officers in research performing organizations
[3] Editors of peer-reviewed journals	[9] Communication and outreach officers in research funding organizations
[4] Members of the committee on publication ethics	[10] Press officers
[5] Research integrity officers	
[6] R&I policy makers	

The institutional Co-investigators were selected based on their experience and professional background. The first Co-investigator was able to mobilize institutional participants with a strong common background in research integrity and ethics (REI) issues. The second Co-investigator recruited institutional participants with a strong common background in science communication. The third Co-investigator provided access to a diverse network of research management professionals.

1.1.4 Focus group 1

The first focus group took place on 5 March 2024 in an online form and involved institutional partners with a common professional background in issues related with REI. The first Co-investigator has a strong professional profile and network in the field of moral philosophy and participates in institutional structures of REI in public research performing and funding organizations and has experience in working in Ethics also at the European Commission. The Co-investigator and the POIESIS local team met in person twice to discuss the research approach and design and identify potential participants in the focus group. This Co-investigator also participated in the first online training organized by the Task Coordinator.

Subsequently, there was continuous communication by email and telephone throughout the process of developing FG1. The recruitment strategy started from a list of twelve potential participants. The list was discussed with the POIESIS researchers, to ensure a consistent professional background in research integrity and diversity in terms of age, gender, degree of experience, and geographical location.

The Co-investigator made the initial contact with potential participants to ask if they would be able to join FG1 on three alternative dates. The date with sufficient quorum was selected (5th of March) and the participants were informed by email about details of their participation in the project and provided with information and Informed Consent materials.

FG1 included eight participants, plus the Co-investigator and two POIESIS observers. The Moderator Guide provided was slightly adapted due to extensive discussions, with some questions under the same section within the guide being posed as a group. The Co-investigator moderated the exercise skilfully, with the POIESIS researchers providing to a brief introduction of the project at the beginning of the session and to farewells, thanks and information on next steps at the conclusion.

FG1 continued for the full possible window of two hours. Participants received an email after the session summarising the next steps in the research, thanking them for their participation, and providing the weblink to the card-sorting activity. The audio recording of the session was transcribed and, due to the high number of people, this work took approximately two hours. The transcription was subsequently translated into English using Deepl, and then further revised by the POIESIS team.

1.1.5 Focus group 2

FG2 took place on 12th of March 2024 also in an online format. The second Co-investigator brought a professional profile and network of contacts in science communication and dissemination in public universities as well as in citizen science practices. The contact with the Co-investigator was exclusively via email and telephone. The Co-investigator could not attend either online training session organized by the Task Coordinator. A video recording of the training was shared to enable preparation for the Co-investigator's moderator role.

The recruitment strategy for FG2 was led by the Co-investigator who was informed about the criteria for selecting participants. The Co-investigator contacted the potential participants and sent them all the required information regarding their participation. FG2 was conducted with five participants, the Co-investigator and two local POIESIS researchers present.

As in FG1, the Moderator Guide provided by the Task Coordinator was slightly adapted through the focus group, and some questions were presented together as a thematic group. The co-investigator moderated the entire session with the POIESIS researchers providing a brief introduction to the project at the beginning of the session and to farewells, thanks, and information on next steps at the conclusion.

The second focus group lasted one hour. Participants received an email after the session summarising the next steps in the research, thanking them for their participation, and providing the weblink to the card-sorting activity. The audio recording of the session was transcribed and relevant passages suitable for use as quotes in the Spain National Report subsequently translated into English.

1.1.3 Focus group 3

The third focus group took place on 26th of March 2024 also in an online format. This focus group aimed to obtain data from institutional partners with management backgrounds in diverse science and innovation organisations. The third Co-investigator has a diverse professional network, including in both the public and private sectors. Contact with the Co-investigator included both in person and telephone and email strategies. The Co-investigator attended the second online training organized by the Task Coordinator.

The recruitment strategy for FG3 was also led by the Co-investigator, who shared a list of potential participants with POIESIS researchers. The Co-investigator contacted the participants and sent them all the required information regarding their participation.

Due to the high-level managerial position of the Co-investigator and the two weeks of local community festivities (Fallas Festival), setting a date for the FG3 was challenging. FG3 had to be twice postponed, and this impacted the final number of participants. Due to the deadline for the National Reports a later alternative date was not considered. FG3 was conducted with three participants, the Co-investigator and one local POIESIS researcher present.

Across the three focus groups, the participation of the Co-investigators provided access to a set of participants that it would have been challenging to reach otherwise. The coherence of discussions and collaboration among FG members were excellent, no doubt due to sharing a professional network. The strengths of the Co-investigator model for focus groups research were clear and participants expressed enthusiasm for the approach taken.

1.2 Participants in the focus groups

Focus group 1

Participant Id.	Gender	Age (approx.)	Position	Institution
FG1_1	Female	45-55	Full professor / Natural sciences. Research integrity background or responsibilities	Public university
FG1_2	Male	55-65	Full professor / Humanities. Research integrity background or responsibilities	Public university
FG1_3	Male	45-55	Professor / Natural Sciences. Research integrity background or responsibilities	Public university
FG1_4	Female	55-65	Manager. Research integrity background or responsibilities	Regional administration
FG1_5	Female	35-45	Researcher / Social sciences	Private university
FG1_6	Male	55-65	Professor / Humanities. Research integrity background or responsibilities	Public university
FG1_7	Male	35-45	Professor / Humanities. Research integrity background or responsibilities	Public university
FG1_8	Male	55-65	Full professor / Humanities. Research integrity background or responsibilities	Public university

Focus group 2

Participant Id.	Gender	Age (approx.)	Position	Institution
FG2_1	Male	45-55	Scientist journalist	Public university
FG2_2	Male	45-55	Comunication manager	Public university
FG2_3	Female	45-55	Comunication manager	Public university
FG2_4	Male	55-65	Manager of research institute	Public university
FG2_5	Male	55-65	Communication manager	Public research performing organization

Focus group 3

Participant Id.	Gender	Age (approx.)	Position	Institution
FG3_1	Female	45-55	Manager (PhD)	Public Official College of professionals
FG3_2	Male	45-55	Manager	Public Official College of professionals
FG3_3	Female	55-65	Manager	Business Association

2 Sequential description of the focus groups

The aim of this section is to provide a brief description of each focus group. The perspective adopted is essentially descriptive and consists of describing synthetically the exchanges, in terms of both form and content. There are three sub-sections in this section, each devoted to a specific focus group.

2.1 Focus group 1

The main topics discussed in Focus Group 1 (FG1) included:

- o The distinction between trust in science and trust in scientists
- o The power of social media and the comparative weakness and narrowness of academic dissemination methods
- o The power of vocal minorities in the information ecosystem
- o The complexity of communicating the uncertainty of scientific knowledge production
- o Barriers to trust including private and state interests and surveillance
- o Generational differences in perceptions, attitudes and information channels
- o The need for research career reform, institutional incentives directed at social integration activities
- o Mandatory training in REI from undergraduate level
- o Lack of commitment of universities to REI
- o Relevance being more important than ubiquity as a criterion motivating the dissemination of research results to citizens.

A main difference of opinions occurred regarding the degree to which the power of social media and vocal minorities reflects trends in broader social attitudes. For example, most people were vaccinated despite the noise and misinformation. A second difference of opinion was in relation to the underlying problem regarding institutional ethics processes. Some participants foregrounded weak commitment of organisations, others the lack of role professionalization and support for additional institutional REI work.

The quality of the exchanges in FG1 was good. Communication blended shared academic knowledge with specific expertise on themes or research topics. The group had strong connections and mutual respect for opinions and frequently followed up on another participants' points to deepen or provide examples. The moderation of these exchanges was effective and efficient. No arguments or emotionally distressing exchanges occurred, in fact FG1 was conducted more in the spirit of a collective reflection on issues that are central to the work and expertise of the professionals involved. There was one period reflecting on the need for reform of rewards for researchers' work on dissemination and promoting ethics that became a little too focused on the needs of researchers rather than how this reform could benefit the science - society relationship or moderation/advance of dis/trust.

All participants engage strongly and interacted coherently, with many hands being raised during an intervention in order to contribute to the line of thinking being explained. Largely these sequences did not lead to disagreement so little use was made of rejoinders - rather the sequence of topics continued to unfold organically.

The meeting met its objective in terms of data collection. And initial round of coding resulted in the use of 23/25 codes. This figure may move up or down in a second round of processing to select quotes for the cross-sectional analysis. In terms of idea-generation the promotion of innovative recommendations was perhaps lacking, with most recommendations linked to quite familiar institutional reform measures. However, ideas such as an Ethics for Influencers can be considered more adventurous.

2.2 Focus group 2

The main topics discussed in Focus Group 2 (FG2) included:

- o The evolution in the last decade toward more professional science communication strategies in the public sector and national media
- o The need for more professionalized science communication in local media, research groups, and projects
- o The need to improve the science literacy of the public, starting at early stages of education

- o Generational differences in perceptions, attitudes, and information channels
- o The need to improve the communication and engagement skills of scientists and the barriers to doing so
- o The responsibility of scientists to disseminate their work, especially in the case of publicly funded research
- o The impact of polarization in politics on trust in media and consequently on communication of science
- o The impact of news about lack of integrity in science and journalism on the general perception of science by the public
- o The impact of “publish or perish” on the integrity of scientific practices and the role of scientific incentives on modulating integrity
- o The positive impact on research careers of engaging in science communication
- o The impact of lack of research integrity on trust in science
- o The connection between social integration and dissemination in building public trust in science.

The quality of the exchanges in FG2 was good. There were no relevant discrepancies in the group. The discussion around the questions posed went smoothly and the participants contributed arguments and facts that complemented the ideas previously presented. The communication combined professional experience on science communication, both from the point of view of institutional communication professionals and from the professional experience as researchers of some participants. Empirical data were also provided to support some of the arguments. As in FG1, participants had strong connections and mutual respect for each other's opinions. The moderation of these exchanges was effective and efficient, accompanying the proposed arguments and elaborating on them. There were no arguments or emotionally distressing exchanges; indeed, FG2 took place rather in the spirit of collective reflection on issues central to the work and experience of the professionals involved.

The meeting met its objective in terms of data collection. An initial round of coding resulted in the use of 55 codes. This figure may change in a second round of processing to select quotes for the cross-sectional analysis. In terms of idea-generation and the promotion of innovative recommendations, these focused on improving science communication strategies and resources, such as exploring new channels for institutional communicators to interact with younger publics and improving the engagement of scientist through incentives to promote social integration and dissemination.

2.3 Focus group 3

The main topics discussed in Focus Group 3 (FG3) included:

- o The communication gap between science and the public due to the lack of both scientific literacy among citizens and communication skills among scientists

- o The complexity of discerning reliable and relevant scientific information in a context of information over-saturation
- o The existence of research areas that are more easily communicated and understood by citizens than others, e.g. health-related topics
- o The power of the media, lobbies, and governments to generate public opinion and the risks associated with such opinions being generated by these groups' own interests
- o A lack of budget within the research system to compete in the creation of the public opinion
- o The difficulty of understanding the complexity of the science and the impact of the different translations on the final message received by the public
- o The distinction between scientific advances, which are less disseminated, and innovation products that capture the public debate
- o The role of researchers and their responsibility to engage in public debate in their research areas
- o Generational differences in perceptions, attitudes and information channels
- o The rationale for promoting social inclusion in science, the barriers to its implementation at different stages of the research process and the perception of which actors should be involved in decision-making processes.

One of the main differences of opinion was in relation to the most appropriate strategies to promote greater public awareness of science and willingness to engage with it. Some participants considered the lack of capacity to understand scientific processes as the key starting point on this issue. However, disagreements were expressed on the best strategies to improve this capacity. On the one hand, citizen participation in science was considered to be ideally desirable and could be a driver for increasing science literacy. On the other hand, it was argued that without an adequate level of science literacy, participation in science, especially in decision-making, was not desirable. In this second line of argument, it was considered that decisions about science should be left to experts and the design of attractive science communication should work in parallel to increase science literacy.

Communication in FG3 was smooth but there were more discrepancies than in the previous groups. The fluidity of the discussion was probably due to the smaller number of participants and their closeness, which allowed discrepancies to be handled calmly and with sufficient time to explain and discuss them. Moderation was key to linking issues and the different contributions of the participants.

The FG3 also met its objective in terms of data collection. And initial round of coding resulted in the use of 43 codes. In terms of recommendations to improve citizens' trust in science, ideas related to the promotion of citizens' interest in science, the

increase of budgets, and the creation of incentives for scientific dissemination and participation of scientists in social forums were addressed.

3 Building trust in science: from perception to institutional engagement

In this section, the aim is to develop a cross-sectional analysis of the exchanges described sequentially in the previous section.

3.1 About science and society

Participants in the three Focus Groups held in Spain were able to articulate the complexity and ambivalence of the relationship between science and society. Expressions of the social value of, and respect for science, were clearly stated, whilst acknowledging that science as a human endeavour is flawed.

I believe that science, as you are saying, is made by people with their virtues and defects, but that science has also demonstrated that it is one of the systems that best allows us to decide and progress in knowledge. (FG3_1)

Qualifications and general expressions of concern about the science – society relationship were common. A prominent key word in two focus groups was 'disconnection'.

...there is still a big disconnection between the general public and science due to a lack of knowledge on the one hand and... due to a lack of accurate communication on the other. That is to say, many times it is not only the receiver who is to blame, but often it is the sender, too. That the sender is at such a level, you know, that the other doesn't know anything. (FG3_2)

Perceptions of this disconnection included the fundamental uncertainty of scientific research, the focus of expectations on the utility of science, and the differentiation of societal groups.

The more you study, the more you realize that absolute truths do not exist and that you have to complement your knowledge (FG1_4)

I think that people may now think, in my opinion, "a scientist is someone who is going to give you a solution, but he has to give it to you and if he doesn't, it's no good", "that's it", no, a scientist does a lot of research until he reaches a solution or maybe s/he doesn't even reach the solution (FG3_3)

Maybe for some people it is the place where all our utopias can be produced, science, but for another important part of

society: distrust. So, it also depends on which part of society you are thinking about. (FG1_2)

The complicated nature of explaining science and the rise of social media are considered to be major factors having an influence on the science - society relationship.

Well, because of the very nature of what it is..., I mean that there is no way to explain... that not even the journalist himself understands it, you know? Well, maybe that's why it doesn't get there. That is to say that we should also think about this, not that not everything is equally communicable or easily communicable (FG3_2)

What they do is look for different sources of information and they rely not on the 9 o'clock news or what El País says in the morning, but on what says I don't know... whatever 'tiktok' there is or any scientific disseminator that they go out Instagram and tell them (FG3_1)

...the new ones that come with that come out of the cradle, already with the TATATATA (imitates the use of a smartphone) and they already know how to handle, but there is an average age that does not even know how to search (FG3_3)

A 'vocal minority' are seen to be particularly important in driving the agenda on social media in such a way that a controversial social issue becomes more directly linked to the credibility of scientific evidence.

[T]he whole issue of COVID vaccines, to give a very clear example, but I think that society as a whole or mostly did not see a problem, they were confident that this vaccine, it was supported by science, but there is a small group of very vocal people who say: "this is not proven, this has these side effects that are not proven, this has these side effects that are not supported by science. (FG1_5)

When talking about science and society it was also suggested that producing forms of outputs that could be more easily consumed by lay persons could help bridge this disconnect and build understanding.

What we also did was a documentary, it's on Youtube, to publish those results, counting on people who had participated in the interviews because it seemed to us that on top of the fact that the idea had been theirs and that they were the ones affected, publishing it in the scientific journal was not going to reach them. (FG1_4)

It was recommended that the idea of producing outputs or making contributions to society should be better integrated in the career

progression systems that structure the social organisation of science. It was also considered that underpinning the reliability and integrity of science, through specific training, should start earlier in the research career trajectory and make societal aspects such as data privacy more integrated in the formation process.

Defining some strategic lines of research and that they are really related to society and that your contribution to society is something that is really valued when it comes to later on, obtaining tenured positions, obtaining professorships and so on, so that you really have to justify this with a narrative beyond the fact that I have participated in these projects, in QIs and so on. (FG1_5)

Training is very necessary and that it should be mandatory from the undergraduate level. Training in Ethics is always optional, with Bioethics in the faculties we have the same problems many times (FG1_4)

I would start at the undergraduate level in the same way that, for example, and many people do not know, that in the matter of Data Protection, both in the regulation and in our law, we should have already integrated it in the studies and we have not even paid attention to it. Both in Data Protection and in new technologies, so I believe that training is a fundamental pillar. (FG1_3)

Overall, the perception of the groups was that a gap exists between science and society that is in a large part due to the uncertainty of the scientific knowledge production process and the difficulties of explaining or making understandable how this relates to technological and social progress. Social media was seen to amplify this disconnect particularly for certain sections of the population, driven by the efforts of what was perceived as vocal minorities linked to controversial topics or social issues. Training, creating career incentives, and extending the types of output typically produced by researchers were all seen as proactive measure for bringing science closer to society.

3.2 About trust in science

The theme of disconnection that was prominent in initial discussion of the science-society relationship blended into the questions of trust and distrust, of how this disconnection can be understood as both a product of distrust of science, or perhaps of its cause. The subject of communicating information also arises, both in terms of media and scientific forms of communication.

...there is a scientism where people need to trust something, they don't trust institutions anymore. I think they trust quite a lot, quite a lot in scientists and they demand absolute certainties from them. (FG1_1)

But it is like that... that science has a trust that is supposedly very important at the level of society. The thing is that I think that what we are talking about here is the lack of trust here in general, of society towards the media, and the lack of trust in science. (FG2_1)

So I don't think it's mistrust, but rather that scientists don't know how to talk to ordinary people. (FG3_3)

There was a repeated emphasis on keeping in mind the distinction between trust in science and trust in scientists.

The data on trust in scientists, it's gone down a little bit in the last few years it seems, but no, no, there's no widespread distrust. Quite the contrary. And in fact in Spain the confidence is quite high, when we also see data regarding other professions. (FG1_4)

The prioritization of entertainment and the capacity of media channels to shape the discourse around science, often in ways that foment distrust, was pictured as a constant struggle that requires dedicated efforts.

[I]t is a matter of media approach, I think in the end that is a sensationalist approach: fear. "What about artificial intelligence?", "Oops, machines are going to dominate us and I don't know what", and "millions of jobs are going to disappear so and so" and that, that's what sells and that's what is being published, especially in the area of artificial intelligence. (FG3_2)

It is a bit like the battle for public opinion, isn't it? I mean... that really many entities of the society are fighting for it constantly with huge budgets. I mean, we are talking about something that there is no kind of coordination in science to dedicate a budget to improve public opinion about science. However, in the political parties there is, in the big companies there is, and even in the small ones! The whole world is already getting involved in public opinion, and the whole world has its own communication agency, well, the whole world! Many, many, companies and organizations of all kinds, even the small ones, so of course, if this is being done by the small ones it is because it is important, to begin with, if resources are dedicated to this it is because it is important, it is not nonsense. More so in a democracy ... If science does not fight this battle because it has no budget and because it is not coordinated to do so, then obviously the message from science does not get through. (FG3_2)

The battle is being fought on new terrain and at times against deliberate attempts to undermine trust in science.

I have heard more than once in older people with Google Now news, that you open, and you only read the headlines and also, they believe it at face value, they have only read the headline and you say, "but where have you seen this?" and they say "my cell phone told me" ... So also the type of news consumption and how it is done I also think it is worrying. (FG1_5)

in relation to COVID, I think there was a certain deliberate manipulation, that is, I think there were deliberate attempts by I don't know who. That is to say, I don't know if there is a conspiracy or conspiratorial sect out there, but there were, let's say, messages clearly directed and clearly oriented to manipulate people. (FG1_8)

However, even in more traditional channels the logic of success in the media field was considered antithetical at times to accurate and appropriate communication. At the same time, there was a strong recognition that the 'academic' understandings of the appropriate forms of communication are simply not effective in new media contexts.

If the distance between what a research team discovers in a laboratory to the information published in a newspaper, no? Maybe what is published in a newspaper is: "New discovery for the cure against cancer", isn't it? It is the headline and in the laboratory what has been discovered is that there is, I don't know, a nucleotide that in a mouse has... has... of course! that is a very important advance for the research team, for cancer and for science, but what the public gets in this newspaper is that there is one more step towards curing cancer (FG1_4)

When we talk about dissemination or especially communication in social networks, on the Internet, it is always approached from an intellectualist perspective, that is, citizens go to the Internet to participate, to deliberate, to disseminate knowledge, but it is not entirely true. That is, there is an emotional aspect that is embedded in social networks, which influences many of the contents that are disseminated, so when conspiracy theories are disseminated, eh... paranoias, you say: well, why does that happen? Well, that happens, doesn't it? Why does it spread? It does not spread because people believe it, it spreads because there is a latent pulse in the social networks, which is the need for status, the need for recognition. (FG1_6)

Contemporary media, and particularly social media platforms, was thus framed as the primary factor undermining trust in science. The lack of authority of the traditional scientific voice, and the

prioritization of entertainment over expertise seemed important principles at work.

However, deeper rationales also underpinned some discussion, particularly in the context of the capacity of vocal minorities to contest expert opinion on open platforms. The rise of explanation with a conspiracy structure was noted, but the fact that such conspiracies often rest on a rational base makes them extremely difficult to counter particularly in relation to the technology that shapes citizens' everyday lives.

Control, not only by the State, but also by companies. So there are, there are, there can be sources of distrust both because people think, "they are not concerned about my interest", "I do not see it", "I do not perceive it", that "I am the ultimate goal of this scientific and technological development", but that there are two great powers, money and control, that can be distorting scientific and technological research. (FG1_2)

In terms of taking steps to improve the trust relationship, participants recommended the relatively standard approach of joining the battle and some more radical innovations addressed to the 'influencers' who may deliberately or unwittingly promote distrust in science and technology.

Maybe this more traditional media model has been broken by... by the emergence of social networks, that right now every person can, can be a media, can say something and can influence society ... What we are talking about, that the institutions, let's say, let's join the battle or let's make that speech using those media too, right? being Youtubers or being on Youtube - even if we are not Youtubers with millions of subscribers. (FG2_1)

We have to do it to reach all generations and an Ethics for Influencers also requires that the people of reference for young people also know how to contribute to the development of science or that it is correctly transferred to the population. (FG1_2)

In summary, the main battleground regarding distrust in science was believed to be social media forms of communication. A fundamental gap between the younger and older generations, between 'boomers' and 'tiktokers' was portrayed as shaping both the channels of communication being used, but also a difference in the capacity to really understand the contexts and drivers of the new platforms.

Whilst public trust in science in Spain is believed to be, and was consistently described as strong in the FG, there was a clear sense that this could not be guaranteed, and that the proliferation of

information and non-expert voices could erode this basic goodwill toward the scientific profession. The emergence of distrust also in opposition to surveillance capitalism, with its ambivalent promises to make life easier, but wholly observable, was understood as a rationale for citizens' acceptance of critical positions on science and technology that can easily blend over into conspiracy and misinformation. Taking ethics to the influencers was proposed as an approach or method to shape or moderate some of the potential excesses of the platform media world.

3.3. About research integrity

There was a tension evident throughout the groups between the perception that there is indeed plenty of misconduct and poor research practices in Spain, and the idea that this might be more due to the classic 'bad apples' spoiling perceptions for the rest.

Fraudulent practices of all kinds can be found in all contexts (FG2_1)

...to say that [Researcher X], in her laboratory for the sixth consecutive year, trying to find something against cancer but is not, no - this is not going anywhere. However, to say "oh, no, the doctoral thesis written by the minister of Germany ... there are parts from here and parts from there". That sells, that's simply why. But really, when you talk to people, they do believe that the scientist is a person of integrity. (FG3_1)

A simple but important point was made by one participant: if citizens don't really understand how scientific work is actually conducted then how easy it for them to understand nuances of integrity in the performance of these practices?

Scientific integrity is only known by scientists ... that write many papers, but people do not know what a paper is, nor an article (FG3_1)

A common perception was that alongside deliberate misconduct there is a widespread use of questionable research practices - often related to poor training.

There are also certain bad practices that occur due to researchers' lack of knowledge. On the one hand it is due to pressure, ambition, that has also been studied, right? But then it is also due to ignorance, with respect to some bad practices regarding, for example, the use of material that you have already published previously. (FG1_7)

Another important perception was that scientific integrity is a holistic concept, that does not simply relate to personal choices

in the laboratory or field, but also to a way of being a professional who contributes constructively to their environment.

A researcher with integrity also has to develop characteristics such as knowing how to work in a team, knowing how to relate to society, having certain communication and relationship skills with society and his environment. (FG1_2)

As a counter to the challenges of lack of research integrity and misconduct, it was observed that the attitude of many universities in Spain needed to change in order to institutionalize REI as a part of research quality.

The universities I think that what they should do is to take it seriously, simply, that is to take seriously the existence and functioning of ethics and integrity committees in research. (FG1_8)

The factors contributing to the problem of research integrity and misconduct included questions about the fitness for purpose of the peer review mechanism.

I think that in the end the problem is that the control mechanisms that we have in the academic world are starting to have problems in each system, because you all know that a lot of things are coming out in the press about scientific articles, I don't know how many, that are damaging (FG2_4)

Another problem identified was the lack of ethics training in the research community, both in order to design and conduct research appropriately, and in exercising control over others' research through formal processes.

In health centres and now I also meet a lot of professionals who have no training in methodology, let alone in research ethics, and we start doing research projects. (FG1_4)

One is the issue of the professionalization of Ethics. I see that we are sought to be in committees and the people who are in committees do it voluntarily and that makes them have a very short career. The committees, for example, the hospital committees of the hospital tend to be always in crisis, but they tend to be always in crisis, to begin with, because they have no budget for anything. And then the people who work on them do so voluntarily. (FG1_2)

One rationale for the flourishing of problems regarding research integrity and misconduct included the 'non-scientific' drivers or motivations of some researchers. A second related to the argument that a deep-seated culture of 'box-ticking' meant that even when ethics compliance was sought it was due to bureaucratic or funder

mandates and did not necessarily indicate any change in research culture.

I believe that science is science, but science is not neutral, that is, science is made by people with an ideology and interests, so... Well, the more polarized it becomes, we cannot deny that there are scientists who are polarized, because there are people who are polarized. (FG2_4)

What is the motivation? It's not to pass these ethical evaluation processes and unfortunately, the numbers are much higher when they have no choice than when they have to choose it as a matter of integrity or concern that they are doing things right (FG1_3)

Fixes for the integrity and misconduct problems focused on bringing the question of values to the fore, coupled with practical interventions and more support across the research cycle.

Also the topic of values must be discussed so we really realize the damage we can do if we do not do things in an ethical way ... where we really move consciences. I think it has to be a formation where consciences are moved and where people stop, think and sometimes I think we have to do less, but better. (FG1_4)

...protocols for the evaluation of the projects, but there are less with respect to the integrity committees or what happens when... a malpractice is committed or a malpractice is known? I mean, there are not so many defined protocols. (FG1_7)

...there should be more follow-up of the Ethics part, because many times only the follow-up of the results is done, but then of the Ethics part there is little follow-up. (FG1_4)

Overall, participants were very clear that a culture of research integrity remains underdeveloped in Spain. While some recourse to the argument 'it's only an isolated few' was made, a majority of participants considered issues of questionable practices to be widespread. Interestingly, as one respondent pointed out, the 'further away misconduct is, the easier it is to see', referring to findings that researchers believed there was less misconduct in their own organisation than in most others. Interestingly, participants did not refer to career stresses such as 'publish or perish' in discussing misconduct, which contrasts to consideration of the social integration in which this was a prominent theme (see section 3.4)

Finally, a clear need for deepening of an integrity culture in research on both the side of scientific communities and research performing organisations, particularly universities, was discussed. Solutions suggested included both promoting reflection on values,

structural improvements to protocols and the professionalization of Ethics Committees, but also to a greater attention to how the ethics process played out across the research process, including the provision of more accessible support and advice.

3.4. About social integration

The topic of social integration, spoken about in the Focus Groups as the participation of citizens in science was where the greatest divergence of opinions emerged when comparing the different groups.

On the one hand, participants in FG1, all of whom are based in or linked closely to universities and academic research, focused on the barriers and the benefits of citizen involvement in research.

Those of you who have been in projects in which you have had to count on different social agents, you will have noticed that it is very difficult to involve people and that it is very difficult to get people to participate. (FG1_5)

Once you have the data, share it with people, right, and see if they interpret it differently. And I think those kinds of changes can be quite positive. (FG1_7)

On the other hand, participants in FG3 were against the concept of social integration and preferred that the domain of research remain in the hands of experts.

I think it's a question like, public jury, yes? or public jury, no? You can't put normal citizens to debate on subjects where there are people who have studied them, who know them. [...] What we must do is to try to get science to arrive in some way, through ethics committees, dissemination by public entities. But not to bring the public to the heart of the matter, because I don't think they will be able to understand it, or disseminate it, or help... No, I don't see it, I don't really see it, as the public jury, I don't see it. (FG3_1)

Well, if citizens support the public budget that is dedicated to research with their budgets, with their taxes, then why couldn't there be research or... citizen budgets, let's say, on research, for example? But what is the practical part, right? [...] It's very difficult for people to get involved in a debate, to give their opinion on something they don't know anything about, it's very difficult. (FG3_2)

And if you start to ask what we spend our budgets on, we get into a mess... If we were a different kind of society, maybe, but if not... I see it all as very utopian... (FG3_1)

The attitude of participants involved in research was positive toward a range of different changes to research and dissemination

activities to incorporate more input or participation from citizens.

Should we also make a dissemination article and send the results previously to the, to the subjects that have participated? Should we publish in public repositories before sending the article to any journal, in your University so that people already have access to that information? I think that all these small steps that are good practices in research allow you to get closer to society. (FG1_7)

In terms of the factors affecting social integration in research, a prominent profile was identified as helpful in attracting collaboration with societal agents with a specific type of demand.

I have experienced it many times, that the fact of being in the media... The fact of being in the limelight, or being in the media in networks helps you get a lot of collaboration projects with companies and others, but I don't know if everything, I mean, I think that most researchers do not see it as part of their work. (FG2_3)

However, from a 'supply-push' perspective, the amount of time and labour required to stage public events, with the ensuing uncertainty about participation levels, prompted some quite direct reflections on the difficulties.

From our day to day, organizing any scientific event is a mini-drama because the public does not attend, attracting people is impossible and you cannot even bring your own people, so, for the scientific centres... (FG3_1)

But who does this? I mean, is this paid in the scientific world? I understand that no. I mean, in the end it's time, you have to dedicate extra time to it. So, it is difficult. (FG3_2)

In discussing the benefits of increased societal integration, participants supported the oft cited by unproven rationale that increased citizen participation can better 'align' scientific research with needs of society, including by opening up participation in research funding Calls.

I believe that it would not be bad if there were calls for proposals in which there were people who do not aspire to a university career, who do not want to be university professors, who are not fighting to compete with others for positions, but who are, for example, doctors or nurses, nurses. They are in positions already working on a day-to-day basis seeing patients, seeing interesting situations that they have published 1 or 2 articles, but if they have a person as

principal investigator or one or two who are going to accompany them in the process. (FG1_2)

One of the traits of a good researcher should also be, not only to think, "I am doing something for society, but also to do something with society". That is, "what I think society needs, may not be what society needs". My research is going in a certain direction, but I do not consult at all with groups that may be affected during the process. (FG1_5)

When it came to recommending mechanisms that could drive an increase in social integration some innovative ideas focused on early stages of the research cycle.

Can society participate beforehand? ... I think that, for example, society can participate by establishing the priority lines of research before a Call... (FG1_8)

Do very good research and with a wider range of people. There could be 20 or 30 people that together we are going to join... we are going to work on one or two articles and that these articles really reflect the day-to-day reality and we do it out of passion, because we like it, because we want to offer something to society with our professional experience. This does not exist at the moment, and I believe that this would bring science much closer to society. (FG1_2)

Other ideas related to how the evaluation and assessment of collaborative or transdisciplinary projects was undertaken.

Incorporate (stakeholders) in the review meetings the review meetings... we incorporate them already in the projects... especially for funded research because otherwise we would be talking about the fact that there has to be an intrinsic motivation for this to be carried out. The different stakeholders that may be affected by the project should be represented in these reviews. (FG1_2)

More traditional was the focus on making researchers understand that developing the aptitudes for disseminating and promoting their research was an increasingly valued professional capability.

...for years we have been providing all the researchers, all the researchers who go through the University's communication office are given a report that says the economic impact that has arisen, that has surfaced, and that has facilitated the societal projection of the University. So, it is true that I have detected that this is a way to motivate people to communicate their research results ... according to the space they have occupied, all those news in all those media: "That campaign has been worth that". So, what does the researcher use this for? They tell us that they use it to ask for

European projects, for example, where it is taken into account (FG2_2)

In summary, institutional stakeholders' perceptions and attitudes toward social integration varied markedly. Researchers and others in university roles see citizen participation as a useful part of a broader strategy to bring science and society closer together. Social integration is seen as having the potential to better align research with social needs and a range of evaluative and reflexive roles were envisaged for citizens and different types of stakeholders. While there was little discussion of integrating citizens in developing research questions or designs, there were recommendations to involve them in funding priority setting, co-investigators, or project evaluators.

Alternatively, non-researchers in the other focus groups considered that citizens do not have technical skills to get involved in decision-making on research processes and that democratic representatives and technicians should identify scientific strengths and research priorities. The only benefit identified by this group related to involving citizens in science was as a strategic way to increase social interest in science. even though barriers were considered more important than the potential benefits of such involvement.

3.5. About institutional contributions to trust in science

Participants with roles in universities were quite critical of the current level and development approaches of universities to communicating science in Spain. This was viewed as one side of the equation in promoting greater trust science.

I think we scientists are not disseminating in the right way and these pseudo-scientists are doing very well, at the level of dissemination. So, this small group of people sows doubts, let's say, in the rest of the population... I think we are not doing so well as scientists in that we are not spreading (information) well, particularly also as this small group of pseudo scientists who are spreading it phenomenally. (FG1_5)

Participants in all FG were similarly of the opinion that improved science communication has a role to play in improving public trust.

The other side of the equation, driving research integrity and ethics in knowledge production, was also considered 'unfinished business' in terms of deepening the culture in research organizations. Establishing prominent and active ethics bodies was considered by some to be the essential first step that needs to be taken in Spanish universities.

The simple fact that there is a structure of ethics committees for the prior control of the projects as well as a commission

or a committee of integrity in research under the vice-rectorships of research, that verifies and monitors in general, that disseminates the culture and that is available for alerts and for cases of complaints or non-compliance and so on, and that this is known and well founded and known by the university community. I think that's enough, it sends enough of a message to ensure scientific integrity. (FG1_8)

Following on from this was consideration that if institutional work on ethics and integrity issues was not recognised in assessment processes then it would be much more difficult to drive institutional change, particularly in the Spanish system in which being able to 'earn points' is part of the calculation every academic makes when planning their activities and contributions to collective processes.

What would be the most appropriate way to integrate society in research, well, I think the easiest way would be to reward, to recognize the researchers. (FG1_3)

The draft that has now been proposed for the accreditation system, here there is a substantial change, that is, the incentives are going to change a lot regarding public commitment. (FG1_7)

Closely related to this focus on rewarding researchers for their contributions to REI work, was the demand that institutional processes and supporting infrastructure be improved.

One is the issue of the professionalization of Ethics. I see that we are sought to be in committees and the people who are in committees do it voluntarily and that makes them have a very short career ... put money in the committees for the needs they have. If a support person is needed to handle all the paperwork, that support person should be there to help people, because what we cannot, what we cannot do is to overload us even more. (FG1_2)

Further, differences in cultural perceptions between senior and junior researchers were observed. With REI processes only recently becoming fully inscribed in Spanish research institutions, participants felt changing attitudes and approaches of experienced researchers to be a very different challenge to appropriately training and imbuing a culture of REI in early career researchers.

Research Centres, both Universities and Centres, I think that we have to train people, not only young people, but also people who have been doing research for a long time and who think that they are doing nothing wrong and probably do many bad things. (FG1_4)

A clear connection here was made to ignorance about what today are considered questionable research practices, and the need for an institutional response that gradually shifts practices rather than focuses on criticism about historical activities.

Finally, the routine involvement of institutional communications offices in research designs that integrate society was advocated. This referred to prior discussions about the challenges and barriers associated with involving citizens in research.

...when researchers at the University need participants for their experiments, no?, many times they can't find them and they ask for help from the communication offices and with a tweet that we send to the media they find the participants very quickly, and then those people are also part of a study that I think is also very positive for them because they know science from the inside, no? And in the end, if they participate in research in this way, we are also bringing these two worlds closer together. So, I think that maybe from the communication office we should also promote much more the experiments and studies that are done in our universities (FG2_P2)

Using institutional communications infrastructure for more 'upstream' phases of the research cycle was recommended.

In conclusion, discussion of institutional contributions to trust in science in Spain was a topic that only strongly engaged participants in FG1. These participants were clear in their recommendations about desirable institutional changes or contributions. These recommendations can be summarised as follows:

- o Recognise and reward researchers for participating in REI work in their organisations;
- o Universities need to display a greater commitment to the importance of REI and provide greater levels of infrastructure support;
- o Adopt a 'no-blame' strategy in relation to improving the ethical conduct of research and the advancement of research integrity, by trying to shift institutional culture through training and support over time;
- o Use institutional communicators to make citizens aware of research in the early stages of its planning and development and to try and invite their participation.

4. Conclusion

Participants in the Spain Focus Groups conducted for Task 3.3 of POIESIS generated informed and considered discussion about the relationships between institutions, researchers and scientific communities, and public trust in science. Participants affirmed

that trust in scientists, as a socially valued profession, had been historically high in Spain and remained so now. However, it was very evident throughout discussions that this strong level of public trust was considered to be under threat. It was consistently argued that social media platforms had opened up a space in which scientific credibility was undermined by 'vocal minorities'. These alternative voices were viewed as having superior capability and technique to attract attention to alternative views of socio-technical controversies, with the Covid-19 pandemic often cited as an example.

A consistent view emerged that the institutional and organisational development of research ethics and integrity (REI) in Spain was in an early stage of its development and professional institutionalization. Universities were framed as not yet taking seriously the need to strengthen administrative procedures such as Ethics Committees and to ensure their function to support and improve REI as a component of scientific excellence. A consistent perspective also emerged in relation to the barriers and difficulties that accompany efforts to enhance citizen participation in research. However, many examples were also given about the benefits of such integration. A general sentiment regarding the mutual benefits that can flow from bringing science and society 'closer together' or into better alignment, was also expressed across all FGs.

Participants in the Spain Focus Groups believe that REI practices and the integration of citizens could be improved through sustained efforts to improve institutional governance and process management. Many organisations in Spain need to deepen their efforts to transform research culture, including by improved incentives, training, and rewards for researchers who perform institutional work. It was also considered that whilst social integration is challenging there are specific opportunities to include citizens in institutional processes including the design of strategic research priorities, transdisciplinary collective publishing activities, and the evaluation of publicly funded research projects, particularly where stakeholder participation has been involved. Participants also considered that institutional communications professionals can play a key role in driving citizen knowledge and participation in their organisation's research, due to their more advanced communication skills. Interestingly, though the dissemination and communication skills of the scientific community were much criticized in comparison both to media professionals and social media 'influencers', there was no significant advocacy for media training for scientists themselves.

Participants in institutional roles the most distant from research voiced a strong alternative opinion - that social integration in science was not desirable. These participants believe experts

should continue to take responsibility for decisions about knowledge production, including ensuring the highest standards of REI comportment. These participants leaned toward questioning whether it was appropriate to expect citizens to assume roles and responsibilities in such highly technical domains.

Key themes and priorities related to improving public trust and social integration in science that emerged from the Spain Focus Groups can be summarised as follows:

- o Sceptical views about science are easy to promote and to counter, due to the uncertainty of knowledge production and the often-ambivalent impacts of S&T 'solution'
- o Reasons for doubting science and technology are often connected to plausible rationales such as exploitation for private profit or state surveillance and represent contests over values as much as facts, and concern emotions as much as rationality
- o Institutional communicators need to fight a continuing battle on the terrain of social media to support public trust in science - scientists are weak performers in this domain
- o Social media influencers are not exempt from questions of ethical responsibility and integrity and ethics should be taken to these actors
- o The communication and dissemination of scientific results does not need to be ubiquitous in principle, but rather the guiding principle should be their relevance to specific societal audiences
- o Processes of formation and development of human capital must integrate a culture of integrity, ethics, and societal engagement from entry into the university community and continue across the research career

poiesis
TRUST IN SCIENCE

National Report: Focus Groups – United Kingdom (UK)

**Project title: Probing the impact of integrity and
integration on societal trust in science**

Project acronym: POIESIS

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1. Introduction

1.1 The UK context

In 2022, the British university sector generated [£130 Billion](#) economic activity, twice as much as the entire British Pharma industry. It employs [240,420](#) (55%) academic staff and [198,835](#) (45%) professionals and administrators (in 2022/23) and teaches [2,862,620](#) students in 218 registered public institutions (Universities, Colleges, Institutes). This whole sector has expanded considerably over the past 10 years, increasing staffing to accommodate rising student numbers.

Of the students, 5% were continental European and another 23% from all over the world. For mainly London-based universities this ratio of international students can be much higher, e.g., University College London 52.6%, London School of Economics 51.3%, Imperial College London, 47.2%. In median 24% of students are post-graduates across universities. This ranges from 0 – 100% depending on the place; some are post-graduate focussed institutions. 39% of all post-graduates in the UK are international students. In this context, national and international image and reputation is a key asset for recruiting students and staff.

University places are fee-based, with national and international students paying different fee levels. For nationals, a loan system is in place on a long-term repayment basis. There is currently a public discussion that this system of finance might not be sustainable: fees are too low to cover university costs, and the future of foreign student body might not be guaranteed. However, Glasgow – where one of our focus groups was held – is in Scotland. Here, higher education is free for locals, and Scotland is also less affected by the Research Excellence Framework (REF) system.

The language used in the UK is as follows: research culture, research governance, knowledge exchange and impact, ethics, research integrity and replicability, public engagement, community engagement, communication, and marketing. Because the REF exercise assesses ‘impacts’ and the ‘research culture’, universities are developing structures and processes under these overall labels. POIESIS project language of PI (public integration) is not used in the UK; instead, we use the term ‘public engagement’ [PE].

The periodic Research Excellence Framework (REF, <https://www.ref.ac.uk/>) seeks to assess the research quality of universities by fields and disciplines (REF groups). The first REF was 2014, then 2021 and the next is slated for 2029. The REF considers three criteria: research quality, impact case studies, and research culture. The significance of this for the present research is that institutions are putting structures and people into place to guide and support their submissions. British universities operate under a regime that has been characterised as ‘competitive accountability’ in pursuit of social impact and public legitimacy (Watermeyer, 2019). In recent years, UK universities have massively extended their communication function, not least in this context of national and international competition (Bauer, 2022; Bauer & Entradas, 2022). A number of national networks and organisation seek to align these efforts.

The UK Research Integrity Office (UKRIO; <https://ukrio.org/>) is the national agency that binds all research institutions into a concordat. This concordat commits signing institutions to submit an annual report of how research ethics and research integrity (RI) is handled and supported, which is a public document. A non-public document reports on any cases and investigations regarding RI. UKRIO serves as a support structure and a discussion forum for the local officer.

The UK Reproducibility Network (UKRN, <https://www.ukrn.org/>) promotes robust research across the UK, investigates factors that contribute to robust research, promotes training and disseminates best practice, and works with various stakeholder to coordinate efforts across the sector.

Similar efforts to create networks and national coordination are currently under way for public engagement (PE), public integration, or knowledge exchange and impact (KEI). Several structures are supporting local staff and offering a discussion forum. Here, the purposes are sliding between public and community engagement (PE) and commercialisation of research into business spin-offs (KEI). Much focus is on defining the impact agenda and definition of ‘research culture’ for the next REF 2029. The National Coordinating Centre for Public Engagement (NCCPE, <https://www.publicengagement.ac.uk/>) arose out of Bristol as a ‘Beacons for Public Engagement’. They offer training, give advice on best practice, champion public engagement (particularly with Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics, STEM) and run a network of public engagement professionals. They also offer a ‘watermark’ to institutions who want to demonstrate they have excellent public engagement. The Knowledge Exchange Concordat <https://www.keconcordat.ac.uk/> goes beyond public engagement to all forms of knowledge exchange including innovation and commercialisation, and is supposed to set out best practice and principles that universities have to demonstrate that they meet. The Concordat has now been taken over by Praxis Auril <https://www.praxisauril.org.uk/> which calls itself the professional body for knowledge exchange (KE), which has historically be more focussed on the innovation and commercialisation of research and not at all on public engagement.

More informal networks exist e.g., Stempra (<https://stempra.org.uk/>) for science communication and the Association of British Science Writers (<https://www.absw.org.uk/>) for science writers and journalism. The British Science Association (<https://www.britishsociety.org/>) used to be an annual conference of scientific debate but has morphed in the past 20+ years into a structure mainly supporting science education and the annual Science Festivals which are hosted by a university around the country.

1.2 Set up of the focus group

Our focus in this research are professional staff at UK universities in 2024 with a brief across research ethics, communication, integrity, engagement, knowledge exchange and research culture.

We conducted four focus groups, one in person (London School of Economics and Political Science, LSE) and three on Zoom (University of Glasgow, University of Bristol and Loughborough University). Initially recruitment proved very difficult because local responsibilities regarding RI and PE were not settled or in turmoil; a late breakthrough led to an existing network of university staff. Local colleagues thus contacted were happy to help with the recruitment and organisation of the focus groups, but more reluctant to become ‘co-investigators’. The issue was task overload and time commitments. We will stay in contact of the local partners all through the process of this research.

Table 1: Names of local contacts and ‘co-investigators’

Place	Dates	Format	Contact	Role descriptions; language used
London	Thursday 29 th February 11:00-13.00	in person	Louise Jones	Head of Research Communications and Engagement; Communications Division; Knowledge Exchange and Impact (KEI) Integrated Service

Bristol	Friday 1st March 13.00-15.00	on Zoom	Dr Gemma Derrick	Associate Professor, Centre for Higher Education Transformation; academically interested in the topic
Glasgow	Monday 19th February, 10.00-12.00	on Zoom	Dr Samantha Oakley	Research Governance and Integrity Manager, Governance, Policy and Integrity Team, Research Services, Research & Innovation
Loughborough	Tuesday 5th March 13.00-15.00	on Zoom	Charles Shannon	Head of Research and Innovation; Quality and Policy; Research and Innovation

We were able to leave the recruitment to the local contacts having explained that we were looking for a discussion with professional staff from the centre and departments to talk about science communication, public engagement, research ethics and research integrity. We were hoping to cover the full range of briefs.

Participants were keen on this exchange among colleagues within their own institutions, as one which would not normally engage this conversation. There was also considerable interest in comparing local activities against other UK institutions and what is happening in Europe.

We simplified our questions for discussion into a short list which all participants would see before the session (see Appendix 1) and we added a question 8b to explore potential tensions and conflicts over RI and PE. The list also showed the Qualtrics link to the short questionnaire.

1.3 Participants in the focus group

Table 2: Characterising the University environment.

	REF 22	Times Global ranking 2024	Academics 2022	Admin 2022	Students 2020	Character of university	Location type	Focus group
Glasgow	13	87	5255	4530	32465 (35%)	Full university, medical school	Scotland*	Yes
LSE	33	46	1830	2260	12050 (57%)	Social science	London*	Yes
Bristol	10	81	3595	4690	27335 (27%)	Full university, Medical school	West England*	Yes
Loughborough	26	251-300	1590	2140	18295 (24%)	Engineering, sport	Midlands	Yes
UCL	22	2	9585	6075	41095 (52%)	Full university Medical school	London*	No
Goldsmith	60	401-500	1170	890	10090 (36%)	Arts & Humanities	London	No
All UK			234k	192k	2,449,000 Median=14000 24%)	218 institutions	UK	

Sources: HESA statistics: academic staff numbers 2022; administrative-professional staff numbers 2022; student numbers 2020 and in () percentage, post-graduates; Times Global University Ranking 2024; REF 2022 Research Excellence Framework ranking. *Russel Group University

Table 3: Details of focus groups participants

	N participants	Gender	Departments and centres	N academics/ professionals	Age	Names of job positions, language used at institutions
Glasgow	7	1 man 6 women	1 department 6 centres	1 academics 6 professionals	4 < 45 3 > 46	RI manager, RE manager, community engagement manager, RI advisor, ethics committee, grant support, head of governance policy

LSE	9	2 men 7 women	3 departments 6 centres	0 academics 9 professionals	5 < 45 4 > 46	Ethics committee, communications manager, knowledge exchange support, PhD manager, impact support, REF support, centre manager, impact manager, head of knowledge exchange
Bristol	6	3 men 3 women	3 departments 3 centres	1 academics 5 professionals	3 < 45 3 > 46	Research development, RI officer, RI reproducibility, UKRIO network, head of PE, meta-science academic
Loughborough	4	1 man 3 women	1 department 3 centres	0 academics 4 professionals	1 < 45 3 > 46	Ethics and RI officer, R&D officer, Research governance officer & PE, head of R&D REF
Total	26	7 men 19 women	6 departments 20 centres	2 academics 24 professionals	13 13	

Comment: participants are characterised by gender, by being academics or professional staff, by age which we estimated as below of above mid-career (45 years)

Table 4: Length of focus group recordings and transcripts

	Length of focus group (in minutes)	Length of transcript (in words)
Glasgow	88	16278
LSE	124	19430
Bristol	94	15749
Loughborough	97	13866
Total	408	65323

Focus groups were opened by the local contact. The discussion was mainly led by Martin Bauer and Bankole Falade. Hannah Bunt was the observer. The local contacts participated in the discussion in their local role, but also helping the discussions along by bringing voices into specific questions. The focus groups lasted a total of 408 minutes; each between 90 and 120 minutes (see Table 4). We had one or two preparation meetings with the local contact, mainly over Zoom (at LSE this happened over a coffee). No post-meetings have happened yet; we envisage a workshop later in the year to discuss results as presented in the national reports and the international comparison. All focus groups were transcribed (see Table 4). The transcript corpus contains 65,323 words, around 15000 words for each focus group. We followed the coding instructions of the POIESIS project. The LSE focus group happened in person, we therefore could offer coffee/tea and lunch was served at the end.

2. Sequential description of the focus groups

We followed the same topic guide in all four discussions: starting with the icebreaker, a) what comes to mind when you hear the phrase ‘science and society’. We then moved to questions b) whether science-society relations are tested by current crisis of public trust, as well as sensitive issues; c) the ideal/good researcher and their falling from grace in misconduct; d) a general discussion of PE. The last point focused on e) the institution, what is done locally in terms of RI and PE, and whether there were any tensions or conflicts among different sectors (communications, RI, PE, KEI, etc), whether there were tensions between centres and departments, or between academic staff and professionals, and whether local efforts are aligning or not with the National frameworks. The London team made initial notes from personal impressions immediately after each discussion, and also held short debriefings sessions after each focus group.

2.1 Focus group 1 (Glasgow, Monday 19th February 2024, 10.00-12.00)

The discussion in Glasgow was the first group and test case. Seven people took part, one man and six women, and it lasted 88 minutes. The local contact was very forthcoming in helping the discussions along. Moderation worked generally well. The group asked for clarification of the term 'science' that would include arts and humanities, which was a strong focus of PE in Glasgow. We clarified by encouraging an inclusive meaning of science reflected in the German term '*Wissenschaft*', focusing on empirical research more broadly.

2.2 Focus group 2 (LSE, Thursday 29th February 2024, 11.00-13.00)

At LSE, nine people took part, two men and seven women, and it lasted just over two hours (124 min). Discussion was lively, one participant had strong and controversial views, which were at times contradicted. One member of the group had previous experience being in university administration in Canada and often made cross-references when talking about issues, e.g., community engagement with indigenous populations. Another person brought in experiences from France.

2.3 Focus group 3 (Bristol, Tuesday 1st March 2024, 13.00-15.00)

In Bristol six people took part, three men and three women, and it lasted 94 minutes; they also wanted the word 'science' to be clarified; it was suggested to talk about 'research', which covers a broader area of activities than 'science' as in STEM. The person representing PE, upon request from colleagues, launched into an extended expose on the meaning of PE. She referred to the 'Wellcome Onion' model of concentric circles of inclusion and escalation from simply informing and inspiring audiences to co-producing with others (see Appendix). One person was actually not employed by the university but was in position as a delegate of the UK Reproducibility Network located in Bristol with the remit RI.

2.4 Focus group 4 (Loughborough, Tuesday 5th March 2024, 13.00-15.00)

In Loughborough, four people took part, one man and three women; all members of a single team (R&D REF governance) and it lasted 97 minutes. A person from marketing had agreed to join but fell ill on the day. At the start of the meeting, we briefly discussed the possibility of postponing the session to a date when other people might be able to join; the locals advised against it, as it was difficult to coordinate a suitable timing even for a Zoom event. Naturally, with all members from the same team, the discussion was somewhat, though not entirely dominated by the team leader.

3. Building trust in science: from perception to institutional engagement

3.1 Associations regarding 'science and society'

Summary: Science and society as a field of activity has not shed its traditional association with the 'laboratory' and 'ivory tower' and the stereotype of people in 'white coats', all which indicate a separation from 'the person on the street'. The phrase is commonly used to indicate there is a problem – the deficit model – with the public needing information and education. 'Research' is deemed a better phrase, as 'science' may be interpreted as Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) only. It is a relationship between partners that involves trust. Much good work

is being done to 'bridge the gap' but soiled by negative media coverage and such events as the COVID-19 pandemic and crisis over the measles, mumps, and rubella (MMR) vaccine. Overall science has had a good impact on society.

The image of science: Participant 13 (P13) said the image of science has not changed from the people in white coat but has been modified for gender inclusivity: "type in research in Google image search, you'll get people in white coats. They're probably different colours and some of them are women now, but they're still doing like science with gear". P13 said the word science is unhelpful when we should be using research. A participant argued that the science equals STEM equation is very UK-centric as in other countries, science is as in German '*Wissenschaft*', meaning an academic and methodical inquiry into the natural and social world, present and historical. P6 described the phrase as nebulous arguing that it sounds more as if you're talking about the more philosophical aspects of it rather than things that affect the person in the street. P7 said the phrase is probably meant to imply that science is part of society, but it usually is used in a way that asserts 'science as being apart from society' and echoes the deficit model approach. P1 also pointed out that contrary to the thinking that society includes the person in the street, in some respects, it does not, although it could involve some public attitudes particularly in the way that priorities are shaped at a higher policy level. The relationship, she argues is mediated by government policies: "we have one government literally telling scientists to burn their [...] research and then another government comes in and funds (the same) research. I see it as a mediated relationship sometimes, not as a simple a to b."

On university and society relations, P3, whose duties cover health and social care, said that in her line of work, when they talk about science, people think of laboratories and health settings. So, they avoid calling it science. When they talk about research, people think that it's about professors in ivory towers with tweed jackets. They therefore changed the vocabulary, so it does not conjure up those images. P10 argued that the university "can seem a bit siloed to the general public" and are more likely to think "scientists are just working away on their projects and their experiments ... (and don't) connect with what that is happening in real life." Other associated and less critical words and phrases include public engagement, public attitudes, building connections, communication, evolution of science, citizen science, meaningful dialogue between researchers and the public, pathways to impact, mutual and respectful relationship, public attitudes, policies, the Royal Society and participatory research, issues of trust, misinformation, and pseudoscience.

Negative representations of science by the media often skew reality and soil perceptions. For P16, the post-war social contract that is now broken down is destabilising science and society relationships in ways that perhaps wasn't in the 50s and 60s. P12 argued that while as a professional, he sees a lot of good work implemented in a positive way in the wider society, as a layman, the vast majority of cases that spring to mind is when there is a negative news story, or when society is going through a challenging time and its "frustrating that the positive news stories, although they are publicised and marketed, aren't probably taken up as much as the challenging areas."

The COVID-19 pandemic, however, enhanced the image of science. For P15, it changed the perceptions of her peers about her former place of work, the pharmaceutical industry: "I sort of moved from being one of those evil pharmaceutical company people who earn loads of money to people who might contribute towards a vaccine for COVID." Acknowledging the image

enhancement, P15 noted that some universities received a “glossy reputation” from their work on COVID-vaccines. The participant however noted that while some debates were very positive, others were very negative as members of the public were quick to pick up on the bits of research that agreed with their views and rejected everything else.

P9 said that from a professional point of view, it comes back to that connection between science and society and how can we bridge that gap; the realms of impact, the advancement for good and the changes which generally benefit society, “and perhaps we haven't quite cracked that yet and got that right.”

3.2 Perceptions of trust in science

Summary: The notion of a crisis of trust in science is not backed by evidence and surveys show trust levels are stable and in a positive direction. However, there may be pockets of distrust fed by social media and fake news. Funders with vested interests may not have public interest in focus and are often a source of distrust. Some areas of science, such as medicine, may experience the occasional crisis due to the nature of their research. Distance of society from science may also create distrust. There is a clear distinction between a researcher being trusted (relationship) and trustworthiness of research (science conduct). Talk of a crisis is best avoided as it can become a self-fulfilling prophecy.

Crisis of trust in science is unfounded: Participants across institutions were of the view that the word crisis is a strong and problematic term and does not best describe the situation with P16 arguing that the talk of crisis can be self-fulfilling and is best avoided. P4 argued that the phrase is unhelpful as it is too broad, as issues are context specific, nation specific and also subject specific. P9 said while the phrase is maybe “a little strong”, there is potentially a lack of it, and it is probably related to the lack of transparency in the messaging and the stories conveyed around different topics. P14 also said the word may be too strong to describe the state of science.

“I think that might be over-egging it [...] there are research areas that do face a lot of public backlash and difficulties for certain researchers [...] I would say they're very minority and it's important not to over-emphasise what a few individuals are doing.” - P14

P21 argued that “the idea of a crisis in trust [...] never seems to be borne out by the evidence that's collected in the various barometers and public attitudes surveys.” P2 found the concept of trust in science “a bit daft” arguing that it is like saying a crisis of trust in post-enlightenment thinking and we would rather go back to pre-enlightenment times when authority was given regardless of fact. He argued further that the only people who talk about trust in science are those with vested interest in promoting ideology over evidence and facts. “I don't think it's a simple answer” said P23, who noted that there are different aspects to different types of science and some members of the public, for instance, may not feel the same investment in the idea of putting people in space. P23 argued that once the trust is broken, it's difficult to fix and once a piece of research is proven to be misleading and withdrawn, it damages reputation in research as a whole and it is not confined to that one study or that one area: “I think it spreads. And I think once that spreads, it's difficult to change people's minds on that [...] like the MMR stuff and linked autism.’

Media as the source of crisis discourse: For P5, public trust in science is very much at the mercy of the media and fluctuates all the time. The participant argued that the level of misinformation out

there makes it difficult for people to trust science and trustworthy sources, such as the Guardian and the BBC, are also guilty sometimes of reporting things that are based on tiny studies or things where there are flaws. He however argued that it also depends on the audience as people who don't have critical thinking skills are susceptible to absorbing what comes out in the media. The issue of politics and media influence on science was debated by participants from one of the universities. Participant P22 argued that it is hard to separate trust in science from the political context where politicians are increasingly dismissive of science and from how we consume media, as the social media, which has been great in some regard, has also led to the proliferation of misinformation. Participant 20, agreeing with P22, said the sort of binary reporting of science stories in the press can be really damaging as it presents a perception that there is this sort of flip flopping when in fact that is not the case at all. P21 noted the difficulty explaining research on the airwaves given that you have a “60 second sound bite”. Agreeing, P25 said it is really tricky to explain anything in any depth within that timeframe and this is how sometimes a vacuum is created where misinformation can creep in. P19 argued that the relationship is perhaps less of a crisis in the UK than in Europe, as UK scientists are pushed to maintain and establish relationships with societal stakeholders in contrast with European colleagues who see such partnerships as an add-on, rather than something extending from their necessary contract with society.

Trust and sensitive research topics: Some areas of science cause more public anxiety than others. Genetic experimentation brings moral and religious concerns, i.e., ‘messing with nature’ while funding sources, e.g., the arms industry, create reputation risks. Others include research into stem cells, climate agenda, vaccines, new developments in technology, artificial intelligence, and genetically modified crops. However, ethics is now more stringently enforced, so trust is restored. The UK COVID enquiry shows the problematic nature of handling the pandemic but local successes in research are a source of local pride.

P24 argued that the public may disagree on religious or moral grounds with experiments in genetic modelling. Although they might be conducted to prevent disease or find medications or treatments, they can be misconstrued to be messing about with nature. Funding research with money from the military also raised concerns regardless of whether the product may be to the benefit of society. P26 argued that taking money from an arms company is not a completely neutral thing with no context around it, thus a researcher will have to consider it carefully and consider the whole research life cycle. P22 argued that some universities may not even be willing to support such funding, but she thinks “those are important conversations to have.” P21 was more critical, asking if researchers should go back to the old Roman wisdom that money doesn't smell, and wherever it comes from, as long as it is doing good research, it is fine. He however noted that that reasoning does not seem to sit easily.

On artificial intelligence research, P23 noted that the technology has both pros and cons. Being new, it is not certain if anybody has solutions to the cons yet. P5 noted that the factors that feed into vaccine hesitancy are different from some of the fears and concerns around AI and therefore, there is need for more specificity in what leads to a lack of trust or fear or anxiety. The participant said they do a lot of work for government agencies that is funded as independent research and

labelled as such. But they noted that there are still times when you must explain this very clearly because there is still the assumption that the funder would have had some influence even if the researchers are completely independent.

Another issue of concern was accountability. P22 argued that public money requires accountability, and the university must be transparent about how that money is being spent. P21 was however of the opinion that using industry money may liberate the researcher from this obligation to which participant 20 replied that it does not liberate the scientist from doing good research and acting with integrity. P21 said research committees should be open and up for dialogue on the research that they are doing because they will hopefully one day have an impact on society. The question now he asked is “where do you have that kind of rational discussion”.

Interdisciplinary issues were also areas of anxiety among researchers with different research ethics requirements in the arts, humanities, social sciences, and medical sciences. Participant 13 described these as ‘cultural wars’, noting it is easier to justify the impact of a tiny bit of research about a receptor on a cell that might make easier to absorb a vaccine than in the arts and humanities.

3.3 Attitudes towards research integrity

Features of the good scientist: A good scientist is transparent, competent, industrious, risk averse, open and honest about findings, seeks maximal impact, involves stakeholders, shares data, is open to counterevidence, has no vested interest, avoids advocacy, and makes replication possible. A good researcher has a track record of good outputs, reputation among peers, engages in cross-disciplinary collaboration, uses robust methodology, seeks public funding, and avoids private funding with vested interests.

P6 said a good scientist thinks through the outcomes and impacts of their work. P23 said a good researcher has a history of publishing good research and being lead investigator and the people they work with have great things to say about them. P21 argued that it is difficult to define in terms of the individual because a lot of it is built on reputation which is hard to define at the start of a career. Participant 20 describes the qualities of a good scientist as discipline-specific, with a social scientist being somebody who is way ahead on acknowledging their subjectivity and who is good at robust methodology, whereas for another discipline it might be somebody who works very openly. For P24, good scientists are those who work hard to try and develop understanding and knowledge in their chosen field and go through robust methodology and even when they do not get the results that they want, are not afraid to publish them. P21 said it is also about how researchers work with their partners and their colleagues and support people coming through the research system and the whole research culture. P22 said it is increasingly about being able to collaborate effectively, maybe across disciplines and maybe across sectors: because societal problems are so complex, they may require multiple disciplines working together. P25 observed that it takes a level of humility to collaborate, especially across disciplines, and that comes more easily to some researchers than to others. P9 said a good scientist, with integrity, strives for that maximum positive impact and involves stakeholders in the co-creation of potential benefits right from the beginning, and also considers the risks, knowing that not all impact is positive. For P16, the qualities to look for in trustworthy scientists would be competence and ethics and everything else pretty much falls under one on the two categories. P14 however argued that these two categories are not enough, asking,

“if we have competence, ethics, openness, honesty, and the scientist is funded by somebody else from outside, what’s the impact of the ... funding on all this?” P3 argued that you can be a brilliant scientist who builds weapons of mass destruction and majority of the public would not describe you as a good scientist. Goodness or badness is a social phenomenon and not professional competence, she argued, and the main issue for the public is motivation if the scientist is being driven by malign or vested intent or the desire to make money for self and employer.

Misconduct: more often incompetence and negligence, than malevolent intent: Scientific misconduct is not a widespread problem, but the media sensationalises some cases, putting careers into jeopardy. Some of these cases result more from incompetence or negligence (ethics failures, biased sampled, etc.) than intent. Lesser forms are more common and may have resulted from work pressures, time pressures, ‘publish or perish’ quandaries, funding deadlines and work overload while higher forms, which are rarer, may be a matter of a corrupt character or lack of training, supervision, and mentorship. Plagiarism occurs more than what is known with some studies indicating prevalence of about 10% and this incident rate keeps the spectre of statutory regulation on the agenda. More serious issues such as data fabrication or partial hiding of data should be treated as non-intentional until proven otherwise to avoid allegations from spite. There is not enough transparency in the UK about misconduct compared with the United States where such cases are centrally recorded. It appears universities in the UK are fostering an environment of cover-up although there is also a culture of whistleblowing.

A good scientist has integrity but on the flipside is research misconduct. Participants 24, 20, and 21 argued that there are different types of misconduct, thus specifics must be defined. Misconduct includes fabrication and plagiarism and can arise from authorship and failure to follow ethics guidelines. For P4 there may be things like unconscious bias that arise in the way the sample was collected or who was asked what and what is then interpreted. P14 argues that there seems to be a consensus that misconduct is more common than is known about without much evidence behind it. While this is an issue that needs to be grappled with, the participant explained that the British culture is not to name and shame, unlike the American model, which has its plus and negative points, whereas in the UK, sometimes things get swept under the carpet. P16, agreeing that there is more misconduct than talked about, argued that there is supporting evidence with a study suggesting it was up to 10%. The participant argued that this is why the issue of regulation, at least in the UK, just keeps coming back and why other countries across Europe have started taking more statutory approaches to this.

For P23, the bigger problem, as to why it happens, is research culture. Some of the problems highlighted include pressure on researchers to publish, to find funding for research and to advance careers, which according to P24 makes researchers feel they have no choice but to cut corners. P21 noted that cutting corners can constitute research misconduct but he does not think it is always intentional. P22 said sometimes it can be accidental or just a genuine error to which P24 added that it could still be wrong although sometimes it is easier to correct than others. Participant 20 said “I think underneath it all is the culture of research as a whole and pressure that we put on people.” Very few are deliberate, he noted: “it's confusion, it's muddles, it's people under pressure, it's, you know, difficult conversations that weren't had and [...] just so often, it's just sort of a mess that could have been sorted out by better communication at the start of a project.” P24 agrees that

errors do occur and may have been due to pressure but noted that these can have dramatic awful effects on individuals and on society if they go unchallenged.

How familiar are researchers with integrity guidelines and codes? Is the culture of integrity perceived as shared or one that needs to be developed? The culture of ensuring research integrity is practised as shared with several layers of scrutiny within the institution. P4 noted that before a project commences, it must go through the departmental committee, then the school committee, then the methods process, indicative of layers of screening before the research gets to the journal. P1 noted also that there is an earlier screening by the research development team on funding applications, professional service, and research colleagues for best practice, all integrated into the grant applications process. P7 noted that although some institutions carry out integrity training to familiarise staff with acceptable procedures and practices, such programmes help with people who accidentally act without integrity but plays a different role in deterring those who knowingly act without integrity. P2 noted that it is rare to have just one author conducting research in her institution as most are collaborative, with external partners and senior academics, thus with internal and external checks and balances.

A debate also ensued on where the responsibility should be for detecting research misconduct given the complicated nature of the research process. Should this be the institution or an external body such as journals, or both should share responsibility? P1 noted that the situation today is that the main scrutiny takes place as part of the peer review process. P7 said that while this may be true, it implies the universities have essentially transferred their responsibility for detecting misconduct that happens within to journals. The limitations of journals picking up misconduct was raised by P4 who argued that a peer review process cannot usually pick up fabrication of results because determined researchers will cover their tracks. P3 added that most journals cannot detect misconduct because they may not be familiar with the institutional processes that each article submitted for publication has passed through, and the sheer volume of articles received from all over the world.

Integrity practices and pitfalls: A summary was provided by P12 as a set of context and moral requirements.

- A financially sound project reduces the chance that shortcuts will be taken.
- Researchers must understand what is required from an ethical perspective.
- Researchers must ensure they know who their collaborators are and their capacity to undertake the project.
- Researchers must be open and prepared to share all data to ensure replicability.

3.4 Attitudes towards public integration

Public engagement varies in magnitude and audiences, is now a pathway to impact (through REF), and increasingly features civic engagement. There is also a spectrum of formats (lectures, conferences, consultations) best exemplified by the Wellcome Trust Onion Model graphic (see Appendix). In practice, it is mainly one-way, not necessarily marketing or publicity, and often extractive. PE staff are also mostly part-time, with implications for continuity. Silo working is also prevalent. Scientists struggle with public engagement due to capacity constraints.

Neither publicity nor marketing but bridging the gap: Perceptions and definition of public engagement varied across participants and institutions due largely to its wide scope and individual institutional practices. P1 was rather scathing in his perception of engagement, describing the notion as a relabelled public understanding of science activity built on the deficit model and masquerading as something slightly more sophisticated. P22 was more enthusiastic, describing it as not just communication, but a two-way dialogue which overlaps with community engagement but at a deeper level. She noted also that there is civic engagement, which is increasingly trendy now, focused on engaging the local community and investing in creating spaces specifically for local civic engagement: “They're all kind of overlapping and sometimes there's confusion around definitions but broadly what we're all trying to do is make research accessible, make the university accessible, have a positive impact.” Participant 13 said public engagement is not marketing or publicity but the biggest part of science communication. Engagement, he said, is not at the end of the product and it's not about dissemination, but instead about engaging the public from the start. For P9, public engagement is that connection between science and society and how we bridge the gap. For P17, public engagement is a ‘spectrum’ of activities best described by the Wellcome Trust model called the ‘public engagement onion’ where you peel off different layers to reveal different forms of public engagement which serve different purposes, such as informing, inspiring, consulting, co-creating, etc. The limits of achievement were noted by P21 who disclosed that less than two percent of members of the public sampled on the streets associate the university with research and innovation activities. He said, it “was quite telling for us actually that somehow the people even around the place where the universities were located, they didn't really associate the university primarily with that function.”

P22, a public engagement manager, said activities by her university range from those with the local community to the international level with several countries and formats from light touch forms, as part of a science festival, through to much more involved consultations, workshops, and focus groups, where you're shaping the research questions:

“So, I guess yeah there's no one way of engaging, it's ... diverse, the people, the groups and the ways that we engage and that the type of engagement being undertaken just really depends on the researcher and on their career stage on their research topic, and whatnot.”

P21 argued that it is no use doing public engagement without a pathway to impact, “and to be honest it's very difficult because unless you're doing some kind of population level activity (that everybody has access to, through mainstream media, or some other channel, it's actually quite hard to create these pathways to impact.”

Risks of public engagement: not always a good thing, nor is more PE always better. P22 noted that public engagement could be damaging if researchers do not have the required skills, or they have not really thought through their engagement methods or who it is that they are engaging with. She cautioned that scientists should not be forced into doing it, because if they do not want to, then it is not going to be very effective. P21 also warned of the potential danger that public engagement becomes a kind of throwaway term for institutions to use when it maybe suits them, maybe for REF and research grants. The question for public engagement activities, P6 asked is: are researchers open to a process in which direct contact with the public would lead to them changing

how they do things, rather than just kind of being used to communicate your results to them?

“There's a difference between involving the public, as more active participants in your research, as opposed to things like the priorities of your research. Can you imagine if we asked the public to scrutinise [...] research programme and give feedback on our programme and we would then take action based on it. I mean I don't think any researcher would be willing to do that, would they?” –

P6

P2 noted that scientists decide what research they should do, not the public, even if the public are paying for it, and journals largely drive the process because they decide what is published and this is what people's promotions are based on:

“The journals are choosing things that they think are important in their field, but they are not necessarily or even at all considering what would be the most helpful to society or the public.”

P4 who works in the health sector, where people who use care services get involved in designing the research, said she often asks researchers if they learnt anything from the participants in the co-produced research and the answer is quite often “no, why would we change what our model was, based on feedback from people.” She said they also have public involvement groups that comment on design and structure. But what they also found is that while there is a community of people that understand research and can follow it, they do end up with the usual people in some cases, such that they do not get a diverse perspective.

P17 observed that public engagement is now almost an accepted way of working which was not there at the time of debates about genetically modified foods. However, society seems to have moved on without the same sort of distrust. That said, there are always new areas such as artificial intelligence and facial imaging technology that pose real ethical questions and it is the responsibility of citizens to be involved in those conversations. He also observed that dialogue around scientific topics tend to be around ethical issues:

“One example springs to mind around synthetic blood, you know, our researchers have done a lot of engagement work to talk to people who are not specialists in that field, and to say what do they think about synthetic blood? Is it a good thing? Is it a bad thing? What would make it better? And, and so they were really in a listening mode.”

For P12, public engagement can bring topical issues and research findings to the public a lot sooner than it might otherwise have done. Using the head guard used in rugby as a case study, he noted that while there was a lot of work already going on, it took the Six Nations Championship to create the needed public awareness and if the technology had been adopted sooner, it may have led to fewer medical conditions that affect players later in life.

Flow back from public engagement to researchers: What is in it for the researcher to engage? P9 said it depends on their motivation. She said she came into her role thinking that every single researcher wants to have an impact and are doing the research for that very reason, but that isn't necessarily the case:

“I think in a lot of instances, academics would be involved from a career progression perspective, most definitely, I think, from an incentive point of view. And I think one of the things that (her university) has been looking at is how they can engage or encourage early researchers to be involved [...] so that it's not [...] the same academics, year on year.”

4. Institutional contributions to trust in science

Ethics screening takes place at various levels and is more of a university research culture with formats varying across institutions. A more formal spotting approach is advocated to prevent breaches. United Kingdom Research and Integrity Office (UKRIO) appears too low key to be effective. Institutions engage in formal and informal public engagement activities, set incentives, support researchers, and provide training for all newcomers.

Institutional approaches to public engagement: There were two noticeable approaches to public engagement: (1) creating conditions within for the public to engage with the university, and (2) going out to meet the public at several fora such as museums, exhibitions, focus groups etc. One of the universities embarked on campus development with the dedication of the ground floor of a new building to local civic engagement. It also engages in researcher development where the researchers build skills by going out and doing public and community engagement with the potential impact of making research accessible, sharing knowledge, raising awareness, and promoting access to research or to the university by groups that are underserved or underrepresented. P22 said by doing public engagement you are potentially bringing people into the university as well and so there is a whole range of potential impacts. In the same line of engagement, P13 said his university aspires to be a civic university that will bring together the towns poorest and richest, into campus, for them to see the university is for them. The university, he said, has a civic engagement team saddled with this responsibility, which is about gauging the city, not the public, and this is different from the public engagement team.

“And I suppose that's where you build up trust in that this place is for me, this is my space. This is not the space on the hill for the researchers, this is somewhere I can go and be involved in and speak to people and have my experience.” – P13

P16 said the approach described by P13 was to make the research trusted and engaged and this is different from the research being trustworthy. P16 works in a research group and to make research a bit more trustworthy, they have a lot of practices that are led from and practiced at the top, making an inspiring example of how one makes the work trustworthy:

“Adopting practices like pre-registration and pre-printing and scrutinising each other's research protocols and having data integrity procedures ... and being able to do that they're being transparent and sharing their research data ... and all are documented in a lab handbook.”

Institutional policies and procedures to promote scientific integrity? P20 said her institution has in place a policy for research integrity which codifies all expectations and is backed up by the research misconduct policy. It outlines what misconduct is and the very strict process that is followed to investigate it as well as other policies relating to ethics and conflict of interest. The institution has

been promoting the code which was recently revised by word of mouth and is considering an online session as well:

“We've done some interesting work on the research integrity side, around equitable partnerships [...] discussions about ensuring that all the partnerships we have [...] everyone's being treated with respect, and everyone's getting to contribute and be recognized for that contribution and reflecting on the, you know, perhaps, the cultural challenges that researchers can encounter.”

P20 also said the institution has mandatory training for postgraduates and all research staff or anyone with professional services who does research, and the institutions approach is unique in that it is assessed with short reflective answers which are then used to inform the institutions work in promoting good practice. P7 noted that her institution is behind others in research integrity training as it still relies on departments to create the atmosphere for good research environment. Other institutions, the participant noted, do mandate training, but this is always problematic and does not necessarily address the problem and may even cause more problems than it solves. P2 noted however that while mandatory training may be problematic, it cannot cause harm in terms of trying to embed something within an institution. She noted that while it takes a while for things to become business as usual, over time it is just part of that embedding process and the training also helps with people who accidentally act without integrity but plays a different role in deterring those who knowingly are acting without integrity. P17 said the university has training session for all staff on the principles of good engagement but it is optional, and people sign up if they want to, but despite being voluntary, they have seen quite a few hundred academics per year through the program. There is also a lot of information on web pages about policies, procedures, how to navigate reporting and the standard annual integrity statement that normally gives a snapshot over the course of the year, but the audience, according to P14, tends to be people internal to the university; researchers or people who need to navigate these processes. P10 said the university has integrity training for new researchers which introduces them to certain situations and issues that might arise to help them to think about their research projects before they are actually doing them, to have a plan, rather than sort of rushing into to doing it. She noted that while the team welcomes the new researchers, the bulk of the responsibility lies with the supervisors, so the system is quite reliant on the input and experience of more senior members. They also have two courses of online ethics training packages the researchers have to do.

What institutional levers are available to promote integration and integrity and how can these be improved? P22 called for more investment in public engagement noting that engagement staff, usually on short term contracts, build a relationship with a community group and then leave when their contract ends. This has been an issue for continuity. The participant observed that for researchers, the biggest barrier for them in doing engagement is time, and so having staff in place to give guidance on how to use their time effectively is important. P24 also observed that there is presently a lot of silo working and the issue needs to be addressed to bring public engagement persons in different departments together:

“Colleges have their own public engagement persons [...] research departments might have an engagement person who's perhaps part time, so it's really kind of sporadic, the staffing, and people are working in isolation, so, one challenge is making sure that we join the dots and that we're

collaborating across the whole university, with each other, because often we have the same user groups, the same communities that we're working with, and as far as the user group is concerned, it doesn't really matter what school or college you're in."

5. Other themes: tensions, potential conflicts models of public engagement

5.1 Tensions and potential conflicts

Academics are worried by the impact of the extra workload they are saddled with by public engagement activities on their already stressed schedule. They thus often push back on such activities. The ethics process is seen as another hurdle to take, rather than a responsibility. Research Excellence Framework (REF) is now part of UK academia; it has been normalised but creates tension across and within universities. REF, with a focus on impact, directs activities, diverts from public engagement and is more of a purpose rather than a by-product of research. REF is annoying for many and is stigmatised. Although it is designed to increase performance in research, teaching and outreach, it risks becoming instituted as 'police force for behaviour change', and it is not sure whether the redirection is right. Also, all kinds of modalities of performance are loaded into the surveillance system: litigation avoidance, EDI, decolonisation, etc. The perception is that it should be internalised, not be a cycling spurt that needs to be undertaken. Cross disciplinary and cross departmental collaboration are also often constrained by budget sharing. There are also tensions created by research integrity procedures and management. Institutions are working on a research culture that bridges gaps between professional and academic staff.

Between professional staff with different briefs: Personality clashes are part of any working group; some professionals have strong views which are not necessarily widely shared. There is little evidence of inherent competition between groups of professionals across communications, research integrity, marketing, public engagement, research and innovation, or governance. We saw or heard little evidence; group discussions were polite; maybe longer conversations would reveal duplications in the briefs, or difference on aim or in the options on how to execute them as a function of structural contradictions in the funding and the briefs.

Between professional staff and academics: Academics were referred to as people who are often grumpy, do not share any enthusiasm for REF and the impact agenda, and seek to avoid additional work arising from it. Thus, they are likely to be evasive and may even push back on issues of PE and RI. P20 attributes this to the system:

"Its lack of time and the pressure that everybody's under that gets surfaced time and time again, and I think again that the system is a major problem, and I think that's where academics feel, you know, sort of quite hostile to the topic, not completely [...] well I suppose you know grumpy, not hostile grumpy."

Between academics across colleges: P24 said one barrier to colleges or faculties working together are the finance systems in that the university does not make it easy to share budgets (rich and large department resent smaller and poorer ones and vice versa; cross-subsidy is contested) and there is lots of red tape that makes collaboration across colleges and schools within a university complicated. Another issue raised is ethics across disciplines. P24 said every year the university

carries out an audit where people in each college look at applications and issues that other colleges have encountered. What they found is that people in the arts perhaps have very different approaches research ethics compared with people in the medical faculties and life sciences. She noted however that even though they disagree at university ethics committee, they do so in a nice supportive way, being very polite to each other and listening:

“I think it really does help to talk things through and I think it helps to promote an understanding of cross-disciplinarity. I think where more serious tensions might occur have really nothing to do with ethics, but they may have to do with [...] finance budgets [...] an administrative issue, not really an ethical issue.”

Between professionals at the Centre and in the Departments: Departments might have their own staffing and priorities which are not in line with those of the Centre. The Centre’s focus seems to be the National priority of REF, which is not at the forefront of public engagement activities of the Departments, e.g., patient engagement for public health, or local community engagement. P21 said his institution’s culture is decentralised and may lead to less reporting and loss of control at the centre:

“We are a very decentralised university fundamentally [...] the positive says we have this really wonderful vibrant community and people do the right things in the right places most of the time but there isn’t often a lot of reporting to the centre so there is tension there, so it’s not so much a lack of harmony [...] and for those of us who work centrally, that can be quite challenging, a bit of the proverbial herding of kittens.”

P12 agreed the drivers of engagement at the centre might not align with that of the academic or the faculties and colleges. However, the university is committed to a certain level of public engagement in order to be successful in the REF and their ability to meet their reporting obligations, or financial obligations, or to ensure that they have got finances coming into the university through QR funding or through the REF or through some other methods. P12 argued that the greatest amount of tension is the level of additional work that academics feel they have to do to undertake the research. Previously, the tension was just not wanting to take responsibility for the financial management of the funding, to get on with the research and somebody else sort out the finances, but nowadays, it is financial management, due diligence, and compliance with legislation such as export controls, the National Security and Investment Act, open access, REF reporting, impact case studies, etc., These additional pressures are, for want of a better word, imposed on the academic community, and makes it difficult for the research to be done.

Between university and national co-ordination (REF, UKRIO): The Research Excellence Framework (REF), the system for assessing the quality of research in UK higher education is a source of tension within the university. REF is the big elephant in the room when talking about public engagement and even about research integrity and innovation. Public engagement is a continuous commitment for universities, while REF is cyclical and focuses attention only every 6-8 years. REF is however funding positions for public engagement, but their brief is wider and not entirely focussed on REF. REF thus provides an opportunity to establish infrastructure for public engagement which then tends to develop its own purposes that go beyond impact studies and the pathways towards these. The United Kingdom Research Integrity Office (UKRIO) is deemed to be a secret organisation,

meant ironically, as very few people seem to know about its activities. The agency seems too low-profile to have any real impact on the research culture in the country.

There are two other institutions universities must account to: the Knowledge Exchange Framework ([KEF](#)) which monitors knowledge exchange between institutions and partners outside academia and the Teaching Excellence Framework ([TEF](#)) which monitors student experience and outcomes at universities and colleges. Both are however optional for universities in Scotland, Wales, and Northern Ireland. P22 noted that her job exists because of REF and the original business case for the university investing in a public engagement post was because of the REF which is “a monetary motivator for the university.” For P4 also, “REF is why I have a job. REF is why we just hired a research culture manager.”

How then does the money floodgate opened by REF affect the vision of research integrity and public engagement and what impact as measured by REF requires one to do? P20 acknowledged there may be tension, but these are from some researchers who think all impact have to be REF compliant. However, smaller scale public and community engagement activities that are not going to be REF impact case studies still have a huge amount of value, so you almost have to reassure researchers that this is still a good thing to do even though it is not considered REF impact. P20 also argued that REF “is a bit of a mixed bag” from an integrity point of view. He noted that many researchers mention the REF in integrity training responses as quite a negative thing because it puts pressure on them to produce high impact papers. Perhaps funders like UKRI and Wellcome are more useful in the emphasis they put on integrity than the REF at the moment. Institutions however have an issue with Wellcome, who wants them to report to them when somebody is being suspected of misconduct, despite privacy concerns and when nothing has been proven.

For P6, the criteria REF uses in its framework for assessment makes institutions shift what they do to fit with REF guidelines, in other words, it dictates “the direction of travel.” P12 said REF is a driver of certain behaviours, but it is not necessarily that those behaviours are particularly good or bad behaviours. The challenge is differentiating between doing it for REF and doing it as part of your good practice:

“So, the question is, should we be doing it anyway? And the REF is just a byproduct of that good behaviour? Or are we so focused on REF that we only do it for REF and the seven years in between, we tend to forget about it.”

For P9, while public engagement and integrity feed heavily into the REF, it becomes “a little bit of a swear word within the university”. She noted that as soon as you mention REF, everybody's demeanour changes, and they are quite negative. The issue now is how we can make this positive because it is not going to disappear.

5.2 Explicit models of thinking about RI and PE In relation to Trust

While most people speak freely and spontaneously about the issue of RI and PE, there were three examples of implicit conceptual schemes emerging through these discussions. Two are related to PE and one is related to RI.

1. A ‘causal model’ of RI and PE on trust in science

An explicit idea of the causal modulation of trust in science in function of RI and PE was put into the discussion. In this idea, RI is a causal factor of (dis)trust, and this causal relation can be moderated by PE; in other words, PE has the capacity to mitigate the withdrawal of trust in science that is potentially caused by misconduct.

2. The ‘Wellcome Onion’ model of public participation

Explicit reference was made to an overview scheme of public engagement formats. The [Wellcome Onion Model](#) is a graphic (see Appendix) that orders different modes of engagement as concentric circles of functions: information, stimulating thinking, creating understanding, informing decision-making, and actually making decisions. These classes of PE formats are ordered on an escalating scale from informing the public to co-producing results in dialogue with the public. Public impact on research and policy or flow back is expected only from dialogical formats.

3. The diffusion model of innovation

One participant made explicit and repeated reference to the diffusion model of innovation and the function of communication to create awareness and to speed up the adoption of innovation process. The participant referred to this model to define the purpose of PE. Enhanced efforts in PE serve to cultivate the ‘early adopters’ for new products and research results in a communication process that is conceptualised as ‘diffusion’ first to early adopters, then to late adopters and finally to laggards.

Public engagement seems to be rationalizable from an engineering point of view within this model of product innovation. P12 argued that public engagement can bring a product to the public a lot sooner than it might have otherwise. He referenced the head guard used in rugby, which only became popular because of the Six Nations tournament, arguing that an earlier adoption of the technology could have had more impact by reducing the medical conditions and the concussions and all the other things that affect athletes in the sport later in life.

“If there were earlier adopters of that technology, you know, how many people could have positively been impacted by that? And if people knew that that work was going on, potentially greater public pressure could have been brought to bear to ensure that that bit of science, all that work was better funded [...] ensuring that [...] that item came into production sooner rather than later.”

4. National Replication Network

One person was located in the university, part of a faculty set-up, but actually, was the local delegate of the National Replication Network. This is a network of coordination for the advocacy and support of systematic replication studies with focus on Pharmacology and Psychology. This person was well informed about the international statistics about ‘misconduct’, and the discourse around it, how it was to be analysed and interpreted. The person was rather reluctant to opine about these matters outside the narrow remit of the available evidence.

5.3 The 'card sort' exercise: 28 communication activities into 4 functions

We added an exercise at the end of the focus group sessions: a short questionnaire in which participants were asked to classify 28 common communication activities of university professionals into four functions: Public Relations with stakeholders (PR), Marketing for students (MA), Public Affairs for policy making (PA) and Science Communication/Public Engagement in the public sphere for debates and deliberations (PE). These functions also separate classical corporate PR functions serving strategic interests from Science Communication with a societal focus of seeking a common understanding (Entradas et al., 2023). The exercise reveals the relative consensus and the variability and fuzziness in the understanding of these key communication functions.

Figure 1: Classification of 28 activities into four communication functions by mode (Mod) and variance (VAR) across 20 responses (UK, N=20)

Alumni relations, crisis communication and press releases are typical PR activities; producing corporate publications, managing the website and university branding are typical Marketing activities; monitoring of education policy, feeding research opportunities to academics and fund raising are deemed typical Public Affairs activities; and advising grant applicants on outreach, writing RI audits for the university, or organising public events deemed to be typical PE activities.

6. Conclusions

6.1 How do institutional stakeholders perceive public trust in science and technology?

The notion of a general crisis of trust in science is not backed by evidence and participants pointed to surveys that show trust levels are stable and in a positive direction. However, there may be pockets of distrust fed by social media and fake news. Funders with vested interests may not have public interest in focus and are often a source of distrust. Distance of society from science may also create distrust. There is a clear distinction between a researcher being trusted (relationship) and trustworthiness of research (scientific conduct). Talk of a crisis is best avoided as it can become a self-fulfilling prophecy.

Some areas of science cause more public anxiety than others. Genetic experimentation brings moral and religious concerns, i.e., ‘messaging with nature’ while funding sources, e.g., the arms industry, creates reputation risks. Others include research into stem cells, the climate agenda, vaccines, new developments in technology, artificial intelligence, and genetically modified crops. Interdisciplinary issues were also areas of anxiety among researchers with different research ethics requirements in the arts, humanities, social sciences, and medical sciences. However, ethics is now more stringently enforced, so trust is recurred. The UK COVID-19 enquiry shows the problematic nature of handling a pandemic but local successes in research are a source of local pride.

6.2 How do stakeholders perceive the culture of research integrity and social integration?

A good scientist is transparent, competent, industrious, risk averse, open, and honest about findings, seeks maximal impact, involves stakeholders, shares data, is open to counterevidence, has no vested interests, avoids advocacy, and makes replication possible. A good researcher has a track record of good outputs, reputation among peers, engages in cross disciplinary collaboration, uses robust methodology, seeks public funding, and avoids private funding with vested interests.

Scientific misconduct is not a widespread problem, but the media sensationalises some cases, putting careers into jeopardy. Some of these cases result more from incompetence or negligence (ethics failures, biased samples, etc.) than malevolent intent. Lesser forms are more common and may have resulted from work pressures, time pressures, publish or perish quandaries, funding deadlines and work overload, while higher forms (e.g., falsification of data or statistics), which are rarer, may be a matter of a corrupt character or lack of training, supervision, and mentorship. Plagiarism occurs more than what is known with some studies indicating prevalence of about 10% and this incident rate keeps the spectre of statutory regulation on the agenda. More serious issues such as data fabrication or partial hiding of data should be treated as non-intentional until proven otherwise to avoid allegations from spite.

There is not enough transparency in the UK about misconduct compared with the United States where such cases are centrally recorded. It might appear that universities in the UK are fostering an environment of cover-up although there is also a culture of whistleblowing. The culture of ensuring research integrity is practised as shared with several layers of scrutiny within the institution.

Public engagement varies in magnitude and audiences, is now a pathway to impact (REF) and increasingly features civic engagement. There is also a spectrum of formats (lectures, conferences, consultations) best exemplified by the Wellcome Trust Onion Model graphic. In practice, it is mainly one-way, not necessarily marketing or publicity, and often extractive. Staff are also mostly part-time, with implications for continuity. Silo working is also prevalent. Scientists struggle with public engagement due to capacity constraints. It is seen as neither publicity nor marketing but bridging the gap. There are risks of public engagement and there is flow back from public engagement to researchers.

6.3 Responsible research practices, social integration, institutional governance and policy

Ethics screening takes place at various levels and is more of a university research culture with formats varying across institutions. A more formal spotting approach is advocated to prevent breaches. United Kingdom Research and Integrity Office (UKRIO) appears too low-profile to be effective. Institutions engage in formal and informal public engagement activities, set incentives, support researchers, and provide training for all newcomers.

There were two noticeable approaches to public engagement: (1) creating conditions within for the public to engage with the university, and (2) going out to meet the public. One institution has a policy for research integrity which codifies all expectations and is backed up by the research misconduct policy which outlines what misconduct is and the very strict process that is followed to investigate it. Some institutions have mandatory training for postgraduates and all research staff or anyone with professional services who does research. Others rely on departments to create the atmosphere for a good research environment. Mandatory training may be problematic and does not necessarily address the problem and may even cause more problems than it solves.

6.4 Other themes: tensions, potential conflicts models of public engagement

Academics are worried by the extra workload they are saddled with by public engagement activities on their already stressed work schedule, they thus likely to push back on such activities. Ethics process is seen as another hurdle to take, rather than a responsibility. The Research Excellence Framework (REF) is now part of academia, has been normalised but creates tension across and within universities. REF with a focus on impact, directs activities, diverts from public engagement, more of a purpose, rather than a by-product of research. REF is annoying for many and is stigmatised. REF together with TEF and KEF, are designed to increase performance in research, teaching and outreach to business and public, it risks becoming instituted as 'police force for behaviour change', and it is not sure whether the redirection is right to guarantee a world class research culture. All kinds of modalities of performance are loaded into this system: litigation avoidance, EDI, decolonisation, student experience etc. Cross disciplinary and cross departments collaboration are also often constrained by budgets sharing. There are also tensions created by research integrity procedures and management. Institutions are working on a culture that bridges gaps between professional and academic staff.

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Appendices

POIESIS WP3 - simplified question guide for focus group discussion

Simplified questions were distributed to all participants before the sessions

https://lse.eu.qualtrics.com/jfe/form/SV_09rYigkGXnCbOHY

Q-0: What comes to mind when you hear the term 'science and society'?

Q1: We often hear about a crisis of trust in science: what are your thoughts and experiences with this?

Q2: Advances in science and technology or certain scientific research might provoke enthusiasm but also worries. Can you think of examples of such reactions?

Q3: From your perspective, what are the qualities of a scientist who works with integrity?

Q4: How common do you think scientific misconduct is? What drives it, and can you think of examples?

Q5: On Public Engagement/Public involvement in science and technology, what formats can PE/PI take? In your own institution, what are the common forms of PE/PI?

Q6: Do you think that the PE/PI disseminates scientific knowledge to the public? How?

Q7: How does your institution promote scientific integrity?

Q8: How does your institution promote public involvement/engagement?

Q8b: Are there any issues arising from these activities in your institution, between professional colleagues? Professional staff and academics? Between the University and Departments? In relation to REF, TEF, and KEF or UKRIO?

Q9: How do you think your work helps to improve the public's trust in science?

The 'Wellcome Onion model' for Public Engagement

In one of the focus group, the PE officer explained ideas about PE to the other participants by sharing a picture of the 'Wellcome Onion model' of public participation.

